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UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI
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SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH, AND TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATION
CYCLE XXXVI

**TRANSFORMATIVE AGREEMENTS IN THE SCIENTIFIC
RESEARCH ECOSYSTEM: CHALLENGES AND
OPPORTUNITIES FOR OPEN ACCESS AND FOR THE ROLE
OF LIBRARIANS IN OPEN SCIENCE**

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List of abbreviations

AAM	Author Accepted Manuscript
AISA	Associazione Italiana per la Promozione della Scienza Aperta = Italian Association for the Promotion of Open science
ANVUR	Agenzia nazionale di valutazione del sistema universitario e della ricerca = National Agency for the Evaluation of the University and Research System
APC	Article Processing Charge
ASN	Abilitazione Scientifica Nazionale = National Scientific Qualification
AT2OA	Austrian Transition to Open Access
CA	Corresponding Author
CARE	Coordinamento per l'Accesso alle Risorse Elettroniche = Coordination for Access to Electronic Resources
CC	Creative Commons
CDA	Consiglio di Amministrazione = Board of Directors
CMC	Computer-mediated Communication
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche = National Research Council
COARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
COPER	Consulta dei Presidenti degli enti pubblici di ricerca = Council of the Presidents of Public Research Institutions
CRUI	Conferenza dei rettori delle università italiane = Conference of Rectors of Italian Universities
CS	CiteScore
DMP	Data Management Plan
EID	Electronic Identifier, i.e. the Scopus ID number
EIFL	Electronic Information for Libraries
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FFO	Fondo di Finanziamento Ordinario = Ordinary Financing Fund from Italian Ministry of University and Research

HE	Higher Education
ICDI	Italian Computing and Data Infrastructure
IFLA	International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions
IRIS	Institutional Research Information System (= CRIS, Current research information system)
ISTI	Institute of Information Science and Technologies "Alessandro Faedo"
ITRN	Italian Reproducibility Network
JIF	Journal Impact Factor
LIBER	Ligue des Bibliothèques Européennes de Recherche = Association of European Research Libraries
OA	Open access
OS	Open science
PY	Publication Year
R&LR	Read and Let Read
ROARS	Return On Academic Research and School (blog in Italian)
S2O	Subscribe to Open
SCI	Science Citation Index
SciELO	Scientific Electronic Library Online
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
TA(s)	Transformative Agreement(s)
VoR	Version of Record
VQR	Valutazione della Qualità della Ricerca = Research Quality Assessment

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Abstract

Aim. This doctoral thesis aimed to contribute to understanding the impact of transformative agreements (TAs) on scientific communication and to evaluate their opportunities and critical issues, mainly focusing on the Italian case. The primary objectives were to observe the number of open access (OA) articles published by authors affiliated with Italian institutions before and after the adoption of several transformative agreements in Italy, to understand the theoretical framework of scientific communication in the digital environment and about open access in Italy, after the introduction of transformative agreements, and to understand the role of academic libraries and librarians in the context outlined.

Background. Scientific communication is a significant part of the research ecosystem. Among other open science (OS) practices, publishing research findings in OA is an opportunity and sometimes a requirement from funding agencies. TAs, which regulate the access to journals and also the possibility of publishing in open access in the subscribed titles by researchers affiliated with the institution signing the agreement, arose in the scientific communication scenario some years ago, with their pros and cons. In Italy, TAs have been negotiated since 2020. Academic librarians manage TAs while they are engaged in several actions to support open access and open science development.

Methodology. A mixed method approach was best suited, so qualitative and quantitative methodologies were selected. The mixed method is a possible approach in libraries and information science. The topic of transformative agreements is complex and requires a comprehensive approach to address its complexity during the research project. In order to answer the research questions, it was necessary to collect data from the opinions and perceptions of key informants, both connoisseurs, and actors in the investigated context, together with data from citation databases OpenAlex, Scopus, and Web of Science, regarding articles authored by affiliated with Italian institutions with publishing year 2018-2022.

Discussion. Because of some limitations in the data available, the extracted dataset provided a somewhat grainy picture. The number of OA articles published by authors affiliated with Italian institutions, particularly in hybrid journals, grew from 2018 to 2022. Data available about articles with corresponding authors from Italy are not complete. However, they were observed and distributed by year, publisher, and institution. Key informants interviewed talked about the strengths and weaknesses of TAs and the librarians' role.

Conclusion. Monitoring TAs is strongly needed; in Italy, data are quite fragmented both on articles published through them and on expenditure. Key informants underlined the advantages of the rapid growth of open access since their adoption and the researchers' satisfaction with them. Conversely, they found that medium- and long-term TAs could not be sustainable. In addition, TAs bring inequalities between wealthy and low-income countries and in the same institution or members within consortia and perpetuate the status quo and the "serials crisis." The crucial point is a reform of the research assessment. Academic librarians could have a vital role in open science advocacy, supporting OA green and diamond, and in engagement towards research assessment and copyright rules reforms.

Keywords: *Transformative Agreements, Open access, Open science, Academic librarians*

1. Introduction

1.1 Statement of the problem

The Internet and the possibilities offered by communication in digital format have led to a growing awareness on the part of researchers, authors and readers of the contributions, and a demand for greater accessibility to scientific literature, translated into various initiatives such as the Budapest Open access Initiative, the Bethesda and Berlin Declarations between 2002 and 2004 (see chapter 2). They have constituted the theoretical formulation for more structured and concrete projects by the communities of researchers, librarians, institutions, research funders, and publishers, such as, for example, institutional and disciplinary open access (OA) repositories, research directories, fully open access journals or new OA publishers and academic presses, research funding calls requiring the open access publication of results, up to the most radical interpretations of open access in violation of copyright rules.

Open access publication still (or for now) concerns the minority of articles, and, in any case, the major international commercial publishers remain the protagonists in the dissemination of scientific communication, also because of the prestige enjoyed by the journals they publish and the links between them and individual and institutional evaluation processes. Many publishers have offered authors the possibility of paying Article Processing Charges (APC) to make individual articles published in OA in journals that remain sold on a subscription basis, generating a so-called “double dipping” for publishers. Such journals where this is possible are called *hybrid journals*. A 2014 report, republished in 2020, intended for several British research funding agencies, had formulated a forecast of the trend of the scientific publication market with the advent and intensification of open access publishing (Björk and Solomon, 2020). Another report, projecting the data about publication and access to open access articles, starting from the dataset originating from the Unpaywall

service¹, tried to estimate the growth until 2025 of the amount of freely accessible literature, both in full open access and hybrid journals: “44% of all journal articles will be available as OA, 70% of article views will be to OA articles” (Piwowar et al., 2019).

With some publishers, also driven by initiatives such as Plan S and its principles (Plan S Principles, 2018; Bianco and Patrizii, 2020; Quaderi et al., 2019), a growing number of institutions in Europe and beyond have started negotiations for TAs in which not only access to journals is regulated and paid for but also the possibility of publishing in open access in the subscribed titles by researchers affiliated with the institution, in practice becoming hybrid most of the journals in their catalogues (general information in Hinchliffe, 2020). Efficiency and Standards for Article Charges (ESAC)² is an initiative coordinated by the Max Planck Digital Library³ to monitor the costs of publishing scientific communication in open access and promote best practices in adopting such agreements, which it keeps track of in the ESAC Registry⁴.

Transformative agreements are expected to bring the opportunities for greater dissemination of open access papers, published in journals with high metrics, with the advantage that the copyright remains to the author. Critical issues also emerge, such as, for example, the management by institutions of the contractual option of open access publication in the event of limits on the number of articles provided for by contractual clauses, and above all sustainability in the medium and long term, if there are contractual increases even above the average of “traditional” agreements.

A 2021 study conducted a first comparison between agreements registered by ESAC, highlighting how the focus of negotiation for institutions has shifted from cost containment to the inclusion of open access publication clauses (Borrego et al., 2021). In this international context, we intend to investigate Italy's state of the art following the advent of transformative agreements to understand their impact on authors' publications belonging to Italian institutions, i.e. universities and public research bodies, about three years after their first introduction in Italy.

¹ <https://unpaywall.org/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

² <https://esac-initiative.org/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

³ <https://www.mpdlib.mpg.de/en/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

⁴ <https://esac-initiative.org/about/transformative-agreements/agreement-registry/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

1.2 Research questions

Following the launch of the transformative agreements in Italy (the first has been operational since July 2020), we wanted to answer the following research questions (RQ):

RQ1: How do publication trends compare before and after transformative agreements were implemented in Italy?

RQ2: Regarding the Italian context, what is the theoretical framework of scientific communication in the digital environment and about open access, also considering the introduction of transformative agreements?

RQ3: What is the role of academic libraries and librarians in the context outlined?

1.3 Aim and objectives

The research project aimed to contribute to understanding the impact of transformative agreements on scientific communication and to evaluate their opportunities and critical issues, mainly focusing on Italy.

The research project objectives were:

- To observe the number of OA articles published by authors affiliated with Italian institutions before and after the adoption of several transformative agreements in Italy and the rating of their OA articles on the total published and indexed in the citation databases Web of Science, Scopus, Dimensions, and OpenAlex.
- To understand the theoretical framework of scientific communication in the digital environment and about open access in Italy, also considering the introduction of transformative agreements.
- To understand the role of academic libraries and librarians in the context outlined.

1.4 Methodology

A mixed method approach was best suited to answer the research questions formulated, so both qualitative and quantitative methodologies were selected. The mixed method is one of the possible approaches in social sciences too, in which libraries and information science stands. The topic of transformative agreements is complex and requires a comprehensive approach to address its complexity during the research project. To answer the research questions, it was necessary to collect data from the opinions and perceptions of key informants, both connoisseurs and actors in the investigated context. It should also be noted that the investigation focused on an up-to-date and rapidly evolving topic. A mixed method approach can provide a rich picture of the observed phenomenon and better answer the research questions. In the present project the quantitative and qualitative methodologies were in an equal status, while the purpose was to collect quantitative and qualitative data simultaneously, combining their analysis to better understand the research problem and answer the research questions. In the convergent parallel design, data were collected simultaneously and analysed separately. The “determination of the consistency-inconsistency status of the results derived from the analysis” (Şahin and Ozturk, 2022).

The more appropriate research methods to be applied were semi-structured interviews and data collection from bibliographic citation databases.

Quantitative data were gathered from different bibliographic citation databases, for each one some notes about data available are given in chapter 4, within research strategies and extraction process. Qualitative data were gathered from interviews to five key informants, two were by written text and three video recorded, then transcribed, and finally translated in English.

1.5 Limitations

Although this doctoral thesis aimed to explore the topic thoroughly, it had limitations in terms of money and time as well as due to the constantly evolving subject. Furthermore, the search was limited by the databases utilized, which had limitations regarding publication

coverage, access via subscriptions, functionality, and metadata indexed and searchable. Extracting large amounts of data simultaneously also requires specialized computer science skills. Additionally, there were limitations on the use and export of data due to proprietary terms of use or technical settings. The limitations of the databases made the extraction and processing of the data more time-consuming than expected. It must be also remarked that the status of an article may change over time, for example if a journal flips from hybrid to full open access, if a journal passes from one publisher to another, if articles stop to be freely accessible.

To contain costs and save participants' time, online meetings or, alternatively, writing responses were proposed. Computer-mediated communication (CMC) and email exchange can limit the interaction between interviewees and researchers compared to physical interaction. However, since the pandemic onwards, remote meetings have become quite common, and the purpose of the research has not been affected.

1.6 Outline of the thesis

The doctoral thesis is structured in 6 chapters.

Chapter 1: Introduction. The first chapter is an introduction to the topic of open access in scientific communication. It specifically focuses on the introduction of “transformative agreements” in the Italian context since 2020. The chapter begins by stating the problem and then presents the research questions, aim, and objectives of the study. It outlines and justifies the methodology used in the research and highlights any limitations encountered.

Chapter 2: Background. The objective of the second chapter is to present the context in which the research was based. This includes the origin of the open access movement, which later has been considered a branch of open science (OS). Next, the librarians’ requirements and their supporting actions to OS, and the identification of scientific research as an ecosystem, both emerging from literature.

Chapter 3: Literature review. The third chapter reviews literature on transformative agreements, exploring their definition, characteristics, opportunities, and critical aspects emerging from previous studies.

Chapter 4: Methodology. The fourth chapter details the methodological approach applied which was the mixed method, the methodology and the research methods used. Ethical considerations and data processing regulation are also discussed in relation to data collection techniques and data analysis.

Chapter 5: Outcomes and discussion. This chapter reports outcomes from data gathered through the research process, those from databases and those from interviews. Outcomes are outlined and discussed.

Chapter 6: Conclusions. In the last chapter, the researcher linked the outcomes with the research aims and objectives and the research questions.

After the Harvard styled reference list in alphabetical order, appendices have been enclosed:

Appendix I: Invitation e-mail

Appendix II: Information on data processing

Appendix III: Interviews

Chapter summary

The chapter introduces the topic of open access scientific communication, which in recent years has seen the introduction of transformative agreements, in which, in a nutshell, institutions pay both to allow researchers to access journals and to let them publish individual open access articles in them. These agreements have both advantages and critical issues, so the research project aimed to investigate the state of the art in Italy three years after the adoption of the first transformative agreement. The research objectives were to observe the number of OA articles published by authors affiliated with Italian institutions, the theoretical framework of scientific communication and the open access in Italy, and the role of librarians in the context outlined. Methodology approach was the mixed method, both quantitative and qualitative methodology were applied, methods to gather data are explained with some research limitations. The last paragraph outlines the thesis.

2. Background

The rise of the Internet and digital communication has led to a greater appreciation of the potential benefits of barrier-free access, exchange, archiving, and searchability of scientific knowledge. This has resulted in various initiatives and movements, including the Budapest Open access Initiative⁵, the Bethesda Statement on Open access Publishing⁶, and the Berlin Declaration on Open access to Knowledge⁷ (translated into Italian and known as Dichiarazione di Messina⁸), collectively known as the “3Bs”, and established between 2002 and 2004. To summarize with Peter Suber's well-known words, “Open access (OA) literature is digital, online, free of charge, and free of most copyright and licensing restrictions.” (Suber, 2012)

Samuel A. Moore's examination of the term “open access” and its origins emphasizes that it is a “boundary object.” This means that while it can be understood easily by different communities, it is open to multiple interpretations and also criticisms from detractors who may find weaknesses in the initiatives that follow from it, concluding that “OA represents a number of approaches and motivations, some thought through better than others, and it is easy for critics to portray a particular approach to OA as representative of all approaches to it.” (Moore, 2017)

The 3Bs provided a theoretical framework for more concrete projects by communities of researchers, librarians, institutions, research funders, and publishers. Some examples of these projects include institutional and disciplinary open access repositories, academic journal directories, fully open access journals or new OA publishers and academic presses, research funding opportunities that require open access publication of results, and even radical interpretations of open access that may violate copyright laws.

⁵ <https://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

⁶ <https://dash.harvard.edu/handle/1/4725199> (accessed 13 May 2024)

⁷ <https://openaccess.mpg.de/Berlin-Declaration> (accessed 13 May 2024)

⁸ http://www.sssup.it/UploadDocs/7109_Dichiarazione_di_Messina.pdf (accessed 13 May 2024)

2.1 The scholarly publishing system

The main phases of the growth and development of the scientific publication system are recalled here to outline the context in which the research project started. We wanted to focus on the publication of scientific periodicals, even if they are not the only form of communication of research findings. This is because transformative agreements mainly focus on journals, and these often make up the largest expense for library systems.

The birth of scientific publishing in the modern sense is unanimously traced back to the publication of the *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society (Phil. Trans.)* in March 1665, on the initiative of Henry Oldenburg, a German theologian, diplomat and natural philosopher (Guédon, 2010). It is also recognized as having the primacy of longevity, being a publication that is still active⁹. It should be noted that the first periodical publication on scientific topics, born only two months earlier (January 1665), was the *Journal des Sçavants* in Paris, on the initiative of Denis de Sallo, a French writer and lawyer from Paris, although it was soon interrupted and resumed much later, at the beginning of the Twentieth Century, with a more literary than scientific intent. In fact, Jean-Claude Guédon points out that “the Parisian publication followed novelty while the London journal was helping to validate originality. Therein lies the significant (and profound) difference between the two periodicals.” (Guédon, 2010). Some of the peculiarities of scientific publication are traced, namely that of recognizing its originality, the validation by the academic community and the preservation.

The Royal Society put in place a formal process and a systematic way to review the research published in the *Phil. Trans.* by the peers. In the meantime, to speed up the dissemination of research, abstracts were also published in the *Proceedings of the Royal Society*.¹⁰ Over than 350 years later, peer reviewing is still considered one of the distinctive and essential features of scientific publication.

Peer review is the process where experts in a particular field evaluate a publication to determine its originality, methodological rigor and impact on the community (Guerrini,

⁹ <https://royalsocietypublishing.org/journal/rstl> (accessed 13 May 2024)

¹⁰ <https://royalsocietypublishing.org/rspl/about> (accessed 13 May 2024)

2022). Typically, the process of publishing an article begins with an evaluation to ensure that it adheres to the formal guidelines, purpose, and thematic area of the journal. If this evaluation is positive, the article is then reviewed by at least two reviewers. If the reviewers are not known to the author, it is called a blind peer review. If the author and reviewers are both unknown to each other, it is called a double-blind peer review. However, it may be arguably easy to trace the author's identity based on the topic, style, or citations used. Open peer review is a practice of science that promotes transparency, in which the review is tracked and made accessible to everyone alongside the publication itself and the identities of authors and reviewers are known by each other.

The mechanism of peer review is codified in precise phases. With the advent of digital, interventions and timing of the transition from the submitted (or pre-print) version to the one accepted for publication (post-print or Author Accepted Manuscript) up to the final version (editorial pdf or Version of Record) published in the journal with pagination, logos, and editorial formatting are traced.

Although it is the subject of an ISO standard (ISO 22392:2020), peer review remains the subject of reflection and discussion, as evidenced by Peer Review Week¹¹, an annual event that from 2016 intends to validate and discuss its application, searching for best practices and avoiding possible distortions.

During the post-World War II era, there was a significant increase in funding for scientific research that was no longer solely dedicated to war purposes. During this time, Eugene Garfield, a chemist, librarian and linguist, created the Science Citation Index (SCI). The SCI is an index of "core journals" in every sector that is considered representative of the "core" science intended to be used by libraries to select essential journals. It is based on the relationship between journals of cited articles and those that cite them. Maybe not properly, the concept of "fundamental" science has been applied to evaluate the quality of journals by calculating the Journal Impact Factor (JIF)¹², which subsequently has been used to determine the quality of the researchers who published in them. The European Commission report published in 2019 summarizes as follows:

scholarly publishing had to adapt to a much-increased demand, and many new journals were started, with overall numbers doubling every fifteen years. Societies

¹¹ <https://peerreviewweek.wordpress.com/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

¹² <https://clarivate.com/webofsciencegroup/essays/impact-factor/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

and associations found the new landscape of scholarly publishing increasingly challenging. In the same period of the 1950s, commercial scholarly publishing managed to establish scholarly journals on a solidly profitable basis. A bit later, they were indirectly helped by the emergence of Eugene Garfield's Science Citation Index, and its associated Journal Impact Factor (JIF). (European Commission. Directorate General for Research and Innovation, 2019)

So, a large number of new universities with their libraries and the SCI index created favorable conditions for the development of a market of great interest to publishers, due to its tendency to inelasticity.

What happened in libraries? In the next decades, the rise of periodical prices became a concerning issue, leading to what is known as the "serials crisis". The costs were too high for libraries to manage with their own funds, which often were also being reduced over time. In the early Nineties, some publishers studied new business models of content in digital format. Just as the invention of movable type printing triggered the evolution of modern scientific communication, the same the advent of the Internet and the digital technologies have radically changed the way scientific literature is disseminated, especially with reference to electronic periodicals.

Librarians have begun to purchase licenses to access publications and no longer physical media, losing some of their "traditional" functions related to the profession. Publishers introduced "Big Deal" agreements by the end of the 1990s. These agreements granted access to the entire collections of their journals for an additional fee over the historical expense for printed subscriptions. The fee was not proportional to the historical expense for the titles already subscribed but was significantly lower. This made the proposal seem indecent but unmissable all over the institutions, in the meantime frequently associated in national or regional consortia. Maintaining Big Deals through the years meant dismissing the subscriptions of other publishers. In addition,

there are more subtle and indirect consequences to the "Big Deal" tactic. By discounting titles at a price that makes the offer irresistible, Elsevier contributes to creating a scholarly landscape that is distorted compared to the normalized scholarly landscape of the "core journals". (Guédon, 2010)

Ezio Tarantino published in Italy in 2011 a reflection on Big Deals, investigating why the business model remains the most widespread, especially at the consortium level, despite its flaws: "Finally answering the "easiest" question (why do publishers insist on the big deal without offering an alternative model? Because it is the most convenient model for them,

evidently) one wonders why consortia and universities are unable to take advantage of this position of exposed weakness.”¹³ (Tarantino, 2011).

To summarize, the scientific publication system is needed to disseminate research findings and evaluate those findings, and for an easy-to-do extension, the current system is needed to evaluate researchers and institutions. On these premises the market of knowledge assumed the characteristics of an anelastic market. A practical synthesis of scientific communication in the digital age is offered by Elena Giglia, who concludes by quoting Goodhart's well-known law: “When a measure becomes a target, it ceases to be a good measure” (Charles Goodhart cited in Giglia, 2017). The same author states that

we need to undermine the logic of excellence and artificial scarcity created by scientific journals (Eve 2016 cited in Giglia, 2016), to ensure that "an ancient tradition and a new technology" truly converge, as we read in the incipit of the Berlin Declaration (Berlin Declaration, 2003, cited in Giglia, 2016). [...] If we think of science as a great conversation, of its collaborative nature, of the advancement of knowledge as its goal, then its requirements will be: a community of serious and credible "peers"; of the "crystals" of knowledge - those moments in which knowledge crystallizes and takes the most diverse forms, certainly different from the traditional magazine (Stern, Guédon and Jentsen 2015 cited in Giglia, 2016); a "fluid" approach to knowledge creation, similar to that of free software developers; data sharing; sharing knowledge; the evaluation of the real quality of a work and not of the publication venue.¹⁴ (Giglia, 2016)

The scientific publication workflow represented in a diagram by Giovanni Salucci¹⁵ summarizes the following steps: funding, research process, research proposal, validation, publication, and exploitation: these recall the main phases of the whole scientific research from the perspective of an ecosystem.

¹³ Rispondendo infine alla domanda “più facile” (perché gli editori insistono con il big deal senza offrire un modello alternativo? Perché è il modello più conveniente per loro, evidentemente) viene da chiedersi come mai i consorzi e le università non riescano ad approfittare di questa posizione di scoperta debolezza. [translation in English by the author]

¹⁴ Bisogna scardinare le logiche dell'eccellenza e della scarsità artificiale creata dalle riviste scientifiche (Eve 2016), per far sì che "un'antica tradizione e una nuova tecnologia" convergano davvero, come si legge nell'incipit della Dichiarazione di Berlino (Berlin Declaration, 2003). [...] Se pensiamo alla scienza come grande conversazione, alla sua natura collaborativa, all'avanzamento della conoscenza come fine, allora i suoi requisiti saranno: una comunità di "peers", seri e credibili; dei "cristalli" di conoscenza - quei momenti in cui la conoscenza si cristallizza e prende le forme più diverse, certo diverse dalla rivista tradizionale (Stern, Guédon e Jentsen 2015); un approccio "fluid" alla creazione di conoscenza, simile a quello degli sviluppatori di software libero; la condivisione dei dati; la condivisione del sapere; la valutazione della qualità reale di un lavoro e non della sede di pubblicazione [translation in English by the author]

¹⁵<https://www.academic-publishing-services.it/flusso-della-pubblicazione-nella-editoria-accademica/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

The 3Bs may arise from the following paradox, too: on the one hand, researchers are authors and reviewers of the research findings; they “feed the publication system,” but when they are readers, they (or their institutions) must pay for the added value that publishers earn. A reflection is required since publishers' (private companies) earnings are mostly publicly funded.

2.2 Open access: a brief history

Chapter 2 began with reference to the 3Bs and the definition of the term open access (OA) as a “boundary object,” according to Moore's reflection. The 3Bs are (or were) the framework in which the actors of the open access movement have moved for their initiatives. Some passages from the three documents are highlighted below.

The Budapest Open access Initiative, 2002, is the first in chronological order and was launched by the Open Society Institute (now Open Society Foundations), and identifies as a “common good” the distribution of scientific literature without access barriers, especially the economic ones of subscriptions:

An old tradition and a new technology have converged to make possible an unprecedented public good. The old tradition is the willingness of scientists and scholars to publish the fruits of their research in scholarly journals without payment, for the sake of inquiry and knowledge. The new technology is the Internet. The public good they make possible is the world-wide electronic distribution of the peer-reviewed journal literature and completely free and unrestricted access to it by all scientists, scholars, teachers, students, and other curious minds. (Budapest Open access Initiative, 2002)

The text highlights how scientific publishing in the digital environment still has a cost but it is lower than those of “traditional” publication in paper. Public institutes or foundations can support this, and the funds freed up by the dismissal of subscriptions could be invested. The practical implementation can be done through two forms. One is self-archiving, i.e. depositing by the author in open and interoperable archives that use the OAI protocol, created by the Open Archive Initiative¹⁶. The other way to implement open access is by

¹⁶ <https://www.openarchives.org/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

creating a “new generation” of completely open access journals. Explicit mention is made of the permitted free uses, without prejudice to the author’s rights to the integrity of the work and to the correct attribution and citation.

Bethesda Statement on Open access Publishing, 2003, is a document released in June 2003 and “divided into four sections: the first is a working definition of open access publication, followed by the reports of three working groups” (Bethesda Statement on Open access Publishing, 2003). The definition of what is open access underlines the rights granted to the user of the work by the author or the copyright owner. Archiving a copy of the work in an open repository immediately after the publication is also expected. The three reports express some principles from the point of view of Institutions and Funding Agencies, Librarians and Publishers, Researchers and Scientific Societies, suggesting the adoption of a multilevel approach, identifying in fact the scientific research (process, financing, and communication) like an ecosystem.

Berlin Declaration on Open access to Knowledge, 2003, “In accordance with the spirit of the Declaration of the Budapest Open access Initiative, the ECHO Charter and the Bethesda Statement on Open access Publishing” (Berlin Declaration, 2003), the Max Planck Society¹⁷ promoted its declaration in a more global perspective, including both scientific knowledge and cultural heritage and listing a number of principles to support the transition to open access paradigm by whole organizations. In Italy, 71 universities undersigned the Berlin Declaration through the Italian Dichiarazione di Messina in 2004¹⁸.

Along the following twenty years, numerous projects have been established for the purpose of self-archiving, which refers to depositing research papers open access in institutional or disciplinary digital repositories. This approach is often referred to as the “*green road*”.

The ArXiv repository, founded in 1991 by Paul Ginsparg, is the longest-running project of this kind. It was established for the purpose of storing preprints in Physics and it is managed by the Cornell University. The project is funded by participating institutions, agencies, and donations. Scholars have the option to upload later versions of their articles, such as postprints or the Version of Record, if they have the right to do so. Most universities and research institutes have established their institutional repositories, while other similar disciplinary repositories have also emerged, typically for preprints.

¹⁷ <https://www.mpg.de/en> (accessed 13 May 2024)

¹⁸ <https://www.cruis.it/open-access.html> (accessed 13 May 2024)

ROAR¹⁹ is the main registry of open repositories, hosted by the University of Southampton and it is one of the projects funded by the JISC²⁰, the English charity that aims promoting the adoption and use of information technology in all its forms to support research and education. JISC supports another project which is the directory OpenDOAR²¹. The former aims to provide information about “the growth and status of repositories throughout the world” as stated in the homepage of ROAR, the latter aims to give “quality-assured” information of repositories “that provide free, open access to academic outputs and resources”, as stated in the homepage of the service.

ROAR allows the direct metadata entry in the registry, while, in OpenDOAR, submissions, requested through a form, are selected by checking if they meet the criteria established: one of these is that “Site **must** [bold text is used in the webpage] have open access content available” as stated in the inclusion criteria section²².

Over time, numerous journals fully open access and peer-reviewed were established, and some publishers were born to publish only open access journals. This approach is often referred to as the “*gold road*”. The first example (still active) is BioMed Central²³, a project established in 1999. It provided authors with the opportunity to publish a certain number of articles in open access in exchange for a yearly membership with their respective institutions. Although BioMed Central was acquired by the commercial publisher Springer in 2008 (it became SpringerNature in 2018), it had little impact on the publisher's business model in the following years. Currently the membership paid by institutions only allows a discount on publication costs.

The Directory of Open access Journals (DOAJ)²⁴ indexes fully open access journals since 2003, the project is supported by donations especially from academic organizations and it is managed by the IS4OA, the Infrastructure Services for Open access, a Community Interest Company based in the United Kingdom, with a branch registered in Denmark. At the time of writing, it counts over 20.300 open access titles from 135 countries in 80 languages. One of its key points is that it includes journals only if they meet the prescribed requirements; the

¹⁹ <https://roar.eprints.org/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

²⁰ <https://www.jisc.ac.uk/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

²¹ <https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/opensoar/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

²² <https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/opensoar/about.html> (accessed 13 May 2024)

²³ <https://www.biomedcentral.com/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

²⁴ <https://doaj.org/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

adherence to criteria is periodically monitored and titles can be excluded until they show that they meet them again.

One of the critical issues for the majority of the open access journals could be to achieve the visibility and the “prestige”, in comparison to the “core journals” often and easily identified by the JIF, the CiteScore²⁵ (CS) or similar parameters. So, the main point concerned the visibility of the journals and the possibility of being indexed at the article level and cited. In 2007, DOAJ had just implemented the indexing and research at the article level. Over time, some of them were indexed among “core journals”. It is notable that DOAJ awards a seal of quality to journals that meet stricter criteria about open access choice. This results an incentive both for journals and for DOAJ reputation, trying to keep out from index the so-called “*predatory journals*.”

According to a commonly accepted definition

Predatory journals and publishers are entities that prioritize self-interest at the expense of scholarship and are characterized by false or misleading information, deviation from best editorial and publication practices, a lack of transparency, and/or the use of aggressive and indiscriminate solicitation practices. (Grudniewicz et al., 2019).

The debate about predatory practices is contemporary, often open access journals are all hastily considered poor quality journals or overlapping with predatory publishing, while Björn Brembs raises the question if even well-known publishers put in place predatory practices (Brembs, 2019). An interesting review about predatory journals recommends a holistic approach in investigating the context and the reasons for the choice to publish in them (Mills and Inouye, 2021). Regardless, DOAJ regularly updates and publishes the list of journals that falsely claim to be indexed in it.

Gold journals can ask authors for a payment to publish their articles, this is the APC (Article Processing Charge) business model. Fortunately, the majority of the journals indexed in DOAJ does not require APC payment. The eventual payment can vary sensibly, based on the purpose of the publisher (if a profit or non-profit organization, for example, some university press). When articles are open, and the authors do not pay for APCs, publishing costs are covered by funding agencies, non-profit organizations, universities and so on. This model is called “*diamond or platinum open access*”.

²⁵ <https://www.elsevier.com/products/scopus/metrics/citescore> (accessed 13 May 2024)

Among many others platinum OA projects, the project SciELO²⁶, an acronym for Scientific Electronic Library Online, was founded in 1997. “Its major objectives at that time were to provide a platform to increase the visibility and impact of scientific research from Brazil and Latin America” (Rocha et al., 2024). In 2023, it celebrated its 25th anniversary and currently hosts not only full open access journals, but a data repository and a preprint repository. The main aim of SciELO is giving visibility to research findings basically from the Brazil and Latin America. The organizations that founded it were the São Paulo Research Foundation and the Latin American and Caribbean Center on Health Sciences Information, joint with Brazilian National Council for Scientific and Technological Development. Now there are many south American countries partners, Portugal and Spain are included too. The regional basis of the development is a key element to grant visibility and ensures continuing of the “biodiversity” in the research.

Publishing open access in the “core journals” to adhere both grant requirements from some agencies, for example the European Commission research financing programs, and simultaneously to gain prestige for personal career started to be quite a need of several researchers, among other possible reasons. So, big commercial publishers started to offer the option of open access publishing in some of their journals. This approach is often referred to as the “*red road*”. In this case, an institution pays for subscribing a journal, and it pays another amount, the APC, to make open access single articles within that journal. The publisher gains a revenue first by the subscriptions, then by publishing openly single articles within the same journals: this phenomenon has been called “double dipping” and the journals offering this become *hybrid journals*.

Initial discussions and experiments around hybrid OA started as early as 1998–1999, but the concept was tested on a wider scale with Springer’s “Open Choice” programme launched in 2004. Springer set the pricing at 3000 USD per article, which has since become more or less of a de facto industry standard. (Laakso and Björk, 2016)

We should recognize that many funding programs accept and provide for the APC payment and that some disciplines consider this option a more acceptable practice than others.

Monitoring the expenditure on APCs either per single article than in the framework of transformative agreements is the goal of the Open APC²⁷ initiative, based on the Bielefeld

²⁶ <https://www.scielo.org/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

²⁷ <https://openapc.net/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

University Library and managed by the OpenAIRE organization through the Nexus project²⁸. Institutions participating supply data on a voluntary basis.

Some publishers make articles from their subscription journals available for free after a certain period of time. This period can range from 6 to 12 months, or even longer, and is sometimes referred to as a “moving wall”. For instance, some publishers may make articles from 10 years ago accessible, but not those published within the last 1 or 2 years. The availability of an article for free despite its “all rights reserved” copyright is a unilateral choice of the publishers. The availability of content may change over time, and there is no specified license for final users. This means that readers can read those articles for free, but the availability of content is not clearly defined. It is quite common for several journals to offer free articles, they are named in the open access panorama, categorized as “*bronze open access*.”

2.3 From open access to open science

Open access to research findings by extension has also included open access to research data, with a view to maximum information sharing and collaboration between researchers, but also with the function of preservation and support for validation and reproducibility. There are repositories that host datasets along with publications, while others are exclusively dedicated to them. The most widely accepted formulation of open data dates back to the Open Definition²⁹ of the Open Knowledge Foundation³⁰, an organization founded in 2004 with the aim of promoting the openness of knowledge and derives from an extension of the definition of open source.

More recently, between 2014 and 2016, a group of experts gathered in the organization FORCE11 (The Future of Research Communications and e-Scholarship)³¹ formulated the

²⁸ <https://www.openaire.eu/openaire-nexus-project> (accessed 13 May 2024)

²⁹ <https://opendefinition.org/od/2.1/en/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

³⁰ <https://okfn.org/en/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

³¹ <https://force11.org/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

so-called FAIR principles³², some technical principles for good practices in data management so that they are truly “Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable”:

The elements of the FAIR Principles are related, but independent and separable. The principles define characteristics that contemporary data resources, tools, vocabularies and infrastructures should exhibit to assist discovery and reuse by third-parties. By minimally defining each guiding principle, the barrier-to-entry for data producers, publishers and stewards who wish to make their data holdings FAIR is purposely maintained as low as possible. The Principles may be adhered to in any combination and incrementally, as data providers’ publishing environments evolve to increasing degrees of ‘FAIRness’. (Wilkinson et al., 2016)

Making data “FAIR” is one of the ways to make *open science* (OS). The definition of open science has been summarized in 2021 in a UNESCO Recommendation:

Open science is defined as an inclusive construct that combines various movements and practices aiming to make multilingual scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone, to increase scientific collaborations and sharing of information for the benefits of science and society, and to open the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation and communication to societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community. It comprises all scientific disciplines and aspects of scholarly practices, including basic and applied sciences, natural and social sciences and the humanities, and it builds on the following key pillars: open scientific knowledge, open science infrastructures, science communication, open engagement of societal actors and open dialogue with other knowledge systems.(UNESCO, 2021)

Therefore, according to UNESCO, the sharing of information throughout the whole research process is identified as a “benefit of science and society” and openness is understood to serve the scientific community in the traditional sense and beyond it, and more generally, to the “societal actors”. Ruben Vicente-Saez and Clara Martinez-Fuentes proposed a definition of open science, following the systematic review conducted by the authors: “open science is transparent and accessible knowledge that is shared and developed through collaborative networks” (Vicente-Saez and Martinez-Fuentes, 2018).

Bianca Kramer and Jeroen Bosman represented like a rainbow some digital and collaborative tool available for every stage of the research process. (Kramer and Bosman, 2018)

³² <https://force11.org/info/the-fair-data-principles/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

Fig.1 Rainbow of open science practices

Open science is an “umbrella term” to indicate all open practices at every stage of research. It includes open education, open data, open source, and, of course, open access to the publication of the results. As far as research is concerned, we mentioned in a previous paragraph the open peer review, which is itself an umbrella concept within which various practical applications are collected. Tony Ross-Hellauer gives this definition:

Open peer review is an umbrella term for a number of overlapping ways that peer review models can be adapted in line with the ethos of Open science, including making reviewer and author identities open, publishing review reports and enabling greater participation in the peer review process. (Ross-Hellauer, 2017)

The inclusion of different models of open peer reviewing is underlined: as stated by UNESCO, open science is an “inclusive construct” open to different implementation models. The “ethos of Open science”, inspired by the principles of transparency, collaboration, and participation is also highlighted.

Open science practices are not solely driven by a researcher’s personal motivation to participate but are also heavily supported by agencies and organizations that have made it a priority. As underlined by Maria Chiara Pievatolo,

however novel it may seem, Open science is a revolution, whose practices are so extraordinary that they need to be mandated by funding and research organizations, only in an astronomical meaning”. [Despite that,] “the idea that science, to be science instead of magic, should be made public is as old as Modern Science itself.” (Pievatolo, 2020)

Many countries have established national plans to promote open science, and the European Commission has funded various open and collaborative science projects in recent years. The

implementation of the European Open science Cloud (EOSC)³³ is a major commitment towards open science, offering a platform to upload publications and datasets, as well as access funding programs and support tools.

The EOSC aims to accelerate the transition to more effective Open science and Open Innovation in a Digital Single Market by removing the technical, legislative and human barriers to the re-use of research data and tools, and by supporting access to services, systems and the flow of data across disciplinary, social and geographical borders. (European Commission. Directorate General for Research and Innovation, 2016)

Regarding the “FAIRness” of data, the European Commission itself in The H2020 Program Guidelines on FAIR Data (H2020 Program)³⁴ expressed the principle “data should be as open as possible and as closed as necessary”, in the contribution of Annalisa Landi et al. the aspect of accessibility is discussed, which should be interpreted as follows:

In particular, the letter “A” in FAIR stands for “*Accessible under well-defined conditions*”. The Accessibility principle, included in the FAIR principle, foresees the creation of metadata describing all the conditions for responsible access to and responsible use of data. (Landi et al., 2020)

The metadata scheme, while being as simplified as possible, should make it possible to specify these conditions of access and responsible use.

The European Commission clarifies that the principle refers to any of the necessities, including intellectual property protection:

The exploitation of research results commercially, such as through patenting, is not in contradiction with open science requirements. The decision to publish through open access should follow the decision to publish directly or file a patent application. This means that any invention that beneficiaries file for patent protection, must not have been made public anywhere before filing the application with a patent office. Open access is the default for research data, but exceptions can be made for legitimate interests or other constraints, such as data protection, privacy, and confidentiality. The justification for access restriction must be provided in the DMP (Data Management Plan).³⁵

Universities, in fact, are also recognized as having a role in research for the purpose of exploiting the results for economic purposes:

Over the last thirty years, advanced countries have undergone significant changes in their productive structure, which has had a profound impact on the institutional

³³<https://eosc-portal.eu/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

³⁴https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf (accessed 13 May 2024)

³⁵https://rea.ec.europa.eu/open-science_en#open-science-and-intellectual-property-rights-ipr (accessed 13 May 2024)

structure and overall framework within which universities operate. As a result, universities have had to expand their objectives, combining the traditional aims of training human capital and creating knowledge with an increasing focus on offering and utilizing research results to facilitate their use for economic purposes within their respective territorial areas.³⁶ (Nadotti, 2023)

The principles of open science appear to be taken for granted in the common opinion, if in a study by Simine Vazire it is stated that “for many non-scientists, learning that transparency is not the norm in science comes as a surprise” (Vazire, 2017), and the context of science communication is compared to that of the used car market:

by keeping vital information private – the raw data, the original design and analysis plan, the exploratory analyses that were conducted along the way to the final analysis authors are hiding valuable information and preventing consumers of their manuscript from being certain about its quality. Just like sellers of used cars keep things like the history of the car and any deep structural problems hidden from the buyers. (Vazire, 2017)

Tsuyoshi Miyakawa, journal editor, on the basis of the experience in this role, calls plainly for the establishment of a “data storage infrastructure to enable the securing and sharing of raw data, based on the understanding that ‘no raw data, no science’.” (Miyakawa, 2020)

The discussion about open science practices is ongoing and relevant to the topic of research integrity and reproducibility. Openness is therefore not only seen as a benefit for society, so the openness of research data during the Covid-19 pandemic is an example³⁷, but also as a benefit for the academic community itself.

For advocates, open science is simply “science done right”.³⁸ While the adoption of open science practices varies across different scientific disciplines, a cultural shift is necessary. A study by Hyunjin Song, David M. Markowitz, and Samuel Hardman Taylor found that academics support open science principles and are more likely to view studies that use open science practices as credible. However, authors also recognize the risk of “open washing”, which is the practice of applying open science principles superficially to gain credibility (Song et al., 2022). The same authors also note that “the absence of open science does not

³⁶ Negli ultimi trent’anni, l’evoluzione cui si è assistito nell’assetto produttivo dei Paesi avanzati ha mutato radicalmente l’assetto istituzionale e il quadro generale di riferimento in cui si sono trovate a operare gli atenei. Le università sono state chiamate ad ampliare le proprie finalità istituzionali, affiancando ai tradizionali obiettivi di formazione del capitale umano e di creazione di conoscenza un crescente impegno nelle attività di offerta e sfruttamento dei risultati della ricerca per facilitarne e incentivarne l’utilizzo a fini economici nei rispettivi ambiti territoriali di riferimento [translation in English by the author]

³⁷https://wellcome.org/press-release/sharing-research-data-and-findings-relevant-novel-coronavirus-ncov-outbreak?utm_source=twitter&utm_medium=o-wellcome (accessed 13 May 2024)

³⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1285575>

guarantee bad science, nor its mere presence guarantee good science” (Markowitz et al., 2021).

This cultural shift seems closely linked to the current research evaluation procedures, which determine recognition, prestige, and career advancement through the well-known “*publish or perish*” mechanism and based on the quantitative impact of the journals where researchers publish their articles. In Italy, about the research assessment, Paola Galimberti states that an intended effect of the quantitative evaluation is that “communities have reacted in an adaptive and opportunistic way to the rules imposed at a national level, with the main purpose of reaching the target rather than doing good research” (Galimberti, 2020).

According to Alberto Baccini, who devoted a monographic study on the research evaluation in 2010, the whole mechanism is fed by contemporary economies, where

research and knowledge have become the main factors in determining the wealth of nations. The consequence of this is that governments place very strong attention on the ways in which knowledge is produced and on the use of public resources for research, in view of often short-term economic growth objectives.³⁹ (Baccini, 2010)

In 2012, the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA)⁴⁰ that “recognizes the need to improve the ways in which the outputs of scholarly research are evaluated” was released. First launched by the American Society for Cell Biology in the annual meeting in San Francisco, it has become next a worldwide initiative, signed to date by individuals and institutions from 165 countries.

After 10 years more than 350 organisations among funders, universities, research centres, infrastructures, and associations, from over 40 countries, launched COARA, Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment⁴¹. An agreement with ten commitments that the signatories declare to join. Each of the participants will pursue specific objectives in a specific time.

Among signatories there are many Italian universities and research centres, and the national agency for research assessment ANVUR⁴². As of 17 January 2024, 682 organisations have signed the agreement.⁴³

³⁹ Nelle economie contemporanee la ricerca e la conoscenza sono diventate i fattori principali nella determinazione della ricchezza delle nazioni. La conseguenza di ciò è che i governi pongono un’attenzione molto forte sulle modalità di produzione della conoscenza e sull’uso delle risorse pubbliche per la ricerca, in vista di obiettivi, spesso di breve periodo, di crescita economica. [translation in English by the author]

⁴⁰ <https://sfдора.org/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

⁴¹ <https://coara.eu/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

⁴² <https://www.anvur.it/news/anvur-firmataria-dellagreement-on-reforming-research-assessment/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

⁴³ <https://coara.eu/agreement/signatories/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

We have provided an overview of some initiatives that are currently underway to promote open access and open science, although there are many others that are not mentioned in this account. As our research project primarily focuses on the Italian context, we now include brief descriptions of some Italian initiatives, in addition to joining COARA by ANVUR and many Italian organizations.

In 2022, Italy approved the National Plan for Open science⁴⁴ alongside the National Research Plan 2021-2027. However, there is currently no specific funding allocated to it. Five main axes of intervention are mentioned with their specific objectives:

1. Scientific Publications
2. Research Data
3. Research evaluation
4. Open science, the Scientific Community and European participation
5. Opening of research data on Sars-Cov.2 and Covid-19

The identified objectives include infrastructure interventions and national coordination of various open science initiatives and practices launched in universities and research centres. Additionally, cultural promotion and intervention on the rules governing copyright or evaluation procedures are necessary, harmonized and in coordination with rules and policies at the European level.

As a bottom-up initiative, similarly to other nations, the 15th of December 2023 a group of Italian universities released a monitoring scheme of open science activities (Schema di monitoraggio attività di Open Science)⁴⁵, in line with the fourth objective of the National Plan for Open science. Participation is free and open to all Italian universities and research institutions. The aim of the project is to gather data, on a voluntary basis, about Open Science practices within the Italian universities and research institutes, in order to monitor their evolution over the years through a homogeneous data collection model consistent with European initiatives and to offer data to be evaluated by policy decisors. (Gruppo di lavoro italiano Monitoraggio attività di Open science, 2023)

From 2021 the portal Open-science.it⁴⁶ is online. The portal is a project of the Institute of Information Science and Technologies “Alessandro Faedo” affiliated with the National

⁴⁴ https://www.mur.gov.it/sites/default/files/2023-01/PNSA_2021-27_ENG.pdf (accessed 13 May 2024)

⁴⁵ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10389873>

⁴⁶ <https://open-science.it/de/home> (accessed 13 May 2024)

Research Council of Italy (ISTI CNR)⁴⁷. The portal hosts general information on Open science, training material, events, national and international news, and updates in Italian language.

Italian Computing and Data Infrastructure (ICDI)⁴⁸ is an initiative that involves some Italian research infrastructures and e-infrastructures, with the aim of promoting synergies at the national level and optimising the Italian participation to European initiatives like the European Open science Cloud (EOSC). ICDI has several actions planned, among them the “Competence Centre”, to empower researchers and to support the Italian national community on open science, FAIR principles for open data and the participation to EOSC. The Competence Centre organizes regularly online training sessions called “Open science Café”.

Other “Cafés” are offered by the Italian peer-led consortium of the Reproducibility Network (ITRN)⁴⁹, called “Repro Café”. This association aims to promote open science practices, particularly “identifying factors that contribute to the robustness of research and the replicability of scientific studies and disseminating them within the Italian scientific community” as stated in the webpage.

In 2015 AISA⁵⁰, the Italian Association for the promotion of open science, (in Italian: Associazione Italiana per la promozione della Scienza Aperta) was founded. AISA aims to promote open science culture and principles by providing training programs, international cooperation, and advocating for policy changes on intellectual property and research assessment among Italian and European decision-makers.

The Conference of Italian University Rectors (CRUI)⁵¹ established a Working Group on Open access, following the Berlin Declaration signed by 71 of its members. This group released several guidelines on best practices for open access, including recommendations on institutional open archives, the types of materials that should be deposited, and fully open access and interoperable electronic journals. The working group also coordinated the definition of procedures for harvesting doctoral theses at the National Central Libraries of Florence and Rome.

⁴⁷ <https://www.isti.cnr.it/en/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

⁴⁸ <https://www.icdi.it/en/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

⁴⁹ <https://www.itrn.org/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

⁵⁰ <https://aisa.sp.unipi.it/about-aisa/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

⁵¹ <https://cruir.it/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

2.4 Librarians “in the open”

The Internet and digital technologies have greatly contributed to redefining the professional skills of librarians, particularly academic librarians. They are no longer limited to supporting members of the academic community as readers but have expanded their roles to become part of the research ecosystem supporting researchers as authors.

First, instead of managing just physical media, they started to manage digital content and to negotiate access rights for their users. However, as discussed in section 2.1, the costs of digital content, especially academic journals, have become unsustainable, leading to cuts in collections: “They buy as much as they can from that core [journals] set. In effect, it has become the “must” set”. (Guédon, 2010).

The open access movement was welcomed for aiming global equity and for the potential of accelerating and improving scientific research. Furthermore, it seemed a solution to the “serials crisis”, as librarians have always been sensitive to the issue of access to information by their users. This is in line with Ranganathan's five laws of librarianship which are all centred on the user, particularly laws No. 2 and No. 3, at the time referring to books:

1. Books are for use.
2. Every person his or her book.
3. Every book its reader.
4. Save the time of the reader.
5. A library is a growing organism. (Ranganathan, 1957)

In the part of the Bethesda statement edited by the Libraries & Publishers Working Group, it is stated that “open access will be an essential component of scientific publishing in the future and that works reporting the results of current scientific research should be as openly accessible and freely useable as possible” (Bethesda Statement on Open access Publishing, 2003). Libraries propose three interventions:

Develop and support mechanisms to make the transition to open access publishing and to provide examples of these mechanisms to the community.

In our education and outreach activities, give high priority to teaching our users about the benefits of open access publishing and open access journals.

List and highlight open access journals in our catalogs and other relevant databases (Bethesda Statement on Open access Publishing, 2003).

After two decades, librarians have begun to apply all three points at different stages, proportionately to their autonomous leeway in the research ecosystem.

Secondly, they got involved in managing open repositories of publications, subsequently open data repositories, advocacy and training activities, editing policies, supporting researchers and so on.

An OECD report states that

Libraries, repositories, and data centres are key actors for and fundamental enablers of open science. Libraries have adapted their role and are now active in the preservation, curation, publication and dissemination of digital scientific materials, in the form of publications, data and other research-related content. Libraries and repositories constitute the physical infrastructure that allows scientists to share, use and reuse the outcome of their work, and they have been essential in the creation of the open science movement. (OECD, 2015)

Gema Bueno de la Fuente, in a Foster⁵² webpage, refers to several competencies required to librarians in the open science field, “to fulfil their role of enablers”:

- Ability to advise on preserving research outputs;
- Knowledge to advise on data management and curation, including ingest, discovery, access, dissemination, preservation, and portability;
- Knowledge to support researchers in complying with the various mandates of funders, including open access requirements;
- Knowledge to advise on potential data manipulation tools used in the discipline/subject;
- Knowledge to advise on data mining;
- Knowledge to advocate, and advise on, the use of metadata;
- Ability to advise on the preservation of project records (e. g. correspondence);
- Knowledge of sources of research funding to assist researchers to identify potential funders;
- Skills to develop metadata schema, and advise on discipline/subject standards and practices, for individual research projects. (Bueno de la Fuente, 2016)

One may say, “Who trains the trainer?” From our perspective, formal library and information science education is not enough to prepare librarians for their future roles. Instead, competencies will rely more on informal and non-formal learning, benchmarking, and learning from other professionals such as data stewards, computer scientists, and specialists.

⁵² <https://www.fosteropenscience.eu/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

The key to success will be sharing, interconnection, and openness among different communities.

Just a recent example, during the LIBER Winter event 2023 held in Fiesole (Florence) on 23 and 24 November 2023, the project of a shared learning hub for librarians dealing with open science was presented: “a series of guides, or curricula, containing recommendations for specific learning activities [...] The aim is to break down the barriers that librarians may encounter during their learning process⁵³. LIBER stands for Ligue des Bibliothèques Européennes de Recherche – Association of European Research Libraries and it claims that it is the voice of Europe’s research library community. Around 420 members participate, the network includes goal-oriented partnerships with other type of organisations.

The global representative organisation IFLA, International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions⁵⁴, released in 2022 a statement on open access after 10 years from the first one, saying that

“Full and immediate free access to research outputs and publications ensures that everyone – including researchers, policy makers, citizens, scientists, and the public – has the data, evidence, and knowledge they need to address societal, environmental, and global challenges”.⁵⁵

Librarians are involved in several EU-funded projects, for example, ORE, Open Research Europe, the “open access publishing venue for European Commission-funded researchers across all disciplines”⁵⁶, or DIAMAS⁵⁷, the European project that aims to support and improve the open access journals published by non-profit organizations, like university and library press.

To briefly mention the Italian situation, Rossana Morriello in 2019 summarized the support of librarians to research and open practices: “The most specific areas that require librarians’ expertise are management of the Current Research Information System (CRIS) and the institutional repository, support in the assessment procedures, and support in the development of open access” (Morriello, 2019).

⁵³ <https://libereurope.eu/eventscalendar/liber-winter-event-2023-in-florence-italy/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

⁵⁴ <https://www.ifla.org/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

⁵⁵ <https://www.ifla.org/news/10-years-of-the-ifla-open-access-statement-a-call-to-action/>(accessed 13 May 2024)

⁵⁶ <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

⁵⁷ <https://diamasproject.eu/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

In Italy, a concrete example of the evolution of services and structures around open science is offered by the University of Milan and described by Paola Galimberti in 2020. The author talks about the crucial need of a cultural change by faculty. The university started interventions 15 years before and she describes five main points: the creation of a working group dedicated to open science practices and support to researchers' community for the institutional repository, the university press, the institutional assessment; a standing committee on open science, with one researcher representative per each department, who discusses documents and policies; training sessions open to those representatives or PhD students; monitoring activities, clearly outlined to reach yearly objectives; taking part of international networks. Galimberti recognizes that the way of the University of Milan cannot be a standard for all universities, however, after 15 years it is verified that some of the open science practices introduced are well established among faculty. (Galimberti, 2020)

The librarians' community seems aware of the importance of opening access to research findings and, more generally, willing and able to be fully engaged in open science.

2.5 Scientific research as an ecosystem

According to the Oxford English Dictionary an ecosystem is

“A biological system composed of all the organisms found in a particular physical environment, interacting with it and with each other. Also in extended use: a complex system resembling this”. (Oxford English Dictionary, 2023)

We have mentioned the stages of the research process and have compared research as an ecosystem several times so far. An interesting article by Samuel G. Robson et al. proposed some targets in relation to open science, for each category of the “research ecosystem” identified as researchers, students, universities, departments, journals, funders and so on. About libraries it is said:

Libraries are already actively engaged in Open access, managing research data, and other areas directly relevant to open research, but can struggle to have broader impact. To connect library services to the broader Open science agenda, libraries require a more holistic approach; one that promotes and advocates broadly for Open access and research data management across the research life cycle. A shift towards

library staff having strong research backgrounds may also benefit a more holistic support of Open science. (Robson et al., 2021)

Research ecosystem is often used to refer to the complexity of the research cycle in its context and with its actors and stakeholders, both treating the topic of the research in general (Bhatt, 2021; Munafò et al., 2022; Recio-Saucedo et al., 2022) or referring to single disciplines. (Rubagumya et al., 2022; Tsui and McKiernan, 2022; Yang et al., 2022)

A recent Italian example: in January 2024, the University of Florence held a conference titled “The Evaluation of Research to the Test of Facts: Models, Policies, and Ongoing Projects”. The conference was organized by the Research Observatory of the University of Florence and the University Library System, in collaboration with Wikimedia Italia. The first session focused on the critical issues of the “*current research ecosystem*”. It seems that discussing on openness has played a role in experimenting and rethinking the entire research process in its context and with all its stakeholders⁵⁸.

2.6 Legal aspects

The debate on openness and open science has raised questions about intellectual property protection. Copyright has its origins in the printing privilege that was granted for the first time to Johann von Speyer in 1469 by the Republic of Venice. This privilege allowed him to print under a monopoly regime for five years in the Venetian territories.

On the death of the printer, which occurred a few months later, the privilege lapsed, but a form of protection remained

for innovations applicable in printing processes or for the publication of literary, scientific and artistic works. In this second case, the system of privileges, created to protect (and promote) new 'businesses' and technical innovations, was translated to the book sector, equating each new edition with a new invention, a new 'industry' in the economic sense. In essence, each new edition was considered an innovation. On the other hand, the role of 'inventor' was attributed to the printer or author and as such deserved to be legally protected because with his ingenuity he made a contribution to the cultural and economic development of the State.⁵⁹ (Squassina, 2019)

⁵⁸ https://www.sba.unifi.it/upload/seminario_17gen2024.pdf (accessed 13 May 2024)

⁵⁹ “Per innovazioni applicabili nei processi di stampa o per la pubblicazione di opere letterarie, scientifiche e artistiche. In questo secondo caso, il sistema dei privilegi, nato a protezione (e promozione) di nuove ‘imprese’

Two general reflections to continue the discussion in the present day, coming from the introduction chapter of the same book: “Economic history has seen privileges as a suitable tool for expressing real public policies to encourage invention, technology transfer and entrepreneurial and proto-industrial initiative⁶⁰” (Nuovo, 2019). “What the system of privileges creates, in effect, is an artificial scarcity of the good-book, which is indispensable if knowledge is to be constructed in such a way as to assume the function of a commodity”⁶¹ (Nuovo, 2019). As introduced in section 2.1, a condition of scarcity has also been created for scientific publications, determining the growth of a publishing market from private initiative highly remunerative.

Copyright is a regulated issue across the world. At the start of open-source initiatives, licenses were formulated to release works that were protected by the respective national systems. These licenses are known as “open” licenses and Creative Commons⁶² (CC) licenses are a popular example of these. CC licenses, currently at version 4.0, were created by a U.S.-based nonprofit organization in the early 2000s. They aim to manage copyright in the most suitable way for the Internet and digital technologies. These licenses allow the author to define the rights that the author reserves to the users of the document, according to the “some rights reserved” model. They are based on copyright and apply to any work protected by copyright. To license a work through CC, the basic prerequisite is to be the owner of the rights granted with the license or to have explicit authorization from the owner of the rights.

Four basic clauses have been formulated and the combination of them expresses what the owner of the rights allows the user to do. Despite of the rights allowed the author is always recognized the author of the work and maintains the right to the integrity of the work.

e innovazioni tecniche, venne traslato al settore librario equiparando ogni nuova edizione ad un nuovo ritrovato, a una nuova ‘industria’ in senso economico. In sostanza, ogni nuova edizione venne considerata un’innovazione. Specularmente veniva attribuito allo stampatore o autore il ruolo di ‘inventore’ e in quanto tale meritevole di essere legalmente tutelato poiché con il suo ingegno apportava un contributo allo sviluppo culturale ed economico dello Stato.” [translation in English by the author]

⁶⁰ “La storia economica ha visto nei privilegi uno strumento adatto ad esprimere vere e proprie politiche pubbliche di incoraggiamento dell’invenzione, del trasferimento tecnologico e dell’iniziativa imprenditoriale e proto-industriale.” [translation in English by the author]

⁶¹ “Ciò che il sistema dei privilegi crea, in effetti, è una scarsità artificiale del bene-libro, indispensabile se la conoscenza deve essere costruita in modo tale da assumere la funzione di merce” [translation in English by the author]

⁶² <https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/cclicenses/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

The common practice before “openness” was the transfer of all economic exploitation rights, which are in any case limited in time, to the publisher. For the publication of an open access scientific work, the application of CC licenses is the most common solution, provided that the author has retained the right of publication for himself or has obtained the permission back later, having initially transferred all the rights to the publisher. Unfortunately, more and more often this benefit has turned into a burden, especially an economic burden for the researcher⁶³, and especially if it has been a matter of complying with the requests of the research funds allocated.

Research funding agencies, such as the European Commission, have placed specific clauses in their calls for proposals to encourage the opening up of research findings. It must be said that often the costs of publication are reimbursed by the funding plans themselves. However, this obligation has contributed to increasing the demand for immediate open access publications, i.e. at the time of first publication by the publisher, and not after a specific waiting time, the so-called “*embargo*”, in journals that were prestigious and useful for the career of researchers. This contributed increasing the costs of APCs. Some agencies are no longer willing to reimburse APCs in journals that are not full open access. Numerous universities and research centres have implemented policies to encourage the open publication of research findings. As part of this effort, affiliated researchers are required to submit a version of their article to open access. This version can be a preprint, postprint, or published version. However, this requirement does not completely resolve the issue, given the complex framework surrounding it.

Roberto Caso's studies dedicated to open science in relation to copyright and intellectual property speak of open science as an “unfinished revolution”. Noting that

it must be admitted that the power of commercial intermediaries has increased considerably over the last twenty years. It is not a question of demonizing the market. Commercial actors – in a capitalist system – can and must play a role in the communication of science. But the point is another: it is necessary to understand whether scientific institutions such as universities can represent a complementary system and not subordinate to that of a highly concentrated market⁶⁴. (Caso, 2019)

⁶³ In one of the webinars on open access publishing addressed by the author to some PhD students at the Università degli studi di Perugia, it emerged that APCs were commonly called “open access tax.”

⁶⁴ “Occorre ammettere che negli ultimi venti anni il potere degli intermediari commerciali è notevolmente aumentato. Non si tratta di demonizzare il mercato. Gli attori commerciali – in un sistema capitalistico – possono e devono svolgere un ruolo nella comunicazione della scienza. Ma il punto è un altro: è necessario capire se le istituzioni scientifiche come le università possono rappresentare un sistema complementare e non subordinato a quello di un mercato fortemente concentrato” [translation in English by the author]

Caso identifies five macro-causes of the unfinished revolution (see Caso, 2019 for an exhaustive reading). In this chapter, the last one mentioned is reported:

The incoherence of supranational, state, and institutional policies. OA (Open access) and OS (Open science) are spontaneous phenomena that have emerged in the academic world. The oligopolistic system that exists within academia has proven to be strong and has only become stronger over time. Some members of the OS movement believe that policies need to be implemented by governing bodies such as supranational organizations, states, funding bodies, universities, and scientific societies. These policies have resulted in positive developments such as the creation of necessary infrastructure for the open science system. However, they do have some drawbacks and side effects. These policies can lead to bureaucratic processes, are not consistent globally, and can be affected by contradictions.⁶⁵ (Caso, 2019)

According to the author, an obstacle that prevents the expansion of open access scientific publications lies in the current copyright legislation and in not considering its possible modifications, as done by some funding agencies or research institutions, whose interventions could be a limitation of the author's scientific freedom. (Caso, 2019)

In this regard, in 2022 the European Commission released a study on copyright in Europe with reference to the results of scientific research and open access (European Commission. Directorate General for Research and Innovation, 2022). There are two possible avenues of intervention, one of a non-legislative nature and one of a legislative nature. It makes a few recommendations for each of them, which are briefly explained here. For a more detailed and exhaustive examination, please refer to Miriana Fierro's Italian Master's Thesis in Law, dedicated to transformative agreements. (Fierro, 2023)

Non-legislative interventions concern employers of researchers that may establish regulations to withhold publication rights on the works of their affiliates. However, these regulations should be limited to only what is strictly necessary for the publication of open access works. On the other hand, publishers have a responsibility to offer clear communication and make explicit commitments to the open access publication of works.

From a legislative perspective, there are four potential scenarios to consider. The first is to harmonize legislation across Europe. The second is to make the exception for scientific research, as outlined in Directive 2001/29/EC on the harmonization of certain aspects of

⁶⁵ “L'incoerenza delle politiche sovranazionali, statali e istituzionali. L'OA [Open access] e l'OS [Open Science] sono fenomeni sorti spontaneamente [...] Il sistema oligopolistico si è dimostrato molto forte e si è irrobustito nel tempo. Allora, una parte del movimento dell'OS ha pensato che ci fosse bisogno di politiche da parte di chi governa le istituzioni scientifiche (organismi sovranazionali, stati, enti finanziatori, università e società scientifiche). Queste politiche hanno avuto effetti positivi come lo sviluppo delle infrastrutture necessarie al sistema della scienza aperta. Ma soffrono di alcune controindicazioni ed effetti collaterali: burocratizzano i processi, sono disomogenee rispetto a un fenomeno per sua natura globale e sono affette da contraddizioni evidenti” [translation in English by the author]

copyright and related rights in the information society, mandatory and clarify its language. The third scenario involves introducing the right of second publication at the European level. Finally, there is the option to harmonize legislation on authorship and first property rights in copyright at the European level, extending it to all works or only to scientific publications. It is interesting that the discussion is shifting on the identification of a human right to open science, and ultimately a right to research, moving from the article 27 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights:

1. Everyone has the right freely to participate in the cultural life of the community, to enjoy the arts and to share in scientific advancement and its benefits.
2. Everyone has the right to the protection of the moral and material interests resulting from any scientific, literary or artistic production of which he is the author,

In terms of human rights the discussion can also be referred to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs),⁶⁶ particularly the fourth: “Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all”. Fierro clearly discusses the point citing other documents (Fierro, 2023).

A final note regarding the Italian scenario: AISA association, previously mentioned, suggests an amendment⁶⁷ to the Italian law on copyright, with the aim of granting a second publication right to the authors of scientific works such as articles published in journals, chapters published in collective books and monographs financed by research funds, as it is in other European countries like Germany, Austria, Netherlands, France, Belgium. (Fierro, 2023).

It should be remembered that in Italy, in 2019, an attempt was made to discuss in parliament a proposal to amend the 1941 copyright law,⁶⁸ aimed at regulating open access to scientific publications, known as the “Gallo law proposal.”⁶⁹ Although it was presented and approved by the Chamber of Deputies, it was never submitted to the Senate of the Republic for final approval.

Since 2013, a law⁷⁰ has asked to publish open access the results of research funded by public funds for an equal or greater share of 50%. This can be done in institutional or disciplinary

⁶⁶ <https://sdgs.un.org/goals> (accessed 13 May 2024)

⁶⁷ <https://aisa.sp.unipi.it/attivita/diritto-di-ripubblicazione-in-ambito-scientifico/novella/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

⁶⁸ Law No. 633 of the 22nd of April 1941 (Last update to the act published on the 30th of December 2023): <https://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:legge:1941-04-22:633> (accessed 13 May 2024)

⁶⁹ <https://www.senato.it/leg/18/BGT/Schede/Ddliter/51466.htm> (accessed 13 May 2024)

⁷⁰ Law No. 91 of the 8th of August 2013, art. 4, no. 2:

repositories. The law requires that the publication should be documented in scientific periodicals (literally, “that have at least two annual issues”). The embargo, allowed from the first publication, is 18 months for publications in the scientific-technical-medical disciplinary areas and 24 months for the disciplinary areas of humanities and social sciences. Being subjected to interpretation, concretely, the law in itself did not determine any significant change in open-access dissemination of the results of the Italian research.

The Italian law on intellectual property, that is currently in effect, dates back to 1941. Although it has undergone some modifications over the years, attempts to revise it more comprehensively have been unsuccessful. The law still does not properly cover the use of intellectual property in libraries or for research and educational purposes. This issue was highlighted in a paper by Antonella De Robbio in 2013. (De Robbio, 2013).

2.7 Ethical aspects

This section provides to put in evidence the link between the PhD program in Ethics of Communication, Scientific Research and Technology Innovation and the topic of the thesis.

The aim of the present research was to understand the impact of Transformative Agreements on scientific communication. The research evaluated the opportunities and the critical issues of TAs, with a particular focus on the Italy case. How to disseminate research findings is a major part of the research cycle or, better, the research ecosystem, and it has ethical implications.

The research topic is a part of the broader theme of open access to research findings and the principles and practices of open science. UNESCO has already stated that opening research processes should be beneficial for science and society. (UNESCO, 2021) Improving transparency and sharing through collaborative networks of scientists should also increase reproducibility and trust in science by the public and by researchers’ communities. Many researchers think that the research findings arising from public funding should be publicly and openly accessible. Some others sustain that accessing without barriers to research findings accelerates global research and innovation and increases knowledge.

<https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2013/10/08/13A08109/sg> (accessed 13 May 2024)

Access to information and knowledge is a commitment for libraries and librarians, their community advocate any attempt to remove barriers and facilitate that everyone meets the information needed. The IFLA statement on open access underlines the aspect, to address societal and global challenges. Libraries are engaged to address those challenges, also referring to the Sustainable Development Goals, all of which require access to information. Barbara Lison, IFLA past president (2021-2023), said that

There is one generic goal that brings it all together: Goal 16, Peace, justice, and strong institutions. And sub-goal 16.10 states that free access to information is a basic precondition for reaching it. So, you could say that 16.10 is the library goal – that’s us – even if libraries are not mentioned explicitly. One of the indicators that demonstrate 16.10 has been achieved is the presence of a constitutional right to free access to information in countries or the existence of a well-established process for ensuring free access.⁷¹

Chapter summary

The second chapter provides an overview of the context in which the research project is running. Firstly, the main characteristics of the scholarly publishing system are described. Secondly, the origin of the open access movement and its implementation methods are explained. The chapter then moves on to discuss open science and its practices, such as open data and open peer review. Next, the role of librarians in the “open panorama” is presented, including some international and Italian initiatives. Finally, the concept that scientific research is an ecosystem comprising different actors and stakeholders is discussed. The chapter also highlights open licenses and some legal aspects related to opening publications within the current law framework. Ethical aspects particularly relevant to the doctoral program are outlined in the end.

⁷¹ <https://blog.degruyter.com/libraries-exist-to-serve-the-sustainable-development-goals-an-interview-with-barbara-lison/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

3 Literature review

First, we want to underline the journal publisher commitments in Bethesda statement. In 2003 they proposed to:

Commit to providing an open access option for any research article published in any of the journals they publish.

Declare a specific timetable for transition of journals to open access models.

Work with other publishers of open access works and interested parties to develop tools for authors and publishers to facilitate publication of manuscripts in standard electronic formats suitable for archival storage and efficient searching.

Ensure that open access models requiring author fees lower barriers to researchers at demonstrated financial disadvantage, particularly those from developing countries. (Bethesda Statement on Open access Publishing, 2003)

We want to mention the Finch report, released in 2012 from the Working Group on Expanding Access to Published Research Findings “to examine how UK-funded research findings can be made more accessible”⁷². The group included “representatives of the HE [Higher Education] sector, research funders, the research community, scholarly publishers, and libraries”⁷³. To summarize the report encouraged to implement the gold road (with APC payment) instead of the green road (self-archiving at no cost), going so far as to recommend “it would be unreasonable to require embargo periods of less than twelve months”. (Working Group on Expanding Access to Published Research Findings, 2012). In any case, in its conclusions, the report advises that

the measures we recommend will bring greater competition on price as well as the status of the journals in which researchers wish to publish. We therefore expect market competition to intensify, and that universities and funders should be able to use their power as purchasers to bear down on the costs to them both of APCs and of subscriptions. (Working Group on Expanding Access to Published Research Findings, 2012)

Over twenty years, open access publication still concerns (or for now) the minority of articles, and, in any case, the major international commercial publishers remain the protagonists in the dissemination of scientific communication, also because of the prestige enjoyed by the journals they publish and the link between them and individual and

⁷² <https://www.researchinfonet.org/finch/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

⁷³ <https://www.researchinfonet.org/finch/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

institutional evaluation processes. As described earlier, recently, publishers have offered authors the option of paying Article Processing Charges to make individual articles published open access in journals that remain on a subscription basis, generating a “double dipping”.

The main source of revenue for publishers arises from subscriptions. In 2019 The European University Association⁷⁴ released a report titled “2019 Big Deals Survey Report” in which the expenditure on “big deals” subscription agreements is esteemed by data gathered from the European consortia. It is stated that “an estimated €475,267,400 is spent annually on Periodicals Big Deals with these five major publishers alone (data from 29 consortia).” (Morais et al., 2019) The five major publishers are: American Chemical Society, Elsevier, SpringerNature, Taylor and Francis, Wiley. Their shares are:

Elsevier 56%;

Wiley 18%;

SpringerNature 16%;

Taylor and Francis 7%;

American Chemical Society 3%.

Two major initiatives on open access were not mentioned in the previous chapter because they heavily influenced the process of negotiating transformative agreements on which the literature review of this chapter focuses.

The Max Planck Society led the Berlin Declaration initiative. Since then, it organized the Berlin Open access conferences⁷⁵ to discuss the state of the art and the progress of open access. During Berlin OA 12th conference in 2015 *the OA2020 program*⁷⁶ was launched. These are the three main goals stated:

Transform the core of today’s scholarly journals from subscription to OA publishing in accordance with community-specific publication preferences.

Pursue this transformation process by converting resources currently spent on journal subscriptions into funds to support sustainable OA business models.

Engage all parties involved in scholarly publishing, in particular universities, research institutions, funders, libraries, and publishers in transformative actions to

⁷⁴ <https://eua.eu/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

⁷⁵ <https://openaccess.mpg.de/Berlin-Conferences> (accessed 13 May 2024)

⁷⁶ <https://oa2020.org/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

achieve a rapid and efficient transition for the benefit of scholarship and society at large.⁷⁷

The goals come from a white paper, discussed later, written by Ralf Schimmer, Kai Karin Geschuhn, and Andreas Vogler, working at the time at the Max Planck Digital Library.

A second initiative took place in 2018: a group of funding agencies called Coalition S established 10 principles in a plan, called *Plan S*⁷⁸. The goal is to increase rapidly the number of open access articles being published by funding research projects that publish their outputs openly. This includes even hybrid journals, through transformative agreements between institutions and publishers. It is expected that the large part of hybrid journals soon become full open access journals. Plan S stands for Plan Speed.

The 8th principle states:

The Funders do not support the ‘hybrid’ model of publishing. However, as a transitional pathway towards full Open access within a clearly defined timeframe, and only as part of transformative arrangements, Funders may contribute to financially supporting such arrangements.

In a report from Clarivate Analytics (the company that owns the Web of Science database) they predicted the impact of Plan S by analysing 2017 data from Web of Science, concluding that

increased and more open access to research outcomes is a public good. If an accelerated shift towards this can be balanced with careful implementation and the retention of those features of the research publishing system that have been of such benefit to society and the economy over the last century then the debate and the effort will be amply repaid. (Quaderi et al., 2019)

Thus, a growing number of institutions, in Europe and beyond, started negotiations for transformative agreements in which not only access to content is regulated and paid for, but also the possibility of publishing in open access in the journals subscribed by researchers affiliated with those institutions.

⁷⁷ <https://oa2020.org/be-informed/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

⁷⁸ https://www.Coalition S.org/plan_s_principles/ (accessed 13 May 2024)

3.1 What are the transformative agreements

ESAC, Efficiency and Standards for Article Charges, is the initiative coordinated by the Max Planck Digital Library that aims to monitor the costs of publishing scientific communication and foster good practices in adopting the transformative agreements it tracks in the ESAC Registry. ESAC states:

Transformative agreement (TA) is an umbrella term ... describing those agreements negotiated between institutions (libraries, national and regional consortia) and publishers in which former subscription expenditures are repurposed to support open access publishing, thus transforming the business model.⁷⁹ (ESAC Initiative)

Lisa Hinchliffe reminds that few “pilot” agreements with publishers with some clauses on open access publishing were established in subscriptions agreements before Plan S but Plan S brought the transformative agreements on the main stage. (Hinchliffe, 2020) Among the differences, there are some key principles and components:

Costs. Libraries seek transformative agreements to shift from paying subscriptions to paying for publishing with the goal of furthering movement toward an open access publishing ecosystem. [...]

Copyright. Transformative agreements tend to require that copyright be retained by the author and not transferred to the publisher. [...]

Transparency. Principles for transformative agreements often insist that the terms of any such agreements be made publicly available. [...]

Transitional. Definitionally, transformative agreements are transitional in that they seek a pathway for a shift away from payment to read and toward payment to publish. They are predicated on an end state in which subscription-based reading payments cease to exist. [...] (Hinchliffe, 2020)

Transparency is crucial, but it's rare for the entire agreement to be made public, which is concerning. Much frequently only the features registered into the ESAC Registry are public, for example the estimated number of articles to be published open access.

So, agreements do not have a standard. To date, they can be grouped into three categories, depending on the type of costs considered:

Offsetting agreements. These are quite similar to traditional subscription agreements, over the expenditure for subscription, there are APC discounts, or a limited number of articles publishable in open access for free.

⁷⁹ <https://esac-initiative.org/about/transformative-agreements/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

Read and publish. These are generally subscription based too, they “emphasize on bundling of costs of reading and publishing into one, with enhanced benefits of publishing” (Bansode and Pujar, 2022). These could not have limitation on the number of articles publishable in open access.

Publish and read. These “emphasize on paying only for publishing while reading comes at no cost” (Bansode and Pujar, 2022).

There is not a model; associations like LIBER outlined some principles⁸⁰ in 2017; ESAC releases recommendations⁸¹ and an overview of guidelines and principles⁸² settled and shared by consortia, based on their experiences and policies.

It is interesting the attention drawn to small publishers too, like scientific societies, university or library presses, small independent presses: in 2023 a toolkit to foster open access agreement for small publishers was published, after a multi-working groups analysis and reflection (Wise and Estelle, 2023). The toolkit provides principles to negotiate transformative or subscribe to open (S2O) model arrangements.

The *subscribe to open model* is

a pragmatic funding model that allows a publisher to convert journals from gated access to OA one year at a time. S2O offers a journal's current subscribers continued access at a discount off the regular subscription price. If current subscribers participate in the S2O offer, the publisher opens the content covered by that year's subscription. If participation is not sufficient – for example, if some subscribers delay renewing in the expectation that they can gain access without participating – then the content remains gated. (Crow et al., 2020)

In this model, there are no financial risks for the publisher. This model could be preferable for small publishers. However, libraries investing in open access publishing do not have the certainty that their investments will pay off.

A 2021 study conducted a first comparison between agreements registered by ESAC, highlighting how the focus of negotiation has shifted from cost containment to the inclusion of open access publication clauses. “Transformative Agreement” is an umbrella concept that encompasses many variations of publishing agreements with publishers, and the studio orders them into “pre-transformative”, partially transformative, and totally transformative.

⁸⁰ <https://libereurope.eu/article/open-access-five-principles-for-negotiations-with-publishers/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

⁸¹ <https://esac-initiative.org/about/transformative-agreements/reference-guide/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

⁸² <https://esac-initiative.org/guidelines/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

Common traits are highlighted, such as the - expected - greater transparency of content compared to previous agreements and the possibility for authors to keep for themselves the publishing rights, which are normally ceded to publishers in traditional practice. (Borrego et al., 2021)

The fundamental requirement of TAs is temporariness until the goal of definitive agreements that make all journals fully and permanently open access is achieved. This seems to be the most precarious requirement, since the first renewals have been completed in Europe; therefore, a second round of transformative agreements is expected globally, and in Italy too. Some agreements include the APC payment for articles published in full open access journals along that for articles in hybrid journals. A journal that completes the transformation to become fully open access is usually called “*flipped journal*”.

There is no standard about TAs, there are no clear boundaries between models, there is no single definition in what is “transformative” and what is not, depending on the characteristics and the consequences of an agreement. With Hinchliffe words:

we may face the reality that the same contract might be listed as transformative by ESAC but considered not transformative by cOAlition S. This is not unlike the question of whether “bronze” open access is really open access. It depends on who you ask. [...] As for defining a “transformative agreement” *per se*, we know from attempts to define open access that definitions are debatable, debated, and continuously emergent. Reflected in this essay is a synthesis of the current terminology as used in recent contracts and policy documents. Given this is a fast-developing area, it is likely that the language will continue to be refined over time. (Hinchliffe, 2020)

Very clearly, in the BOAI recommendations, released in 2022, it is stated that

we’ll refer to these agreements collectively as “read-and-publish” agreements, while acknowledging that there are many variations on the theme. We don’t use the term “transformative” because it’s not self-explanatory, because it preempts a useful term that could apply to other transformative or transformational initiatives, and because it’s more honorific than descriptive. (Budapest Open Access Initiative: 20th anniversary recommendations, 2022)

Among society publishers there are some that are planning to change business models in 2025 from Read and publish to Subscribe to open, as announced by the Biochemical Society.⁸³ (Hoogendoorn and Redvers-Mutton, 2024)

⁸³ <https://www.biochemistry.org/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

3.2 A tour worldwide

Several articles have been published regarding experiences of negotiating transformative agreements.

Austria signed his first offset agreement in 2014 with IOP, the Institute of Physics, it was the first of that kind. The experience of the University of Vienna stressed the importance of a clear and straightforward open access workflow, for example on eligible authors or on the identification of the corresponding author, observing that every agreement has a workflow different from others. The authors underline that consortia should ask for workflow improvements and experiment performance-related payments for an amount of the sum agreed (Pinhasi et al., 2018).

In 2020, Pinhasi et al. reflected on issues related to sustainability and observed that the fees for Gold Open access were increasing at a faster pace than expected (Pinhasi et al., 2020). In a 2021 paper, the Austrian consortium evaluated the “Austrian Transition to Open Access” (AT2OA) and the involvement of funding agencies, national consortium, universities, and research institutes. The paper emphasized the significance of having a clear workflow and high-quality bibliographic metadata for monitoring and evaluating agreements. At a consortium level, it was noted that “disparity between some institutions’ existing subscription spend and their publishing output was evident from early on” (Pinhasi et al., 2021). As a result, a redistribution of costs was implemented in the medium term, generating an internal debate within the consortium.

The redistribution in a consortium is an issue in the perspective of sustainability of TAs for single members. Another advise on this is coming also from the Swedish consortium: “As some organizations are research intensive and some are not, a fair and transparent model for a required cost reallocation must also be developed.” (Lundén et al., 2018). In addition, in Sweden “in order to reach the target of immediate OA on publication of publicly funded research outputs by 2026 set by the Swedish Government, there is a strong need for institutional reallocation of funds” (Lundén et al., 2018). The impression is that costs are increasing over the initial previsions.

About this, Earney in 2018 wrote that

Open access Coordination Group monitoring the UK transition to OA suggested that offsetting agreements had acted as a constraint on rises in APCs for hybrid journals. This constraint may come in a number of forms such as discounts on the cost of APCs, credits based on overall spend with a publisher which can be redeemed against the cost of either subscriptions or APCs, or agreements which for a single fee include subscriptions and APCs. The overall impact of such schemes is to limit any increases in the overall cost to an institution. (Earney, 2018)

The same author reports several data from a national monitoring, for example that “of UK outputs, 37% (vs. 25% globally) are freely available to the world immediately on publication, either through gold or green OA”. On the other hand, “the average APC increased in cost by 16% between 2013 and 2016” and “the average cost of an APC is over 25% higher in hybrid OA journals than pure gold OA journals” (Earney, 2018).

Parmed and Säll, talking again of Sweden, underline the impact of the transformative agreements on the profession of librarians too, with new tasks and workflows that demand acquiring new competencies. Authors find them in different categories:

Communications. Researchers affiliated should be well informed and updated.

Verification process. Often through a dashboard, it should report full metadata, clear data about the corresponding author and a way to easily communicate with the publisher.

Eligibility. Verification on the compliance of the request to all the clauses of the agreement it is required and very often there are case to study on.

Publication types. It clearly could be specified the article type, in case of limitation on the number of articles per year, they state that is preferable to open a research article than a commentary.

Title changes. Flipped journals could not be in the TAs anymore, so changes should happen at the end of agreements to be clear from the beginning if the journal is eligible or not. (Parmhed and Säll, 2023)

Germany, through the DEAL Konsortium⁸⁴, put in place a national alliance between institutions in order to negotiate with three of the five major publishers in the market. In a recent study on OA in German landscape, it is said that

Even though transformative agreements are met with scepticism for a number of reasons, including the costs, distributional effects within the German research system and their focus on the three largest publishers that have contributed a lot to the serials crisis in the past, the analysis shows that they are an effective means for the OA transformation with impact on the landscape as a whole. (Taubert et al., 2023)

⁸⁴ <https://deal-konsortium.de/en/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

The same authors released a second part of their studies in 2024 more focusing on open archives: indeed a multiperspective data gathering and data analysis is required to investigate about open access in a country. (Taubert et al., 2024)

A report released in France in 2021 by the French Committee for Open science⁸⁵ analysed the transformative agreements until concluding that TAs are not suitable for a stable transition to open access publishing. One of the causes is that

contractual clauses mechanically prevent the move towards fully open access production. The systematic choice to limit eligible articles to corresponding authors from the institutions, the voluntary nature of the approach in almost all agreements, the limited volume of publishable articles, the choice of a restricted scope, excluding in particular journals supposedly the most prestigious ones (The Lancet, Cell, Nature...) are all factors leading to the exclusion of many articles from open access⁸⁶. (Dufour et al., 2021)

According to the report, the TAs reveal not to be really oriented to openness but more oriented in shifting institutions' expenditure from subscriptions to open access publishing, which is slightly different. Indeed, France has only four transformative agreements registered in ESAC Registry, started very recently. In April 2023 the French consortium Couperin updated strict guidelines⁸⁷ to negotiate future agreements. In the framework of the French national plan on open science it has launched online a "barometer of open science in France"⁸⁸.

In Spain, negotiations at national level started after an alliance between the CRUE, the Spanish National Rectors' Conference and the CSIC, the Spanish National Research Council. Negotiations are

part of the objective of promoting a new open science environment in Spain, seek to replace the current pay-to-read model with one of pay-to-read and pay-to-publish in open access the works of authors of the Spanish universities affiliated to the CRUE and CSIC, which corresponds to more than 90% of the scientific research produced in Spain. (Rodríguez-Bravo et al., 2021)

⁸⁵ <https://www.ouvrirlascience.fr/home/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

⁸⁶ "Les clauses contractuelles empêchent mécaniquement d'évoluer vers une production entièrement en accès ouvert. Le choix systématique de limiter les articles éligibles aux auteurs correspondants des institutions, le caractère volontaire de la démarche dans la quasi-totalité des accords, le volume limité des articles publiables, le choix d'un périmètre restreint excluant notamment les revues supposément les plus prestigieuses (The Lancet, Cell, Nature...) sont autant de facteurs amenant à l'exclusion de nombreux articles de l'accès ouvert" [translation in English by the author]

⁸⁷ <https://www.couperin.org/non-classe/2023-negotiations-guidelines/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

⁸⁸ <https://barometredelascienceouverte.esr.gouv.fr/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

Spain negotiated national agreements with four out of the five major publishers. Costs are reallocated through the pre-existing Spanish consortia. In addition, there are agreements with single consortia or single universities, such as the Universitat de Barcelona, as showed in the ESAC Registry.

An interesting initiative is the Open science Observatory, a common methodology between the Universitat de Barcelona and the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, that it is suggested that could be applied worldwide (Rovira and Labastida, 2019).

According to George Machovec

The early success of many publish and read contracts in Europe has been expedited by governmental or funder mandates which have assisted libraries and countries in developing transformative agreements. In North America, the lack of such mandates has meant that libraries and consortia must pursue such agreements based on their own beliefs about the value of such a publishing model with the goal, at a minimum, of developing contracts that would be cost neutral to the group (Machovec, 2019).

It seems that in the United States of America, negotiating transformative agreements is an autonomous initiative of libraries or consortia not supported by governments. However, one of the first TAs concluded was between the California Digital Library and Cambridge University Press in 2019. Two main weaknesses are indicated by Machovec: one is that “without funding body participation the move for change will be slowed and more difficult”; the second is that institutions “are primarily teaching-focused with relatively small amounts of published research. This actually represents the largest number of American colleges and universities” (Machovec, 2019).

In 2019 a paper by Debat and Babini, they studied the impact of adhesion to Plan S from Latin America institutions, concluding that

it is important to question asymmetrical discussions where privileged institutions unilaterally draft and commit the forthcoming global scholarly publishing landscape. A more reasonable and inclusive agenda where nations and institutions of diverse realities may participate in the scientific discourse and propose a fair, equilibrated, and rational ecosystem for the future of publishing should be embraced (Debat and Babini, 2019).

Most of the Latin American countries developed open access platforms like the mentioned SciELO, this strategy is still remarked by the two authors:

the future of open access global scholarly communications and open science will benefit from the existence of a growing number of institutions, countries, and regions that support and give priority to community-led nonprofit open access initiatives. This vision and these values are not reflected in Plan S (Debat and Babini, 2019).

Colombia consortium shared the strategies of conducting three negotiations of TAs (Muñoz-Vélez et al., 2024); the National Autonomous University of Mexico arranged some transformative agreements since 2021 and Marquez et al., writing on this experience conclude that

in the case of Latin America, institutions that carry out research and are obliged to publish articles in high-level journals, Plan S, the cOAlition S initiative and transformative agreements are a great support for Open access publishing, as they directly lower the costs of APCs. Of course, it is not all the journals or the ones that researchers require, but it is a first step towards Open science in Latin America. On the other hand, it is also true that Latin America always adheres to initiatives when they have already been worked on and established by the European and North American scientific communities, which allows us to make decisions based on previous experiences. better analyzed, close to our reality and with more room for negotiation with publishers, among some of the factors that must be considered in order to join them.⁸⁹ (Marquez et al., 2023)

Bansode and Pujar in 2022 observed that “transformative agreements have marked their presence in India, but not to the extent as it is observed in European countries and the USA” (Bansode and Pujar, 2022). Indeed, they listed four TAs not yet registered in ESAC Registry. Among the causes detected they underline that “research funding for APC is rare/very low” and the “fixed library budgets, no uptake towards publishing costs” (Bansode and Pujar, 2022).

South Africa registered 11 transformative agreements in the ESAC Registry. Many others agreements, often with some of the small publishers, involve other African countries, especially through the non-profit organization EIFL, which stands for Electronic Information for Libraries⁹⁰.

CAUL is the Council of Australian University Librarians. In 2021 released a statement

CAUL has recently introduced a “FastTrack to OA” initiative to simplify and speed up the process towards open access through transformative agreements, with the aim of neutralising cost impacts to members as far as possible. This initiative includes the stated principle that there is sufficient money in the publishing ecosystem and that

⁸⁹ “En el caso de América Latina, las instituciones que realizan investigación y están obligadas a la publicación de artículos en revistas de un alto nivel, el Plan S, la iniciativa cOAlition y los acuerdos transformativos son un gran apoyo para la publicación en Acceso Abierto, ya que de forma directa se abaten los costos de los APC. Desde luego, no son todas las revistas ni las que los investigadores requieren, pero es un primer paso hacia la Ciencia Abierta en América Latina. Por otro lado, también es cierto que América Latina siempre se adhiere a las iniciativas cuando éstas ya han sido trabajadas y establecidas por las comunidades científicas europeas y norteamericanas, lo que nos permite tomar decisiones basadas en experiencias previas, mejor analizadas, cercanas a nuestra realidad y con mayor margen de negociación con las editoriales, entre algunos de los factores que deben considerarse para incorporarnos a ellas” [translation in English by the author]

⁹⁰ <https://www.eifl.net/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

there should be no additional cost for transformative agreements. It is also acknowledged that transformative agreements are one strategy towards the achievement of the end goal of open access to journal articles⁹¹.

Since 2020, CAUL has registered in ESAC Registry 30 agreements.

A monitoring initiative called COKI, Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative, has been established from the Curtin University in Australia. Joining open data available from other databases it offers an overview of the research outputs available in open access from 2000 to 2023⁹².

Strictly limited to transformative agreements, the ESAC Registry⁹³ is the registry in which consortia or single institutions register their agreements. On the other hand, the ESAC Market Watch⁹⁴ analyses data from the registry and other databases to provide an up-to-date picture of the state of the art regarding transformative agreements. It is important to note that the registry is voluntary, so the data may not be exhaustive or speedy up to date.

Fig.2 TAs at a glance

⁹¹https://www.caul.edu.au/sites/default/files/documents/caul-doc/caul_position_-_end_goal_of_open_access_to_journal_articles_final.pdf (accessed 13 May 2024)

⁹²<https://open.coki.ac/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

⁹³<https://esac-initiative.org/about/transformative-agreements/agreement-registry/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

⁹⁴<https://esac-initiative.org/market-watch/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

3.3 Opportunities and critical issues

In the framework of transformative agreements, authors have the opportunity to publish their research articles in open access in many of the “core journals”. They can license the editorial version of their articles under a Creative Commons license, without worrying about versioning, embargo limits or choice of repository. This workflow fits relatively easily into the traditional publication process of research results, and the best part is that there is no additional cost to the authors. Considering these aspects, it seems that eventual critical issues should be justified by the happy end of the process; after all, we have more scientific articles published in open access than before. In 2022 Moskovkin et al. measured that

the interest of scientific communities in the availability of scientific information reflects the fact that in a little less than half a year the number of agreements increased by more than 1.7 times, and for the entire period of our more than one-year study, the growth was 2.3 times. (Moskovkin et al., 2022)

OA2020 initiative took place on the assumption that time was ripe, and transformative agreements were sustainable. In fact, the white paper 2015 of the Max Planck Digital Library authors concluded that

regardless of some regional specialties, scientific publishing is a truly international enterprise. Therefore, a fundamental change in the underlying business model can only be achieved on a global scale. The world’s research organizations, together with their libraries, need to act jointly and with some coordination, with the key aim of shifting the money out of the subscription system and so that it can be re-invested in open access publishing. This coordinated move will also give an unambiguous message to the publishers, so that they themselves can adapt to the new business model with confidence in its financial sustainability for the future. In the end, neither the libraries nor the publishing houses need lose their roles; all the players will be transformed, emerging with new vigor in a modernized publishing system. The time is ripe for the global research community to accelerate the transition to open access. (Schimmer et al., 2015)

According to the paper cited, if the expenditure of subscriptions incurred in a year were used to pay for all the articles published in the same year, the cost per article would range from 3,800 to 5,000 euros. However, it is worth noting that the average expenditure per article for open access publishing projects such as SCOAP3⁹⁵ is only around 1,100 euros. Based on this, the paper concludes that there is enough funding available to shift the spending from subscriptions to APCs, which would accelerate the transition to open access publishing. This

⁹⁵ <https://scoap3.org/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

would be beneficial for both the institutions and the publishers, as the expenses would be incurred anyway, but the shift would result in a win-win situation for both parties.

The libraries' existing acquisition budgets must therefore be the crucial fiscal reservoir for such a transformation. All that remains for the implementation of this clear philosophy is to be assured that there is sufficient money in the system for such a switch to be feasible. (Schimmer et al., 2015)

SCOAP3, just mentioned, is a project coordinated by the CERN (European Organization for Nuclear Research) since 2014. SCOAP3 stands for Sponsoring Consortium for Open access Publishing in Particle Physics. SCOAP3 has converted key journals (published by major commercial publishers) in the field of High-Energy Physics to Open access and continues to support OA publishing in these journals at no direct cost for authors. Costs are covered by the institutions which authors are affiliated with on the output basis, so each country contributes proportionally to its scientific output in the field.

The analysis of APC payments observed in Schimmer's et al. contains data from Germany, UK and Austria in the 2014 year. Average APC value calculated is under 2.000 euro per article, so the construct that "there is enough money in the system" seems correct.

After almost 10 years later, something seems different. Currently, APC per one article in Nature journal is £8890.00/\$12290.00/€10290.00.⁹⁶ Of course, it is one of the highest APC costs, and Nature is one of the most prestigious scientific research journals.

The increasing demand for paying APCs through transformative agreements or by direct payment has driven up prices. Costs of APC in 2014 were such, because there were subscription agreements, in their absence publishers concentrate their revenues on APCs.

Copiello in 2020 made a simulation on the publisher Elsevier about

APCs level in the case all the articles are published using the author-pays model, under the hypothesis of a constant profit margin in comparison with the recent past. [...] The results point at APCs that, on average, would be around twice the current level in order to preserve the publisher's profit margin (4173–4482 USD in comparison to 2544 USD) (Copiello, 2020).

Sumiko Asai studied open access articles in hybrid journals of the same publisher stated that "Open access seems to create barriers against research dissemination from developing countries, although it removes a financial obstacle to acquiring articles." (Asai, 2024)

⁹⁶ <https://www.nature.com/nature/for-authors/publishing-options> (accessed 13 May 2024)

In Ángel Borrego's recent review on APC payments; he concludes that

commercial publishers fix APCs depending on the reputation assigned to journals by peers. There is ample evidence of the relationship between high impact metrics and higher and faster rising APCs. Even if researchers develop any price sensitivity in selecting publication venues, they make decisions based on the value assigned to journals. (Borrego, 2023)

Klebel and Ross-Hellauer in 2023 according to their analysis on APCs payments stated that

the observed forces clearly perpetuate the system of cumulative advantage inherent to academia, as well-funded research groups are better able to secure OA publications in prestigious journals with high APCs, leading to citation advantages and further funding down the line. (Klebel and Ross-Hellauer, 2023)

The inequity arising from APC payment model seems not only between countries to different income but also between research groups, more or less "visible", or researchers at an early stage versus senior researchers. In addition, the allocation of costs among members of the consortia seems another critical issue of potential inequity. As stated by Hinchliffe for traditional subscription agreements

any consortia rely on a cost share model based on institutional FTE, but considerations of historic spending, overall library budget/size, the availability of central funding if any, and other factors can come into consideration (Hinchliffe, 2019)

for example, if contracts are "opt-in", in which institutions can choose to participate or not, or "all-in", in which institutions must participate.

It seems quite curious to Hinchliffe that mainly consortia maintain previous allocation criteria: "the general approach to the question of cost share for transformative agreements has been to set it aside" (Hinchliffe, 2019). As seen earlier, in some country like Austria or Spain the issue was discussed.

Farley et al. identified six points of weakness, referred to as "six myths busted", related to transformative agreements in scholarly publishing. The authors argue that TAs do not promote equity in scholarly publishing and, in fact, may exacerbate existing inequities between countries, institutions, and researchers. Additionally, TAs are not necessarily effective in promoting open access publications, as the ultimate impact of TAs remains unclear. Despite claims to the contrary, TAs do not move away from an APC (article processing charge) model of business, as APCs remain at the core of the TAs. Furthermore, TAs are not transparent regarding costs, with few exceptions. Without understanding the true costs, TAs perpetuate the serials crisis. Libraries are not necessarily in a better position

in negotiations with publishers, as they end up spending more on both subscriptions and APCs and due to possible pressure from publishers on researchers during renewals (Farley et al., 2021).

Similarly, Schmal, investigating on “how transformative are transformative agreements”, concludes that

analyzing the impact of the two German transformative agreements with Springer Nature and Wiley on eight disciplines (and a residual multidisciplinary field) and 6.1 million publications raises one central issue Either the actual (theoretically positive) effect is not quite visible in the econometric estimation, or the DEAL contracts do not change the publishing market in the sense that they cause overwhelming interest among academics to publish their work in eligible journals (at least in the short run). (Schmal, 2024)

About the position of libraries in negotiations, (we include library systems and consortia under the term “libraries”) we want to remind that especially major publishers have the chance to gather a lot of information from their point of view about usage of their platform, behaviour of researchers as readers and as authors, knowing not only what is cited but also what is searched for, when and from who, tracking often at the individual level, potentially profiling deeply institutions and individuals. The phenomenon of “platformisation” has been discussed first about general platforms, and recently focusing on the scholarly ones. On this, reference is made in full to Lai Ma’s reflections, reporting below part of the conclusions:

There is an urgent need for researchers, librarians, university management, funders and the general public to understand the very fact that some (not all) publishers-turned-platforms do not treat knowledge as a public good, nor do they have ethical concerns for open access or data privacy. Rather, they create technologies of control to create a hypercompetitive environment with the purpose of increasing the volume of publications. It is because the higher the number of publications, the more data can be collected for data products and consultancy services that can be sold right back to research institutions. Meanwhile, they deny those who are less privileged in the knowledge production ecosystem, particularly researchers who are not affiliated with resourceful research institutions. The open access movement cannot succeed when platforms hold power and control over not only scholarly information, but also data about researchers and research activities. The fight for the ethical principles of information access and privacy and against platformisation of scholarly information is critical and pressing (Ma, 2023).

Farley et al. finally states that

although TAs increase the OA output from participating institutions, they have unintended consequences for the ecosystem. “Transforming” payments for licensing materials to subsidizing publication fees simply moves the paywall from reading to publishing, further stratifying researchers. TAs reinforce existing inequity, rather than solve access issues. TAs are too new to fully gauge their impact, but historical

trends (Big Deals, the rise of APCs, the consolidation of publishing markets) and current data suggest that libraries should cautiously assess the “transformative” nature of these deals (Farley et al., 2021).

Budapest Open Access Initiative released some recommendations in 2022, the 20th anniversary of the Declaration. It identifies 4 high-level recommendations:

1. Host OA research on open infrastructure. [...]
2. Reform research assessment and rewards to improve incentives. [...]
3. Favor inclusive publishing and distribution channels that never exclude authors on economic grounds. Take full advantage of OA repositories and no-APC journals (“green” and “diamond” OA). Move away from article processing charges (APCs).
4. When we spend money to publish OA research, remember the goals to which OA is the means. [...] Move away from read-and-publish agreements. (Budapest Open Access Initiative: 20th anniversary recommendations, 2022)

Even if it is declared that they “support experiments” and recommend that “institutions make their support appropriately experimental or provisional” with a deadline, as Plan S do, the recommendations provide a long list of critical issues about TAs, among them it is highlighted that

[these] agreements not only entrench the APC model, but also entrench the current system of journal prestige and the current winners under that system. Likewise, these agreements tend to be made by the largest and wealthiest universities, widening rather than narrowing the publishing-access gap between them and less wealthy institutions. (Budapest Open Access Initiative: 20th anniversary recommendations, 2022)

In its annual report, released in June 2023, Plan S gave evidence on the transformation of hybrid journals into full open access journals. Titles in the Plan S program Transformative Journals (TJ)⁹⁷ mostly failed the targets. More in details, the Plan S program requires that

participating journals must share data showing the OA penetration rate and whether they have met their agreed targets. Specifically, TJ titles are required to demonstrate an annual increase in the proportion of OA research content of at least 5% points in absolute terms **and** [emphasis by the author] at least 15% in relative terms, year-on-year. Journals in the programme also agree to flip to full OA when 75% of the research content is published in this way (Coalition S, 2022).

2022 data analysed show these results on the total of 2326 titles:

- 26 titles (1%) flipped to full OA from 1st January 2023
- 695 titles (30%) met or exceeded their OA growth targets and remain in the TJ programme

⁹⁷https://www.Coalition_S.org/addendum-to-the-Coalition_S-guidance-on-the-implementation-of-Plan_S/ (accessed 13 May 2024)

- 1589 titles (68%) failed to meet their OA growth targets and will be removed from the TJ programme.
- 16 other titles (1%) were removed from the programme for other reasons. Such reasons include the publisher no longer holding that title, having ceased publication of a title, among others.⁹⁸

The report underlines that

it is especially discouraging to note that there are at least six titles, published by Springer Nature, which have been unilaterally withdrawn from the TJ programme, despite meeting this 75% OA penetration rate threshold. For example, the 100% of the articles published in the journal *European Journal for Security Research* were published OA in 2022; for the *International Review of Intellectual Property and Competition Law* the OA penetration rate was 95%. Even ignoring the question as to what content subscribers are still paying for, if a title is not prepared to flip at these levels of OA, the only logical conclusion is that they will never flip to full OA (Coalition S, 2022).

It seems that the publishers themselves do not have a long-term strategy about transforming hybrid journals into full open access publishing, if even journals meeting the requisite do not “flip”. On the contrary, it must be remembered that some journals stopped to be partners of commercial publishers. One example is the journal “*Demography*” that left SpringerNature in 2020 to become a full open access title of Duke University Press, and from 2024 a S2O journal⁹⁹.

As a result, Plan S confirmed in early 2023 that as of the end of 2024, financial support for open publications through transformative arrangements would cease.¹⁰⁰

At the end of October 2023, Plan S announced the “Towards Responsible Publishing” proposal, on the example of Latin America experience.

Two main points are shown in the proposal that is open to public comments until April 2024:

1. Authors, not third-party suppliers, decide when and what to publish.

In such a ‘scholar-led’ publishing system, third-party suppliers can still offer and charge for services that facilitate peer review, publication and preservation. However, they will not block scholars from sharing their work at any stage during the research and dissemination process.

2. The scholarly record includes the full range of outputs created during the research cycle, and not just the final journal-accepted version.

By making early article versions and peer review feedback critical elements of the scholarly record, a future scholarly communication system can capture research ‘in the act’. Shining a light on how research progresses towards increasingly trustworthy

⁹⁸https://www.Coalition_S.org/blog/transformative-journals-analysis-from-the-2022-reports/ (accessed 13 May 2024)

⁹⁹<https://read.dukeupress.edu/demography> (accessed 13 May 2024)

¹⁰⁰https://www.Coalition_S.org/Coalition_S-confirms-the-end-of-its-financial-support-for-open-access-publishing-under-transformative-arrangements-after-2024/ (accessed 13 May 2024)

knowledge creation offers opportunities for reviewing and filtering scholarly outputs for the purposes of curation and research assessment.¹⁰¹

The new commitment seems to support first the green open access and the diamond open access. A comment on the launch of the proposal appeared in Nature and underlined that

one criticism of Plan S was that it was launched with little input from the research community, a mistake that the leaders don't want to repeat. After the consultation process on the proposal, the coalition will publish a revised version for member funders to consider. The proposal says that even if funders adopt the refined strategy, other open-access business models "will continue to be supported by cOAlition S for some time". (Liverpool, 2023)

This was noted earlier, reporting the article by Debat and Labini (Debat and Babini, 2019). Loyal Liverpool also gathered some opinions of experts and publishers, here summarised:

"I can imagine there will be lots of commercial lobbying pointing out reasons this is destined to fail," says Stephen Curry, director of strategy at the Research on Research Institute in London. When asked to comment on the proposal, an Elsevier spokesperson emphasized the value of the firm's work in supporting peer review, training editors and improving article content. A spokesperson for Wiley said that the proposal was "an interesting perspective" and that Wiley also felt that researchers should be able to choose the most appropriate venues to publish their work. "Publishers have a crucial role to play in further improving the global research ecosystem," they said, adding that they "are keen to engage with any proposal that seeks to address routes to responsible publishing".(Liverpool, 2023)

It is worth noting that publishers themselves highlight their crucial role in the research ecosystem, for this a responsible behaviour is required. From the perspective of society publishers, Anderson et al. state that "size is a factor":

with limited resources we have had to prioritize initiating conversations with consortia and institutions in strategic areas, i.e. those with strong OA mandates or high publishing output. This is not because we do not want agreements outside of those areas but because we cannot afford to enter complex and protracted negotiations where there may be a lower potential for success. This is likely to be a situation very familiar to librarians who wish to support society publishers but also need to get the big agreements across the line first.(Anderson et al., 2022)

Destro Bisol et al., in 2022, wrote an article comparing transformative agreements and the self- archiving (green open access). They explain with evidence that

very importantly, the potential effectiveness of the green road is supported by empirical data. In fact, by sharing not embargoed post-prints, the open-access rate of recent peer-reviewed publications (first semester 2020) covering the ten deadliest diseases in the world would have risen from 49% to 77% on average, increasing the

¹⁰¹<https://www.Coalition.S.org/blog/introducing-the-towards-responsible-publishing-proposal-from-Coalition-S/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

baseline value from a minimum of 38% (respiratory infections and tuberculosis) to a maximum of 70% (maternal and neonatal diseases). An important implication of these data is that the transformative agreements established so far did not prevent a significant part of publications (51%) from being closed access. It is also worth noting that with systematic use of the green road we could get important medical literature closer to the open-access rate observed for papers concerning COVID-19 (close to 90%), which may be regarded as the best case of openness in scientific publishing observed so far. (Destro Bisol et al., 2022)

They underline some issues with TAs, highlighting opportunities of the green road, that should be considered by the health researchers' community to which they belong. Abadal highlights three main distortions from the APC payment in a 2022 work, which are "uncontrolled APC price increases", a publishing gap "between journals that charge APCs and those that do not" and "double charges" arising from hybrid journals (Abadal, 2022). Facing the phenomenon, the open access movement is divided into two main positions:

"Critics of APCs argue that they are a perversion of the open access model that do nothing to promote equity and in fact foment inequality". "Latin American organisations, include a clear rejection of APCs and" "argues that the diamond model is the one that ensures greater equity. This argument is irrefutable. The reality, however, is that a model that is clearly promoting inequality (the APC model) has moved much more quickly and has effectively taken over" (Abadal, 2022).

More recently, A.J. Boston underlines three attitudes, at least from the libraries leaderships: "pragmatically in favor, ideologically opposed, or simply sort of confused about the whole thing". (Boston, 2023) The same author launched a novel (and provocative as he said) proposal in 2021 concerning a new business model, named Read and Let Read (R&LR), with the following elements:

Read: A research institution/library will prepay a publisher a base amount each year according to the total number of articles that institutional users downloaded during the previous year, multiplied by two, which covers the base amount (as described) plus any additional downloads made above the base amount during the coverage year.

Let Read: Any downloads unclaimed by the institution during the coverage year are donated in the following year to any user online.

Updated valuation: All subscription-only articles cost \$0.50 to download. (Boston, 2023)

The purpose of the model is not that articles are published open but

is to make every article in a publisher portfolio available to users in institutions and outside them at approximately the same rate. Providing the same benefit to well-affiliated and less-affiliated users alike makes this an equitable strategy. And because R&LR is agnostic toward corresponding author affiliation, global readers will gain access to the widest possible scholarly corpus, eliminating citation advantages associated with an author's ability to pay. (Boston, 2023)

This proposal received several comments on which the author tried to answer. It is important to note that the goal is not to offer open articles with open licenses for full access and reuse, but rather to make papers more readable and accessible to readers without charging them. Additionally, it aims to address some of the issues with the current model of paying for publication. This proposal has not been discussed in Italy yet.

3.4 In Italy

In 2019, there were two meetings held in Rome organized by the Italian National Research Council (CNR) in February¹⁰² and the Conference of Italian University Rectors (CRUI) in May¹⁰³ that opened a debate in Italy on transformative agreements. Inside the CRUI works the CARE group (Gruppo di Coordinamento per l'Accesso alle Risorse Elettroniche)¹⁰⁴ that coordinates the negotiation of electronic resources agreements at a national level since 2014. In 2020, the first transformative agreement was concluded. There are currently 14 transformative agreements signed by Italian institutions and in the ESAC Registry, with one concluded but not registered yet¹⁰⁵.

Fig.3 TAs in Italy at a glance

¹⁰² <https://www.oi.unito.it/new/transformative-agreements-e-plans/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

¹⁰³ <https://www.cruirisorselettroniche.it/convegno-cruir-care-21maggio-2019/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

¹⁰⁴ <https://www.cruirisorselettroniche.it/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

¹⁰⁵ <https://www.elsevier.com/open-access/agreements/cruir> (accessed 13 May 2024)

Tessa Piazzini wrote one of the first articles on TAs in Italian, outlining the international context and underlined a key point useful for the Italy context too, referring to a Machovec paper:

Regardless of the positions, what has emerged is that, in order to even hypothesize a transformation of the current agreements, it is necessary to know some fundamental elements: who publishes, how much and in what place and what are the costs incurred so far by research institutions for open access publications. Hence the need for academic libraries and consortia to develop tools and methods to analyze the publication paths of their authors, statistics on the use of resources, and funding channels.¹⁰⁶ (Machovec, 2020 cited in Piazzini, 2020)

In addition to the theme of monitoring, before starting a negotiation and during the years of application of a transformative agreement, Capaccioni underlines a second key point which is the internal organizational structure of the institutions for the management of TAs:

The second issue concerns the new functions that university library systems will have to perform following the introduction of TAs. It is a topic that has not yet been investigated. The impression is that universities are moving in a haphazard manner, adopting various types of interventions, ranging from maintaining the status quo, to the attribution of new responsibilities to libraries, to a summary reorganization of the structures involved in the procedure. Instead, a specific technical area of the university should be provided within which the various components involved (librarian, publishing, research area) can collaborate with each other¹⁰⁷ (Capaccioni, 2021).

Some Italian researchers discussed the transformative agreements and more in general the business model of APC payment among peers in their discipline, for example Destro Bisol mentioned earlier. Italian psychologists Cubelli e Della Sala wrote in 2021 that

The original intention of the OA initiative was that information derived from taxpayers' money, such as the results of research carried out in public universities by publicly funded researchers, should be made available to everyone free of charge. Now, given the fees imposed by publishers to publish in journals that have become “transformative”, the costs are so high that they will be partly absorbed by the universities, i.e. they will be paid for with public money. Exactly what was set out to

¹⁰⁶ “Indipendentemente dalle posizioni, quello che è emerso è che, per poter anche solamente ipotizzare una trasformazione degli attuali accordi, sia necessaria la conoscenza di alcuni elementi fondamentali: chi pubblica, quanto e in quale sede e quali siano i costi finora sostenuti dagli enti di ricerca per le pubblicazioni in accesso aperto. Da qui la necessità che le biblioteche accademiche e i consorzi sviluppino strumenti e modalità per analizzare i percorsi di pubblicazione dei propri autori, le statistiche di uso delle risorse, i canali di finanziamento (Machovec 2020)” [translation in English by the author]

¹⁰⁷ “La seconda questione riguarda le nuove funzioni che i sistemi bibliotecari di ateneo si troveranno a svolgere a seguito dell’introduzione dei TA. È un argomento ancora poco indagato. L’impressione è che le università si stiano muovendo in ordine sparso adottando interventi di varia natura che vanno dal mantenimento dello status quo, all’attribuzione di nuove competenze alle biblioteche, a una sommatoria riorganizzazione delle strutture coinvolte nella procedura. Si dovrebbe invece prevedere una specifica area tecnica di ateneo all’interno della quale possano collaborare tra di loro le diverse componenti coinvolte (bibliotecaria, editoriale, della ricerca)” [translation in English by the author]

counteract! [...] It's probably better to pay to read what's already been published than to pay to publish what may never be read.¹⁰⁸ (Cubelli and Della Sala, 2021)

In Italy, the increase of 18 points of VAT sometimes applied on the contractual portion dedicated to publication (in some cases it almost corresponds to the total contractual amount) also plays a role, adding material to the discussion on economic sustainability, at least precisely in Italy. It can determine heavy increases in expenditure that institutions could not face or they could face by cutting other important resources and peculiar services. With regard to the application of the VAT rate, Antonio Uricchio published a comment (Uricchio, 2023) on the provisions arising from some questions on the subject addressed to the Agenzia delle Entrate, the Italian national tax agency (Uricchio, 2023). It must be remembered that in Italy, since 2015, the VAT rate on digital books with ISBN and journals with ISSN has reduced to 4%, as it is for books and journals printed on paper.

Regarding expenditure there are issues with observations due to non-disclosure agreements between consortia and publishers. About that, it is worth noting that publishers have access to global information while consortia only have complete knowledge of their own agreements. An effort to increase the awareness of consortia who negotiate TAs is made internationally by the OA2020 Community of Practice, in which members share experiences and updates. However, in Italy public administrations are obliged by the law to publish a minimum set of data about annual expenditure. The following diagram arises from expenditure data publicly available at the national consortium level¹⁰⁹. It represents the share difference between the amount paid for the last traditional agreement and the first transformative agreement, calculated on the average amount, including VAT, paid by CRUI, between 2017 and 2022, to each publisher with whom an agreement is registered in ESAC. This analysis was carried out for the 10 publishers who have agreements negotiated by CRUI and registered in ESAC. The percentage increase cannot be calculated for agreements with publishers 2, 5, and 6 as the data is too partial. The following data was presented by the

¹⁰⁸ “L’iniziativa OA, nelle sue originali intenzioni, si basava sul principio che informazioni derivanti dal denaro dei contribuenti, come i risultati di ricerche svolte in atenei pubblici da ricercatori stipendiati con denaro pubblico, dovessero essere messe a disposizione di tutti gratuitamente. Ora, date le tariffe imposte dalle case editrici per pubblicare sulle riviste diventate «transformative», i costi sono talmente elevati che saranno in parte assorbiti dalle università, cioè saranno pagati con soldi pubblici. Esattamente ciò che ci si prefiggeva di contrastare! [...] Probabilmente è meglio pagare per leggere quello che è stato già pubblicato che pagare per pubblicare ciò che potrebbe non essere mai letto” [translation in English by the author]

¹⁰⁹ <https://cruir.it/bandi-di-gara-e-contratti-pubblici/articolo-1-comma-32,-legge-n190-12.html> (accessed 13 May 2024)

researcher during the last GenOA week meeting¹¹⁰: the average increase observed varies from 12.18% to 39.48% (Gamboni, 2023).

Following again the contribution to reflection by Cubelli and Della Sala, they recognize diamond open access as a potential avenue to pursue, though they find it challenging to implement:

A possible turning point could come if the universities themselves took control of academic publications, managing their own journals under the OA regime. If that were the case, no one would have to pay: not the readers, but not the authors either. The costs of universities to run these journals would be (much) lower than those incurred today to pay subscriptions and tomorrow to pay OA to publishing houses¹¹¹. (Cubelli and Della Sala, 2021)

Finally, they affirm that most of all “in the long term, we need more public morality and more individual ethics in the management of scientific dissemination.”¹¹² (Cubelli and Della Sala, 2021)

¹¹⁰ <https://openscience.unige.it/genOAweek2023> (accessed 13 May 2024)

¹¹¹ “Una possibile svolta potrebbe avvenire se gli atenei stessi assumessero il controllo delle pubblicazioni accademiche, gestendo loro proprie riviste in regime di OA. Se così fosse, nessuno dovrebbe pagare: non i lettori, ma neppure gli autori. I costi degli atenei per gestire queste riviste sarebbero (di molto) inferiori a quelli sostenuti oggi per pagare abbonamenti e domani per pagare OA alle case editrici” [translation in English by the author]

¹¹² “a lungo termine servono più moralità pubblica e più etica individuale nella gestione della disseminazione scientifica” [translation in English by the author]

From the perspective of Italian publishers, Piero Attanasio, president of AIE, Associazione Italiana Editori,¹¹³ the national association of publishers, states that the discussion is on open sciences, a plural concept. Open sciences are related to the different needs and habits of communicating research findings through disciplines. In force of this plurality there are plurality of solutions in which publishers still remain partners discuss with:

it follows that there is no recipe, other than the continuous search for solutions, as suggested in Budapest twenty years ago. Without taking anything for granted. The position of the Italian Publishers Association (2022) on open sciences has tried to take this path. In doing so, it posed questions that were disrespectful of the dogmas dictated by the promoters of an open science (in the singular). That the existence of a price for access, for example, can serve, in certain cases, as an incentive for authors and editors to work more on the texts, to make them more comprehensible outside the circle of ‘peers’. Or that peer review may not be enough if there is not also a judgment of the other with whom you want to collaborate, according to the definition of the Foster project. Or that, in certain cases, open access to reading can close access to the possibility of publishing or, in the non-democratic countries where most of the world's population lives, the control of funds for publications can be, for certain disciplines, a powerful instrument of censorship. Cases, countries, disciplines, different contexts must be the guide.¹¹⁴ (Attanasio, 2022)

In Italy the discussion on TAs is part of the discussion about open science, it is transversal to different disciplines and involves various researchers from physics to law, from political science to information science, together with technicians, librarians, administrators, and research staff, as show the several meetings occurred since now, for example:

4.12.2020, online, *Pagare per leggere o pagare per scrivere: un dilemma insuperabile?*¹¹⁵ (=Paying to read or paying to write: an insurmountable dilemma?, [translation by the author])

2-3.3.2021, online, *Etica e pragmatica dell’open access: Incontri e conversazioni al CNR*¹¹⁶ (=Ethics and Pragmatics of Open access: Meetings and Conversations at CNR, [translation by the author])

¹¹³ <https://www.aie.it/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

¹¹⁴ “ne consegue che non esiste una ricetta, se non la ricerca continua di soluzioni, come suggerito a Budapest vent’anni fa. Senza dare nulla per scontato. La posizione dell’Associazione italiana editori (2022) sulle scienze aperte ha provato a imboccare questa strada. nel farlo ha posto questioni irrispettose dei dogmi dettati dai promotori di una scienza aperta (al singolare). Che l’esistenza di un prezzo per l’accesso, ad esempio, possa fungere, in certi casi, da incentivo perché autori e redattori lavorino di più sui testi, per renderli più comprensibili al di fuori della cerchia dei «pari». O che la peer review possa non essere sufficiente se non vi è anche un giudizio di quell’altro con cui si vuole collaborare, secondo la definizione del progetto Foster. O che, in certi casi, l’accesso aperto alla lettura possa chiudere l’accesso alla possibilità di pubblicare o, nei paesi non democratici in cui vive la gran parte della popolazione mondiale, il controllo dei fondi per le pubblicazioni possa essere, per certe discipline, un potente strumento di censura. I casi, i paesi, le discipline, i diversi contesti devono essere la guida” [translation in English by the author]

¹¹⁵ <https://aisa.sp.unipi.it/pagare-per-leggere-o-pagare-per-scrivere-un-dilemma-insuperabile/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

¹¹⁶ <https://www.cnr.it/it/evento/17127/etica-e-pragmatica-dell-open-access> (accessed 13 May 2024)

6-7.12.2022, Rome, *Gli Enti pubblici di ricerca per la Scienza Aperta - Primo convegno nazionale del gruppo di lavoro Open science della CoPER*¹¹⁷

(=Public Research Institutions for Open science - First national conference of the CoPER Open science working group, [translation by the author])

19.12.2023, Rome, *Il diritto alla ricerca. Nuove frontiere e profili evolutivi del diritto d'autore*¹¹⁸

(=The right to research. New frontiers and evolutionary profiles of copyright, [translation by the author])

Other places of conversation we want to mention are the annual meetings organized by AISA¹¹⁹ and the GenOA week¹²⁰, the annual meeting on open access and open science, with an increasing national relevance, organized by the University of Genoa, the ROARS blog¹²¹ and the list of distribution “OA-Italia.”¹²²

Chapter summary

The literature review in this chapter discusses the documents that led to the introduction of transformative agreements. It provides a definition of TAs in the context of their various solutions and gives an overview of the experiences and key points that have emerged globally from the adoption of TAs. The chapter also examines the opportunities and critical issues of TAs, such as the increase in open access publications released under Creative Commons open licenses, the rise in prices, and the risk of unsustainability in the medium and long term. Possible risks of inequity are outlined, and further interventions and possible solutions are accounted for, while the open access movement is divided in its judgment on TAs. Finally, the chapter concludes with a focus on the debate on transformative agreements in Italy.

¹¹⁷ <https://agenda.infn.it/e/ConvegnoOpenscienceCoPER2022> (accessed 13 May 2024)

¹¹⁸ <https://www.igsg.cnr.it/2023/12/il-diritto-alla-ricerca/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

¹¹⁹ <https://aisa.sp.unipi.it/attivita/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

¹²⁰ https://openscience.unige.it/notizie_eventi (accessed 13 May 2024)

¹²¹ <https://www.roars.it/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

¹²² <https://liste.cineca.it/cgi-bin/mailman/listinfo/oa-italia> (accessed 13 May 2024)

4 Methodology

The research project aimed to contribute to understanding the impact of transformative agreements on scientific communication and to evaluate their opportunities and critical issues, mainly focusing on the Italy case.

The research project objectives were:

- To observe the number of OA articles published by authors affiliated with Italian institutions before and after the adoption of several transformative agreements in Italy and the rating of their OA articles on the total published and indexed in the citation databases Web of Science, Scopus, Dimensions, and OpenAlex.
- To understand the theoretical framework of scientific communication in the digital environment and about open access in Italy, also considering the introduction of transformative agreements.
- To understand the role of academic libraries and librarians in the context outlined.

According to the objectives the research questions were:

RQ1: How do publication trends compare before and after transformative agreements were implemented in Italy?

RQ2: Regarding the Italian context, what is the theoretical framework of scientific communication in the digital environment and about open access, also considering the introduction of transformative agreements?

RQ3: What is the role of academic libraries and librarians in the context outlined?

To answer to the research questions the mixed method approach was applied, so both qualitative and quantitative methodology were selected. The more appropriate research methods to be applied were semi-structured interviews and data collection from bibliographic citation databases.

4.1 Research approach

To answer the research questions formulated, a mixed method approach was best suited. Library and Information Science is part of the social sciences and mixed methods is one of the possible approaches. The topic of transformative agreements is complex and requires a comprehensive approach to address its complexity during the research project. A mixed method approach can provide a rich picture of the observed phenomenon and better answer the research questions. From literature review, two main positions evaluating the transformative agreements have emerged. A mixed method approach can help to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon and opinions in favour and against it and investigate them more in-depth.

The mixed method approach is a fairly new research approach that recognizes the value of both the positivist and constructivist paradigms. This approach views both paradigms as important and combines them to better answer research questions. In this approach, the researcher is expected to understand the strengths and weaknesses of each method and use them effectively to gain a better understanding of the phenomenon under investigation. By combining the two methods, the mixed method approach provides a more comprehensive understanding of the subject matter than a single approach could offer. “Mixed-method researchers believe that this hybrid method can serve as a bridge by eliminating the distinction/contradiction between the two paradigms” (Onwuegbuzie & Leech, 2005 cited in Şahin and Ozturk, 2022).

The mixed method approach was first introduced in the 1990s and was documented in the first manual by Tashakkori and Teddlie in 2003. The second edition of the manual has since been published. “Before the incompatibility thesis (i.e. stating that it was inappropriate to mix quantitative and qualitative methods) researchers who used mixed methods to answer their research questions were mostly unaware that they were doing anything out of the ordinary.” (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2024)

From a skewed viewpoint, qualitative research is seen as absolutely relativistic and quantitative research as objectivistic. The three formal ontological categories in Habermas' theory of communicative action offer a more nuanced view, situating validity claims in objective, subjective, and normative worlds. Such an analysis helps us to understand validity and truth claims as they occur in these different ontological worlds. The formal ontological categories also clarify that MMR is feasible within a

communicative-pragmatic framework and that qualitative and quantitative research methods are not necessarily objectivistic or relativistic (Ma, 2012).

According to Ma, “mixed methods research that combines large-scale data analyses and a detailed description of community practice may provide us with a richer understanding of information and information-related phenomena”(Ma, 2012)

Lastly, the doctoral program in Ethics of Communication, Scientific Research, and Technology Innovation at the Università degli Studi di Perugia ¹²³ is an interdisciplinary PhD program that welcomes diverse research approaches. This program has provided us with the confidence and motivation needed to develop our research, formulate research questions, and utilize the mixed method approach.

4.2 Research methodology

To answer the research questions, the mixed method approach is suitable for. It means that both qualitative and quantitative methodologies will be carried out. “Research question should dictate the methodological approach that is used to conduct the research” (Corbin and Strauss, 2015). To answer to the research questions, it is necessary to collect data from the opinions and perceptions of key informants, both connoisseurs and actors in the investigated context. It should also be noted that the investigation focuses on an up-to-date and rapidly evolving topic. For these reasons, it is necessary to introduce qualitative methodology to collect “rich” data for a deeper investigation. Qualitative methodology includes interaction between researcher and participants and hermeneutics, “depending on both the tacit and the explicit knowledge of the researcher” (Pickard, 2013), that interprets phenomena, gives his/her representation.

“The idea that the combination of quantitative and qualitative methods, instead of using a single method, will provide a better understanding of the research problem is the basic assumption of mixed method research” (Creswell, 2012 cited in Şahin and Ozturk, 2022). “Scientists who contributed to the development of mixed-method research only think that

¹²³ <https://fissuf.unipg.it/didattica/dottorato/dottorato-di-ricerca-in-etica-della-comunicazione-della-ricerca-scientifica-e-dell-innovazione-tecnologica> (accessed 13 May 2024)

they should prefer this method when the research problem requires it. There are five main reasons for the mixed research method” (Greene, Caracelli and Graham, 1989 cited in Şahin and Ozturk, 2022): triangulation, complementarity, development, initiation, expansion. For this research project, the main purpose was to use qualitative results to enhance the interpretability of findings obtained through quantitative research, so the main reason is the complementarity.

According to Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, it is necessary to determine the appropriate mixed method for the research project and the dominance of one of the two methodologies. The time of their implementation has to be planned, with the sequence of the methodologies (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004). In the present project the two methodologies are in an equal status, while the purpose is to collect quantitative and qualitative data simultaneously, combining their analysis to better understand the research problem and answer to the research questions. In a convergent parallel design, data are collected simultaneously and analysed separately. The “determination of the consistency-inconsistency status of the results derived from the analysis” (Şahin and Ozturk, 2022).

4.3 Research methods

Collecting data from bibliographic citation databases was the method to conduct the part of the research with quantitative methodology. The eventual limitations and research strategies are given in data collection paragraph.

As stated by Laakso and Björk

study of full OA journals is commonly facilitated by data retrievable from the Directory of Open access Journals and study of OA uptake in general can be attempted by conducting a search for instance using Web of Science or Scopus indexed articles as a basis (see for instance Archambault et al., 2014). No such index exists for hybrid journals and searches are made difficult because many subscription journals in addition to hybrid OA articles also include other articles made open for promotional purposes, often on a temporary basis using a moving wall technique. Alternatively, publishers might incorporate a delayed OA policy where all articles become freely available after a set timeframe from publishing (Laakso and Björk, 2016).

There exist some issues in searching for data about open access articles coming from hybrid journals. Laakso and Björk state that

The lack of an index for OA articles published in hybrid journals can be assumed to be a major obstacle for why no extensive earlier studies have been conducted. No study so far has been based around both journal and article-level metrics, going from observations of individual articles to aggregate figures for the journal level of analysis. So far studies have been individual snapshots of specific points in time put together by disparate bits and pieces of data to paint partial pictures when it comes both to scope and chronology (Laakso and Björk, 2016).

Asai analysed data from databases focused on APC like OpenAPC and DOAJ, concluding that “databases have different characteristics, we must choose a database according to the purpose of the analysis.” (Asai, 2023)

One of the research objectives was to observe the number of open access publications during the period of 2018 to 2022 and to monitor the impact of the TAs on the number of publications with authors affiliated with Italian institutions. Data sources still give fragmented pictures of the state of the art, due to lack of standardization of metadata and different criteria on building the knowledge base of each database.

The most popular service that gives attribute to articles depending on the type of open access is Unpaywall¹²⁴ an open-source project by OurResearch¹²⁵, a non-profit organization leading a number of open-source projects, among other the cited OpenAlex, recently released¹²⁶.

The categories are green open access / gold open access / hybrid open access / bronze open access (Piwowar et al., 2018). The organization published the workflow-style description of the analysis to determine the status of the article,¹²⁷ here reported:

¹²⁴ <https://unpaywall.org/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

¹²⁵ <https://ourresearch.org/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

¹²⁶ <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-022-00138-y> (accessed 13 May 2024)

¹²⁷ <https://support.unpaywall.org/support/solutions/articles/44001777288-what-do-the-types-of-oa-status-green-gold-hybrid-and-bronze-mean-> (accessed 13 May 2024)

Fig.4 Unpaywall, workflow-style description for OA attribute

Unpaywall data on open access is used to categorize open access type in all four databases observed, this could be a good point to the observation. It must be remarked that the status of an article may change over time, for example if a journal flips from hybrid to full open access, if a journal passes from one publisher to another, if articles stop to be freely accessible. Data extracted can give a fairly grainy picture of the phenomenon, not a high-resolution portrait.

Semi-structured interviews were the selected method to conduct the part of the research to collect qualitative data. The key-informant interview was based on a guided track of open-ended questions to which the interviewee answers freely. It can lead the researcher to deepen the themes that have emerged with further questions.

Interviews are usually used when we are seeking qualitative, descriptive, in-depth data that is specific to the individual and when the nature of the data is too complicated to be asked and answered easily. This does not apply to researcher-administered questionnaires but all other interviews allow for some degree of interaction between the researcher and the subject. Interviews can be used for reconstruction of events, descriptions and feelings about current events and predictions of future developments (Pickard, 2013).

According to Kvale, the interview method has seven steps: thematizing, designing, interviewing, transcribing, analysing, verifying and reporting (Kvale, 1996 cited in Pickard, 2013). The first step is to identify one or more themes appropriate to the interview; then the

design of the interview means to provide a guide depending on the type of the interview. The project required a semi-structured interview in order to “ensure that each interview covers basically the same ground but gives the interviewer considerable discretion in the conduct of the interview” (Ellis, 1993 cited in Pickard, 2013). Guided interviews offer researchers a comprehensive approach to cover all relevant areas of a topic while allowing them the freedom to explore and ask additional questions. This approach provides the opportunity to clarify or investigate more in-depth whenever necessary. The analysis of data is an ongoing process that starts from the interview itself and every other reflection that emerges from it. The verification stage is the moment in which a researcher asks himself if the perimeter of the answers overlaps that of the questions. It also covers a verification step with the interviewee, to ensure that what is transcribed is what the interviewee thought and wanted to express. The report phase is to share information emerged in the research report as outcomes, balancing interpretation of data and real data by citation, noting that every word is data (Pickard, 2013).

4.4 Quantitative data collection

For quantitative data collection purpose, we made use of citation databases Web of Science, Scopus, Dimensions (freemium version), and OpenAlex. These databases are considered the most comprehensive ones. It is assumed that they provide bibliographic references to journals published by major international publishers with whom transformative agreements are in force, including Italy.

The bibliographic data of articles published in 2023 were excluded from the tests. This is because the year had not yet concluded when the tests began, and it was assumed that the data for the year 2023 would not be complete and stable enough, not even in January 2024, when the research project ended. However, during the tests, we found that data fluctuations are continuous as knowledge databases can receive data updates on articles with any publication date. The data elaborated depicts a snapshot of a particular day. As DeltaThink¹²⁸ states in a recent report “the data sources change over time, so we restate our findings each

¹²⁸ <https://deltathink.com/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

year to reflect the latest data available. Even a few weeks' difference in timing of analysis can make a significant difference in results"¹²⁹.

Each of the databases declares to use OA data from Unpaywall. Except Dimensions freemium version, the OA attribute is distinct in different types of OA, so Open access type filters were applied as they were available. The research strategy first ran without filters by country, secondly filtering by "Country = Italy" (this filter is not available in Dimensions freemium). The country field is filled with the country of the affiliation of each author of each article. Therefore, this first dataset contained articles in which at least one author (corresponding author or not) was affiliated with an Italian institution. Data from databases were extracted different times for testing a uniform research strategy. The data presented in the thesis were updated to the 10th of January 2024 if not differently declared.

Data extracted give a picture, as defined as possible, of the dimensions of the open access articles both globally and selecting those published by Italian authors, individually or as co-authors, from 2018 to 2022. Even if some transformative agreements cover the APC payment for articles published in fully open access journals (gold open access), a significant portion of the expenses associated with transformative agreements is allocated to hybrid journals. As such, the percentage of hybrid open access articles is emphasized, apart from data from Dimensions. However, we underline that we might not be able to appreciate the full effect of changes in an institution through bibliometric means in the short term.

Another type of analysis was conducted trying to analyse the open access articles published in the timespan identified by an Italy institution affiliated corresponding author. Databases that contain metadata about corresponding author (CA) that can be managed at a country level are from Web of Science and Scopus. In both databases the CA metadata is not clearly separated from other data, and it was found not uniform, except for the country noun. In exported files, metadata about corresponding author appears even if it is not directly searchable with simple or advanced search functionalities. Databases applied limits on the number of records that can be exported simultaneously in a format containing the CA metadata. For all databases the web interface was used both for searching and for exporting records.

¹²⁹ <https://deltathink.com/news-views-open-access-market-sizing-update-2022/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

4.4.1 Data collection

This section provides additional details about each database used. Data exported in “csv” format or “txt” format was consolidated and managed with Microsoft Excel 365.

Dimensions

The Dimensions database was accessed for free after registration. Some of the functionalities are not available for free, among these the advanced search features. For this reason, it was possible to search under limited criteria. The data gathered was the number of *publications* in years 2018-2022. Then the “all OA” filter was applied to results, in order to select the number of publications with an OA attribute, further distinctions on OA were not possible. No filters about country could be applied.

OpenAlex

OpenAlex is an open platform freely accessible, it gathers bibliographic references of several type of publications and data, collectively called “works”. Functionalities are available to all users. First the filter “type of works” was applied and limited to “articles”. Filter “open access” without any specification was applied and then the “open published” one which groups hybrid open access and gold open access. In OpenAlex presentation, it is declared that “the dataset currently lacks metadata about funding sources, as well as metadata about corresponding authors. Overall, much work remains to be done in validating and studying completeness and accuracy of the dataset, particularly in comparison to similar tools” (Priem et al., 2022).

Scopus

Scopus is the citation database owned by Elsevier publisher, now RELX company. From Scopus cumulative data on OA was extracted as the other databases, while dataset based on Italian corresponding authors was updated on the 15th of January 2024. Some advises about the quality of data and the extraction process in a report by Andrew Gray (Gray, 2020) were taken into account.

Web of Science

Web of Science is the citation database owned by Clarivate Analytics. From Web of Science cumulative data on OA was extracted as the other databases, while dataset to identify article published in the transformative agreement framework and with Italian corresponding authors was updated on the 17th of January 2024.

4.5 Qualitative data collection

All the interviews for this research project were conducted through computer-mediated communication (CMC). There has been an ongoing debate about its use in scientific research, with arguments for and against (Pickard, 2013). It must be said that the Covid-19 pandemic enhanced the CMC communication, making it to be considered as a common way to communicate, even if differences between communication in presence or at distance remain relevant. However, for this project, CMC was applied to contain costs and save participants' time. It also allowed participants to choose the time and method of their interview - whether they preferred to answer through writing or talking. Even if the interaction with the researcher was different, it was important that key informants could freely choose the way they wanted to be interviewed. Two of the interviews were conducted asynchronously and delivered via email, while three were conducted synchronously and video recorded. The types of research output resulting from these interviews are different: the written texts allow for more reflection and formal writing, and one of them contains hyperlinks to additional resources. In contrast, the transcriptions reflect less formal language and the synchronous interaction between the interviewer and the researcher. The semi-structured interviews ran on the following track:

- 1) The TAs are with us. Do they really increase access to research? What is their impact?
- 2) What is next? TAs have strengths and weaknesses ...How can TAs be fair and sustainable?

3) In Italy, how are research bodies, authors and librarians facing changes in scholarly communication brought by TAs?

4) Do librarians have a "key-role"? What is in their near future?

Many aspects of the interview need to be prepared apart from the track, for example the invitation mail, the eventual arrangement on the date, the scheduled time. The written interviews were sent in English language after one and three weeks, the three interviews collected lasted in an hour or less.

4.5.1 Interviews

Key informants were asked to participate in the research project on the 1st of September 2023. The first contact email explained the research purposes and the list of the interview questions was sent in attachment for preview. Two of them chose to answer by written text, they sent the answers by mail on the 7th and on the 20th of September. The other three were interviewed remotely on the 7th, the 9th and the 21st of September.

The transcriptions were based on the text generated automatically by the Microsoft Teams functionality, the text needed a consistent review, and corrections were made by the researcher. English words used during the interview are in italics. The transcription of each interview and the related translation in English were sent on the 18th of January 2024. The author translated the interview into English, supported by the translation function of Microsoft Word 365. Apart from some minimal intervention on one of these, interviewees did not ask any change. The interviewees expressed consent to the video recording at the beginning of the interview, then they confirmed the consent by email on different dates.

From the interviews the researcher outlined main themes emerging from the dialogue, discussed in the Outcomes chapter.

4.6 Ethics

Key informants participated in the research project after invitation on a voluntary basis. They were aware of the purpose of the research project and that data were gathered for research and study purposes only. The data processing document was shared with all participants. Methodology and research methods were presented during the evaluation meetings of the PhD research projects. Pseudonymisation measures were applied to prevent key informants from being recognized and to give more importance to words and concepts than whoever told them. However, to associate univocally statements and opinions to each of participants, they have been identified as K1, K2, K3, K4 and K5.

The researcher declares non conflict of interest. The research does not aim to evaluate, confront, or promote any commercial product.

4.7 Data processing and regulation

4.7.1 Interviews

Based on the literature review and readings, five Italian “key informants” were invited by email, asking for their availability for an interview on the topic of the transformative agreements (Appendix I).

The questions were attached to the invitation email, and after acceptance, two of the key informants chose to answer by written text. A copy of the two documents containing the written answers has been collected and added in Appendix IV, "as they are."

The three other experts engaged in the research chose to be interviewed and gave their consent by email for the interview to be video recorded by the Microsoft Teams function and notification under the privacy policy of Microsoft¹³⁰ and according to the Università

¹³⁰ <https://privacy.microsoft.com/it-IT/privacystatement#mainnoticetoendusersmodule> (accessed 13 May 2024)

degli Studi di Perugia Regulation on the processing of personal data implementing the GDPR, General Data Protection Regulation, i.e., Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of April the 27th 2016, and the Italian Legislative Decree 196/2003¹³¹.

While using the Microsoft Teams app, they could access the video recording once interviewed. They finally received a copy of the transcription of their own interview in Italian (Appendix III) for eventual personal review. The author translated the interview into English, supported by the translation function of Microsoft Word 365.

All interviewees received a copy of the data processing steps followed by the researcher (Appendix II), here briefly summed up, reminding that the interview was conducted for research and study purposes only and, in the case of oral interviews, the personal data processed were the *recorded voice* and the *recorded image* of the interviewees:

- The video recording is temporarily stored only in the researcher's personal working area;
- The video recording will be deleted after the presentation and public discussion of the doctoral thesis;
- The transcription of each interview and the related translation in English is part of the doctoral thesis in the appendix;
- Parts of the interview not relevant to the topic are replaced by the following characters: "[...]";
- Personal names (people, institutions, publishers, ...) are replaced with the digits "xxxxxx" unless they are substantially essential to the meaning of the concept;
- Every interviewee received a copy of his/her interview transcription for eventual personal review. The transcription has been translated into English by the researcher, supported by the translation function of Microsoft Word 365.
- Any information relating to agreements not available to the public has been omitted in the transcript.

Pseudonymisation measures were applied to prevent key informants from being recognized and to give more importance to words and concepts than whoever told them. The interviewees were aware that the researcher had given consent for the doctoral thesis to be released in open access form by the University of Perugia at the times and in the forms established by the university itself.

¹³¹ <https://www.unipg.it/files/statuto-regolamenti/regolamenti/reg-trattamento-dati-personali.pdf> (accessed 13 May 2024)

4.7.2 Data from databases and websites

Data processed for tables and graphs presented in the PhD thesis are:

- publicly available or published under an open or CC0 license;
- extracted from Web of Science and Scopus databases, proprietary databases accessible to the researcher through the Università degli Studi di Perugia subscription. The amount of data extracted for study and research purposes only is intended and covered by fair use¹³².

A declaration of the sources accompanies each table or graph.

Chapter summary

The fourth chapter details the methodology and research methods used. To answer the research questions formulated, a mixed method approach is best suited, so both qualitative and quantitative methodology have been selected. Mixed method is one of the possible approaches in social sciences too, in which Libraries and Information Science stands. The topic of transformative agreements is complex and requires a comprehensive approach to address its complexity during the research project. A mixed method approach can provide a rich picture of the observed phenomenon and better answer the research questions.

The more appropriate research methods to be applied are semi-structured interviews and data collection from bibliographic citation databases. Quantitative data were gathered from different bibliographic citation databases, for each one some notes are given about data available, research strategies and extraction process. Qualitative data were gathered from interviews to five key informants, two were by written text and three video recorded, then transcribed, and finally translated in English. Data processing regulation are explained. Ethical considerations are also discussed in relation to data collection techniques and data analysis.

¹³²https://clarivate.com/wp-content/uploads/dlm_uploads/2023/11/Terms-of-Use_3.1-CV-November-2023.pdf
https://clarivate.com/wp-content/uploads/dlm_uploads/2022/11/Clarivate-Website-copyright-notice-November-2022.pdf
<https://www.elsevier.com/legal/elsevier-website-terms-and-conditions>
(accessed 13 May 2024)

5 Outcomes and discussion

5.1 Quantitative data analysis

5.1.1 An overview of OA and OA hybrid

Data on OA articles out of the total number of articles with publication year (PY) 2018-2022 indexed in each database was collected. Some notes about:

- data comes from four different sources: Dimensions, OpenAlex, Scopus, Web of Science. Databases have different perimeters of coverage, so the share calculated on data is presented separately one per database.
- data can contain duplicate.
- Unpaywall includes bronze open access in “OA all” data extraction along with other OA types (gold, green, and hybrid).
- hybrid open access group contains any open access article with an open license published in a hybrid journal. Distinctions whether the APC is paid under a transformative agreement or not cannot be done.
- gold open access group includes both diamond OA journals and APC payment full open access journals.

Starting with an overview, the database Dimensions indexes different type of records, collectively called as “items”. Database was accessed in freemium version; no other filters were available.

Fig.5 Dimensions, share of OA

According to Dimensions, items available OA overcome those closed since 2019. The share increased until 2022.

OpenAlex indexes different types of items, collectively called “works”. High numbers are rounded to the nearest thousand.

Fig.6 OpenAlex, share of OA on works

Considering all “works”, the total OA share is around 30% in 2018 and in 2022 is over 54%. OA hybrid share increases of around 9%.

Filtering data by type of publication = “article”, the increase grows from over 30% in 2018 to more than 60% in 2022, OA hybrid increases of around 6% in the timespan.

Fig.7 OpenAlex, share OA on articles

OpenAlex is a database where “Works are scholarly documents like journal articles, books, datasets, and theses. OpenAlex indexes over 240M works, with about 50,000 added daily”¹³³. For the presence of a large number of types of works non indexed in other databases, data were secondly filtered by type of publication = articles. In Scopus and in Web of Science the filter by article was not applied.

In Scopus database OA hybrid is named “OA hybrid-gold”, however it is separated from OA gold. For the study purpose it is used “OA hybrid” as other databases use. Based on Scopus data the “OA all” globally increases from around 40% of 2018 to over 47% in 2022, the hybrid share increases from around 3% to over 6,5%.

Fig.8 Scopus, share of OA on items

¹³³ <https://docs.openalex.org/api-entities/works> (accessed 13 May 2024)

In Web of Science the OA hybrid is named “Gold-hybrid”, however separated from OA Gold. For the research purpose it appears in tabs and figures as “OA hybrid”. According to data extracted from Web of Science, for the publication years considered, the OA all cumulatively passes from almost 40% to over 47%, while the percentage of OA hybrid increases more than 3 points.

Fig.9 Web of Science, share of OA on items

The OA percentages increase in all databases considered, both for OA all and for OA hybrid.

5.1.2 Italy as country affiliation

Data were then filtered by Affiliation country value = “Italy” in the three databases where possible (Dimensions freemium version is without filters). The results concerning authors with Italian affiliation follow.

Fig.10 OpenAlex, share of OA on Italian works

Fig.11 OpenAlex, share of OA on Italian articles

According to data from OpenAlex, the percentage of OA “works” authored by Italian institutions affiliated is over 48% with the publication year 2018 and increases to over 64% with the 2022 publication year. OA hybrid passes from 5,73% to 12,68% over the period. Filtering by “article”, “OA all” share increases from over 51% to around 69%, the OA hybrid share passes from 6,16 % to 13,27%.

Fig.12 Scopus, share of OA on Italian items

Percentages by Scopus show that OA all share passes from around 45% to over 60%, while the OA hybrid share from 4,20% to 11,04%.

Fig.13 Web of Science, share of OA on Italian items

Percentages by Web of Science show that OA all share passes from over 46% to over 60%, while the OA hybrid share from 6,40% to 13,67%.

Authors affiliated with an Italian research institution as authors or co-authors of items OA with publication year 2018-2022 are observed. OA percentages increase in all databases considered for OA all and OA hybrid. To summarize, the percentage of “Open access All” publications on the total number of items published stood at between 45% and 51% of indexed publications in 2018, while 2022 it increased and stood at between 60% and 69% in

2022. Over the same period, the hybrid OA went from 4.20% to 6.40% in 2018 to 11.04% to 13.67% in 2022.

On the other hand, the percentage of OA all, without distinction of affiliation, depending on the database considered, for 2018 publications is around 30%, 35%, 39%, and up to 49%, while for 2022, it is between 47% and over 60%.

The percentage of hybrid OA, without distinction of affiliation, depending on the database considered, for 2018 publications is 3.18% and up to 5.53%, while in 2022, it is up to 6.56% and up to 13.32%.

We know that transformative agreements mainly increase the OA hybrid globally and in Italy. With the data observed, it is impossible to define the picture further. As underlined earlier, the hybrid open access attribute refers to articles paid through a TA and single articles paid to be published OA through other funds.

5.1.3 Data on publications through Italian TAs

Usually, through transformative agreements, the corresponding author affiliation is the institution paying the APC for that article. Two attempts to extract data regarding only articles published open access through Italian transformative agreements were made, one in the Scopus database and one in the Web of Science database. It should be noted that the corresponding author's metadata is not searchable through the web interface functionalities.

In Scopus the metadata about corresponding author appears in the records extracted, in the field “corresponding author address”. Addresses are not normalized while the country is. Exporting records with multiple metadata is limited to 2000 records per time, which made the extraction process time-consuming. However, thanks to the guidelines shared by Andrew Gray in 2020 (Gray, 2020), a dataset was successfully created. It contains OA hybrid articles from authors affiliated with Italian institutions, with publication year 2018-2022. Data extracted were updated on the 17th of January 2024. Articles were deduplicated by EID (Electronic Identifier, i.e. the Scopus ID number), then the value “Italy” was extracted from the corresponding author address. The number of records after deduplication is 9932. The

dataset contains OA hybrid articles with a corresponding author affiliated to an Italian institution, both published through transformative agreements and out of them.

Market Watch by ESAC estimates that there are 26070 articles publishable OA through Italian TAs in the whole period 2020-2022¹³⁴. We cannot verify the gap through other sources. We can suppose an overestimation of ESAC, or that ESAC data contains OA gold articles, or that, for some reason about quality, completeness or updating data, in Scopus database not all articles published OA hybrid are correctly assigned to OA hybrid attribute, or some of them result now with OA gold attribute, because in the meanwhile the journal flipped to full open access. This could be part of future research. Country and publisher fields were normalized, then the records were distributed by year and publisher. Normalizing per institution of the corresponding author, that is a field variously compiled, could be part of future research too.

The following table and graph display the yearly growth rate of the OA hybrid during the 5 years.

SCOPUS dataset	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	total
OA hybrid articles	1647	1549	2024	2366	2346	9932
yearly value variation related to 2018 value	100	-6%	23%	44%	42%	
yearly value variation related to previous year value	100	-6%	31%	17%	-1%	

Table 1. Scopus, yearly growth rate of OA hybrid PY 2018-2022 with CA from Italy

Fig.14 Scopus, increase of OA hybrid, Italian CA

¹³⁴ <https://esac-initiative.org/market-watch/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

The following two tables display the distribution of OA hybrid articles based on their year of publication and publisher. The first table indicates the total number of articles extracted, while the second table shows the annual percentage of OA hybrid articles in the sample. The years in which a transformative agreement was in place are highlighted. The percentage of OA hybrid articles increases during the years of a TA, while, for some other publishers, it may decrease.

Publisher	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	total
SPRINGER	246	245	690	1036	884	3101
ELSEVIER	521	534	374	291	229	1949
others	407	236	264	202	215	1324
WILEY	142	167	148	412	428	1297
ACS	17	21	201	92	120	451
OUP	77	87	27	71	82	344
NATURE (SPRINGER)	63	59	34	38	41	235
RSC	17	16	44	33	72	182
CUP	8	12	51	40	68	179
TANDF	48	73	20		9	150
DE GRUYTER	19	16	34	26	31	126
IEEE	11	10	20	19	65	125
EMERALD	1	1	45	33	41	121
SAGE	15	27	11	21	11	85
LIPPINCOTT WKH	12	15	17	18	20	82
IOP	14	7	20	14	16	71
APS	13	10	6	7	7	43
BMJ	13	10	11	5	4	43
AIP	3	3	7	8	3	24
Total	1647	1549	2024	2366	2346	9932

Table 2. Scopus, OA hybrid PY 2018-2022 with CA from Italy, distribution by publisher

Publisher yearly share	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	share on 5 years TA from	source
SPRINGER	14,94%	15,82%	34,09%	43,79%	37,68%	31,22%	2020 ESAC
ELSEVIER	31,63%	34,47%	18,48%	12,30%	9,76%	19,62%	2023 publisher's website
others	24,71%	15,24%	13,04%	8,54%	9,16%	13,33%	
WILEY	8,62%	10,78%	7,31%	17,41%	18,24%	13,06%	2020 ESAC
ACS	1,03%	1,36%	9,93%	3,89%	5,12%	4,54%	2020 ESAC
OUP	4,68%	5,62%	1,33%	3,00%	3,50%	3,46%	
NATURE (SPRINGER)	3,83%	3,81%	1,68%	1,61%	1,75%	2,37%	
RSC	1,03%	1,03%	2,17%	1,39%	3,07%	1,83%	2022 ESAC
CUP	0,49%	0,77%	2,52%	1,69%	2,90%	1,80%	2020 ESAC
TANDF	2,91%	4,71%	0,99%	0,00%	0,38%	1,51%	
DE GRUYTER	1,15%	1,03%	1,68%	1,10%	1,32%	1,27%	2020 ESAC
IEEE	0,67%	0,65%	0,99%	0,80%	2,77%	1,26%	2022 ESAC
EMERALD	0,06%	0,06%	2,22%	1,39%	1,75%	1,22%	2020 ESAC
SAGE	0,91%	1,74%	0,54%	0,89%	0,47%	0,86%	
Wolters K. Health-Lipp.	0,73%	0,97%	0,84%	0,76%	0,85%	0,83%	2021 ESAC
IOP	0,85%	0,45%	0,99%	0,59%	0,68%	0,71%	2023 ESAC
APS	0,79%	0,65%	0,30%	0,30%	0,30%	0,43%	
BMJ	0,79%	0,65%	0,54%	0,21%	0,17%	0,43%	
AIP	0,18%	0,19%	0,35%	0,34%	0,13%	0,24%	2020 ESAC
Total	1647	1549	2024	2366	2346	100,00%	

Table 3. Scopus, percentage of OA hybrid PY 2018-2022 with CA from Italy, distribution by publisher

The second attempt to extract data concerning only articles published open access through Italian transformative agreements was made in *Web of Science*. The APC payment through a transformative agreement negotiated through the consortium CRUI-CARE generally appears in the article. This metadata is included in funding information, and the funding fields are searchable through the database's web interface. Data extracted were updated on the 15th of January 2024. The research ran a search for "CRUI-CARE" in the funding agency and funding text fields, limited to publication years 2020-2022. In fact, 2020 started the first Italian TA. In *Web of Science*, the export function is limited to a maximum of 1000 records at a time. After deduplication, the dataset contains 10614 records. In addition to the possible reasons mentioned earlier for the dataset extracted from Scopus, this dataset could not be complete because the Funding text about APC could not appear in the article. The metadata of the funding institution noun through the consortium is quite cured, so it was pretty easy to work on and normalize it. The following table shows the distribution of the OA hybrid articles per institution member of the consortium until a minimum of 100 OA hybrid articles with publication year 2020 – 2022.

Institution within consortium CRUI-CARE	2020	2021	2022	total
Università degli Studi di Padova within the CRUI-CARE Agreement	25	158	235	418
Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna within the CRUI-CARE Agreement	29	167	220	416
Università degli Studi di Roma La Sapienza within the CRUI-CARE Agreement	35	139	211	385
Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II within the CRUI-CARE Agreement	21	150	189	360
Università degli Studi di Milano within the CRUI-CARE Agreement	18	135	195	348
Università degli Studi di Torino within the CRUI-CARE Agreement	21	125	155	301
Università degli Studi di Firenze within the CRUI-CARE Agreement	19	98	183	300
Politecnico di Milano within the CRUI-CARE Agreement	20	121	150	291
Università di Pisa within the CRUI-CARE Agreement	18	85	99	202
Università degli Studi di Milano-Bicocca within the CRUI-CARE Agreement	9	62	129	200
Università degli Studi di Pavia within the CRUI-CARE Agreement	20	67	88	175
Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore within the CRUI-CARE Agreement	9	90	75	174
Università degli Studi di Genova within the CRUI-CARE Agreement	16	65	92	173
Politecnico di Torino within the CRUI-CARE Agreement	15	78	75	168
Università degli Studi di Salerno within the CRUI-CARE Agreement	6	48	110	164
Università degli Studi di Verona within the CRUI-CARE Agreement	11	66	81	158
Università degli Studi di Palermo within the CRUI-CARE Agreement	12	59	81	152
Università degli Studi di Brescia within the CRUI-CARE Agreement	8	39	81	128
Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche within the CRUI-CARE Agreement.		15	113	128
Università degli Studi della Campania Luigi Vanvitelli	8	47	67	122
Università degli Studi di Catania within the CRUI-CARE Agreement	5	61	50	116
Università degli Studi di Trieste within the CRUI-CARE Agreement	14	34	68	116
Università degli Studi di Bari Aldo Moro within the CRUI-CARE Agreement	9	50	53	112
Università degli Studi di Perugia within the CRUI-CARE Agreement	14	39	57	110
Università degli Studi di Trento within the CRUI-CARE Agreement	10	41	53	104
Università degli Studi di Ferrara within the CRUI-CARE Agreement	3	36	63	102
total	375	2075	2973	5423

Table 4. Web of Science, distribution of the OA hybrid articles per institution member

The two sets of data extracted and used to explore the impact of the OA hybrid articles through transformative agreements in Italy since their launch in 2020 lack accuracy and completeness. Therefore, the retrieved data can only be considered as a sample, which shows a trend but not the complete picture. Despite this, the data does provide a synthetic representation, albeit incomplete, of some of the impacts of TAs in terms of article quantity and distribution.

5.2 Qualitative data analysis

5.2.1 Emerging themes

Monitoring

All the key informants interviewed agreed on the need to monitor the articles published open access paid by APC, through transformative agreements or out of them, and the related expenditure.

K3 refers to Plan S report (Coalition S, 2022), summarizing that “TAs had a scarce impact on effective transformation”, “only 1% out of the 2326 titles in their transformative programme shifted totally to Open access, and 68% failed to meet their targeted Open goals” (K3, p.1), with K4: “the Coalition S, which supported the TAs, is now recording their failure” (K4, p.1).

K2 states that “this is a classic example where the same information is looked at, let's say, from two different starting points and therefore gives absolutely opposite results” (K2, 0:1:59.220 --> 0:2:29.550). In parallel to the Plan S report (Coalition S, 2022), K2 refers to the announce of SpringerNature that emphasizes the crucial role of TAs in the transition to OA, as for example stated on the press release of the 5th of June 2023:

New data from Springer Nature shows the vital role transformative agreements (TAs) are playing in driving the global transition to open access (OA). They are the main reason OA is increasing in Springer Nature’s hybrid journals, delivering OA equity across all academic disciplines¹³⁵.

K5 notices that

it is very interesting to have the picture of what is changing or has changed, how they have increased, how much has been saved, how much has been spent and how much has been spent per article (K5, 0:35:13.550 --> 0:35:20.60).

At institutional level, some analysis is conducted: “we have a very low cost per article, because so many have published in this way” (K5, 0:35:13.550 --> 0:35:20.60).

¹³⁵<https://group.springernature.com/gp/group/media/press-releases/transformative-agreements-playing-vital-role-in-oa-transition/25433850> (accessed 13 May 2024)

As the first question of the interview was on the TAs impact, K2 states that

we would like to measure the impact. It is certainly a substantial economic impact, it is a pity, in fact, that this thing is not in the least measurable, because with the data in hand, perhaps those who then have to make decisions would perhaps have a more responsible attitude (K2, 0:5:39.190 --> 0:5:47.270).

The need for the data about expenditure to be available at a national level is underlined, to pursue and sustain responsible and conscious choices. K2 remarks the non-disclosure clauses still included in most of TAs, despite of the transparency expected from the OA2020 initiative “Expression of interest in the large-scale implementation of open access to scholarly journals”, undersigned by a large number of institutions¹³⁶.

About monitoring, K1 reminds that through organizations at a national level like CoPER¹³⁷ and CRUI

there are joint initiatives to proceed with a revision of the accounting systems to make this monitoring easier, because so far monitoring has not been able to be done in a simple way, because these items of expenditure [APCs] were distributed in different expenditure chapters. But now we're going to try to have a single chapter, so we can do the monitoring in a much, much more efficient way (K1, 0:7:11.340 --> 0:7:40.690).

The initiatives want to monitor the APCs paid by institutions out of the TAs. By the way on the 25th of September 2023 the CoPER Open science Working Group released the “Guidelines for monitoring Article Publication Charges (APCs) or publication costs in Open access”¹³⁸ to be used by the national network of public research bodies. Initiatives like Open APC require that institutions are able to collect quite easily the set of data on APC expenditure to participate in and regularly update it. To date, Open APC shows data from five Italian institutions.¹³⁹ Part of this research presented an attempt of monitoring TAs, arising from data publicly available or collected by proprietary bibliographic citation databases, subscribed by most universities. Further development of the research could lead a more suitable dataset. At least about TAs, maybe more complete data is available at consortium level, unless it is covered by non-disclosure clauses.

About that, AISA, the 16th of March 2024, published a public letter to CRUI¹⁴⁰ in which it asks “CRUI CARE to make public all the data on the transformative agreements it has”. To

¹³⁶ <https://oa2020.org/mission/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

¹³⁷ <https://home.infn.it/coper/openscience.html> (accessed 13 May 2024)

¹³⁸ <https://doi.org/10.15161/oar.it/143140>

¹³⁹ <https://treemaps.openapc.net/apcdata/openapc/#institution/country=ITA> (accessed 13 May 2024)

¹⁴⁰ <https://aisa.sp.unipi.it/contratti-trasformativi-una-lettera-aperta-alla-crui/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

date no public answer was given by CRUI CARE. In the same letter, AISA underlines that many European countries released reports at a national level, one of the most recent is the UK report commissioned by JISC, where, among a large number of data, it is said that “at the rate observed in the review, the ‘big five’ publishers would take more than 72 years to flip their TA titles”. (Brayman et al., 2024) SCONUL,¹⁴¹ the UK charity Society of College, National and University Libraries, responded appreciating the report¹⁴² and adding that “Financial divestment in underperforming TAs should be used to fund alternative models”. (SCONUL, 2024)

K1 summarizes to see “a positive function” of TAs, subordinated to its verification. “This function in the northern hemisphere, this positive function, must be verified that it is actually accompanied by a freer and therefore less [oligopolistic] market, because otherwise it has failed, the system has failed” (K1, 0:7:11.340 --> 0:7:40.690).

K4 observes that

in a competitive market, peer review and publishing services could be organized and provided by other private publishers, or by public institutions through university presses and libraries. On the other hand, in the increasingly concentrated market of the "brand value", the latter cannot be replaced (K4, p.2).

Openly K3 states that one of the two factors that complicate the situation in Italy is “the lack of data about previous APCs costs, percentage of Open articles, etc ...” adding that “libraries were never asked to produce - and never collected, as it’s not so easy due to administrative internal workflows - the annual expenditures for hybrid APCs, often budgeted in the most creative ways” (K3, p.3). K2 refers to an Italian institutions informal working group who aims to develop

“a data collection model - that we will share with all the universities as soon as possible - to be able to collect the data a little bit both from the point of view of the output... These are the results, but also from an input point of view, how long did it take? Me, how much money, how much funds, how many people...(K2, 0:16:50.710 --> 0:17:7.820)

The data collection model was released very recently by the working group¹⁴³. The topic of monitoring seems a crucial point to take care of. The data is quite fragmented at the moment.

¹⁴¹ <https://www.sconul.ac.uk/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

¹⁴² <https://www.sconul.ac.uk/News/View?g=a62842ce-2592-4397-8655-aa350dc979d3> (accessed 13 May 2024)

¹⁴³ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10389873>

Researchers' satisfaction and awareness

Considering the satisfaction of the researchers registered by K5 and K1, thoughts on TAs should be positive. K1 says “my colleagues, really like transformative agreements when it comes to nationally stipulated agreements, none obviously likes to use their research money to pay for APCs”. However, K1 also keeps in mind that “they are always funded by money that comes, let's say, from libraries, redirected from subscriptions”. (K1, 0:7:11.340 --> 0:7:40.690). K5 openly says that “looking at it from the researchers' point of view, it has to be said that transformative agreements are having a great success.” (K5, 0:0:40.70 --> 0:0:53.790). K5 continues talking about their own experience:

the reception that these agreements have had has been excellent. In short, apart from a few rare voices of dissent, of mathematicians, on the contrary, however, in general the numbers of published articles are excellent, even the feedback from the messages, phone calls, conversations that we have had are all thanking for the initiative, because more and more open access is required for the publication of certain research, and these researchers paid and pay the APCs by their research funds (K5, 0:0:40.70 --> 0:0:53.790).

Considering the TAs resolve in many cases a practical short-term problem to the researchers, they are welcome. K5 adds

the transformative agreement is an excellent solution for those who do not have major problems regarding the future of open access and have as their primary objective, the basic one, to publish in open access in excellent journals in order to make their research more open, as achievable as possible and that can also be useful for their career (K5, 0:2:50.70 --> 0:2:59.960).

According to the experience of K5, during the approval process internal to the institution by the board of directors

no criticism came, none, I expected maybe to have to face someone who would have said but, how much does it cost us? But no, because evidently, its practical usefulness has been perceived. I would say that the positive thing we have experienced is precisely the satisfaction for the practical aspects solved, the fact that they solve a problem that was there and somehow solve it, offloading it on someone else. (K5, 0:23:25.520 --> 0:23:29.910)

K5 refers to the fact that APCs payment through the TAs is charged to the library budget, which is generally financed by the FFO - Fondo di Finanziamento Ordinario -, the Ordinary Fund allocated yearly by the Italian Ministry of University and Research to public universities.

K4 underlines that

with some notable exceptions, such as the University of Milan's Open access group, the TAs have been accepted and implemented in the most uncritical way, even if the agreements negotiated by the CRUI centralize the negotiation but not the expenditure and the relative responsibility. (K4, p.2)

K3 openly states that the second factor that complicates the Italian situation is the “complete lack of awareness among researchers about the costs and mechanisms of the current publishing system”. K3 cites experiences from abroad where the community of researchers of certain countries or institutions showed awareness of the process of negotiations:

when negotiations with publishers to get effective and real transformative agreements were broken due to the intransigence of publishers in not meeting the libraries requests (with a subsequent no-access policy to the publishers platforms), researchers aware of the costs and mechanism of publishing stood with negotiators and renounced to access for some months (in Germany, years) without complaining, as they knew they were fighting for a greater benefit, as it happened at the University of California (K3, p.3).

That is confirmed by K5: “I have met very few teachers who are really concerned, inclined to welcome, to share the ethical demands of open access” (K5, 0:2:50.70 --> 0:2:59.960). It appears that the satisfaction of researchers is related to solving practical problem to cope with meeting the requirement of publishing open access, which is included in several research funding programs and publishing in core journals to gain prestige for future funding and personal career advancement, despite eventual price increases, perceived acceptable at the moment, maybe for a lack of awareness or because currently decisions of institutions seem based more on short-term forecasts.

Sustainability

K4 states that TAs “do not reduce, and may even increase, the expenditure of academic and research libraries on “top” scientific journals” (K4, p.1). The strength point of TAs should have been the “cost neutrality” as K2 remarks:

here's the strong point, in my opinion it should have been this neutrality, right? So, I turn everything I pay to read into a contribution to publish, this thing didn't happen that way; So, what started out as a strength turned out to be a weakness, because in fact the system costs more. Sustainability, in my opinion, is not there, that is, medium-term sustainability should be lacking (K2, 0:8:18.710 --> 0:8:29.500).

Retracing part of the history of the introduction of TAs, K1 recalls the principle summarized by Ralph Schimmer, then Director of Scientific Information at the Max Planck Digital Library, following the 2015 OA Transition White Paper (Schimmer et al., 2015):

he says why we don't transfer, that is, why we don't move to the pay-to-publish market, because "*there's enough money in the system*" anyway, we're going to save ourselves anyway, because we're paying a lot more for subscriptions than we would pay for a reasonable APC per article (K1, 0:1:39.630 --> 0:2:10.880).

This argument was true at the APC prices of that time. In addition, K1 remarks what economists say about publishing market which is anelastic:

I am forced to buy all the journals because, if I have to do a search I can't choose, I buy this or that, so it's a rigid market in a way, every single publication is a monopoly, because the publisher has my publication in his hands; conversely, the APC market should be in theory a less rigid market, therefore more competitive (K1, 0:3:2.350 --> 0:3:31.500).

K4 underlines that “if you are willing to pay a monopoly price to publish an article in OA, you should be aware that you are recognizing that you are not getting editorial services: you are getting evaluation” (K4, p.2), referring to Schimmer words: “transforming the existing core journals’ business models while simultaneously maintaining their function of providing quality assurance through peer review, publishing services and brand value”¹⁴⁴. K4 highlights that currently Ralph Schimmer is Senior Director, Government Partnerships and Public Policy in John Wiley & Sons, Inc¹⁴⁵.

K3 states that “as they are negotiated now, at least in Italy, TAs are neither fair nor sustainable, due to their weaknesses” listed by the interviewee. One of these is “they still combine subscriptions + APCs, at the only benefit of publishers” (K3, p.2). In the words of K5:

even if the initial dream of simply seeing the amount of what you paid to access transformed into what you pay to publish, and maybe this dream is, let's say it was, it was a dream, in the sense that the amounts are, even I must say logically, increased compared to [traditional agreements] since publishers when they propose a transformative one, they add, at least in the first instance, as a first request what they earned from access and what they earned from publication, i.e. from APCs, and this, however, weighs down the budget of library systems, basically, which are the ones that pay (K5, 0:2:50.70 --> 0:2:59.960).

¹⁴⁴ https://www.mpd.lmpg.de/images/documents/Nachrichten/schimmer_ResearchEurope.pdf (accessed 13 May 2024)

¹⁴⁵ <https://newsroom.wiley.com/press-releases/press-release-details/2023/Open-Science-Leader-Dr.-Ralf-Schimmer-Joins-Wiley/default.aspx> (accessed 13 May 2024)

K2 lists why TAs are not sustainable in the medium term: “increasingly expensive transformative agreements getting longer, more and more with periods that are also quite long and with very, very mixed conditions, very different from each other”. To summarize the opinions, current transformative agreements do not seem sustainable in the medium/long-term. About the future, K5 says:

in fact, the real problem that I have always seen with this type of agreements is the future, about which few still have clear ideas. The publishers themselves, in my opinion, do not have it because, if the goal is to completely transform journals into open access, they will have to deal with the fact that there will be no more subscriptions for those who just want to read (K5, 0:10:29.10 --> 0:10:39.450).

K5 closes the answer to question no.2 as follows: “let's say that it is a moment in which there are more questions than answers” (K5, 0:16:59.870 --> 0:17:8.50).

K1 summarizes as follows:

Yes, the weakness aspect, that is, they are not “*sustainable*” if you prove after 4, 5, 6 years that the market does not open. If the market doesn't open up, all publishers have raised their APCs, no new publishers have come into lower APCs, so it doesn't work. So that's the absolute limit, sustainability (K1, 0:15:25.320 --> 0:15:48.450).

Inequality

K4 frames the inequality at the beginning of the first answer:

from the outset, it was clear that they could only have increased access to a very limited part of research: that carried out by researchers working in very rich institutions that chose to sign them and continue to pay monopoly prices. And it was also quite clear that they would have made it increasingly difficult for researchers working in "poor" institutions to be visible in the so-called top journals, because they could not afford the same monopoly prices (K4, p.1).

K3 says that transformative agreements “might have increased a bit the access for the readers, but they also created more entry barriers for authors in low-income countries not able to pay the requested APCs” (K3, p.1). Quoting a researcher from Indonesia K3 states that “it’s just a solution working for the global North, for those who can afford it, and it was not negotiated or even discussed with the vast majority of researchers not working in Europe or the US” (K3, p.1). K3 adds “they are not inclusive, as they are only available to the global North institutions, further marginalizing the global South. TAs reinforce the existing inequalities” (K3, p.2).

K1 states that inequality should be avoided not or not only for ethical reasons but for convenience, even if “there are often publishers who apply palliatives, which are waivers”. In fact, sometimes publishers do not ask APC payment to facilitate researchers from country to low-income:

southern hemisphere, let's say, does not have, in general, the possibility of paying to publish. So, this is a very serious problem, not for ethical or conceptual reasons, but for utilitarian reasons, because for us, the northern hemisphere, it is convenient for the southern hemisphere to continue to publish anyway, because science has no boundaries and therefore clearly the diversity, *the diversity*, of the southern hemisphere is fundamental in infinite fields (K1, 0:7:11.340 --> 0:7:40.690).

K1 outlines another possible inequality between early-stage career researchers and senior researchers: “It would be terrible to go into a model where the costs of APCs were paid for by research funds, because that would “kill” young people who naturally have less research funding” (K1, 0:7:11.340 --> 0:7:40.690).

K5 remarks another eventual front of possible inequality between institutions that “publish and the institutions that do not publish, or that publish little, that is, that they will therefore find themselves paying to publish, when, on the other hand, they do not publish and it is also a problem of a purely accounting nature” (K5, 0:16:59.870 --> 0:17:8.50).

To summarize, transformative agreements and, in general, the pay-per-publish model can bring inequality between countries, early-career stage researchers and senior researchers, different research groups within the same discipline, and even research groups or authors in the same institution. They also could open a critical point in allocating costs among consortia members.

Research assessment

K1 notes that the research

it's a complex system, it has to work, the other thing I want to say right away, which you know for sure, is that all this vicious circle is hinged on research evaluation, because as long as research evaluation is based on the Impact Factor of a journal and on the so-called perceived prestige of the container and not of the content that is the article, clearly we will never get out of this, so let's make it clear right away that research assessment is the crucial thing.

“TAs could become fair and sustainable only if we do away with the reason for their monopoly and oligopoly high prices, that is an administrative research assessment emphasizing “publish or perish” and the proprietary bibliometric” databases. That is what

states K4, underlining how sustainability is connected to the evaluation of research, as also mentioned earlier. Remarking that

it has been a wonderful business for the oligopolists of scholarly publishing: while it has become easier and easier to bypass them in reading, thanks to public repositories and Sci-hub¹⁴⁶, you cannot bypass them in writing, if the administrative research evaluation keeps on making you addicted to their “brand value” (K4, p.2).

K3 says that “if you don’t move away from the journal ranking obsession, and you still evaluate the “box” and not the content, publishers will always sell at their prices “prestigious” journals” (K3, p.2). About the research assessment, K3 mentions the COARA initiative, which was signed by more than 40 Italian institutions, including ANVUR, the national agency for research assessment. K3 highlights that COARA envisions “a strong, deep, and long-awaited reform of the research assessment criteria.” (K3, p.2). K5, as underlined earlier, mentions that TAs let researchers cope with publishing in open access and publishing in “excellent journals”, that can be “useful for their career” (K5, 0:2:50.70 -> 0:2:59.960). K2 recognizes that librarians are well-positioned to provide a comprehensive perspective on science communication, incorporating various viewpoints including evaluation. This topic is discussed more in detail below. It seems that the research assessment is a crucial point, or perhaps the most crucial point.

Diamond OA and Green OA

Talking about TAs, all the key informants mention other open access road, like Diamond and Green. K5 affirms that

the goal of a truly free access, the goal of an academy that totally retains not only the rights, but also the whole process of publishing the results of the research is not achieved with the transformative agreements. They are in some way, someone argues, a kind of drug of the market, as they move away from the finish line the possibility of truly transforming scholarly communication towards the green way, towards publication on repositories or whatever it is that they have a validity for the purposes of career (K5, 0:2:50.70 --> 0:2:59.960).

In K4’s opinion, “TAs discourage universities and research institutions from promoting and funding local “diamond” and scholarly-driven OA initiatives, even if this is now the EU’s

¹⁴⁶ Sci-hub is a shadow library website and defines itself as “the first pirate website in the world to provide mass and public access to tens of millions of research papers”.

preferred option” (K4, p.1). K4 refers to DIAMAS,¹⁴⁷ a European-funded project to support, enhance, and improve institutional open access publication services.

K3 reprises the Council of the European Union citation:

as it clearly results from the Council Conclusions (9616/23)¹⁴⁸ in June 2023, there is an alternative way to go, which is the so-called Diamond institutional publishing, for a “high-quality, transparent, open, trustworthy and equitable scholarly publishing”. Diamond journals are 100% in the hands of the community, they have low costs for scalable infrastructures, they are 100% open and authors retain their rights. This is the real Open access as foreseen in the Berlin Declaration (K3, p.2).

K2 refers to a recent experience shared by the University of Geneva regarding Switzerland's national policy on open access, summarizing: “when one of our researchers asks for funding for Gold open access, we put the same funding on the Diamond. So, this is a policy” (K2, 0:10:28.370 --> 0:10:43.700).

“I think it's essential not to tie yourself to any model and especially not to tie yourself to the payment of [APCs], so to keep all the other avenues open: so, the *green*, the *diamond*, also other very important models like *Subscribe to open*” states K1 (K1, 0:12:54.380 --> 0:13:22.280).

Even the members [in cOAlition S] that at the beginning were pushing a lot exclusively for the APC model, have realized that it may not work so all of us together, compact as always, we are continuing to support *green*, so, great support for open, interoperable archive networks (K1, 0:15:52.800 --> 0:16:19.160).

Again, talking about cOAlition S, quite returning to scientific communication's origins, K1 states that the organization is

moving towards the *diamond* hypothesis. The *diamond* is a form of return to the University Press: to maintain the circuit of peer review, within the academic institutions, without necessarily turning to commercial publishers or turning to commercial publishers who however obey very precise rules, including economic ones, dictated and under the control of universities and research institutes (K1, 0:17:9.620 --> 0:17:39.730).

A recent paper discussed the effects of Quebec’s provincial funding agency¹⁴⁹ (FRQ) policy as a member of cOAlition S, stating that “[diamond open access] is a model with great potential for supporting affordable open access of the published version”. (Harris et al., 2024)

¹⁴⁷ <https://diamasproject.eu/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

¹⁴⁸ <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-9616-2023-INIT/en/pdf> (accessed 13 May 2024)

¹⁴⁹ <https://frq.gouv.qc.ca/en/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

Enrico Massimo Dotti remarks that

the movement for open access also arose to counter the reduction of science and research products to a pure commodity, but in my opinion this contrast is rendered at least partly ineffective because it is implemented with policies that in other terms propose the same problem instead to solve it ¹⁵⁰

and concludes that “we should start calling only what is free from editorial speculation open access.” ¹⁵¹ (Dotti, 2024)

During the discussion on green open access, the topic of Creative Commons licenses applicable to archived versions was brought up. The researcher introduced the conversation on licenses, noting that some publishers no longer allow CC licenses to be associated with deposited versions¹⁵², likely due to the increase of transformative agreements and the pay-per-publish model. In response to this, K1 emphasized the importance of negotiating specific clauses for green open access: “this is crucial. That is, the Green Way and then showing the postprint with CC-BY, this is a fundamental battle” and “that's central. Because... Because the scientific content is guaranteed by the AAM which, is identical to *the Version of Record*, VoR, and this also satisfies all the requirements of our research evaluation” (K1, 0:29:56.670 --> 0:30:30.180).

K2 announces that “we are now implementing a feature [in the institutional repository], both with Sherpa and Unpaywall, which allows us to find the correct version with the correct license”. “This is yet another trap of commercial publishers who obviously make things more and more complicated for you in one way, so that you necessarily go and get the other, which at this moment for them are the transformative agreements” (K2, 0:37:28.710 --> 0:37:58.550). About licensing, going back to TAs, K3 notices that “there is no preference/obligation to associate a CC BY license, allowing also for restrictive licenses such as CC BY NC ND which basically are not open” (K3, p.2). However, K5 underlines that about self-archiving in institutional repositories, “[in the agreements at a consortium level] the clause has always remained that it is possible to publish in their institutional repositories, moreover” (K5, 0:32:33.540 --> 0:32:37.260).

¹⁵⁰ Il movimento per l'accesso aperto è sorto anche per contrastare la riduzione a pura merce della scienza e dei prodotti della ricerca, ma questo contrasto è reso a mio avviso almeno in parte inefficace perché attuato con politiche che ripropongono in altri termini lo stesso problema invece di risolverlo [translation in English by the author]

¹⁵¹ Dovremmo cominciare a chiamare open access solo quello che si sottrae alla speculazione editoriale [translation in English by the author]

¹⁵² In Sherpa/Romeo, currently, publishers often allow a “bespoke license” to the accepted version in institutional repositories see, for example, <https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/id/publication/7936> (accessed 13 May 2024)

K1 highlights the potential of a national institutional repository network, currently not existing, for research assessment:

the main thing that has lagged far behind is the network, at least national, interoperable of research archives. Because we don't have it, it wouldn't take much to create it, because everyone, institutions, universities have their own archives and are already interoperable. We need a general portal that coordinates them and makes them interoperable. And if we did, we would heal the absurd, one of the absurdities which is that we have to buy the evaluation from the paid databases (K1, 0:43:55.160 --> 0:44:24.910).

Along the license theme goes the topic of the right retention strategy, that is in fact realized in K1's institution. The open access policy states that researchers do maintain copyright on the Author Accepted Manuscript: "the core of the problem, is that, if the publisher asks you, before taking the draft, to give up the rights, the author has no choice, that is, he has to change journal" (K1, 0:39:8.700 --> 0:39:39.510).

All the interviewees refer to green open access and diamond open access. To sum up their opinions these two paths must be maintained, widened, and given priority.

National plan

Regarding national initiatives, Italy has had a national plan for open science since June 2022 (section 2.3). K2 underlines the importance of monitoring to understand the starting point to plan objectives and activities. An Italian open science plan has been established, but activities must be explicitly funded, and a national coherent policy is needed. Some initiatives arise by single institutions, for example, delivering institutional guidelines and policies on open access or open science or establishing Dean's delegates on Open science (K2, 0:19:30.340 --> 0:20:0.870):

the Open science Plan develops when you know, I start from here, otherwise if you don't know where you're starting from, you can't say where, where you want to go, right? Now I have the impression that after the first phase in which there was a bit of agitation, many universities where there is not one, let's say a particular awareness, have remained at the same point, in short, so things are not developing there, despite the fact that you still receive requests from the rest of Europe ... And I must say, however, that I have seen instead that in some universities where, um, in short, in some way this sensitivity was born, because unfortunately they really are, let's say, local situations (K2, 0:19:30.340 --> 0:20:0.870).

K1 cites the Italian national plan on open science regarding the training on open science:

[It] has five directions, as our National Plan for Open science says, we do not open it, but we could open up the whole discourse of data and open data, data stewards ... Also in this discourse, these figures, who are they, who will they be? And so, I think that the message reaches researchers in a much more effective way, if it is carried not only by the librarian, but also by another researcher who has already been informed (K1, 0:20:32.410 --> 0:20:58.460).

Ethics

All the interviewees talked about ethical aspects when talking about transformative agreements and, more generally, about the communication of research results. K2 speaks of informed and responsible choices supported by monitoring data: “those who then have to make decisions would perhaps have a more responsible attitude” and cites the example of the French consortium: “I must say that I find very responsible, very responsible the French attitude that with respect to these transformative agreements has held a totally ... totally imaginary, coherent with a single transformative agreement for now and that's it” (K2, 0:1:59.220 --> 0:2:29.550). K4 talks about the responsibility of implementing TAs: “The TAs have been accepted and implemented in the most uncritical way, even if the agreements negotiated by the CRUI centralize the negotiation but not the expenditure and the relative responsibility” (K4, p.2).

About limitations of TAs, K5 states:

The other limitation, the one of an ethical nature, which I referred to, was the fact that it is said that the transformative agreements does not move, they do not go, let's say, not even to try to solve, it does not even come close to solving the problem of the possession of research and the maintenance of research in the institutional academic environment in which it is carried out. That is, the big publishers still have a strong power, because the research is published in the journals anyway (K5, 0:2:50.70 --> 0:2:59.960).

K3 underlines the need for awareness to drive the choices: “In the future, there should be a serious data collection and an intense awareness raising among researchers and administrators” (K3, p.3). K1 says

It's all connected, very, very complex and this is also fascinating, because it's about changing a market [that] is assumed between 10 and 20 [billion a year worldwide] and in the hands of 5 publishers, this is an operation that then the knowledge market, this, this is the most unacceptable thing, isn't it? (K1, 0:43:1.860 --> 0:43:16.10).

K1 cites the ethical aspect of the experience in working group on open science: “The working groups are all made up of researchers with various levels of experience and sensitivity, and

in fact it is an activity that we do for pure ethical reasons, because it is not part of our research activity” (K1, 0:20:32.410 --> 0:20:58.460).

I wouldn't put this entry [the OA through the transformative agreements], not even among the voices of Open science, that is, in my opinion, it's the umpteenth, the umpteenth trick, the umpteenth, the umpteenth process through which publishers basically exploit institutions (K2, 0:1:59.220 --> 0:2:29.550).

K2 does see the need of a “cultural change”:

if the goal [of TAs] was to activate a cultural change, the average researcher, the one who goes to the Springer website that approved the article and who chooses open access, does not understand in which field he is working, who pays and what, so there is no cultural change. If the goal was, let's say, let's make the research processes more transparent: this transparency is lacking because I don't know what I pay for and how much I pay (K2, 0:1:59.220 --> 0:2:29.550).

On the other hand, K2 says: “I believe that open access at any cost cannot, should not exist” (K2, 0:10:28.370 --> 0:10:43.700). In K2's opinion “is a little bit part of that process of trials and errors that science goes through and therefore also the tools, let's say, supporting science, go through this, is definitely a trial that has been done. It's a mistake that, in my opinion, is turning out to be a mistake” (K2, 0:1:59.220 --> 0:2:29.550).

However, one of the merits of transformative agreements is that they bring to the fore the debate on what is right and what is not right in communicating science and, more in general, in the research ecosystem.

5.2.2 The librarians' role

Emerging themes on the librarians' role are reported apart from others.

In the digital environment

Librarians play a role in various research and open practices, such as managing institutional repositories. K1 remarks that librarians “have a fundamental role”: “I see in the near future of librarians a very, very strong digitization that is going very well, the push towards the green way and that of the archives”, “with their professional skills in librarianship, [they] work extremely well with computer scientists”. K1 adds that “the librarian, still maintains his essential skills of librarianship, skills on metadata, with the rigor that training has

provided him, so I see a digital future for librarians, which is already happening in fact” (K1, 0:25:45.470 --> 0:25:58.660).

On the contrary, in the current context, if “TA's OA will remain the main Italian path to OA” K4 sees “a shift towards “platformisation” that will render most librarians and most libraries useless, if we mean them as repositories of literature they own” (K4, p.3.).

K5, talking about librarians in libraries says that “Librarians, I think, feel a little bit marginalized by this process... They already were, they began to be so when they were a bit deprived of their traditional tasks, in turning on subscriptions, deciding which ones to turn on or off, that is”. This is because

Generally they are the systems, the central offices, those that then subscribe to the resources and also because, precisely, while before the researcher had some reason to consult the librarian in a journal to ask for a subscription and so on, now from this strict point of view he knows that he has to turn to an office [with one librarian for all the libraries] that deals with this (K5, 0:21:27.960 --> 0:21:33.410).

The changes in librarianship in the digital age and the competencies and skills a librarian should have in the digital environment are subjects discussed so far in literature, going deep to the topic goes beyond the purpose of this research.

A jigsaw: TAs hidden costs

K3 underlines that transformative agreements “create a jigsaw access situation, in which something is open, and something still closed, randomly” (K3, p.2). This “jigsaw” is also a cost on librarians, in terms of management during the workflow but also a cost in terms of clear communication to researchers. K2 also notice it:

I saw the other disadvantage, be careful, is that they are all quite cumbersome, so some have journals yes, journals no, this one is inside, this is outside, this and this list, this another list, that is, it's really chaos for a researcher who also wants to try to understand something, in my opinion it's discouraging (K2, 0:7:28.840 --> 0:7:43.170)

The aforementioned aspect can be discouraging for researchers and can contribute to the creation of inequalities, as discussed earlier.

About that, recently Maria Cassella wrote that “libraries effectively feed a circuit that forces them to promote the services offered by publishers, thus increasing the costs of a contract,

once again favouring the oligopolistic system of the main international publishers.”¹⁵³
(Cassella, 2024)

Awareness of librarians

The interviewees discuss the awareness of librarians about transformative agreements:

I have the impression that libraries, with a view to offering a service to their users, think that, how to say, open access at any cost is a good thing, while instead I believe that open access at any cost cannot, should not exist. So, on the one hand, in my opinion there is certainly an attitude, pardon the term, a bit uncritical towards this phenomenon, that is, one says oh well, gosh, I have problems getting open access off the ground, now let's do the transformative agreements and the thing takes off. It doesn't work like that (K2, 0:10:28.370 --> 0:10:43.700).

So at the beginning there was a great deal of support, a great push and now there is a little more realism and it seems to me that in all libraries yes, we are realizing that in fact, however, these APCs are not going down, they are not going down, so in all libraries there is a clear perception that it is essential to proceed with *monitoring* accurately these costs (K1, 0:19:36.800 --> 0:20:0.970).

In Italy, as publicly pointed out by AISA, the Italian Association for the promotion of Open science, since 2019, TAs have been negotiated at particularly unfavourable conditions for institutions - and favourable for publishers: 5 years length, applied only to hybrid journals, no clear timeline for the transition (K3, p.2).

K3 closes the interview stating that “Libraries and librarians should play a more critical role in negotiations and take strong stances against the clear maneuvers of publishers to make this supposed “transition” last forever to their economic benefit” (K3, p.3).

In an ecosystem as the research is, awareness is a shared requirement among the academic community as a whole.

Advocacy

Underlining the lack of awareness by some researchers, K3 finds that librarians have

a crucial role in training about what Open access really is (in Italy, we are still seeing in public debates and on social media all the worse myths about Open access), in

¹⁵³ Le biblioteche alimentano di fatto un circuito che le obbliga a promuovere i servizi offerti dagli editori, facendo così crescere i costi di un contratto, favorendo ancora una volta il sistema oligopolistico dei principali editori internazionali. [translation in English by the author]

publicly declaring the insane amount of money they spend every year in subscriptions - to avoid the misconception “today reading is for free, why should I pay to publish?”

Moreover, librarians could contribute to create “awareness among researchers about the mechanism of the current scholarly publication market and its link to the research assessment criteria, which guarantees huge net gains to publishers - paid by public money” (K3, p.3). K1 underlines that “So, it's all a work that requires an education of the author and it's also a help, you can't leave the author alone in front of a publisher who normally has the position of strength” (K1, 0:39:8.700 --> 0:39:39.510) and details that “the message reaches researchers in a much more effective way, if it is carried not only by the librarian, but also by another researcher who has already been informed” (K1, 0:20:32.410 --> 0:20:58.460). K4 closes the interview citing from Lai Ma paper:

four actions to fight the platformisation of scholarly information: (1) Educate researchers about commercial publishers and APCs; (2) Allocate library budget to support scholar-led and library publishing; (3) Engage in the development of public research infrastructures and copyright reform; and (4) Advocate for research assessment reforms (Ma, 2023).

Librarians should engage themselves in the four actions for the benefit of the “knowledge production ecosystem” in Ma words, and “in their best interest” (K4, p.3).

Holistic approach and Alliances

Talking about the role of the librarians, the theme of holding a holistic approach and the importance of being part of networks is highlighted by K2:

I believe that they have a key role, that the skills of librarians are fundamental to be able to read what is happening, that is, if you are a librarian you read, how to say, what has happened in the field of scientific communication, even these merges, these purchases made, precisely, what do I know from Elsevier that buys the social research network, from Springer buying Research Square, from Elsevier managing SciVal, etc... So if you're a librarian, in my opinion, you have, let's say, you're on a higher step, let's say, you have an advantage in reading what happens within science communication, always, in fact, assuming you want to see it (K2, 0:13:45.670 --> 0:14:20.550)

In open science working groups within the Alliances whom K2's institution belongs to

directors of library systems have this issue on their hands, how to say, not only from an economic point of view, but also from an ethical point of view, from a technological point of view, from the point of view of development, from the point of view of evaluation. Let's say with an all-round vision, that this is perhaps what we lack a little. But of course, in my opinion they should play a fundamental role. In

short, a fundamental role in reading and in the possibility of reading and facilitating the reading of these phenomena (K2, 0:13:45.670 --> 0:14:20.550).

To summarize, it is underlined the holistic approach and the privileged point of view of librarians, and the importance of sharing and collaboration among communities.

Chapter summary

This chapter reports outcomes from data gathered through the research process, those from databases and those from interviews. From quantitative data analysis comes an overview on all types of open access and hybrid open access publication rates. Next, two datasets regarding some Italian data about TAs are presented. Qualitative data gathered through interviews are discussed by emerging themes: monitoring, researchers' satisfaction and awareness, sustainability, inequality, research assessment, diamond OA and green OA, national plans on open science, copyright and ethics. The chapter ends with the themes about the librarians' role like digital environment, awareness, and advocacy.

6 Conclusions

In this section the outcomes are linked with the research questions and the research aims and objectives. The research questions of the research were:

RQ1: How do publication trends compare before and after transformative agreements were implemented in Italy?

RQ2: Regarding the Italian context, what is the theoretical framework of scientific communication in the digital environment and about open access, also considering the introduction of transformative agreements?

RQ3: What is the role of academic libraries and librarians in the context outlined?

The research project objectives were:

- To observe the number of OA articles published by authors affiliated with Italian institutions before and after the adoption of several transformative agreements in Italy and the rating of their OA articles on the total published and indexed in the citation databases Web of Science, Scopus, Dimensions, and OpenAlex.
- To understand the theoretical framework of scientific communication in the digital environment and about open access in Italy, also considering the introduction of transformative agreements.
- To understand the role of academic libraries and librarians in the context outlined.

6.1 OA articles by authors affiliated with Italian institutions

RQ1 was “How do publication trends compare before and after transformative agreements were implemented in Italy”?

In order to *observe the number of OA articles published by authors affiliated with Italian institutions before and after the adoption of several transformative agreements in Italy*, data was collected from the OpenAlex, Scopus, and Web of Science databases. The rating of their OA articles on the total published and indexed in these citation databases was also calculated. Some limitations in data collection were considered, i.e.: the coverage of each database, the possible presence of duplicates, the fact that the “open access” attribute cumulatively also includes “bronze open access” articles, the fact that “hybrid open access” indiscriminately contains both articles published in open access through transformative agreements and those out of them, just as the gold open access includes both diamond and APC paid journals and finally, the corresponding author's data cannot be directly queried from the search web interface, neither simple nor advanced. In any case, in the period observed, i.e., with the year of publication 2018-2022, for authors affiliated with Italian institutions, it can be stated:

the percentage of “Open access all type” publications on the total number of items published stood at between 45% and 51% of indexed publications in 2018, while 2022 it increased and stood at between 60% and 69% in 2022;

over the same period, the hybrid OA went from 4.20% to 6.40% in 2018 to 11.04% to 13.67% in 2022;

on the other hand, the percentage of OA, all without distinction of affiliation, depending on the database considered, for 2018 publications is around 30%, 35%, 39%, and up to 49%, while for 2022, it is between 47% and over 60%;

the percentage of hybrid OA without distinction of affiliation, depending on the database considered, for 2018 publications is 3.18% and up to 5.53%, while in 2022, it is up to 6.56% and up to 13.32%;

Therefore, the increase of OA share is observed from the data; the values of authors affiliated with Italian institutions are similar in trend to those without distinction of affiliation.

The percentages vary greatly depending on the database observed and the perimeter of the database, given that the attribution of the OA information comes from the same source, i.e., Unpaywall. The observed data give a trend, a relatively nuanced picture of the situation.

Two attempts were made to select data regarding open-access articles related to the transformative agreements. The dataset from Scopus included 9932 hybrid open-access articles with the publication year 2018-2022, both through transformative agreements and

out of them, by corresponding authors affiliated with Italian institutions. The number of OA hybrid articles in 2022 increased by around 42% over 2018.

Observing data by publishers, during the years, the number of articles published through TAs increased at the expense of other publishers without TA concluded.

The dataset from Web of Science included 10614 articles, with the publication year 2020-2022 reporting the funding note that the OA publication is “under the CRUI-CARE agreement.” 2020 is the year when the first TA started in Italy. After normalizing the institution name for the record, a distribution through consortium members was done, highlighting institutions with more than 100 articles in the timespan.

Market Watch by ESAC estimates that there are 26070 articles publishable OA through Italian TAs in the whole period 2020-2022. We could not verify the gap through other sources. We could suppose an overestimation of ESAC, or that ESAC data contains OA gold articles not included in the data set extracted, or that, for some reason about quality, completeness or updating data, in Scopus database not all articles published OA hybrid are correctly assigned to OA hybrid attribute, or some of them result now with OA gold attribute, because in the meanwhile the journal flipped to full open access. Establish the most realistic number of OA articles in the period 2018-2022 could be part of future research, hopefully helped and strengthened by the release of data held by CRUI-CARE about OA publications through TAs. Observing the limitations and considering the relevance assumed, databases could improve the quality of data about the corresponding author to facilitate monitoring. The resulting picture from data extracted is rather grainy.

The qualitative data also strongly suggested the necessity of monitoring. To represent the situation, observations on more targeted data would be appropriate, and a more precise representation would support future decisions. To date, the data available are fragmented. Interviewees referred to some documents released in 2023 by single or grouped Italian institutions with the aim of facilitating gathering data on open science and APC expenditure from single Italian institutions. Considering the strong need of public data at a national level it is hoped that the most part of Italian universities and research institutions can contribute gathering data. An effort on more clearly managing and gathering data about the APC expenditure is also required to technicians, administrative personnel and librarians through their institutional accounting systems. However, like every other experimental application, monitoring and verification of data are needed. Knowing more about OA publications under

the TAs, and their distribution among institutions member of the consortium, could contribute to the evaluation of their impact and possible inequalities and sustainability issues.

6.2 Open access in Italy at the time of TAs

RQ2 was “regarding the Italian context, what is the theoretical framework of scientific communication in the digital environment and about open access, also considering the introduction of transformative agreements”?

To understand the theoretical framework of scientific communication in the digital environment and about open access in Italy, also considering the introduction of transformative agreements, monitoring is a key point. It should cover data on the money invested in the payment of APCs both through transformative agreements and out of them, hopefully at the national level, since negotiations for transformative agreements have taken place at that level, and they are mainly financed with public funds at the national level. The aim should be, at least, to understand whether the appreciation of transformative agreements for their offering a short-term solution by coping requests for open access publication of research funding calls with those for publication in core journals, useful for individual and institutional evaluation, is sustainable over time, considering the increases in expenditure already observed. To date, it is possible to observe at the national consortium level the increase in the average expenditure, including VAT, of pre- and post-transformation agreements for some publishers (value varies from 12.18% to 39.48%).

More detail in spending data would increase awareness and allow for informed decisions. Non-disclosure clauses should not be applied in any of the part within consortia members at any stage of the negotiation and maintenance of the agreements, given that institutions share the responsibility of negotiating and at the end sign them up. Sharing as possible throughout the academic community could raise institutions' awareness so they could participate in supporting the work of national negotiating teams. Such agreements should be negotiated within a national open science policy framework with shared and funded objectives. National and single institutional plans should include specific objectives supporting the development of *diamond* and *green* open access.

Inequality is a theme that emerged at different levels. The current TAs seem to reinforce the inequities between richer and lower-income countries, research groups of the same discipline and between different disciplines, early-stage career researchers and senior researchers, and researchers from the same institution. They can also create inequities in the distribution of costs among the members of the same consortium.

The crucial point seems to be the research assessment, both institutional and individual, guided by quantitative criteria and closely linked to the prestige of core journals. COARA's ten commitments, signed by the National Research Evaluation Agency, should lead to a profound and long-awaited reform. Until then, even transformative agreements do not seem to make a dent in the status quo.

Some interviewees underlined researchers' satisfaction which seems to go with the lack of awareness about the context. The satisfaction of researchers is related to solving the practical problem to cope with meeting the requirement of publishing open access, which is included in several research funding programs and publishing in core journals to gain prestige for future funding and personal career advancement, despite eventual price increases, perceived acceptable at the moment.

The majority of researchers seem to lack awareness about the market's inelasticity, the oligopoly, the expenditure for APCs, the costs of subscriptions and transformative agreements, and the issues related to them. The strong link with the current evaluation system, characterized by the heavy use of quantitative mechanisms and criteria, also determines that APCs' growth is associated with the prestige of journals, perpetuating the distortions of the “serial crisis.”

Discussion on ethical aspects seems to be one of the main merits of transformative agreements, bringing to the fore the debate on science communication and the entire research ecosystem. Becoming aware of the complexity of balancing the research ecosystem is an ethical issue that concerns all stakeholders.

6.3 The role of academic librarians

RQ3 was “what is the role of academic libraries and librarians in the context outlined”?

In order to *understand the role of academic libraries and librarians in the context outlined*, it can be stated that librarians seem to play a crucial role as their skills and competencies adapt to the digital environment and follow its evolution. Instead of this, they could become quite useless in future scenarios if they do not update their competencies and become more engaged, supporting the whole research cycle in the research ecosystem.

Librarians have to cope with transformative agreements (or they should look for alternatives?) and the application of their possible limitations; some of them are about journals, eligible or not, that create a jigsaw, which is also discouraging for researchers and represent hidden costs, because additional work is required to manage different models and peculiar limitations of every TA negotiated.

Librarians, especially at the beginning, appeared not fully aware of the transformative agreements, particularly about their weaknesses. Instead, they can play a critical role in negotiations to address more favourable conditions than the current one. As underlined earlier, the negotiations would be facilitated by data monitoring, information sharing through the community, and a financed national policy on open science with specific objectives. Furthermore, in a national shared perspective, a direction on national policy could emerge, deciding whether and how open access on APC-payment model, through transformative agreements or not, is a road to run, “at any cost”.

Underlined the lack of awareness by some researchers, librarians can play a role in advocacy on the current scholarly communication markets. They can support, also allocating money for, scholar-led and library publishing (the diamond open access), and give information and help authors manage their publication rights, for instance through Creative Commons licenses.

They should also engage themselves in developing public research infrastructures and reforming the copyright and research assessment rules. Holding a holistic approach, a favourable point of view by the since long knowing market conditions, products, publications, and copyright instances, and facilitated by their position in putting together different competencies to serve their communities, they could make a difference in

increasing the awareness of researchers. Some interviewees highlighted that education and training on open access and open science practices are better accepted when carried out by peers, from early adopter researchers to other researchers.

Librarians should exploit the interaction between academic or professional communities and alliances between institutions to share information and reflections, towards the common strategic objectives of developing public research infrastructures and reforming the rules on copyright and research assessment for the benefit of the research ecosystem and ultimately of the entire society.

In conclusion, the research project aimed to contribute to understanding the impact of transformative agreements on scientific communication and to evaluate their opportunities and critical issues, mainly focusing on Italy. Developing the research process emerged the lack of data in Italy stable and publicly available, about expenditure on TAs and more in general on APCs and about publication although some recent initiatives have been started.

Lack of data is quite a non-sense regarding open science practices, and obstacles a clearer comprehension of the phenomenon and its evolution in the national and international context. The fragmentation of the data, particularly in Italy, also reflects the composite framework that characterizes the country in so many other aspects. Nonetheless, every possible effort by the various members of the academic community is due and necessary with a view to correcting possible distortions in the scientific research ecosystem, for the benefit of the academic community itself which is responsible for carrying out the scientific research and of the entire society. Further research on open science principles and practices, considering other changes and new presences on stage, like artificial intelligence, should facilitate the awareness and the reflection of actors and decision makers in the research ecosystem. Librarians, with continuously updated competencies in managing and preserving data in the digital environment, joined with their traditional attitude and professional aim of serving their communities and granting access to information to everyone who needs it, are ready on stage.

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Appendices

Appendix I: Invitation e-mail

Da: Valentina Gamboni <valentina.gamboni1@studenti.unipg.it>

Inviato: venerdì 1 settembre 2023 15:49

A: xxxxxxxxxxxx

Cc: Valentina Gamboni <valentina.gamboni@unipg.it>

Oggetto: Richiesta di disponibilità per intervista

Gentile xxxxxxxxxxxx,

sono Valentina Gamboni, bibliotecaria all'Università degli studi di Perugia e attualmente dottoranda in Etica della comunicazione, ricerca scientifica e innovazione tecnologica. Il mio progetto di ricerca riguarda la comunicazione scientifica ad accesso aperto, e in particolare l'impatto dei cosiddetti "contratti trasformativi" e il ruolo dei bibliotecari.

Ho letto e seguito diversi suoi interventi, le chiedo disponibilità per una intervista in qualità di "key informant", se le fosse possibile.

Mi farebbe molto piacere poter pianificare un meeting per incontrarci da remoto. Comprendendo che gli impegni sono molti, le anticipo in allegato le domande e se vorrà potrà in alternativa rispondere per mail con un testo o una registrazione audio, a sua convenienza.

La tesi è in lingua inglese e le domande sono in inglese, può rispondere in italiano se lo desidera.

La ringrazio fin da ora e resto a disposizione, in attesa di un suo cenno di riscontro.

I più cordiali saluti

Valentina Gamboni

Valentina Gamboni

PhD Student in Ethics of Communication, Scientific Research and Technology Innovation

Department of Philosophy, Social and Human Sciences, and Education

University of Perugia

Italy

I'm Valentina Gamboni, a librarian at the University of Perugia and a PhD student in Ethics of Communication, Scientific Research and Technological Innovation. My research project concerns open access science communication, particularly the impact of so-called "transformative agreements" and the role of librarians.

I have read and followed several of your speeches; I ask you to be available for an interview as a "key informant," if possible.

I would love to schedule a meeting to meet remotely. Understanding that there are many commitments, I anticipate the questions attached. Alternatively, you can reply by email with a text or an audio recording at your convenience. The thesis is in English, and the questions are in English; you can answer in Italian if you wish. Thank you in advance, and I remain at your disposal, waiting for your feedback.

Sincerely,

Valentina Gamboni

Appendix II: Information on data processing

Title: Transformative agreements in the scientific communication ecosystem: challenges and opportunities for open access and open science and the role of librarians

Research project by Valentina Gamboni

The research is conducted under the PhD course in Ethics of Communication, Scientific Research and Technology Innovation (XXXVI), Department of Philosophy, Social and Human Sciences, and Education, University of Perugia, Italy.

Supervisor is prof. Loris Lino Maria Nadotti.

The aim of the research is to contribute to understanding the impact of transformative agreements (TA) on the scientific communication and to evaluate their opportunities and critical issues, particularly focusing on Italy case. Key informants' interviews are part of the research project, it is understood that each interview is conducted solely for research and study purposes. Pseudonymisation measures are applied to prevent key informants from being recognised, to give more importance to words and concepts than whoever told them.

Oral interviews

Interviewees accepted by email that the interview would be video recorded by the Microsoft Teams function under the privacy policy of Microsoft (<https://privacy.microsoft.com/it-IT/privacystatement#mainnoticetoendusersmodule>) and according to the Università degli studi di Perugia Regulation on the processing of personal data implementing the GDPR, General Data Protection Regulation, i.e. Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016, and the Italian Legislative Decree 196/2003 (<https://www.unipg.it/files/statuto-regolamenti/regolamenti/reg-trattamento-dati-personali.pdf>). The personal data processed are the *recorded voice* and the *recorded image* of the interviewees.

- The video recording is temporarily stored only in the researcher's personal working area;
- The video recording will be deleted after the presentation and public discussion of the doctoral thesis;
- The transcription of each interview and the related translation in English is part of the doctoral thesis in the appendix;
- Parts of the interview not relevant to the topic are replaced by the following characters: "[...]";
- Personal names (people, institutions, publishers, ...) are replaced with the digits "xxxxxx" unless they are substantially essential to the meaning of the concept;
- Every interviewee receives a copy of the transcription of his/her interview for eventual personal review. The transcription is translated into English by the researcher supported by the translation function of Microsoft Word 365.

Any information relating to agreements not available to the public is omitted in the transcript.

Written interviews

- A copy of the document containing answers has been collected and added in appendix "as it is".

The interviewees are informed that the researcher expressed consent to the release of the doctoral thesis in open access by the University of Perugia, in the forms and times established by the university itself.

Appendix III: Interviews

Trascrizione dell'intervista a K1

[...] indica parti di conversazione non rilevanti rispetto al tema.

0:0:0.0 --> 0:0:6.60

[...]

0:0:47.10 --> 0:1:4.100

R

Ma sì, sì sì. Perfetto, benissimo anche per me. Allora, i *transformative agreements are with us, do they really increase access to research?* Veramente aumentano l'accesso alla ricerca? Qual è il loro impatto, *what's their impact?*

0:1:5.220 --> 0:1:39.310

K1

Eh, ma io penso che il ruolo degli accordi trasformativi sia ad oggi un po' controverso in generale, allora senza, senza impiegare troppo tempo, rifaccio un minimo di storia perché credo di averla, di averla vissuta insieme a molti altri. La prima volta che sentii parlare di questo, di questa idea fu da Ralph Schimmer che a quel tempo era direttore della Digital Library del Max Planck Institute.

0:1:56.750 --> 0:1:57.990

R

Ok.

0:1:39.630 --> 0:2:10.880

K1

E anche rappresentante SCOAP3, noi, cioè

Transcription of the interview with K1

[...] indicates conversation not relevant to the topic.

0 0 0.0 -- > 0 0 6.60

[...]

0:0:47.10 --> 0:1:4.100

R

But yes, yes yes, perfect, great for me too. So, *transformative agreements are with us, do they really increase access to research?* Do they really increase access to research? *What's their impact?*

0:1:5.220 --> 0:1:39.310

K1

Eh, but I think that the role of transformative agreements is a bit controversial in general, so without, without taking too much time, I will redo a minimum of history because I think I have it, that I have lived it together with many others. The first time I heard about this, this idea, it was from Ralph Schimmer who at that time was director of the Digital Library of the Max Planck Institute.

0:1:56.750 --> 0:1:57.990

R

Ok.

0:1:39.630 --> 0:2:10.880

K1

io, come XXXX abbiamo aderito sin dall'inizio, quindi dal 2007 alla progettazione del progetto SCOAP3, trainato dal CERN, e Ralph Schimmer era il referente nazionale per la Germania e fu di lui, diciamo, l'idea base che presentò e che era quella molto semplice del "there is enough money in the system", quindi lui dice, facciamo il conto di tutti gli articoli pubblicati al mondo e poi facciamo il conto di tutti gli abbonamenti pagati, se dividiamo quello che paghiamo per gli abbonamenti, per gli articoli pubblicati vediamo che l'APC, già a quel momento si cominciava a parlare di APC, cioè il costo, ha un valore enorme tipo 5 – 6000, 7.000 euro, che a quel tempo era un valore enorme. Quindi dice perché non trasferiamo, cioè perché non ci spostiamo sul mercato del pagare per pubblicare, perché "*there is enough money in the system*", comunque alla fine andremo a risparmiarci, perché noi in effetti stiamo pagando per gli abbonamenti molto di più di quello che pagheremmo per un APC ragionevole per articolo.

0:3:2.350 --> 0:3:31.500

K1

Parallelamente gli economisti, i colleghi economisti, fra cui in Italia, certamente qualcuno più informato, ad es. il professor Alberto Pozzolo, che è stato coordinatore del gruppo CARE della Crui fino a 2 - 3

And also a SCOAP3 representative, we, that is, me, as XXXX we have adhered from the beginning, so since 2007 to the design of the SCOAP3 project, led by CERN, and Ralph Schimmer was the national referent for Germany and it was of him, let's say, the basic idea that he presented and that was the very simple one of "there is enough money in the system", so he says, let's count all the articles published in the world and then let's count all the paid subscriptions, if we divide what we pay by the subscriptions, by the published articles we see that the APC, already at that time we were starting to talk about APC, that is, the cost, has a huge value like 5 – 6.000, 7.000 euros, which at that time was a huge value. So, he says why we don't transfer, that is, why we don't move to the pay-to-publish market, because "*there's enough money in the system*" anyway, we're going to save ourselves anyway, because we're paying a lot more for subscriptions than we would pay for a reasonable APC per article.

0:3:2.350 --> 0:3:31.500

K1

At the same time, economists, fellow economists, including in Italy, certainly someone more informed, e.g. Professor Alberto Pozzolo, who was coordinator of the CARE group of the CRUI until 2-3 years ago, we collaborate a lot and he is a

anni fa, collaboriamo un sacco ed è un amico, ha spiegato molto bene perché sarebbe stata forse un'opportunità passare al mercato delle APC. E questo è proprio il nocciolo, uno dei noccioli del problema. Per gli economisti il mercato dell'abbonamento è "io pubblico senza pagare". Poi però devo comprare le riviste, è un mercato estremamente rigido quindi, perché? Perché di fatto io regalo il mio prodotto all'editore e rimango senza il mio prodotto e poi sono costretto a comprare tutte le riviste perché, se devo fare una ricerca io non posso scegliere, compro questa compro o quell'altra, quindi è un mercato rigido in un certo senso, ogni singola pubblicazione è un monopolio. Perché l'editore ha in mano la mia pubblicazione, *conversely*, il mercato degli APC invece dovrebbe in teoria essere un mercato meno rigido, quindi più competitivo. Perché? Perché io prima di scegliere una rivista e quindi pagare per la pubblicazione, pubblicazione che poi resta open access, io posso scegliere, ho in mano il prodotto e quindi posso scegliere, questo è per gli economisti, dicevo, una cosa buona, perché dovremmo passare ad un mercato meno oligopolistico di quello degli abbonamenti. Questa proposta si concretizzò grazie al Max Planck Institute, nel progetto OA 2020, che quindi vide varie vicende ancora

friend, he explained very well why it would have been perhaps an opportunity to move to the APC market. And this is precisely the crux, one of the cruxes of the problem. For economists, the subscription market is "I publish without paying." But then I have to buy journals, it's an extremely rigid market so, why? Because in fact I give my product to the publisher and I am left without my product and then I am forced to buy all the journals because, if I have to do a search I can't choose, I buy this or that, so it's a rigid market in a way, every single publication is a monopoly.

Because the publisher has my publication in his hands, *conversely*, the APC market should be in theory a less rigid market, therefore more competitive. Why?

Because before I choose a journal and then I pay for the publication, a publication that then remains open access, I can choose, I have the product in my hands and therefore I can choose, this is for economists, I said, a good thing, because we should move to a less oligopolistic market than that of subscriptions.

This proposal materialized thanks to the Max Planck Institute, in the OA 2020 project, which therefore saw various events still in progress and from there these agreements were in fact born, in which I pay to publish... now

in corso e da lì sono di fatto nati questi contratti, in cui pago per pubblicare... adesso contratti trasformativi, è un nome utilizzato negli ultimi anni, che a me non piace per niente, forse l'ha creato Coalition S... non mi ricordo, questo è però il fatto, abbiamo visto che non trasformano quindi le riviste ibride che hanno aderito, questi contratti trasformativi di fatto rimangono però. Non importa, cioè io cambierei il nome, li chiamerei Publish and Read oppure pay for publish and [pay] for APC. La tappa successiva è stata nel 2018: Coalition S, questa è stata un'esperienza molto importante. Abbiamo aderito come unica istituzione italiana e diciamo che ci sono stati vari piccoli cambiamenti di rotta in Coalition S, cioè perché chiaramente è una collaborazione democratica, quindi ci sono varie voci, allora da una parte c'eravamo noi, i francesi, gli spagnoli. E molto spingevamo e spingiamo ancora verso la strada verde. Quindi gli archivi e il diritto di pubblicare la *accepted manuscript*, cioè l'ultima versione finale dell'articolo prima della pubblicazione, cioè con la revisione editoriale, però senza il logo nel numero di pagina, né il numero di volume della rivista. Quindi, d'altra parte, invece, c'era tutta la fascia nordeuropea che si allineava verso il progetto OA2020, quindi APC ad ogni costo.

transformative agreements, it's a name used in recent years, which I don't like at all, maybe it was created by Coalition S... I don't remember, but that's the fact, we've seen that they don't transform the hybrid journals that have joined, these transformative agreements actually remain. It doesn't matter, i.e. I would change the name, call them Publish and Read or pay for publish and [pay] for APC. The next stage was in 2018: Coalition S, this was a very important experience. We joined as the only Italian institution and let's say that there have been several small changes of course in Coalition S, that is, because clearly it is a democratic collaboration, so there are various voices, so on one side there were us, the French, the Spanish. And we were pushing a lot, and we are still pushing towards the green road. Hence the archives and the right to publish the *accepted manuscript*, i.e. the last final version of the article before publication, i.e. with editorial review, but without the logo on the page number, nor the volume number of the journal. So, on the other hand, there was the whole northern European belt that aligned itself towards the OA2020 project, so APC at any cost.

0:6:36.900 --> 0:7:6.950

K1

At the beginning Coalition S said no to

0:6:36.900 --> 0:7:6.950

K1

All'inizio Coalition S disse no all'ibrido, quindi la lotta era contro gli ibridi, andiamo verso il modello [pay for] APC. Poi ci fu una piccola correzione di rotta, spinta soprattutto da noi, dicendo no all'ibrido però sì a tutto il resto; quindi, sì al green, sì alle altre forme di Diamond, a quel tempo già se ne comincia a parlare, e sì anche agli APC, purché sia una vera trasformazione, quindi ci sia un vero trend di trasformazione alla rivista completamente aperta.

0:7:11.340 --> 0:7:40.690

K1

Allora adesso dove ci troviamo? Ci troviamo in uno scenario mondiale ma anche italiano, perché la CRUI soprattutto ha aderito già da tempo a questi contratti nazionali diciamo "publish and read", fra virgolette trasformativi, e cominciamo a vedere un po' l'andamento del trend di questi costi. Allora questi costi di fatto ancora non scendono, quindi probabilmente è troppo presto, non possiamo sapere se il mercato, si è veramente reso meno [ndr: più] competitivo grazie al passaggio al pagamento degli APC, però è cruciale, è proprio fondamentale, attivare e rendere operativo il monitoraggio di questi prezzi, di queste APC, per permetterci anche fra

hybrids, so the fight was against hybrids, let's go towards the [payment for] APC model. Then there was a small course correction, pushed above all by us, saying no to hybrid but yes to everything else; so, yes to green, yes to other forms of Diamond, at that time we were already starting to talk about it, and yes to APCs as well, as long as it is a real transformation, so there is a real trend of transformation to the completely open access journal.

0:7:11.340 --> 0:7:40.690

K1

So where are we now? We are in a global scenario but also in Italy, because the CRUI above all has already adhered to these national agreements for some time now, let's say "publish and read", transformative in quotation marks, and we are beginning to see a little the trend of these costs. So these costs are not yet going down, so it is probably too early, we cannot know if the market has really become less competitive thanks to the transition to the payment of APCs, but it is crucial, it is really fundamental, to activate and make operational the monitoring of these prices, of these APCs, to allow us even in a few years to really draw conclusions, That is, to understand, from an economic point of view, are we saving money? Are we at least paying the same or even paying more? This is a bit like the

qualche anno di tirare veramente le somme, cioè, capire, dal punto di vista economico, noi ci stiamo risparmiando? Stiamo almeno pagando uguale o addirittura paghiamo di più? Questa è un po' la filosofia, direi italiana, cioè della CRUI. Insomma, io parlo per l'XXXX che stiamo seguendo, quindi la massima priorità è e continua ad essere la strada verde, ai contratti trasformativi aderiamo, però, diamo estrema importanza al monitoraggio di questi APC. Oh beh, anche la CRUI sta facendo lo stesso, ci sono iniziative congiunte per procedere a una revisione dei sistemi contabili per rendere più facile questo monitoraggio, perché finora il monitoraggio non si è potuto fare in maniera semplice, perché queste voci di spesa erano distribuite in diversi capitoli di spesa. Invece adesso cercheremo di avere un unico capitolo, quindi si potrà fare il monitoraggio in maniera molto, molto più efficiente. Allora ho fatto una digressione enorme. La domanda iniziale era se [i contratti trasformativi] hanno contribuito rendere più semplice o no la distribuzione della conoscenza.

Beh, per i paesi sviluppati sì, nel senso che ai colleghi, io sono ricercatore, ai miei colleghi, i contratti trasformativi piacciono molto quando si tratta di contratti stipulati nazionalmente, a nessuno piace ovviamente usare i propri soldi di ricerca

philosophy, I would say Italian, that is, of the CRUI. In short, I speak on behalf of the XXXX that we are following, so the highest priority is and continues to be the green road, we adhere to transformative agreements, however, we give extreme importance to the monitoring of these APCs. Oh well, the CRUI is also doing the same, there are joint initiatives to proceed with a revision of the accounting systems to make this monitoring easier, because so far monitoring has not been able to be done in a simple way, because these items of expenditure were distributed in different expenditure chapters. But now we're going to try to have a single chapter, so we can do the monitoring in a much, much more efficient way. So, I made a huge digression. The initial question was whether [transformative agreements] helped to make the distribution of knowledge easier or not.

Well, for developed countries yes, in the sense that my colleagues, I am a researcher, my colleagues, really like transformative agreements when it comes to nationally stipulated agreements, none obviously likes to use their research money to pay for APCs, but this, but this is excluded, that is, no way it is said that the author has to pay with his own research money for APCs, no, They are always funded by money that comes, let's say,

per pagare gli APC, ma questo, ma questo è escluso, cioè in nessun modello si sta dicendo che l'autore deve pagare con i propri soldi di ricerca gli APC no, sono sempre fondi che vengono diciamo dalle biblioteche ridirezionati dagli abbonamenti. Sarebbe terribile andare in un modello in cui i costi degli APC fossero pagati dai fondi di ricerca, perché questo ucciderebbe i giovani che naturalmente hanno meno fondi di ricerca. Va bene, quindi questa è una cosa che stiamo cercando di sempre di chiarire; quindi, una funzione positiva io la vedo. Questa funzione nell'emisfero nord, questa funzione positiva, bisogna verificare che effettivamente sia accompagnata da un mercato più libero e quindi meno [oligopolistico] perché altrimenti è fallito, il sistema è fallito.

E ci sono moltissime comunità, anche in Italia, che si rifiutano di pagare per pubblicare, ad esempio, i matematici, gli informatici, per motivi anche etici, logici, rispettabilissimi; però il problema grave è l'emisfero sud, perché l'emisfero sud diciamo non ha, in generale, possibilità di pagare per pubblicare. Allora questo è un gravissimo problema, non per motivi etici o di concetto, ma utilitaristici, perché a noi, emisfero nord, conviene che l'emisfero sud continui a pubblicare comunque, perché la scienza non ha confini e quindi chiaramente la diversità, la *diversity*,

from libraries, redirected from subscriptions. It would be terrible to go into a model where the costs of APCs were paid for by research funds, because that would kill young people who naturally have less research funding. Okay, so that's something we're always trying to clarify; So, I see a positive function. This function in the northern hemisphere, this positive function, must be verified that it is actually accompanied by a freer and therefore less [oligopolistic] market, because otherwise it has failed, the system has failed. And there are many communities, even in Italy, that refuse to pay to publish, for example, mathematicians, computer scientists, for ethical, logical, very respectable reasons; But the serious problem is the southern hemisphere, because the southern hemisphere, let's say, does not have, in general, the possibility of paying to publish. So this is a very serious problem, not for ethical or conceptual reasons, but for utilitarian reasons, because for us, the northern hemisphere, it is convenient for the southern hemisphere to continue to publish anyway, because science has no boundaries and therefore clearly the diversity, *the diversity*, of the southern hemisphere is fundamental in infinite fields. We are not talking about medicine, biology, but in all fields like this; so, there's a very, very important reason why

dell'emisfero sud è fondamentale in infiniti campi. Non parliamo della medicina, della biologia, ma insomma in tutti i campi così; quindi, c'è un motivo molto molto importante per cui se l'emisfero sud decide che, se i trasformativi non sono sostenibili, si vada verso un altro modello. Quindi sono molti i “caveat”, secondo me bisogna essere molto cauti.

0:11:33.320 --> 0:11:36.130

R

Sì grazie, grazie veramente sono...

0:11:37.370 --> 0:11:38.40

K1

E lo so, io spero.

0:11:44.550 --> 0:11:45.460

K1

Eh sì.

0:11:37.980 --> 0:11:48.370

R

...sono contenta, ecco di sentire questo perché è un ecosistema, diciamo da salvaguardare, no? In un certo senso, quindi, ehm, deve funzionare.

0:11:46.200 --> 0:12:10.50

K1

È un sistema complesso, deve funzionare, l'altra cosa che voglio dire subito, che tu sai sicuramente, è che tutto quanto questo circolo vizioso è incardinato sulla *research evaluation*, perché finché la *research evaluation* sarà basata sull'Impact Factor di una rivista e sul prestigio, cosiddetto,

if the Southern Hemisphere decides that if transformative agreements aren't sustainable, they move towards another model. So, there are a lot of caveats, in my opinion you must be very careful.

0:11:33.320 --> 0:11:36.130

R

Yes, thank you, thank you very much I am...

0:11:37.370 --> 0:11:38.40

K1

And I know, I hope so.

0:11:44.550 --> 0:11:45.460

K1

Oh, yes.

0:11:37.980 --> 0:11:48.370

R

... I'm happy to hear this because it's an ecosystem, let's say to be safeguarded, right? So, in a way, uhm, it has to work.

0:11:46.200 --> 0:12:10.50

K1

It's a complex system, it has to work, the other thing I want to say right away, which you know for sure, is that all this vicious circle is hinged on research evaluation, *because as long as research evaluation is based on the Impact Factor of a journal and on the so-called perceived prestige of the container and not of the content that is the article, clearly we will never get out of this, so let's make it clear right away that research assessment is the crucial thing.*

percepito del contenitore e non del contenuto che è l'articolo, chiaramente non ne usciremo mai, quindi mettiamo subito in chiaro che il *research assessment* è la cosa cruciale.

0:12:21.820 --> 0:12:29.110

R

Esatto, è vero, è il convitato di pietra, lo chiamo io nelle conversazioni.

0:12:30.680 --> 0:12:50.970

R

Va bene ... la seconda domanda, grossomodo credo che l'abbia già affrontata. Cosa succederà? Ci sono fattori positivi e negativi, debolezze e forze dei contratti trasformativi, come possono essere giusti, diciamo, e sostenibili, *how TAs can be fair and sustainable?*

0:12:54.380 --> 0:13:22.280

K1

Per loro natura i contratti trasformativi hanno caratteristiche non sempre *fair* e non sempre sostenibili, la *fairness* la vedo nell'implementazione di alcune azioni volte a salvaguardare le categorie, come dire, a rischio, quindi nell'emisfero Nord i giovani sicuramente, le piccole università, nell'emisfero sud, tutto l'emisfero sud; adesso ci sono spesso editori che applicano dei palliativi, che sono delle *waivers*, cioè non fanno pagare gli APC, ad esempio, ad università del Sud. Però insomma, sono tutti abbastanza, tutti abbastanza dei

0:12:21.820 --> 0:12:29.110

R

That's right, it's true, he's the guest of stone, I call him in conversations.

0:12:30.680 --> 0:12:50.970

R

Okay ... The second question, roughly speaking, I think you have already addressed. What's next? There are positive and negative factors, weaknesses, and strengths of transformative agreements, how can they be fair, shall we say, and sustainable, *how can TA be fair and sustainable?*

0:12:54.380 --> 0:13:22.280

K1

By their nature, transformative agreements have characteristics that are not always *fair* and not always sustainable, I see *fairness* in the implementation of some actions aimed at safeguarding the categories, how to say, at risk, so in the northern hemisphere young people certainly, small universities, in the southern hemisphere, the whole southern hemisphere; now there are often publishers who apply palliatives, which are *waivers*, i.e. they do not charge APCs, for example, to universities in the South. But in short, they are all enough, all quite palliatives. I think it's essential not to tie yourself to any model and especially not to tie yourself to the payment of [APCs], so to keep all the

palliativi.

Io penso che sia essenziale non legarsi a nessun modello e specialmente non legarsi al pagamento degli [APC], quindi tenere aperte tutte le altre strade: quindi il Green, il Diamond, anche altri modelli molto importanti tipo *Subscribe to open* che è un tipo di modello collaborativo basato sull'abbonamento che dice essenzialmente: tu paghi l'abbonamento, eh? Se il numero di abbonamenti pagati per un certo anno non scende sotto una soglia, che è ragionevolmente fissata dall'editore abbastanza vicina, diciamo, al livello standard, che assicura la sopravvivenza della rivista e la fattibilità economica della rivista, allora, gli articoli dell'anno precedente sono lasciati ... no, gli articoli dell'anno stesso sono lasciati in open access, sono open. Sì, e questo è un modello che è abbracciato appunto da esempio da dalle comunità di matematici, la European Mathematical Society pubblica con questo modello. Insomma, tanto per dire, ci sono altri modelli; quindi, non

0:15:11.560 --> 0:15:26.550

R

Eh no, no, era questa qua ... come possono essere "*fair and sustainable*".

other avenues open: so the Green, the Diamond, also other very important models like *Subscribe to open* which is a type of collaborative model based on the subscription that essentially says: you pay the subscription, eh? If the number of paid subscriptions for a certain year does not fall below a threshold, which is reasonably set by the publisher close enough, say, to the standard level, which ensures the survival of the journal and the economic viability of the journal, then, the previous year's articles are left ... No, the articles of the same year are left in open access, they are open. Yes, and this is a model that is embraced as an example by the mathematical community, the European Mathematical Society publishes with this model. In short, just to say, there are other models; Therefore, you don't have to tie yourself to a model of *transformative agreements*. Anyway, these are, this is a type of action. And then the second part of the question was...

0:15:11.560 --> 0:15:26.550

R

Oh no, no, it was this one ... how they can be "*fair and sustainable*". Basically, we said that they have potential, they have positive sides and negative weaknesses, but we have, I think, already talked about them enough.

0:15:25.320 --> 0:15:48.450

Fondamentalmente avevamo detto che hanno potenzialità, hanno lati positivi e aspetti di debolezza, negativi, ma ne abbiamo, penso parlato già a sufficienza.
0:15:25.320 --> 0:15:48.450

K1

Sì, l'aspetto di debolezza, cioè, non sono "sustainable" se si dimostra dopo 4, 5, 6 anni che il mercato non si apre. Se il mercato non si apre, tutti editori hanno alzato i loro APC, nessun nuovo editore è entrato ad abbassare gli APC, quindi non funziona. Quindi questo è il limite assoluto, la sostenibilità.

0:15:49.90 --> 0:15:53.640

R

E nel caso, dobbiamo immaginare nuovi modelli?

0:15:52.800 --> 0:16:19.160

K1

Ci stiamo pensando, in Coalition S, che fortunatamente è fatto di persone che ragionano, senza troppi pregiudizi. Anche l'Europa del Nord si è resa conto ... Anche i componenti che all'inizio spingevano moltissimo esclusivamente per il modello APC, si sono resi conto che potrebbe non funzionare quindi tutti quanti insieme, compatti come sempre, stiamo continuando a sostenere il Green, quindi grande supporto per reti di archivi aperti, interoperabili. Ci sono varie azioni, sulle quali non so molto, di modifiche della

K1

Yes, the weakness aspect, that is, they are not "sustainable" if you prove after 4, 5, 6 years that the market does not open. If the market doesn't open up, all publishers have raised their APCs, no new publishers have come into lower APCs, so it doesn't work. So that's the absolute limit, sustainability.

0:15:49.90 --> 0:15:53.640

R

And if so, do we have to imagine new models?

0:15:52.800 --> 0:16:19.160

K1

We're thinking about it, in Coalition S, which fortunately is made up of people who reason, without too many prejudices. Northern Europe has also realized ... Even the members that at the beginning were pushing a lot exclusively for the APC model, have realized that it may not work so all of us together, compact as always, we are continuing to support Green, so great support for open, interoperable archive networks. There are various actions, on which I don't know much, of changes in the legislation, because one of the fundamental points to make the results of the research available is [the deposit] with a zero embargo, which in Italy cannot be done, right? There is the copyright law which says two years, in other countries the legislation is much more permissive, it

legislazione, perché uno dei punti fondamentali per rendere disponibile i risultati della ricerca è [depositare] con embargo zero, cosa che in Italia non si può fare, no? C'è la legge sul diritto d'autore che dice due anni, in altri paesi la legislazione è molto più permissiva, dice un anno, addirittura sei mesi; quindi, l'obiettivo sarebbe quello di andare a embargo zero e di farlo in maniera comune con tutta l'Europa e quello sarebbe una forma molto, molto importante.

0:17:11.560 --> 0:17:12.820

R

Ok.

0:17:9.620 --> 0:17:39.730

K1

E quindi questo è la [via] green, la spinta per il Green e poi, anche in Coalition S, stiamo muovendo verso l'ipotesi del *Diamond*, quindi il *Diamond* è una forma di ritorno alle University Press: mantenere il circuito della revisione della *peer review*, della revisione paritaria, all'interno delle istituzioni accademiche, senza rivolgersi necessariamente a editori commerciali oppure rivolgendosi a editori commerciali che però obbediscano a regole ben precise, anche economiche, dettate e sotto il controllo delle università e degli istituti di ricerca. E questo in un certo senso è tornare verso le origini, perché, diciamo la teoria scientifica nasce nel

says one year, even six months; therefore, the goal would be to go to a zero embargo and to do it in a common way with the whole of Europe and that would be a very, very important form.

0:17:11.560 --> 0:17:12.820

R

Ok.

0:17:9.620 --> 0:17:39.730

K1

And so this is the green [way], the push for Green and then, also in Coalition S, we are moving towards the Diamond hypothesis, so the Diamond is a form of return to the University Press: to maintain the circuit of peer review, within the academic institutions, without necessarily turning to commercial publishers or turning to commercial publishers who however obey very precise rules, including economic ones, dictated and under the control of universities and research institutes. And that's kind of going back to basics, because let's say scientific theory was born in the UK, let's say with Newton, the Royal Society... Take back this mechanism a little.

0:18:16.260 --> 0:18:48.330

R

Right, thanks! And now a little more focus in Italy, if possible: how can they, that is, how are the institutions, research institutions, authors and even librarians

Regno Unito, diciamo con Newton, la Royal Society ... Riprendersi un po' in mano questo meccanismo.

0:18:16.260 --> 0:18:48.330

R

Giusto, grazie! E adesso un po' più di focus in Italia, se possibile: come possono, cioè, come stanno, diciamo affrontando, ecco, il cambiamento gli enti, le istituzioni di ricerca, gli autori e anche i bibliotecari. Dal tuo punto di vista di vista, rileggo [la domanda] in inglese: *in Italy, how are research bodies, authors and librarians facing changes in scholarly communication brought by TAs*, se effettivamente stanno modificando proprio il processo della comunicazione della ricerca.

0:18:51.930 --> 0:19:5.0

K1

No, allora in Italia parliamo. Parliamo subito delle biblioteche ... in Italia allora l'Italia in generale segue i trend europei, e i bibliotecari sono sulla prima linea, sono sempre stati sulla prima linea anche in Italia; quindi, il movimento open access ha visto un aiuto enorme, una spinta enorme da parte dei bibliotecari. I maligni possono dire perché erano loro che pagavano gli abbonamenti e non riuscivano più a pagarli. C'era la curva che saliva, non si fermava mai. Però non è solo questo, non è solo questo, è che nel mondo bibliotecario c'è una grandissima sensibilità ...

facing, let's say, the change. From your point of view, I reread [the question] in English: *in Italy, how are research bodies, authors and librarians facing changes in scholarly communication brought by TAs*, if indeed they are changing the process of research communication.

0:18:51.930 --> 0:19:5.0

K1

No, then in Italy let's talk. Let's talk about librarians right away... in Italy, then, Italy in general follows European trends, and librarians are on the front line, they have always been on the front line in Italy as well; So, the Open access movement has seen tremendous help, a huge push from librarians. The evil ones can tell because they were the ones who paid for the subscriptions and could no longer pay them. There was the curve that went up, it never stopped. But it's not just this, it's not just that, it's that in the library world there is a great sensitivity ...

0:19:37.40 --> 0:19:37.970

R

... to the access ...

0:19:36.800 --> 0:20:0.970

K1

... To these problems, to access, yes, to access to information, and therefore they are at the forefront, absolutely. The same phenomenon has also occurred for transformative agreements, so at the

0:19:37.40 --> 0:19:37.970

R

... all'accesso ...

0:19:36.800 --> 0:20:0.970

K1

... verso questi problemi, all'accesso, sì, all'accesso all'informazione e quindi sono in prima linea, assolutamente. Anche per i contratti trasformativi si è verificato lo stesso fenomeno, quindi all'inizio c'è stato un grande sostegno, una grande spinta e adesso c'è un po' più di realismo e mi sembra che in tutte le biblioteche sì, ci si stia rendendo conto che in effetti, però, questi APC non calano, non scendono, quindi in tutte le biblioteche c'è la percezione chiara che sia fondamentale procedere al *monitoring* accurato di questi costi. Tra l'altro ci sono dei progetti che ti danno già l'infrastruttura ... C'è un progetto molto molto famoso, si chiama OPEN APC, ti fornisce tutta l'infrastruttura e ogni biblioteca deve inserire i propri dati, però poi dopo tutta l'analisi è fornita centralmente.

0:20:32.410 --> 0:20:58.460

K1

E già molte biblioteche italiane partecipano; negli EPR, gli enti pubblici di ricerca, hanno aderito al CNR sicuramente, poi stiamo comunque cercando di far aderire maggior numero possibile di enti e, come dicevo questa azione di

beginning there was a great deal of support, a great push and now there is a little more realism and it seems to me that in all libraries yes, we are realizing that in fact, however, these APCs are not going down, they are not going down, so in all libraries there is a clear perception that it is essential to proceed with *monitoring* accurately these costs. By the way, there are projects that already give you the infrastructure ... There's a very, very famous project, it's called OPEN APC, it provides you with all the infrastructure and each library has to enter its own data, but then after all the analysis is provided centrally.

0:20:32.410 --> 0:20:58.460

K1

And already many Italian libraries are participating; in the EPRs, the public research institutions, the CNR certainly joined, then we are still trying to get as many institutions as possible to join and, as I said, this action of rationalization of the accounting system to make it easier to monitor the expenses of the APCs will certainly help this process. From the colleague's point of view, it is another matter, in general the researcher does not want, let's say that first he must be informed because, if he is not informed, he does not want to change habits, that is, he does not realize ... Ah, but as before I

razionalizzazione del sistema contabile per rendere più facile monitorare delle spese degli APC sicuramente aiuterà questo processo. Dal punto di vista del collega è un altro discorso, in generale il ricercatore non vuole, diciamo che prima deve essere informato perché, se non viene informato, non vuole cambiare le abitudini, cioè non si rende conto ... Ah, ma come prima non pagavo, adesso devo pagare o pagare io i miei fondi ... come funziona? ... Non vuole essere distratto. E però, una volta che il messaggio viene, gli viene portato. Ed è meglio che venga portato da un altro ricercatore, quindi questo è fondamentale. Lo sviluppo e la formazione di ricercatori che formano sull'accesso aperto sulla scienza, aperta in generale, perché adesso qua parliamo di accesso aperto, però scienza aperta naturalmente ha cinque direzioni, come il nostro Piano Nazionale per la Scienza Aperta dice, non lo apriamo, però potremmo aprire tutto il discorso dei dati e degli open data, data steward, anche su questo discorso, queste figure, chi sono, chi saranno? E quindi io penso che il messaggio arrivi in maniera molto più efficace presso i ricercatori, se viene portato, oltre che dal bibliotecario, anche da un altro ricercatore che si è già informato.

E questo è quello che nei gruppi di lavoro a cui partecipo cerchiamo proprio di fare, i

didn't pay, now I have to pay or pay with my own funds ... How does that work? ... He doesn't want to be distracted. And yet, once the message is brought to him, it is brought to him. And it's better to be brought by another researcher, so that's critical. The development and training of researchers who train on open access on science, open in general, because now here we are talking about open access, but open science of course has five directions, as our National Plan for Open science says, we do not open it, but we could open up the whole discourse of data and open data, data stewards ... Also in this discourse, these figures, who are they, who will they be? And so, I think that the message reaches researchers in a much more effective way, if it is carried not only by the librarian, but also by another researcher who has already been informed. And this is what we try to do in the working groups in which I participate, the working groups are all made up of researchers with various levels of experience and sensitivity, and in fact it is an activity that we do for pure ethical reasons, because it is not part of our research activity.

0:23:5.200 --> 0:23:8.30

R

It will not be counted for evaluations...

0:23:9.140 --> 0:23:32.220

gruppi di lavoro sono formati tutti da ricercatori con vari livelli di esperienza e sensibilità, e di fatto è un'attività che facciamo per puri motivi etici, perché non è che fa parte della nostra attività di ricerca.
0:23:5.200 --> 0:23:8.30

R

Non sarà annoverata per le valutazioni...
0:23:9.140 --> 0:23:32.220

K1

Eh no, diciamo di no, non viene, non viene annoverata, sebbene adesso negli enti di ricerca ci sia la terza missione, però questa attività di scienza aperta, insomma, è un po' qui e un po' là. Quindi, ehm ... diciamo che chi lo fa, ci sono anche altre attività; quindi, chi lo fa non lo fa per, diciamo, per la carriera. Però questo è importante, istituzionalizzare, cioè, è importante che si diano risorse, perché altrimenti il numero di persone, di ricercatori che si occupano di scienza aperta non cresce, dobbiamo cercare di coinvolgere anche e soprattutto i più giovani, per cui qual è il problema? Noi gruppi di lavoro siamo tutti un po' vecchierelli ... perché? Perché quello che dovevamo fare l'abbiamo fatto, però al giovane se dici: ora spendi, non so, 2 - 3 ore a settimana per la scienza aperta, le deve togliere dalla sua attività di ricerca, è una cosa che è molto difficile da fare oggettivamente, e non consiglierei a nessun giovane di farlo, quindi è importante che le

K1

Oh no, let's say no, it doesn't come, it's not counted, although now in research institutions there is the "Third mission", but this open science activity, in short, is a little here and a little there. So, uhm... Let's say that those who do it, there are also other activities; So, those who do it don't do it for, let's say, their career. But this is important, institutionalizing, that is, it is important that resources are given, because otherwise the number of people, of researchers who deal with open science does not grow, we must try to involve also and above all the youngest, so what is the problem? We working groups are all a bit old-fashioned ... why? Because we did what we had to do, but if you say now you spend, I don't know, 2 - 3 hours a week on open science, he has to take it out of his research activity, it's something that is very difficult to do objectively, and I wouldn't advise any young person to do it, so it's important that the institutions, Universities and research institutions should also recognize this type of work.
0:24:16.810 --> 0:24:43.210

R

Clear, thank you, you are absolutely right, now in my small way, in short, I identify myself, and even in the younger colleagues, in short, it is necessary that they are trained, that we talk about it and it

istituzioni, università, enti di ricerca riconoscano anche questo tipo di lavoro.

0:24:16.810 --> 0:24:43.210

R

Chiaro, grazie, ha perfettamente ragione, adesso nel mio piccolo, insomma, mi immedesimo, e anche nei colleghi più giovani, insomma, si è necessario che siano formati, che se ne parli ed è giusto che prendano consapevolezza innanzitutto dei propri diritti in qualità di autori, di cosa è importante. Poi però, giustamente dici, il tempo è quello, comunque io la carriera la devo costruire; quindi, ogni momento speso diciamo per una cosa che poi non mi rende, è un costo che devo affrontare nel percorso.

0:24:51.530 --> 0:25:22.180

K1

Posso aggiungere che comunque sulle problematiche e tematiche della scienza aperta c'è una grandissima sensibilità delle associazioni di giovani, perché abbiamo avuto moltissimi contatti con l'associazione dottorandi ad esempio, ma anche con altre associazioni europee, c'è una grandissima sensibilità, c'è un grandissimo interesse e molta preoccupazione, ovviamente, però, insomma, il nostro compito, è quello di non solo tranquillizzare, ma diciamo fornire gli strumenti per rendere questa transizione *sustainable* dal punto di vista di un *early stage researcher*, diciamo.

is right that they become aware first of all of their rights as authors, of what is important. But then, you rightly say, that is the time, in any case I have to build a career; So, every moment spent, let's say, on something that doesn't pay me, is a cost that I have to face along the way.

0:24:51.530 --> 0:25:22.180

K1

I can add that in any case on the problems and issues of open science there is a great sensitivity of the associations of young people, because we have had a lot of contacts with the doctoral student association for example, but also with other European associations, there is a great sensitivity, there is a great interest and a lot of concern, obviously, but, in short, our task, is to not only reassure, but let's say provide the tools to make this transition *sustainable* from the point of view of an *early stage researcher*, let's say.

0:25:32.800 --> 0:25:43.930

R

Thank you, thank you... Last question, which I think we have already addressed, but I will read it to you again, for the sake of completeness: *do librarians have a key-role? What's in their near future?*

0:25:45.470 --> 0:25:58.660

K1

Oh yes, of course. They absolutely had, but they still have a fundamental role and I

0:25:32.800 --> 0:25:43.930

R

Grazie, grazie... ultima domanda, che secondo me abbiamo già affrontata, però te la rileggo, per completezza: *do librarians have a key-role? What's in their near future?*

0:25:45.470 --> 0:25:58.660

K1

Eh sì, certamente. Hanno assolutamente avuto, ma hanno anche adesso un ruolo fondamentale e io nel *near future dei librarians* vedo, e si sta già verificando, una digitalizzazione molto molto spinta e che va molto bene verso la spinta alla via verde e a quella degli archivi; abbiamo moltissimi collaboratori e collaboratrici che si sono formati nei campi, ad esempio, delle *digital humanities* e che con le loro competenze professionali di biblioteconomia lavorano estremamente bene con gli informatici. Perché, se vogliamo spingere la Via verde, quindi degli archivi interoperabili e anche agire nell'ambito della valutazione della ricerca, in Italia VQR, è essenziale essere padroni di tutta una serie di strumenti informatici sui metadati che fino a una generazione fa forse due i bibliotecari non avevano, adesso invece ci sono, cioè, sono arrivati i nuovi bibliotecari e bibliotecarie con questi strumenti specifici e questo è veramente molto bello perché possiamo fare dei lavori

see in the *near future of librarians* a very, very strong digitization that is going very well the push towards the green way and that of the archives; we have many collaborators who have been trained in the fields, for example, of *the digital humanities* and who, with their professional skills in librarianship, work extremely well with computer scientists. Because, if we want to push the Green Way, therefore interoperable archives and also act in the field of research evaluation, in Italy VQR, it is essential to be masters of a whole series of IT tools on metadata that until a generation ago perhaps two librarians did not have, but now there are, that is, the new librarians have arrived with these specific tools and this is really very nice because we can do work together, like, I don't know, that the librarian writes or helps to write a script in Python to automatically import XXXX articles from ArXive, the *subject repository* that we use in the STM, in short, it is very very interesting, a very interesting procedure.

Because then the librarian, still maintains his essential skills of librarianship, skills on metadata, with the rigor that training has provided him, so I see a digital future for librarians, which is already happening in fact.

0:27:56.680 --> 0:28:26.330

insieme, di tipo, non so, che il bibliotecario scrive o aiuta a scrivere uno script in Python per importare automaticamente gli articoli di XXXX da ArXive, il *subject repository* che usiamo nelle STM, insomma è molto molto interessante, un procedimento molto interessante. Perché poi il bibliotecario, mantiene comunque le sue competenze essenziali di biblioteconomia, competenze sui metadati, con il rigore che la formazione gli ha fornito, quindi vedo un futuro digitale per i bibliotecari, che già sta succedendo però di fatto.

0:27:56.680 --> 0:28:26.330

R

Vorrei andare un pochino più nello specifico perché ci siamo passati sopra e questo non attiene alle domande precise, però se hai ancora tempo approfitto e riguarda il discorso delle licenze, anche perché hai citato adesso ArXive. ArXive prevede una licenza di deposito specifica, non ha le Creative Commons, ma la licenza di ArXive. Questo discorso delle licenze, non so se è una associazione che ho fatto io un pochino pericolosa, però da quando esistono i contratti “Read and publish” mi sembra che ottenere una licenza Creative Commons CC-BY, su un postprint sia diventata una cosa che l'editore “fa pesare”. Insomma, ci sono delle licenze apposite, non puoi associare una CC, l'editore ti dà la

R

I would like to go a little more specific because we have gone over it and this does not pertain to the precise questions, but if you still have time, I take advantage and it concerns the issue of licenses, also because you mentioned ArXive now. ArXive has a specific deposit license, it does not have the Creative Commons, but the ArXive license. I don't know if this issue of licenses is a bit of a dangerous association that I have made, but since the existence of "Read and publish" agreements it seems to me that obtaining a Creative Commons CC-BY license on a postprint has become something that the publisher "makes you weigh". In short, there are special licenses, you can't associate a CC, the publisher gives you the possibility to deposit, but then you can't associate a license, you don't understand what you can do, apart from reading from a repository. Am I the only one who noticed this? It's true, isn't it, what opinions do you have?

0:28:55.610 --> 0:29:23.710

K1

So I'm not an expert, I'm absolutely ignorant of licensing, all I know comes from the work done in Coalition S, which is therefore very little... That said, you're definitely right. In fact, I should have said it: one of the limitations of transformative agreements is this, you're not guaranteed

possibilità di depositare, però poi non puoi associare una licenza, non si capisce cosa si può fare, a parte leggere da un repository.

Ho notato solo io questo? È vero, non è vero, che opinioni hai?

0:28:55.610 --> 0:29:23.710

K1

Allora non sono un esperto, sono assolutamente ignorante di licenze, tutto quello che so viene dal lavoro fatto in Coalition S, che quindi è molto poco ... premesso questo, hai sicuramente ragione.

Infatti, avrei dovuto dirlo: uno dei limiti dei contratti trasformativi è questo, non sei garantito di avere CC-BY ... Adesso mettiamo da parte ArXiv perché ArXiv è "buono", e non è un editore.

0:29:22.880 --> 0:29:25.170

R

Assolutamente, assolutamente.

0:29:24.50 --> 0:29:35.750

K1

Però, è chiaro, questo è un limite, chiaramente un limite, perché spesso non si riesce a contrattare CC- BY, ma hai molti altri paletti...

0:29:29.110 --> 0:29:57.400

R

Eh, oppure se lo metti, se si mette diciamo a pagamento, no, perché allora se vuoi, se vuoi la CC- BY te la faccio pagare con le APC e tutto quanto. Se invece pubblici alla maniera tradizionale, diciamo sotto

to have CC-BY... Now let's put aside ArXiv because ArXiv is "good", and it's not a publisher.

0:29:22.880 --> 0:29:25.170

R

Absolutely, absolutely.

0:29:24.50 --> 0:29:35.750

K1

However, it's clear, this is a limit, clearly a limit, because often you can't negotiate CC-BY, but you have many other stakes...

0:29:29.110 --> 0:29:57.400

R

Eh, or if you put it, if you put it let's say for a fee, no, because then if you want, if you want the CC-BY I'll make you pay for it with APCs and everything. If, on the other hand, you publish in the traditional way, let's say under subscription, you can show your postprint, but you can no longer associate a CC of any kind, unless ... And so it's a bit unpleasant about it.

0:29:56.670 --> 0:30:30.180

K1

Oh no, no, but this and this is crucial. That is, the Green Way and then showing the postprint with CC-BY, this is a fundamental battle... this is the priority of XXXX, absolutely, and I believe also of many other research institutions. We've developed a Zenodo based archive that's good for publications, for data, for codes, for software, which is all linked and we

sottoscrizione, il tuo postprint lo puoi far vedere, però non puoi associare più una CC di nessun tipo, a meno che ... e quindi è un po' antipatica questa faccenda.

0:29:56.670 --> 0:30:30.180

K1

Eh no, no, ma questo è cruciale. Cioè, la Via verde e quindi far vedere il postprint con CC-BY, questa è una battaglia fondamentale ... questa è la priorità dell'XXXX, assolutamente e credo anche di molti altri enti di ricerca. Abbiamo sviluppato un archivio basato su Zenodo che va bene per le pubblicazioni, per i dati, per i codici, per i software, che è tutto collegato e rilasciamo automaticamente un DOI per ogni prodotto che inseriamo... Beh, abbiamo un nuovo disciplinare, approvato due mesi fa, che ricalca un po', diciamo i *template* della CRUI, più tiene conto di tutti quanti gli altri disciplinari delle università che sono arrivati finora. Però il deposito della AAM [*Author Accepted Manuscript*] oppure postprint, è uguale, nell'archivio istituzionale "di soggetto" è uno dei punti irrinunciabili, è irrinunciabile e noi lo diciamo, nel disciplinare c'è l'obbligo di depositare nell'archivio con CC-BY e diciamo chiaramente che se l'editore chiede di firmare un *copyright transfer agreement* in cui si abbandonano i diritti sulla AAM, sul postprint, non deve essere

automatically release a DOI for every product we enter... Well, we (In XXXX) have a new policy, approved two months ago, which follows a bit, let's say, the CRUI templates, plus takes into account all the other university regulations that have arrived so far. However, the deposit of the AAM [*Author Accepted Manuscript*] or postprint, is the same, in the institutional archive "of subject" is one of the indispensable points, it is indispensable and we say it, in the specification there is the obligation to deposit in the archive with CC-BY and we clearly say that if the publisher asks to sign a *copyright transfer agreement* in which the rights to the AAM, to the postprint, are abandoned, it does not have to be signed, so on this we must be clear and draconian, that is, the AAM is owned by the XXXX. Therefore, the author cannot assign the rights to the publisher on the AAM. And that's central. Because? Because the scientific content is guaranteed by the AAM which, is identical to the *Version of Record*, VoR, and this also satisfies all the requirements of our research evaluation, because the VQR fortunately also admits as open access the deposit of the postprint, i.e. the AAM, in the archives, so in this way, safeguarding the AAM or postprint, the circle closes a bit. That is why I have said from the outset that the main strategy, the priority, should

firmato, quindi su questo bisogna essere chiari e draconiani, cioè la AAM è di proprietà dell'XXXX.

Quindi l'autore non può cedere i diritti all'editore sulla AAM. E questo è centrale. Perché? Perché il contenuto scientifico è garantito dalla AAM che, è identico alla *Version of Record*, VoR, e questo soddisfa anche tutti i requisiti della nostra valutazione della ricerca, perché la VQR fortunatamente ammette come open access anche il deposito del postprint, cioè l'AAM, negli archivi, quindi in questo modo, salvaguardando la AAM o postprint, si chiude un po' il cerchio, per questo ho detto sin dall'inizio che la strategia principale, prioritaria, dovrebbe essere la via verde. Quando potremmo essere tranquilli? Quando verrà modificata la legislazione italiana sul diritto autore. Questa è l'altra azione normativa che alcuni giuristi, stanno cercando di fare in Italia. Un anno fa, a dicembre 2021, abbiamo creato il gruppo di lavoro Open science di CoPER, la Consulta dei Presidenti degli Enti pubblici di Ricerca, un gruppo di lavoro Open science e abbiamo organizzato il primo convegno. È piuttosto interessante perché credo sia venuto abbastanza bene perché l'abbiamo fatto veramente multidimensionale; quindi, abbiamo coperto dalla *research evaluation* agli *open data*, eccetera, e abbiamo anche incluso

be the green way. When could we be quiet? When will the Italian legislation on copyright be modified? This is the other regulatory action that some jurists are trying to do in Italy. A year ago, in December 2021, we created the CoPER Open science working group, the Council of Presidents of Public Research Institutions, an Open science working group and organized the first conference. It's pretty interesting because I think it came out pretty well because we did it really multidimensional; So, we've covered everything from *research evaluation* to *open data*, etc., and we've also included the legal aspect of copyright. A very interesting contribution was that of a colleague, a mathematician from Milan who is part of an association, who launched the concept of access to scientific information from research, financed by public funds, as one of the human rights, in connection with UNESCO and other international bodies that safeguard human rights. This is let's say, as the English speakers say, a very interesting spin, why not? It could be...

0:33:48.800 --> 0:33:50.520

R

It moves up the level...

0:33:50.290 --> 0:33:52.880

K1

It moves up the level, exactly, exactly.

l'aspetto giuridico sul diritto d'autore. Un contributo molto interessante è stato quello di un collega, un matematico di Milano che fa parte di un'associazione, che ha lanciato il concetto di accesso all'informazione scientifica della ricerca, finanziata da fondi pubblici, come uno dei diritti dell'uomo, in collegamento con UNESCO e con altri organismi internazionali che salvaguardano i diritti dell'uomo. Questo è diciamo, come dicono gli anglofoni, uno *spin* molto interessante, perché no? Potrebbe essere ...

0:33:48.800 --> 0:33:50.520

R

Sposta il livello ...

0:33:50.290 --> 0:33:52.880

K1

Eh sposta il livello, esattamente, esattamente.

0:33:53.620 --> 0:34:3.710

K1

E quindi, se non hai il riferimento di questo workshop, te lo mando, però dovresti trovarlo prima.

0:34:2.480 --> 0:34:5.690

R

Grazie, sì, sì, lo troverò, penso. Perfetto.

0:34:4.640 --> 0:34:8.90

K1

CoPER, primo convegno nazionale.

0:34:10.510 --> 0:34:11.310

R

Benissimo.

0:33:53.620 --> 0:34:3.710

K1

And so, if you don't have the reference for this workshop, I'll send it to you, but you should find it first.

0:34:2.480 --> 0:34:5.690

R

Thank you, yes, yes, I'll find it, I think.

Perfect.

0:34:4.640 --> 0:34:8.90

K1

CoPER, first national conference.

0:34:10.510 --> 0:34:11.310

R

Very well.

0:34:11.650 --> 0:34:16.70

K1

And the work then after in CoPER is going on, there are various working groups ... We hope to have other results soon, however, this would be a really important struggle to be waged, an important action that can start from an initiative, for example, of popular law, because it is the reform of copyright, it can be the subject of a popular initiative. In fact, this had also been discussed in the context of the work of AISA, the Italian Association for the Promotion of Open science.

[...]

0:37:26.320 --> 0:37:31.780

R

0:34:11.650 --> 0:34:16.70

K1

E il lavoro poi dopo in CoPER sta andando avanti, ci sono vari gruppi di lavoro ... Speriamo di avere altri risultati presto, però, questa sarebbe una veramente una lotta importante da fare, un'azione importante che può partire da un'iniziativa, ad esempio, di legge popolare. No, perché è la riforma del diritto d'autore, può essere oggetto di un'iniziativa popolare. In realtà di questo se n'era discusso anche nell'ambito dei lavori di AISA, l'Associazione italiana per la Promozione della Scienza Aperta.

[...]

0:37:26.320 --> 0:37:31.780

R

Senti, due parole sulla *Right Retention Strategy*, se le hai, un'opinione.

0:37:33.200 --> 0:37:41.10

K1

Eh allora, beh, l'abbiamo vista nascere. Abbiamo anche uno dei nostri legali di XXXXXXXXX, ha partecipato al gruppo di lavoro, è interessante perché è stato sicuramente un esperimento nuovo. Almeno io non sapevo di nessun altro, ha gettato il sasso nello stagno proprio su questo argomento dei diritti che è cruciale e centrale.

[...]

Listen, a few words about *the Right Retention Strategy*, if you have them, an opinion.

0:37:33.200 --> 0:37:41.10

K1

Well, well, we saw her born. We also have one of our lawyers from XXXXXXXXX, he participated in the working group, it's interesting because it was definitely a new experiment. At least I didn't know about anyone else, he threw a pebble into the pond on this very issue of rights that is crucial and central.

[...]

0:38:44.840 --> 0:39:7.460

K1

Oh yes, so I said that it was certainly a very interesting experiment. We participated in the work as Coalition S. The XXXX has not applied it explicitly because for us it is already so, that is, for us the author does not have to give up the rights ...

0:39:5.860 --> 0:39:7.740

R

Have you formalized it yet?

0:39:8.700 --> 0:39:39.510

K1

Yes, we formalized it only two months ago, but it was also the same three years ago, years ago, when *retention* started and moreover our lawyers were very doubtful that, given this *warning*, we would have

0:38:44.840 --> 0:39:7.460

K1

Eh sì, allora dicevo che è stata un esperimento sicuramente molto interessante. Abbiamo partecipato ai lavori come Coalition S. L'XXXX non l'ha applicata in maniera esplicita perché per noi è già così, cioè per noi l'autore non deve cedere i diritti ...

0:39:5.860 --> 0:39:7.740

R

L'avete già formalizzato?

0:39:8.700 --> 0:39:39.510

K1

Sì, Lo abbiamo formalizzato solo due mesi fa, però era così anche tre anni fa, anni fa, quando è partita *retention* e inoltre i nostri legali erano molto dubbiosi sul fatto che, dato questo *warning*, saremmo stati in grado, con il sistema giuridico italiano, di rivalerci sugli editori che avessero chiesto di cedere i diritti, perché questo è il meccanismo: noi avvertiamo tutti gli editori che una certa istituzione ritiene i diritti sulla AAM, quindi l'editore non può, non può chiedere di cederglieli. Se lo fa, può essere portato in giudizio perché lo sapeva e sta cercando di cambiare, diciamo adesso non so che cosa, ma insomma, degli aspetti contrattuali, comunque sta cercando di fare un'operazione che non è consona. I nostri avvocati hanno detto che non sarebbe passata, diciamo da qui; quindi, è

been able, with the Italian legal system, to retaliate against publishers who had asked to transfer the rights, because this is the mechanism: we warn all publishers that a certain institution retains the rights on the AAM, so the publisher cannot, cannot ask to give them to them. If he does that, he can be taken to court because he knew it and he's trying to change, let's say now I don't know what, but in short, the contractual aspects, anyway he's trying to do an operation that is not appropriate. Our lawyers said it wouldn't pass, let's say from here; So, it's useless because this right already existed and the legal action would have been, would not have been effective in the Italian system, so we didn't actually speed it up, but it's very, very important. What is in the end, however, the core of the problem, is that, if the publisher asks you, before taking the draft, to give up the rights, the author has no choice, that is, he has to change journal. So, in short, this is a little bit of shifting responsibility to the author, isn't it? If, on the other hand, he asks you, after he has accepted the draft and even after he has done all the *peer review*, after the article has been there, if he asks you afterwards, in our system it never happens that the publisher refuses to publish. So now probably some publisher will listen to what I'm saying, but let's say in the field of physics, even if you don't

inutile perché già esisteva questo diritto e l'azione legale sarebbe stata, non sarebbe stata efficace nel sistema italiano, quindi non l'abbiamo effettivamente velocizzata, però è molto, è molto importante. Qual è alla fine però, il nucleo del problema, è che, se l'editore ti chiede prima di prendere la bozza di cedere i diritti, l'autore non ha scelta, cioè, deve cambiare rivista. Quindi insomma, questo è un modo un pochino di scaricare responsabilità sull'autore, no? Se invece ti chiede, dopo che ha accettato la bozza e dopo addirittura che ha fatto tutta la *peer review*, dopo che c'è stato l'articolo, se te lo chiede dopo, nel nostro sistema non succede mai che l'editore si rifiuti di pubblicare. Quindi adesso probabilmente qualche editore ascolterà quello che sto dicendo, però diciamo nell'ambito della fisica, se anche non si firma, perché non possiamo, non possiamo firmare la copia del *transfer agreement*, l'articolo che ho pubblicato esce ugualmente. Perché? Perché l'editore ha già impiegato i *referees*, ha già speso soldi per fare la [pubblicazione], quindi non gli conviene dire no, allora non te lo pubblico, però insomma, è un modo per lasciare, per lasciare un po' allo sbaraglio l'autore e alla fine si risolve sempre in questo fatto, cioè l'autore deve essere aiutato, quindi gli va detto, tu non puoi cedere i diritti, però ci rendiamo conto che magari non puoi

sign, because we can't, we can't sign the copy of the *transfer agreement*, the article I published comes out anyway. Why? Because the publisher has already employed the *referees*, he has already spent money to do the [publication], so it is not convenient for him to say no, then I will not publish it to you, but in short, it is a way to leave, to leave the author a little in the lurch and in the end it always resolves into this fact, that is, the author must be helped, so he must be told, you can't give up the rights, but we realize that maybe you can't publish in that journal, we help you find another one, even if it's due, considering the fact that the Impact Factor is starting to be not so crucial, so you can find another journal with prestige, let's say not impact but equivalent prestige, without receiving a great deal of damage. So, it's all a work that requires an education of the author and it's also a help, you can't leave the author alone in front of a publisher who normally has the position of strength.

0:42:34.810 --> 0:42:40.950

R

Of course, I'm thinking of early *career researchers*, who are obviously the first to suffer the consequences, aren't they?

0:42:46.180 --> 0:42:54.890

K1

pubblicare su quella rivista, ti aiutiamo a trovarne un'altra, anche dovuto, considerato il fatto che l'Impact Factor sta cominciando a non essere così cruciale, quindi tu puoi trovarti un'altra rivista con prestigio, diciamo non impatto ma prestigio equivalente, senza ricevere un grande danno. Quindi però è tutta un'opera che richiede un'educazione dell'autore ed è anche un aiuto, non si può lasciare l'autore da solo di fronte a un editore che normalmente ha la posizione di forza.

0:42:34.810 --> 0:42:40.950

R

Certo, penso proprio a gli *early career researchers*, che ovviamente sono i primi a subire le conseguenze, no?

0:42:46.180 --> 0:42:54.890

K1

Esatto, esattamente questa per noi è la preoccupazione maggiore, assolutamente, per gli *early career researchers*, sicuramente.

0:42:55.380 --> 0:42:55.860

R

Chiaro, ma quante cose veramente ... un sistema ... è complesso.

0:43:1.860 --> 0:43:16.10

K1

È tutto collegato, moltissimo, molto complesso e questo è anche affascinante, perché si tratta di cambiare un mercato, lo sai, da 10 ai 20 miliardi l'anno

That's right, that's exactly the biggest concern for us, absolutely, for *early career researchers*, definitely.

0:42:55.380 --> 0:42:55.860

R

Clear, but how many things really ... A system ... It's complex.

0:43:1.860 --> 0:43:16.10

K1

It's all connected, very, very complex and this is also fascinating, because it's about changing a market, you know, from 10 to 20 billion a year worldwide is, at least, if 10 or 20 or between 10 and 20.

0:43:11.990 --> 0:43:17.710

R

Eh or maybe... Here, it is assumed between 10 and 20...

0:43:21.960 --> 0:43:23.980

R

That's right, that's right.

0:43:18.310 --> 0:43:27.690

K1

It is assumed between 10 and 20 and in the hands of 5 publishers, this is an operation that then the knowledge market, this, this is the most unacceptable thing, isn't it?

0:43:28.410 --> 0:43:33.770

R

That's right... which is not a common good regardless. In short, we have to think about it.

0:43:35.220 --> 0:43:44.270

mondialmente sono, almeno, se 10 o 20 o fra 10 e 20.

0:43:11.990 --> 0:43:17.710

R

Eh o forse... Ecco, si ipotizza tra 10 e 20...

0:43:21.960 --> 0:43:23.980

R

Esatto, esatto.

0:43:18.310 --> 0:43:27.690

K1

Si ipotizza tra 10 e 20 e in mano a 5 editori, questa è un'operazione che poi il mercato della conoscenza, questa, questa è la cosa più inaccettabile, no?

0:43:28.410 --> 0:43:33.770

R

Esatto ... che non è un bene comune a prescindere. Insomma, ecco dobbiamo riflettere.

0:43:35.220 --> 0:43:44.270

K1

Eh sì, ... come impostazione del tuo corso c'è un fondamento etico fortissimo, perché mai deve essere così, eh?

0:43:43.740 --> 0:43:57.0

R

Esatto, quindi, che cosa altro manca secondo te, per tutti? Ecco domande che mi vengono per via. Cos'altro manca? Forse delle infrastrutture un pochino più "concorrenziali", vorrei dire, rispetto al mercato privato.

K1

Oh yes, ... There is a very strong ethical foundation for your course, why does it have to be this way, eh?

0:43:43.740 --> 0:43:57.0

R

Exactly, then, what else do you think is missing, for everyone? Here are questions that come to my way. What else is missing? Perhaps infrastructures that are a little more "competitive", I would say, compared to the private market.

0:43:55.160 --> 0:44:24.910

K1

Many things, many things, mah ... then the PNSA, National Plan for Open science was a fundamental, fundamental document, thank goodness we had it, I don't know if you followed the work, but it lasted 2, 3 years, Roberto Caso is among the editors, together with other colleagues, so the PNSA says all the right things, shareable and all our action is directed along the 5 directions of intervention, But it doesn't give the budgets, it doesn't give the economic resources to implement them, so that's missing, so that's missing. There is a lack of resources to implement them. Now there is a table, at the beginning of the year it was formed, a ministerial table for the implementation of the National Open science Plan, the coordinator is Donatella Castelli, from the

0:43:55.160 --> 0:44:24.910

K1

Molte cose, molte cose, mah ... allora il PNSA, Piano Nazionale per la Scienza Aperta è stato un documento fondamentale, fondamentale, meno male che l'abbiamo avuto, non so se hai seguito i lavori, però è durato 2, 3 anni, Roberto Caso è tra gli editori, insieme ad altri colleghi, quindi il PNSA dice tutte cose giuste, condivisibili e tutta la nostra azione è indirizzata lungo le 5 direzioni di intervento, però non dà i budget, non dà le risorse economiche per attuarle, quindi questo manca, quindi questo manca. Mancano le risorse per attuarle. Adesso c'è un tavolo, è stato formato l'inizio dell'anno, un tavolo ministeriale di attuazione del Piano Nazionale di Scienza Aperta, la coordinatrice è Donatella Castelli, del CNR di Pisa, ci aspettiamo cose buone, la cosa che, secondo me, è la cosa principale che è rimasta molto indietro è la rete, nazionale almeno, interoperabile di archivi della ricerca. Perché non l'abbiamo, non ci vorrebbe moltissimo per crearla, perché tutti, enti, università hanno degli archivi propri e sono già interoperabili. Ci vuole un portale generale che li coordini e renda interoperabili. E se l'avessimo, guariremmo l'assurdo, uno degli assurdi che è quello che la valutazione la dobbiamo comprare

CNR of Pisa, we expect good things, the thing that, in my opinion, is the main thing that has lagged far behind is the network, at least national, interoperable of research archives. Because we don't have it, it wouldn't take much to create it, because everyone, institutions, universities have their own archives and are already interoperable. We need a general portal that coordinates them and makes them interoperable. And if we did, we would heal the absurd, one of the absurdities which is that we have to buy the evaluation from the paid databases Web of Science and Scopus.

0:45:28.300 --> 0:45:52.340

K1

And that's the thing, that is, the umpteenth moment when we pay the publishers again, and, in one case, in a blatant conflict of interest, so with a national network of research archives we would give ... i.e. in this way ANVUR should not require compulsorily, in short, practically compulsorily, indexing on these two paid archives.

0:45:53.170 --> 0:46:16.110

K1

ANVUR even if he realizes it, that is, he has been repeatedly asked "why do we continue to pay?" The answer, at least the answers I've heard on at least a couple of occasions have been "there is no

dai database a pagamento Web of Science e Scopus.

0:45:28.300 --> 0:45:52.340

K1

E questa è la cosa, cioè l'ennesimo momento in cui paghiamo di nuovo gli editori, e, in un caso, in palese conflitto di interessi, quindi con una rete nazionale di archivi della ricerca daremmo ... cioè in questo in questo modo ANVUR non dovrebbe richiedere obbligatoriamente, insomma praticamente obbligatoriamente l'indicizzazione su questi due archivi a pagamento.

0:45:53.170 --> 0:46:16.110

K1

ANVUR anche se ne rende conto, cioè è stato più volte chiesto "come mai continuiamo a pagare?" La risposta, almeno le risposte che ho sentito io almeno in un paio di occasioni sono state "non c'è l'alternativa" e quindi crediamo in questa alternativa, cioè facciamola. Quindi questo, secondo me, di tutte le cose è la cosa che dovrebbe essere prioritaria: rete interoperabile degli archivi ad accesso aperto.

0:46:21.540 --> 0:46:25.80

R

Assolutamente, purché siano implementati, aggiornati, resi veramente pieni di quello che è pubblicato.

alternative" and so we do believe in this alternative, that is, let's do it. So that, in my opinion, is the thing that should be prioritized: an interoperable network of open access repositories.

0:46:21.540 --> 0:46:25.80

R

Absolutely, as long as they are implemented, updated, made really full of what is published.

0:46:30.270 --> 0:47:0.520

K1

Of course, of course, of course, in this we need policies, then disciplinarys, therefore the mandatory deposit, where every institution or university obliges to deposit ... We need this, we don't need sanctions, we don't have any sanctions, it's an obligation, but there is no sanction. This is where communication, communication and training comes in, which is the fourth direction of the PNSA. This is crucial, so if we want to put a second thing it is the support for communication, for the training of colleagues, especially colleagues, by librarians and researchers together.

0:47:10.700 --> 0:47:40.230

R

I agree with this observation, researchers, let's say more attentive or more informed simply for these times they would be nice older brothers, let's say, to make a little

0:46:30.270 --> 0:47:0.520

K1

Certo, certo, certo, in questo ci vogliono le *policies*, quindi i disciplinari, quindi il deposito obbligatorio, dove ogni ente o università obbliga a depositare ... su questo ci vuole, non servono sanzioni, non abbiamo nessuna sanzione, è un obbligo, ma non c'è nessuna sanzione. Qui entra la comunicazione, comunicazione e formazione che è la quarta direzione del PNSA. Questo è cruciale, quindi se vogliamo mettere una seconda cosa è il supporto alla comunicazione, alla formazione dei colleghi, soprattutto dei colleghi, da parte di bibliotecari e i ricercatori insieme.

0:47:10.700 --> 0:47:40.230

R

Sono d'accordo con questa osservazione, i ricercatori, diciamo più attenti o più informati semplicemente per questi tempo e sarebbero dei bei fratelli maggiori, diciamo per rendere un pochino familiare l'espressione è per indirizzare, per dare forza alla comunicazione. Sì, perché la comunicazione del tecnico ha una pregiudiziale che passa per *bureaucracy* inutile, pesante, noiosa...

0:47:44.880 --> 0:47:46.40

R

È un dato di fatto.

familiar the expression is for the to direct, to give strength to communication. Yes, because the communication of the technician has a prejudicial that passes for *useless, heavy, boring* bureaucracy...

0:47:44.880 --> 0:47:46.40

R

It's a fact.

0:47:50.280 --> 0:47:50.550

R

Yes.

0:48:2.570 --> 0:48:3.740

R

Yes, it's true.

0:47:39.810 --> 0:48:10.120

K1

That's right, exactly, it's wrong, it's wrong, but it's what I've seen in about ten years of activity, that's how it is, that's just how it is. The message doesn't get through well, that is, why the recipient, if the librarian tells him, ah, what, the librarian wants to tell me where to publish? That is, and it completely closes there, you can't do that, unfortunately... Unfortunately, this is a criticism for my colleagues, for the authors, not for the employees, they do their job.

0:48:12.600 --> 0:48:13.170

R

Thank you.

0:48:10.190 --> 0:48:21.300

K1

0:47:50.280 --> 0:47:50.550

R

Sì.

0:48:2.570 --> 0:48:3.740

R

Sì, è vero.

0:47:39.810 --> 0:48:10.120

K1

Esatto, esattamente, è sbagliato, è sbagliato, però è quello che ho visto in una decina d'anni attività, è così, è proprio così. Non arriva bene il messaggio, cioè perché il destinatario, se glielo dice il bibliotecario, ah, ma che, il bibliotecario vuole dirmi dove pubblicare? Questo è, e chiude completamente lì, non si può fare così, purtroppo ... purtroppo, questa è una critica per i miei colleghi, per gli autori, non per gli impiegati, fanno il loro lavoro.

0:48:12.600 --> 0:48:13.170

R

Grazie.

0:48:10.190 --> 0:48:21.300

K1

Benissimo, però devono essere, secondo me, proprio come hai detto tu dei tutor, fratelli maggiori, più anziani, perché non hanno problemi di carriera, certo.

[...]

0:53:4.630 --> 0:53:16.210

R

Benissimo, io non ho altre domande. Penso di averti stressato a sufficienza.

Very well, but in my opinion, just as you said, they must be tutors, older brothers, because they don't have career problems, of course.

[...]

0:53:4.630 --> 0:53:16.210

R

Very well, I don't have any other questions. I think I've stressed you out enough.

0:53:15.960 --> 0:53:23.790

K1

No, look, I'm pleased. Then. In short, for undergraduates, doctoral students, it is our duty to lend a hand.

0:53:21.730 --> 0:53:34.750

R

For this I thank you twice, thank you because I have gathered several times from your words this attention to young people. I'm not young, but, in short, as a student I am.

[...]

0:55:51.330 --> 0:55:56.980

K1

Well, good job ... Bye.

0:53:15.960 --> 0:53:23.790

K1

No, guarda, mi fa piacere. Poi. Insomma, per laureandi, dottorandi, è il nostro dovere dare una mano.

0:53:21.730 --> 0:53:34.750

R

Per questo grazie bis, grazie perché l'ho colto parecchie volte dalle tue parole questa attenzione ai giovani. Io non sono giovane anagraficamente, però, insomma, come studi si.

[...]

0:55:50.90 --> 0:55:54.270

R

Benissimo, va bene allora buon proseguimento di giornata e di ferie mezze.

0:55:51.330 --> 0:55:56.980

K1

Beh, buon lavoro ... ciao.

Trascrizione dell'intervista a K2.

[...] indica parti di conversazione non rilevanti rispetto al tema.

[...]

0:1:19.480 --> 0:1:41.430

R

Grazie 1000, perfetto, OK, cominciamo con le domande. Quindi penso che le avrai sotto, ma le riporto. Ovviamente possiamo parlare in italiano, sarà mia cura

Transcript of the interview with K2.

[...] Indicates parts of the conversation that are not relevant to the topic.

[...]

0:1:19.480 --> 0:1:41.430

R

Thank you, perfect, OK, let's start with the questions. So, I think you'll have them underneath, but I'll bring them back. Of course, we can speak in Italian, I will take

eventualmente, poiché la tesi sarà in lingua inglese, di fare la trascrizione e traduzione.

0:1:41.530 --> 0:1:44.970

R

le faccio in inglese, come preferisci? In realtà ecco come è per meglio per te.

0:1:43.780 --> 0:1:46.280

K2

No, no, sì, parliamo in italiano.

0:1:46.0 --> 0:1:57.260

R

OK, i trasformativi sono con noi, *do they really increase the access to the research?*, quindi veramente aumentano l'accesso alla ricerca? Qual è il loro impatto?

0:1:59.220 --> 0:2:29.550

K2

Ma, dunque, a mio parere ehm, e questo lo vedrai in un articolo, in un post che uscirà su ROARS fra un paio di giorni, a mio parere ci sono punti di vista diversi di guardare le cose. Proprio recentemente è uscita questo grido trionfante di Springer che dice che attraverso i contratti trasformativi abbiamo raggiunto un aumento delle pubblicazioni ad accesso aperto, ovviamente non dicono a quali costi e con quali guadagni, e questa informazione diciamo deve essere letta invece con il commento che Plan S fa, che Coalition S fa del raggiungimento da parte di alcuni editori di un ipotetico target annuale che invece boccia solennemente

care of the transcription and translation, since the thesis will be in English.

0:1:41.530 --> 0:1:44.970

R

I do them in English, how do you prefer? Actually, here's how it's best for you.

0:1:43.780 --> 0:1:46.280

K2

No, no, yes, we speak Italian.

0:1:46.0 --> 0:1:57.260

R

OK, the transformative agreements are with us, *do they really increase the access to the research?* So, do they really increase access to research? What is their impact?

0:1:59.220 --> 0:2:29.550

K2

But, so, in my opinion um, and you'll see this in an article, in a post that will be published on ROARS in a couple of days, in my opinion there are different points of view to look at things. Just recently this triumphant cry came out from Springer saying that through transformative contracts we have achieved an increase in open access publications, obviously they do not say at what cost and with what gains, and this information we say must be read instead with the comment that Plan S makes, that Coalition S makes of the achievement by some publishers of a hypothetical annual target that instead solemnly rejects Springer. So, in my

Springer. Quindi, secondo me, allora in primo luogo dipende da chi ne parla e dal punto di vista e questo è un classico esempio per cui la stessa informazione viene guardata, diciamo da due punti di partenza diversi e quindi dà risultati assolutamente opposti. Ecco, quindi, io credo che questa cosa dei contratti trasformativi faccia un pochino parte di quel processo di *trials and errors* che la scienza attraversa e quindi anche gli strumenti, diciamo di appoggio alla scienza attraversano questo è sicuramente un trial che è stato fatto. È un errore che a mio parere si sta rivelando tale se no appunto adesso non ci sarebbe tutta questa enfasi sul Diamond eccetera... e quindi ehm, diciamo se devo dire ... hanno avuto successo?, a mio parere no, nel senso che, se l'obiettivo era quello di attivare un *cultural change*, il ricercatore medio, quello che va sul sito di Springer che gli ha approvato l'articolo e che sceglie l'open access, non capisce in che ambito sta lavorando, chi paga e che cosa, quindi non c'è un *cultural change*. Se l'obiettivo era, rendiamo, diciamo, i processi di ricerca più trasparenti: questa trasparenza manca perché io non so per che cosa pago e quanto pago, perché i contratti sono secretati, hanno vincoli di riservatezza e quant'altro. Io non metterei questa voce, neppure fra le voci dell'Open science, cioè,

opinion, then in the first place it depends on who is talking about it and the point of view, and this is a classic example where the same information is looked at, let's say from two different starting points and therefore gives absolutely opposite results. So, I think that these of transformative agreements is a little bit part of that process of *trials and errors* that science goes through and therefore also the tools, let's say supporting science, go through this is definitely a trial that has been done. It's a mistake that, in my opinion, is turning out to be a mistake, otherwise there wouldn't be all this emphasis on the Diamond and so on... And so, uhm, let's say if I have to say... Have they been successful?, in my opinion not, in the sense that, if the goal was to activate a cultural change, the average researcher, the one who goes to the Springer website that approved the article and who chooses open access, does not understand in which field he is working, who pays and what, so there is no cultural change. If the goal was, let's say, let's make the research processes more transparent: this transparency is lacking because I don't know what I pay for and how much I pay, because the contracts are classified, have confidentiality constraints and so on. I wouldn't put this entry, not even among the voices of Open science, that is, in my opinion, it's the umpteenth,

secondo me, è l'ennesima, l'ennesimo trucco, l'ennesimo, l'ennesimo processo attraverso il quale gli editori sostanzialmente sfruttano le istituzioni. Quindi questo. Io ho una visione molto negativa e devo dire che trovo molto responsabile, molto responsabile l'atteggiamento francese che rispetto a questi contratti trasformativi ha tenuto proprio una posizione totalmente...

0:5:39.610 --> 0:5:40.480

R

...Sfavorevole?

0:5:39.190 --> 0:5:47.270

K2

Totalmente immaginaria, coerente con un unico contratto trasformativo per ora e basta. Insomma, questa cosa, peraltro, ecco un attimo, quindi questo per quanto riguarda i possibili vantaggi che io non vedo, mentre invece quali sono, qual è l'impatto? L'impatto ci piacerebbe misurarlo. È sicuramente un impatto economico consistente, è un peccato, appunto, che questa cosa non sia minimamente misurabile, perché con i dati alla mano, forse chi poi deve prendere decisioni magari avrebbe un atteggiamento più responsabile.

0:6:26.630 --> 0:6:29.680

R

Grazie, OK, grazie.

the umpteenth trick, the umpteenth, the umpteenth process through which publishers basically exploit institutions.

So, this. I have a very negative view and I must say that I find very responsible, very responsible the French attitude that with respect to these transformative agreements has held a totally ...

0:5:39.610 --> 0:5:40.480

R

... Unfavourable?

0:5:39.190 --> 0:5:47.270

K2

Totally imaginary, coherent with a single transformative contract for now and that's it. In short, this thing, by the way, here is a moment, so this as far as the possible advantages are concerned, which I do not see, while what are they, what is the impact? We would like to measure the impact. It is certainly a substantial economic impact, it is a pity, in fact, that this thing is not in the least measurable, because with the data in hand, perhaps those who then have to make decisions would perhaps have a more responsible attitude.

0:6:26.630 --> 0:6:29.680

R

Thank you, OK, thank you.

0:6:31.170 --> 0:6:52.860

R

0:6:31.170 --> 0:6:52.860

R

Allora procediamo con la successiva,

What's next? I trasformativi hanno punti di forza e di debolezza, diciamo per un equilibrio doveroso nell'indagine cerchiamo entrambi e come possono i trasformativi essere *fair and sustainable*, quindi essere diciamo ecco giusti, in un certo senso e sostenibili.

0:6:52.100 --> 0:7:21.840

K2

Certo, certo beh, l'idea iniziale che diciamo questi contratti fossero *cost neutral*, non era affatto sbagliata, no? Quindi l'idea che nel sistema c'è una certa quantità di soldi quantificata, 10 miliardi o quello che è; quindi, nel sistema ci sono fondi a sufficienza. L'idea è quella di spostare questi 10 miliardi dal *pay per read* al *pay per publish*.

0:7:28.840 --> 0:7:43.170

K2

E questa cosa, appunto, non è stata. Non ha avuto poi questo tipo di traduzione. Perché proprio oggi insomma vedevo ecco l'altro svantaggio, attenzione, è che sono tutti piuttosto farraginosi, per cui alcuni hanno riviste sì, riviste no, questa sta dentro, questa sta fuori, questo e questo elenco, questo un altro elenco, cioè, è il caos veramente per un ricercatore che volesse

So, let's proceed with the next one, *What's next?* Transformative agreements have strengths and weaknesses, let's say for a dutiful balance in the investigation we look for both and how can TAs *be fair and sustainable*, so be let's say that's right, in a sense and sustainable.

0:6:52.100 --> 0:7:21.840

K2

Sure, of course, well, the initial idea that we say these contracts were *cost neutral*, it wasn't wrong at all, was it? So, the idea that there's a certain amount of quantified money in the system, \$10 billion or whatever; So, there are enough funds in the system. The idea is to move these 10 billion from pay per read to pay per publish.

0:7:28.840 --> 0:7:43.170

K2

And this was not. He didn't have that kind of translation. Because just today I saw the other disadvantage, be careful, is that they are all quite cumbersome, so some have journals yes, journals no, this one is inside, this is outside, this and this list, this another list, that is, it's really chaos for a researcher who also wants to try to understand something, in my opinion it's discouraging.

0:8:8.480 --> 0:8:12.530

K2

Eh so, so, no, the question was.

anche cercare di capire qualcosa, secondo me è scoraggiante.

0:8:8.480 --> 0:8:12.530

K2

Eh quindi Eh, dunque no, la domanda era.

0:8:14.990 --> 0:8:17.830

K2

Forza e debolezza quindi? Il punto, il punto di forza.

0:8:13.200 --> 0:8:18.550

R

Se ci sono punti di forza e debolezza, se ci sono, e se c'è sostenibilità.

0:8:18.710 --> 0:8:29.500

K2

Ecco il punto di forza, secondo me avrebbe dovuto essere questa neutralità, no? Quindi trasformo tutto quello che io pago per leggere in contributo per pubblicare, questa cosa non è avvenuta in questo modo; quindi, quello che era nato come punto di forza si è dimostrato poi un punto di debolezza, perché di fatto il sistema costa di più. La sostenibilità, secondo me, non c'è, cioè la sostenibilità a medio termine dovrebbe venir meno. Perché appunto, a mano a mano che vediamo allungarsi la lista di questi contratti trasformativi sempre più costosi, sempre più con periodi anche piuttosto lunghi e con condizioni diciamo molto, molto miste, molto anche diverse l'uno dall'altra, secondo me, diciamo, non è sostenibile nel medio.

0:8:14.990 --> 0:8:17.830

K2

Strength and weakness then? The point, the strength.

0:8:13.200 --> 0:8:18.550

R

If there are strengths and weaknesses, if there are, and if there is sustainability.

0:8:18.710 --> 0:8:29.500

K2

Here's the strong point, in my opinion it should have been this neutrality, right? So, I turn everything I pay to read into a contribution to publish, this thing didn't happen that way; So, what started out as a strength turned out to be a weakness, because in fact the system costs more.

Sustainability, in my opinion, is not there, that is, medium-term sustainability should be lacking. Because precisely, as we see the list of these increasingly expensive transformative contracts getting longer, more and more with periods that are also quite long and with very, very mixed conditions, very different from each other, in my opinion we say it is not sustainable in the medium term.

0:9:27.510 --> 0:9:28.120

R

Short?

0:9:25.110 --> 0:9:41.560

K2 In the medium term ..., in the short, short term, medium and long term

0:9:27.510 --> 0:9:28.120

R

Breve?

0:9:25.110 --> 0:9:41.560

K2

Nel medio periodo ..., nel breve, nel breve termine, nel medio e lungo termine assolutamente no, tanto è vero che appunto Coalition S che li aveva promossi all'inizio ha detto appunto alla fine del 2024 basta!, insomma, o sei dentro o sei fuori.

0:9:42.770 --> 0:9:43.490

R

Esatto.

0:9:47.450 --> 0:9:58.330

R

Arrivo scusi Eh... mi provo, provo scusami, provo a segnare anche delle note per tenere traccia, poi quando riascolterò e riscriverò soprattutto, grazie davvero, molto chiaro tutto quanto. Grazie veramente, allora in Italia come gli enti di ricerca, gli autori e i bibliotecari stanno ponendosi davanti alle sfide nella comunicazione accademica portate dai trasformativi. Se sono portate, se sfide sono insomma, ecco, questo lo puoi ridiscutere.

0:10:28.370 --> 0:10:43.700

K2

A mio parere e ci sono due elementi: da un lato, ma questo francamente non è solamente delle comunità italiane, o meglio

absolutely not, so much so that Coalition S that had promoted them at the beginning said precisely at the end of 2024 it's enough!, in short, either you are in or you are out.

0:9:42.770 --> 0:9:43.490

R

That's right.

0:9:47.450 --> 0:9:58.330

R

Excuse me, I am trying to make some notes to keep track, then when I'll listen again and rewrite above all, thank you very much, everything is very clear. Thank you truly, then in Italy as research institutions, authors and librarians are facing the challenges in academic communication brought by transformative agreements, If they are talented, if they are challenges, in short, well, you can discuss this.

0:10:28.370 --> 0:10:43.700

K2

In my opinion and there are two elements: on the one hand, but frankly this is not only of the Italian communities, or rather ... I don't know if you have picked up on the comments of some of the figures on the Elsevier contract that was concluded in Germany. And then the comments are very negative, but they don't come. They don't come from libraries. Well, I have the impression that libraries, with a view to offering a service to their users, think that,

... non so se hai colto i commenti di alcune di alcune figure al contratto di Elsevier che è stato concluso in Germania. E allora i commenti sono molto negativi, però non arrivano. Non arrivano dalle biblioteche. Ecco, io ho l'impressione che le biblioteche, nell'ottica dell'offrire un servizio ai propri utenti pensino che, come dire, l'open access a qualsiasi costo sia una buona cosa, mentre invece io credo che l'open access a qualsiasi costo non possa, non debba esistere. Quindi da un lato, secondo me c'è sicuramente un atteggiamento, passami il termine, un po' acritico nei confronti di questo fenomeno, cioè uno dice vabbè, caspita, ho dei problemi a far decollare l'open access, adesso facciamo i trasformativi e la cosa decolla. Non funziona così perché, se, e ritorniamo alla prima domanda, non cambia l'atteggiamento delle persone, se non cambi la mentalità, se non capisci ... Oggi c'era un bel seminario sulla sostenibilità fatto all'interno della LERU¹⁵⁴ dall'Università di Ginevra che diceva la seguente cosa, il francese diceva: quando un nostro ricercatore chiede finanziamento per il Gold open access si mette lo stesso finanziamento sul Diamond. Allora questa è una politica, noi purtroppo, e questo è l'altro problema italiano, non abbiamo politiche sulla *scientific communication*,

how to say, open access at any cost is a good thing, while instead I believe that open access at any cost cannot, should not exist. So, on the one hand, in my opinion there is certainly an attitude, pardon the term, a bit uncritical towards this phenomenon, that is, one says oh well, gosh, I have problems getting open access off the ground, now let's do the transformative agreements and the thing takes off. It doesn't work like that because, if, and let's go back to the first question, people's attitudes don't change, if you don't change their mentality, if you don't understand... Today there was a nice seminar on sustainability done within the LERU by the University of Geneva that said the following thing, the French said: when one of our researchers asks for funding for Gold open access, we put the same funding on the Diamond. So, this is a policy, unfortunately, and this is the other Italian problem, we don't have policies on *scientific communication*, so we don't have policies, we accept, we say rather uncritically what are the conditions set by the publishers and then, and this is the most serious thing, even today we don't have data. So, we don't know, the ministry doesn't know how much is spent on open access; So, these are three things that I think we should think about.

¹⁵⁴ LERU, League of European Research Universities: <https://www.leru.org/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

quindi non abbiamo politiche, accettiamo, diciamo in maniera piuttosto acritica quelle che sono le condizioni poste dagli editori e poi, e questo è la cosa più grave, ancora oggi non abbiamo dati. Quindi noi non sappiamo, il ministero non sa quanto si spende per l'accesso aperto; quindi, questi sono tre elementi su cui a mio parere si dovrebbe riflettere.

0:13:18.870 --> 0:13:19.760

R

Grazie. Senza una consapevolezza della situazione, del contesto, difficile prendere decisioni in generale, su qualunque ambito. No? OK. L'ultima domanda riporta ancora il focus sui bibliotecari, se hanno o non hanno un ruolo chiave o comunque cosa c'è nel loro prossimo futuro?

0:13:45.670 --> 0:14:20.550

K2

Tu lo sai che io rimango una bibliotecaria, ma sono uscita dalle biblioteche, quindi afferisco appunto ad altre strutture. Allora io credo che abbiano un ruolo chiave, che le competenze dei bibliotecari siano fondamentali per poter leggere quello che avviene, cioè se tu sei un bibliotecario leggi, come dire, quello che è avvenuto nell'ambito della comunicazione scientifica, anche proprio questi *merge*, questi acquisti fatti, appunto, che ne so da Elsevier che si compra il social research network, da Springer che si compra

0:13:18.870 --> 0:13:19.760

R

Thank you. Without an awareness of the situation, of the context, it is difficult to make decisions in general, in any area.

No? OK. The last question still brings back the focus on librarians, whether they have a key role or in any case what is in their near future or not?

0:13:45.670 --> 0:14:20.550

K2

You know that I remain a librarian, but I have left libraries, so I belong to other structures. So I believe that they have a key role, that the skills of librarians are fundamental to be able to read what is happening, that is, if you are a librarian you read, how to say, what has happened in the field of scientific communication, even these *merges*, these purchases made, precisely, what do I know from Elsevier that buys the social research network, from Springer buying Research Square, from Elsevier managing SciVal, etc... So if you're a librarian, in my opinion, you have, let's say, you're on a higher step, let's say, you have an advantage in reading what happens within science communication, always, in fact, assuming you want to see it, so surely then, when we are in two big alliances, one is LERU and the other is 4EU+ and within the Open science groups, because there are groups on Open science,

Research Square, da Elsevier che gestisce SciVal, eccetera... Allora se tu sei un bibliotecario secondo me hai, diciamo, sei su un gradino più alto, diciamo, hai un vantaggio nella lettura di quello che avviene all'interno della comunicazione scientifica, sempre, appunto, ammesso che tu lo voglia vedere, quindi sicuramente allora, quando noi siamo in due grosse alleanze, una è la LERU e l'altra è 4EU+¹⁵⁵ e all'interno appunto dei gruppi sull'Open science, perché ci sono proprio gruppi sull'Open science, ci stanno i direttori delle biblioteche, e ci sto io che però non sono direttore di una biblioteca, perché noi abbiamo appunto una struttura diversa. Scusa, i direttori dei sistemi bibliotecari, non i direttori delle biblioteche, e questi direttori di sistemi bibliotecari hanno sotto le mani, come dire, questo tema veramente non solo dal punto di vista economico, ma anche dal punto di vista etico, dal punto di vista tecnologico, dal punto di vista proprio dello sviluppo, dal punto di vista della valutazione, diciamo con una visione a tutto tondo, che è questo forse che un pochino da noi manca. Però certo, secondo me dovrebbero avere un ruolo fondamentale. Insomma, un ruolo fondamentale proprio nella lettura e nella possibilità appunto di leggere e di facilitare la lettura di questi fenomeni.

there are library directors, and I'm there, but I'm not the director of a library, because we have a different structure. Sorry, the directors of library systems, not the directors of libraries, and these directors of library systems have this issue on their hands, how to say, not only from an economic point of view, but also from an ethical point of view, from a technological point of view, from the point of view of development, from the point of view of evaluation, Let's say with an all-round vision, that this is perhaps what we lack a little.

But of course, in my opinion they should play a fundamental role. In short, a fundamental role in reading and in the possibility of reading and facilitating the reading of these phenomena.

0:16:25.930 --> 0:16:52.130

R

So also, to support the strategy of the university as a whole ... Other things come to mind, because the interview actually ended here, but if there are strategies that you see as possible ... because Italy has these defects in general, no, that it is always a bit scattered, it goes a little on its own this or that, there is perhaps a little more of a mental habit that accompanies us.

K2

¹⁵⁵ 4EU+European University Alliance: <https://4euplus.eu/4EU-1.html> (accessed 13 May 2024)

0:16:25.930 --> 0:16:52.130

R

Quindi anche proprio di supporto alla strategia dell'ateneo nel suo intero ... mi vengono in mente altre cose, perché le domande in realtà sono finite qua, però se ci sono delle strategie che tu vedi possibili ... perché l'Italia ha questi difetti in generale no, che è sempre un po' sparsa, va un po' per conto proprio quello o quell'altro, c'è forse un po' più un'abitudine mentale che ci accompagna.

0:16:50.710 --> 0:17:7.820

K2

Si no, allora attenzione, perché poi c'è, cioè gli inglesi che si danno così tante arie, gli irlandesi che si danno così tante arie, spendono vagonate, vagonate di fondi sui contratti trasformativi. Però, loro ce li hanno.

Quindi, come dire, per carità, non che questa cosa li giustifichi eh, però, eh, quando io, quando io vedo ecco quanto poco è finanziato da noi il Diamond e quanto tanto invece sono finanziati i trasformativi, mi dico, secondo me la Francia ha sicuramente individuato una strategia intelligente. Quindi il Green soprattutto, e poi tanto metto sul Gold, tanto metto sul Diamond. Questo, secondo me, potrebbe essere un indirizzo; l'altra cosa che è un pochino quella che stiamo facendo adesso, con un gruppo di lavoro

Yes no, then be careful, because then there is, that is, the English who give themselves so many airs, the Irish who give themselves so many airs, spend truckloads, truckloads of funds on transformative contracts. However, they have them. So, as if to say, for heaven's sake, not that this thing justifies them, eh but eh, when I see how little the Diamond is financed by us and how much the transformative ones are funded, I say to myself, in my opinion France has certainly identified an intelligent strategy. So, the Green above all, and then the more I put on the Gold, the more I put on the Diamond. This, in my opinion, could be an address; The other thing that is a little bit what we are doing now, with a working group, let's say informal, is the collection of data on open science, because our country is one of the few countries that does not have, let's say, public statistics. So, what we're trying to develop is a data collection model that we will share with all the universities as soon as possible to be able to collect the data a little bit both from the point of view of the output... These are the results, but also from an input point of view, how long did it take? Me, how much money, how much funds, how many people, etc. In short, so it is also this issue of monitoring, of becoming aware of what is there and what could be done, in my opinion is important.

diciamo informale, è la raccolta dei dati sulla scienza aperta, perché il nostro paese è uno dei pochi paesi che non ha diciamo statistiche pubbliche. Ecco quindi ehm, quello che stiamo cercando di sviluppare è proprio un modello di rilevazione dei dati che insomma, appena possibile poi condivideremo con tutte le università per potere un pochino raccogliere i dati sia dal punto di vista dell'output... questi sono i risultati, ma anche dal punto di vista dell'input, quanto ci è messo? Io, quanti soldi, quanti fondi, quante persone eccetera. Insomma, quindi è anche questo tema del monitoraggio, della presa di coscienza di quanto c'è e quanto potrebbe essere fatto, secondo me è importante.

0:18:58.50 --> 0:19:4.90

R

Grazie, grazie, mi vengono in mente altre domande, ma non so se posso ancora approfittare...

0:19:2.930 --> 0:19:6.450

K2

Sì, sì, guarda, io fino alle quattro ho tempo per cui sì, sì.

0:19:5.620 --> 0:19:30.500

R

Ah OK, allora vado anche un po' a ruota libera perché mi fa piacere. Per esempio, il Piano Nazionale per la Scienza Aperta è uscito, diciamo, ha già quasi un anno di vita. Insomma, nella sua prospettiva di

0:18:58.50 --> 0:19:4.90

R

Thank you, thank you, other questions come to mind, but I don't know if I can still take advantage of...

0:19:2.930 --> 0:19:6.450

K2

Yes, yes, look, I have time until four o'clock so yes, yes.

0:19:5.620 --> 0:19:30.500

R

Ah OK, then I'm also going to freewheel a bit because I'm pleased. For example, the National Plan for Open science is out, let's say, it's already almost a year old. In short, from the perspective of its application it should be fairly well received, right? And instead, perhaps many universities have not equipped themselves or the ministry itself, I don't know, ... What judgment, what thoughts do you have on this?

0:19:30.340 --> 0:20:0.870

K2

Yes, here too, in my opinion, we say the idea behind this working group. In short, what we have done together with this group of universities, there will be 10-12, in short, even of different sizes, to try to see what the different problems are, and it is precisely that of having, let's say, a starting point, right? So, the Open science Plan develops when you know, I start from here, otherwise if you don't know where

applicazione dovrebbe essere abbastanza recepito, no? E invece forse tanti atenei non si sono attrezzati o lo stesso ministero, non so, ... che giudizio, che pensiero hai su questo?

0:19:30.340 --> 0:20:0.870

K2

Sì, anche qui secondo me, diciamo l'idea che sta alla base di questo gruppo di lavoro. Insomma, che abbiamo fatto insieme a questo gruppo di atenei, saranno 10-12, insomma, anche di dimensioni diverse, per cercare di vedere quali sono le diverse problematiche ed è proprio quella di avere, diciamo, un punto di partenza, no? Quindi il Piano della Scienza Aperta si sviluppa nel momento in cui tu sai, parto da qui, sennò se non sai da dove parti non puoi dire dove, dove vuoi arrivare, no? In questo momento io ho l'impressione che dopo la prima fase in cui c'è stata un po' di agitazione, molti atenei dove non c'è una, diciamo una particolare consapevolezza, siano rimasti allo stesso punto, insomma, quindi lì le cose non si sviluppano, nonostante poi comunque ti arrivino le sollecitazioni dal resto d'Europa ... E devo dire però che ho visto invece che in alcuni atenei dove ehm, insomma, in un qualche modo è nata questa sensibilità, perché purtroppo veramente sono diciamo situazioni locali, cioè all'Università di Bologna, fino a che ne so due anni fa non

you're starting from, you can't say where, where you want to go, right? Now I have the impression that after the first phase in which there was a bit of agitation, many universities where there is not one, let's say a particular awareness, have remained at the same point, in short, so things are not developing there, despite the fact that you still receive requests from the rest of Europe ... And I must say, however, that I have seen instead that in some universities where, um, in short, in some way this sensitivity was born, because unfortunately they really are, let's say, local situations, that is, at the University of Bologna, as far as I know two years ago nothing was done. Now they have a delegate for Open science, they have the project on data stewards, they have ... at the CNR they have produced their plan, let's say their guidelines, in short, a plan on open science. In Trento they also have a delegate and a commission on Open science. They are doing the same thing in Turin. They did the same thing in Padua. That is, it seems to me that things that were absolutely punctiform before are now becoming, beginning to take hold. But precisely, always on the initiative of the individual institutions, that is, the ministry limited itself, let's say, to publishing the plan, but then A) it did not put money into it, B) it did not put policies into it,

si faceva niente. Adesso hanno un delegato per l'Open science, hanno il progetto sui data steward hanno ... al CNR hanno prodotto il loro piano, diciamo le loro linee guida, insomma, un piano sulla scienza aperta. A Trento anche loro hanno un delegato e una commissione sull'Open science. La stessa cosa stanno facendo a Torino. La stessa cosa hanno fatto a Padova. Cioè, mi sembra che cose che prima erano assolutamente puntiformi, adesso diventano, cominciano a prendere piede. Però appunto, sempre su iniziative delle singole Istituzioni, cioè il ministero si è limitato, diciamo, a pubblicare il piano, ma poi A) non ci ha messo soldi, B) non ci ha messo politiche, di conseguenza a queste condizioni ovviamente non puoi aspettarti di avere dei risultati. Ecco.

0:22:15.740 --> 0:22:45.140

R

Sì, non accade da sé, diciamo, non tutto accade da sé, certamente. E invece per tornare anche un po' all'esperienza che raccontavo anche l'anno scorso a GenOA Week io e altre colleghe, noi siamo, ci siamo accorti, diciamo nel bene e nel male, che i nostri ricercatori hanno cominciato a considerare il pensiero open access e non neanche open science, solo open access, in due fasi, quando abbiamo comunicato l'esistenza di trasformativi: abbiamo cercato, e anche qui ovviamente la

consequently under these conditions obviously you cannot expect to have results. Here.

0:22:15.740 --> 0:22:45.140

R

Yes, it doesn't happen by itself, let's say, not everything happens by itself, of course. And instead, to go back to the experience that I also recounted last year at GenOA Week, I and other colleagues, we are, we have realized, let's say for better or for worse, that our researchers have begun to consider open access thinking and not even open science, only open access, in two phases, one when we communicated the existence of transformative agreements: We tried, and even here obviously the difficulty was to give a correct institutional communication, I personally would not have celebrated too much, but I would have said: we would have paid this money anyway, if you want to take advantage there are these situations here. And two when we found ourselves for the VQR campaign, the last one, therefore, with the requirement of Article 8 for open access. Your thoughts on this: were they good opportunities or were they wasted opportunities? Because then we saw a lot of, how to say, difficulties, anyway, here, talking about licenses, talking about what you had done with the publisher to a researcher who, rightly, had not asked

difficoltà era dare una comunicazione istituzionale corretta, io personalmente non avrei festeggiato più di tanto, ma avrei detto: questi soldi li avremmo pagati comunque, se volete approfittare ci sono queste situazioni qua. E due quando ci siamo trovati per la campagna VQR, l'ultima, quindi, con il requisito dell'articolo 8 per l'accesso aperto. Il tuo pensiero su questo: sono state occasioni buone oppure sono state occasioni sprecate?

Perché poi abbiamo visto un sacco di, come dire, di difficoltà, comunque, ecco, parlare di licenze, parlare di che cosa avevi fatto con l'editore a un ricercatore che, giustamente, non si era posto il problema fino al giorno precedente, è diventato complicato.

0:23:30.570 --> 0:23:49.830

K2

Sì, allora questa cosa fatta ex post, allora ti devo dire che noi siamo stati l'unico ateneo che non ha riaperto le schede della VQR, cioè noi quello che era open access, lo abbiamo lasciato open access nella fase di selezione dei prodotti, ed è rimasto così, è rimasto così, quindi noi non abbiamo fatto nessun lavoro aggiuntivo. Abbiamo semplicemente guardato nel momento di selezione dei lavori che, se il file era open access che potesse che potesse essere aperto, no, quindi, che cosa è arrivato alle

himself the problem until the previous day, became complicated.

0:23:30.570 --> 0:23:49.830

K2

Yes, so this thing done ex post, then I have to tell you that we were the only university that did not reopen the VQR cards, that is, we left what was open access, we left it open access in the product selection phase, and it remained like this, it remained like this, so we did not do any additional work. We simply looked at the time of selecting the works that, if the file was open access that could be opened, no, then, what got to the institutions? In my opinion, the idea came as usual, oh well, I didn't think about it before now, then, you have to think about it, that is, in my opinion, that's not how you create, that you create awareness, right? This year we participated in this tripartite conference of EOSC, and I presented a poster on six months of training within our university. In these six months of training, we have provided more than 120 hours of training on Open science alone. In my opinion, this is the point, that is, it is necessary to put researchers in a position to know how to read phenomena: I'll give you an example. Maybe it has reached you too and anyway I will talk about it in this post that I do on ROARS, about this offer by xxxxxxxx of courses on how to make a journal, how to write a

istituzioni? Secondo me è arrivata come al solito, appunto, l'idea, vabbè, non ci ho pensato prima adesso, poi, ci devi pensare, cioè, secondo me, non è così che si crea, che si crea consapevolezza, no? Quest'anno noi abbiamo partecipato a questa conferenza tripartita di EOSC e io ho presentato un poster su sei mesi di formazione all'interno del nostro ateneo. In questi sei mesi di formazione noi abbiamo erogato più di 120 ore di formazione solo sull'Open science. Ecco secondo me, come dire, è questo il punto, cioè, è necessario mettere i ricercatori nella condizione di saper leggere i fenomeni: ti faccio un esempio. Forse sarà arrivato anche a voi e comunque ne parlerò in questo post che faccio su ROARS, di questa offerta di xxxxxxx di corsi su come si fa una rivista, come si scrive un articolo scientifico e sui trasformativi, corsi in italiano che, diciamo sono promossi dalla xxxxxxx, insieme a CRUI-CARE, e ora? Cioè, uno dice, vabbè seguo questo, diciamo una persona che non ha particolare sensibilità dice vabbè, può essere interessante. Sono un dottorando, adesso vado a seguire... a me i miei docenti della commissione, mi hanno scritto e mi hanno detto, Oh, ma cos'è 'sta cosa? Ma cosa pensa di venirci a insegnare? xxxxxxx? Cioè, è possibile che un editore venga a insegnare a me che sono ricercatore o ai miei allievi come si scrive

scientific article and on transformative, courses in Italian that, let's say are promoted by xxxxxxx, together with CRUI-CARE, and now? I mean, one says, oh well, I'll follow this, let's say a person who doesn't have any particular sensitivity says okay, it can be interesting. I'm a PhD student, now I'm going to follow... My professors on the Committee wrote to me and said, Oh, what is this thing? But what do you plan to teach us? xxxxxxx? That is, is it possible for a publisher to come and teach me, I am a researcher, or my students, how to write an article? So, in my opinion, this is what we have to get to, that is, the ability to say: things happen, but I place them, let's say in their proper context. Right now, in my opinion, we are very far from this situation.

0:26:47.150 --> 0:27:17.190

R

Thank you, I have some bitter thoughts right now... On the other hand, I have a curiosity, if you can tell me a little bit about how it works, so that such a voice can be heard, at least in the specific case of a small university like mine. The librarian's voice is the last to be heard. The librarian is a solver of practical problems, in fact he basically creates problems when he comes, if he comes at some point like this, for example, precisely in going to recover for evaluation after everything was

un articolo? Quindi, secondo me, è questo a cui si deve arrivare, cioè la capacità di dire: le cose avvengono però io le colloco, diciamo nel loro giusto contesto. Ecco, in questo momento, secondo me, siamo molto lontani da questa situazione.

0:26:47.150 --> 0:27:17.190

R

Grazie, ho dei pensieri amari in questo momento ... invece ho una curiosità, se mi puoi raccontare un po' come funziona, perché possa diciamo "prendere piede", essere ascoltata una voce del genere, almeno nel caso specifico di una piccola università come la mia. La voce del bibliotecario è l'ultima che viene ascoltata. Il bibliotecario è un risolutore di problemi spicci, anzi fondamentalmente ne crea quando si presenta, se si presenta in qualche frangente come questo, per esempio, appunto nell'andare a recuperare per la valutazione dopo che tutto era pubblicato, abbiamo creato problemi; quindi, non è che andiamo proprio con una faccia serena, non ci presentiamo come ... il nodo qual è? Raccontami perché a xxxxx avete un po' più di voce. Che cosa è successo? Ci sono strutture dedicate, siete in tanti, è trasversale, raccontami un po'.

0:27:40.250 --> 0:28:6.540

K2

Si beh, noi, appunto abbiamo questa struttura. Eh, è un pochino un'anomalia no,

published, we have created problems; So, it's not that we go right with a serene face, we don't present ourselves as... What is the knot? Tell me why at xxxxxxx, you have a little more voice. What happened? There are dedicated facilities, there are many of you, it's transversal, tell me a little bit.

0:27:40.250 --> 0:28:6.540

K2

Yes, well, we have this structure. Well, it's a bit of an anomaly, no, in the sense that we have this structure that oh well, in one way or another it's built around my skills, so obviously, that is, what I have to do between now and the moment I retire, is to try to strengthen it to such an extent that it doesn't fall apart.

The structure deals with evaluation, VQR, ASN etc ... It deals with performance and therefore also [supports] the Evaluation Unit, the Quality Assurance Committee, etc. And then it has a very substantial part that is dedicated to open science. Because I say that it is very substantial, because inside there are four people who validate the IRIS registrations, there are those who manage the archive of the research data because we have an instance of Dataverse, now there are 2, 3 or rather, research fellows, who should be trained as data stewards and ... What else is there? Well, then there's the University Press, so both books and journals, then 60 Open access

nel senso che noi abbiamo questa struttura che vabbè, in un modo o nell'altro è costruita intorno alle mie competenze, quindi ovviamente, cioè quello che io devo fare da qui al momento in cui andrò in pensione, è cercare di rafforzarla a tal punto per cui poi non mi vada in pezzi. La struttura si occupa di valutazione, VQR, ASN eccetera ... Si occupa di performance e quindi anche [supporta] il Nucleo di valutazione, il Presidio di qualità eccetera. E poi ha una parte molto consistente che è dedicata all'open science. Perché dico che è molto consistente, perché dentro ci stanno quattro persone che validano le registrazioni di IRIS, ci sta chi gestisce l'archivio dei dati della ricerca perché noi abbiamo un'istanza di Dataverse, adesso sono in arrivo 2, 3 anzi, assegnisti, che dovrebbero essere formati come data steward e ... Che altro c'è? Eh beh, poi c'è l'University Press, quindi sia libri che riviste, quindi 60 riviste open access Diamond e la University Press Open access Diamond. Quindi diciamo questo settore, insomma, è un settore piuttosto forte. Come si costruisce una reputazione? Beh, sicuramente attraverso una cosa che noi abbiamo sempre fatto con grande cura che è quella appunto di rendicontare tutto quello che facciamo, quindi attraverso testi, ma anche attraverso dati, quindi questo è un primo punto.

Diamond journals and the Open access Diamond University Press. So let's say this industry, I mean, it's a pretty strong industry. How do you build a reputation? Well, certainly through something that we have always done with great care, which is precisely to report everything we do, so through texts, but also through data, so this is a first point.

0:30:2.60 --> 0:30:33.150

K2

The appointment of a delegate for Open science was important, so let's say working side by side with this. First, she was a woman, now unfortunately she has gone to xxxxx. Now we have a male delegate too, but in short, with a good degree of awareness and so this was, it was certainly important that there was also a representative of the teaching staff. The Open science Commission was important because I'm not the one who goes to the department to tell the story. That's how it's done, that's how it is done, but it's a colleague of theirs who goes to the department and says, there's this thing, there's this other thing and so on, so we certainly say this, this mediation is done precisely by the members, we have one per department; So, it's usually an associate rather than even full professors, so they're very good at that, and they're very, very active. In short, proactive, that's it.

0:30:2.60 --> 0:30:33.150

K2

È stata importante la nomina di un delegato per l'Open science, quindi lavorare diciamo fianco a fianco con questa. Prima era una donna, adesso purtroppo è andata a xxxxx. Adesso abbiamo appunto un delegato uomo anche lui, però insomma, con un buon grado di consapevolezza e quindi questo è stato, è stato sicuramente importante il fatto che ci fosse anche un rappresentante del corpo docente. La Commissione Open science è stata importante perché non sono io che vado nel dipartimento a raccontare. Si fa così, si fa così, ma è un loro collega che va nel dipartimento e dice, c'è questa cosa, c'è quest'altra cosa eccetera, quindi sicuramente diciamo questa, questa mediazione è fatta appunto dai membri, noi ne abbiamo uno per dipartimento; quindi, di solito è un associato piuttosto che anche professori ordinari, per cui, insomma, sono molto bravi peraltro, e sono molto, molto attivi. Insomma, proattivi, ecco.

0:31:13.880 --> 0:31:14.630

R

Ho capito.

0:31:14.810 --> 0:31:39.220

K2

E sì, più o meno è questo. Poi ovviamente ti aiutano, che ne so il fatto di avere uno o due obiettivi all'interno del piano

0:31:13.880 --> 0:31:14.630

R

I understand.

0:31:14.810 --> 0:31:39.220

K2

And yes, more or less that's it. Then, of course, they help you, I don't know, the fact that they have one or two objectives within the strategic plan, which at the departmental plans must have, let's say, must somewhat reflect the objective of the university. And then I don't know if your university participates in any European alliance.

0:31:40.0 -- > 0:31:42.370

R

Eh? Purtroppo, purtroppo no.

0:31:41.640 --> 0:32:15.40

K2

Well, it is the real engine, here I have to say it really loud and clear, the participation in these alliances because both in LERU and in 4EU+ Open science has a central role and consequently, how to say, at some point in 2017 all LERU universities had a data policy and we had to run like crazy to be able to have the data policy too. And in Italy, however, we were the first at that point to have it.

0:32:15.110 --> 0:32:19.90

K2

So surely this stimulus that comes from the outside is very important.

strategico, che ai piani dei dipartimenti devono avere, diciamo, devono un po' rispecchiare l'obiettivo dell'ateneo. E poi io non so se la vostra università partecipi a qualche alleanza europea.

0:31:40.0 --> 0:31:42.370

R

Eh? Purtroppo no, purtroppo no.

0:31:41.640 --> 0:32:15.40

K2

Ecco, è il vero, vero motore, qui lo devo dire proprio chiaro e tondo, la partecipazione a queste alleanze perché sia nella LERU che in 4EU+ l'Open science ha un ruolo centrale e di conseguenza, come dire, a un certo punto nel 2017 tutte le università LERU avevano una policy sui dati e abbiamo dovuto correre come dei matti per riuscire ad avere anche noi la policy sui dati. E in Italia comunque eravamo i primi a quel punto ad averla.

0:32:15.110 --> 0:32:19.90

K2

Quindi sicuramente questo stimolo che viene dall'esterno è importantissimo.

0:32:19.240 --> 0:32:24.220

R

Giusto? Ci sono altre università partner in LERU partecipanti?

0:32:24.250 --> 0:32:51.550

K2

No, italiane no. E anche in 4EU+ no, siamo noi, però, per dire, l'Università di Bologna

0:32:19.240 --> 0:32:24.220

R

Right? Are there any other partner universities in LERU participating?

0:32:24.250 --> 0:32:51.550

K2

No, Italian no. And even in 4EU+ no, it's us, but let's say, the University of Bologna participates in the Guild, which is another, another alliance, the University of Turin participates in another alliance. So, this thing about European universities is very important because there is always a specific point about Open science.

0:32:52.230 --> 0:32:59.660

R

Well, thank you, it's a good thing, it's a nice tow. Are we saying no? Well, it has a nice function of pulling the alliance.

0:32:59.590 --> 0:33:2.410

K2

Yes, because you learn so much ... [...]

However, it is always networks and contacts that are fundamental, in short.

[...]

0:35:33.850 --> 0:36:4.340

R

We seemed to see that perhaps, with a booster effect typical of transformative agreements, being able to publish the postprint with a Creative Commons license

partecipa alla Guild, che è un'altra, un'altra alleanza, l'università di Torino partecipa ad un'altra alleanza. Quindi questa cosa delle università europee è importantissima perché proprio c'è sempre un punto specifico sull'Open science.

0:32:52.230 --> 0:32:59.660

R

Bene, grazie, è una bella cosa, è un bel traino. Diciamo no? Beh, ha una bella funzione di traino l'alleanza.

0:32:59.590 --> 0:33:2.410

K2

Sì, perché impari tantissimo ... [...] comunque sono sempre reti e contatti che sono fondamentali, insomma.

[...]

0:35:33.850 --> 0:36:4.340

R

Ci è parso di vedere che forse, con un effetto booster proprio dei trasformativi, poter pubblicare il postprint con una licenza Creative Commons è diventata una scommessa esatto, tutt'al più c'è la Creative Commons CC BY NC ND, cioè la proprio la "non creative commons" quasi ... Su questo punto un tuo parere su che cosa si può pensare? Ecco, come fare? Perché effettivamente il postprint ci speravamo, lo davamo un po' per assodato che potesse andare con Creative Commons

has become an exact bet, at most there is the Creative Commons CC BY NC ND, that is quite the "non-creative commons"

... On this point, what do you think of what can be done? Here, how to do it? Because we were actually hoping for the postprint, we took it for granted that it could go with Creative Commons where it pleased, at least after a certain time.

0:37:28.710 --> 0:37:58.550

K2

We are now implementing a feature [in the institutional repository], both with Sherpa and Unpaywall, which allows us to find the correct version with the correct license. So, this, as far as, let's say, the activity, and it will be presented shortly at the Iris Focus Group, to understand, this is certainly precisely an element that will help those who then have to work, those who have to associate the correct licenses, etc ... from an operational point of view. On the other hand, from a theoretical point of view, we certainly say, this is yet another trap of commercial publishers who obviously make things more and more complicated for you in one way, so that you necessarily go and get the other, which at this moment for them are the transformative contracts because they earn, I won't say double, for heaven's sake no, but in short, they earn more.

dove ci pareva, almeno dopo un certo tempo.

[...]

0:37:28.710 --> 0:37:58.550

K2

Noi stiamo implementando adesso una funzionalità [nell'archivio istituzionale], sia con Sherpa che con Unpaywall, che ci permette di individuare la corretta versione con la corretta licenza. Quindi questo, per quanto riguarda, diciamo l'attività, e verrà presentata peraltro a breve al Focus Group di Iris, per capire, questo è sicuramente appunto un elemento che potrà aiutare chi deve poi lavorare, chi deve associare le licenze corrette, eccetera ... dal punto di vista operativo.

Dal punto di vista invece teorico, sicuramente diciamo, questa è l'ennesima trappola degli editori commerciali che ovviamente ti rendono le cose sempre più complicate per una strada, in modo che tu necessariamente vai a prendere l'altra, che in questo momento per loro sono i contratti trasformativi perché guadagnano non dico il doppio, per carità no, però insomma guadagnano di più.

[...]

Trascrizione dell'intervista a K2.

[...] indica parti di conversazione non rilevanti rispetto al tema.

[...]

0:1:19.480 --> 0:1:41.430

R

Grazie 1000, perfetto, OK, cominciamo con le domande. Quindi penso che le avrai sotto, ma le riporto. Ovviamente possiamo parlare in italiano, sarà mia cura eventualmente, poiché la tesi sarà in lingua inglese, di fare la trascrizione e traduzione.

0:1:41.530 --> 0:1:44.970

R

le faccio in inglese, come preferisci? In realtà ecco come è per meglio per te.

0:1:43.780 --> 0:1:46.280

K2

No, no, sì, parliamo in italiano.

0:1:46.0 --> 0:1:57.260

R

OK, i trasformativi sono con noi, *do they really increase the access to the research?*, quindi veramente aumentano l'accesso alla ricerca? Qual è il loro impatto?

0:1:59.220 --> 0:2:29.550

K2

Ma, dunque, a mio parere ehm, e questo lo vedrai in un articolo, in un post che uscirà su ROARS fra un paio di giorni, a mio parere ci sono punti di vista diversi di

Transcript of the interview with K2.

[...] Indicates parts of the conversation that are not relevant to the topic.

[...]

0:1:19.480 --> 0:1:41.430

R

Thank you, perfect, OK, let's start with the questions. So, I think you'll have them underneath, but I'll bring them back. Of course, we can speak in Italian, I will take care of the transcription and translation, since the thesis will be in English.

0:1:41.530 --> 0:1:44.970

R

I do them in English, how do you prefer? Actually, here's how it's best for you.

0:1:43.780 --> 0:1:46.280

K2

No, no, yes, we speak Italian.

0:1:46.0 --> 0:1:57.260

R

OK, the transformative agreements are with us, *do they really increase the access to the research?* So, do they really increase access to research? What is their impact?

0:1:59.220 --> 0:2:29.550

K2

But, so, in my opinion um, and you'll see this in an article, in a post that will be published on ROARS in a couple of days, in my opinion there are different points of

guardare le cose. Proprio recentemente è uscita questo grido trionfante di Xxxxxxx che dice che attraverso i contratti trasformativi abbiamo raggiunto un aumento delle pubblicazioni ad accesso aperto, ovviamente non dicono a quali costi e con quali guadagni, e questa informazione diciamo deve essere letta invece con il commento che Plan S fa, che Coalition S fa del raggiungimento da parte di alcuni editori di un ipotetico target annuale che invece boccia solennemente Xxxxxxx. Quindi, secondo me, allora in primo luogo dipende da chi ne parla e dal punto di vista e questo è un classico esempio per cui la stessa informazione viene guardata, diciamo da due punti di partenza diversi e quindi dà risultati assolutamente opposti. Ecco, quindi, io credo che questa cosa dei contratti trasformativi faccia un pochino parte di quel processo di *trials and errors* che la scienza attraversa e quindi anche gli strumenti, diciamo di appoggio alla scienza attraversano questo è sicuramente un trial che è stato fatto. È un errore che a mio parere si sta rivelando tale se no appunto adesso non ci sarebbe tutta questa enfasi sul Diamond eccetera... e quindi ehm, diciamo se devo dire ... hanno avuto successo?, a mio parere no, nel senso che, se l'obiettivo era quello di attivare un *cultural change*, il ricercatore medio,

view to look at things. Just recently this triumphant cry came out from Xxxxxxx saying that through transformative agreements we have achieved an increase in open access publications, obviously they do not say at what cost and with what gains, and this information we say must be read instead with the comment that Plan S makes, that Coalition S makes of the achievement by some publishers of a hypothetical annual target that instead solemnly rejects Xxxxxxx. So, in my opinion, then in the first place it depends on who is talking about it and the point of view, and this is a classic example where the same information is looked at, let's say from two different starting points and therefore gives absolutely opposite results. So, I think that these of transformative agreements is a little bit part of that process of *trials and errors* that science goes through and therefore also the tools, let's say supporting science, go through this is definitely a trial that has been done. It's a mistake that, in my opinion, is turning out to be a mistake, otherwise there wouldn't be all this emphasis on the Diamond and so on... And so, uhm, let's say if I have to say... Have they been successful?, in my opinion not, in the sense that, if the goal was to activate a cultural change, the average researcher, the one who goes to the Xxxxxxx website that

quello che va sul sito di Xxxxxxxx che gli ha approvato l'articolo e che sceglie l'open access, non capisce in che ambito sta lavorando, chi paga e che cosa, quindi non c'è un *cultural change*. Se l'obiettivo era, rendiamo, diciamo, i processi di ricerca più trasparenti: questa trasparenza manca perché io non so per che cosa pago e quanto pago, perché i contratti sono secretati, hanno vincoli di riservatezza e quant'altro. Io non metterei questa voce, neppure fra le voci dell'Open science, cioè, secondo me, è l'ennesima, l'ennesimo trucco, l'ennesimo, l'ennesimo processo attraverso il quale gli editori sostanzialmente sfruttano le istituzioni. Quindi questo. Io ho una visione molto negativa e devo dire che trovo molto responsabile, molto responsabile l'atteggiamento francese che rispetto a questi contratti trasformativi ha tenuto proprio una posizione totalmente...

0:5:39.610 --> 0:5:40.480

R

...Sfavorevole?

0:5:39.190 --> 0:5:47.270

K2

Totalmente immaginaria, coerente con un unico contratto trasformativo per ora e basta. Insomma, questa cosa, peraltro, ecco un attimo, quindi questo per quanto riguarda i possibili vantaggi che io non vedo, mentre invece quali sono, qual è

approved the article and who chooses open access, does not understand in which field he is working, who pays and what, so there is no cultural change. If the goal was, let's say, let's make the research processes more transparent: this transparency is lacking because I don't know what I pay for and how much I pay, because the agreements are classified, have confidentiality constraints and so on. I wouldn't put this entry, not even among the voices of Open science, that is, in my opinion, it's the umpteenth, the umpteenth trick, the umpteenth, the umpteenth process through which publishers basically exploit institutions. So, this. I have a very negative view and I must say that I find very responsible, very responsible the French attitude that with respect to these transformative agreements has held a totally ...

0:5:39.610 --> 0:5:40.480

R

... Unfavourable?

0:5:39.190 --> 0:5:47.270

K2

Totally imaginary, coherent with a single transformative agreement for now and that's it. In short, this thing, by the way, here is a moment, so this as far as the possible advantages are concerned, which I do not see, while what are they, what is the impact? We would like to measure the

l'impatto? L'impatto ci piacerebbe misurarlo. È sicuramente un impatto economico consistente, è un peccato, appunto, che questa cosa non sia minimamente misurabile, perché con i dati alla mano, forse chi poi deve prendere decisioni magari avrebbe un atteggiamento più responsabile.

0:6:26.630 --> 0:6:29.680

R

Grazie, OK, grazie.

0:6:31.170 --> 0:6:52.860

R

Allora procediamo con la successiva, *What's next?* I trasformativi hanno punti di forza e di debolezza, diciamo per un equilibrio doveroso nell'indagine cerchiamo entrambi e come possono i trasformativi essere *fair and sustainable*, quindi essere diciamo ecco giusti, in un certo senso e sostenibili.

0:6:52.100 --> 0:7:21.840

K2

Certo, certo beh, l'idea iniziale che diciamo questi contratti fossero *cost neutral*, non era affatto sbagliata, no? Quindi l'idea che nel sistema c'è una certa quantità di soldi quantificata, 10 miliardi o quello che è; quindi, nel sistema ci sono fondi a sufficienza. L'idea è quella di spostare questi 10 miliardi dal *pay per read* al *pay per publish*.

impact. It is certainly a substantial economic impact, it is a pity, in fact, that this thing is not in the least measurable, because with the data in hand, perhaps those who then have to make decisions would perhaps have a more responsible attitude.

0:6:26.630 --> 0:6:29.680

R

Thank you, OK, thank you.

0:6:31.170 --> 0:6:52.860

R

So, let's proceed with the next one, *What's next?* Transformative agreements have strengths and weaknesses, let's say for a dutiful balance in the investigation we look for both and how can TAs *be fair and sustainable*, so be let's say that's right, in a sense and sustainable.

0:6:52.100 --> 0:7:21.840

K2

Sure, of course, well, the initial idea that we say these agreements were *cost neutral*, it wasn't wrong at all, was it? So, the idea that there's a certain amount of quantified money in the system, \$10 billion or whatever; So, there are enough funds in the system. The idea is to move these 10 billion from pay per read to pay per publish.

0:7:28.840 --> 0:7:43.170

K2

0:7:28.840 --> 0:7:43.170

K2

E questa cosa, appunto, non è stata. Non ha avuto poi questo tipo di traduzione. Perché proprio oggi insomma vedevo ecco l'altro svantaggio, attenzione, è che sono tutti piuttosto farraginosi, per cui alcuni hanno riviste sì, riviste no, questa sta dentro, questa sta fuori, questo e questo elenco, questo un altro elenco, cioè, è il caos veramente per un ricercatore che volesse anche cercare di capire qualcosa, secondo me è scoraggiante.

0:8:8.480 --> 0:8:12.530

K2

Eh quindi Eh, dunque no, la domanda era.

0:8:14.990 --> 0:8:17.830

K2

Forza e debolezza quindi? Il punto, il punto di forza.

0:8:13.200 --> 0:8:18.550

R

Se ci sono punti di forza e debolezza, se ci sono, e se c'è sostenibilità.

0:8:18.710 --> 0:8:29.500

K2

Ecco il punto di forza, secondo me avrebbe dovuto essere questa neutralità, no? Quindi trasformo tutto quello che io pago per leggere in contributo per pubblicare, questa cosa non è avvenuta in questo modo; quindi, quello che era nato come punto di forza si è dimostrato poi un punto di

And this was not. He didn't have that kind of translation. Because just today I saw the other disadvantage, be careful, is that they are all quite cumbersome, so some have journals yes, journals no, this one is inside, this is outside, this and this list, this another list, that is, it's really chaos for a researcher who also wants to try to understand something, in my opinion it's discouraging.

0:8:8.480 --> 0:8:12.530

K2

Eh so, so, no, the question was.

0:8:14.990 --> 0:8:17.830

K2

Strength and weakness then? The point, the strength.

0:8:13.200 --> 0:8:18.550

R

If there are strengths and weaknesses, if there are, and if there is sustainability.

0:8:18.710 --> 0:8:29.500

K2

Here's the strong point, in my opinion it should have been this neutrality, right? So, I turn everything I pay to read into a contribution to publish, this thing didn't happen that way; So, what started out as a strength turned out to be a weakness, because in fact the system costs more. Sustainability, in my opinion, is not there, that is, medium-term sustainability should be lacking. Because precisely, as we see

debolezza, perché di fatto il sistema costa di più. La sostenibilità, secondo me, non c'è, cioè la sostenibilità a medio termine dovrebbe venir meno. Perché appunto, a mano a mano che vediamo allungarsi la lista di questi contratti trasformativi sempre più costosi, sempre più con periodi anche piuttosto lunghi e con condizioni diciamo molto, molto miste, molto anche diverse l'uno dall'altra, secondo me, diciamo, non è sostenibile nel medio.

0:9:27.510 --> 0:9:28.120

R

Breve?

0:9:25.110 --> 0:9:41.560

K2

Nel medio periodo ..., nel breve, nel breve termine, nel medio e lungo termine assolutamente no, tanto è vero che appunto Coalition S che li aveva promossi all'inizio ha detto appunto alla fine del 2024 basta!, insomma, o sei dentro o sei fuori.

0:9:42.770 --> 0:9:43.490

R

Esatto.

0:9:47.450 --> 0:9:58.330

R

Arrivo scusi Eh... mi provo, provo scusami, provo a segnare anche delle note per tenere traccia, poi quando riascolterò e riscriverò soprattutto, grazie davvero, molto chiaro tutto quanto. Grazie veramente, allora in Italia come gli enti di

the list of these increasingly expensive transformative agreements getting longer, more and more with periods that are also quite long and with very, very mixed conditions, very different from each other, in my opinion we say it is not sustainable in the medium term.

0:9:27.510 --> 0:9:28.120

R

Short?

0:9:25.110 --> 0:9:41.560

K2 In the medium term ..., in the short, short term, medium and long term absolutely not, so much so that Coalition S that had promoted them at the beginning said precisely at the end of 2024 it's enough!, in short, either you are in or you are out.

0:9:42.770 --> 0:9:43.490

R

That's right.

0:9:47.450 --> 0:9:58.330

R

Excuse me, I am trying to make some notes to keep track, then when I'll listen again and rewrite above all, thank you very much, everything is very clear. Thank you truly, then in Italy as research institutions, authors and librarians are facing the challenges in academic communication brought by transformative agreements, If they are talented, if they are challenges, in short, well, you can discuss this.

ricerca, gli autori e i bibliotecari stanno ponendosi davanti alle sfide nella comunicazione accademica portate dai trasformativi. Se sono portate, se sfide sono insomma, ecco, questo lo puoi ridiscutere.

0:10:28.370 --> 0:10:43.700

K2

A mio parere e ci sono due elementi: da un lato, ma questo francamente non è solamente delle comunità italiane, o meglio ... non so se hai colto i commenti di alcune di alcune figure al contratto di XXXXXXXX che è stato concluso in Germania. E allora i commenti sono molto negativi, però non arrivano. Non arrivano dalle biblioteche. Ecco, io ho l'impressione che le biblioteche, nell'ottica dell'offrire un servizio ai propri utenti pensino che, come dire, l'open access a qualsiasi costo sia una buona cosa, mentre invece io credo che l'open access a qualsiasi costo non possa, non debba esistere. Quindi da un lato, secondo me c'è sicuramente un atteggiamento, passami il termine, un po' acritico nei confronti di questo fenomeno, cioè uno dice vabbè, caspita, ho dei problemi a far decollare l'open access, adesso facciamo i trasformativi e la cosa decolla. Non funziona così perché, se, e ritorniamo alla prima domanda, non cambia l'atteggiamento delle persone, se non cambi la mentalità, se non capisci ...

0:10:28.370 --> 0:10:43.700

K2

In my opinion and there are two elements: on the one hand, but frankly this is not only of the Italian communities, or rather ... I don't know if you have picked up on the comments of some of the figures on the XXXXXXXX agreement that was concluded in Germany. And then the comments are very negative, but they don't come. They don't come from libraries. Well, I have the impression that libraries, with a view to offering a service to their users, think that, how to say, open access at any cost is a good thing, while instead I believe that open access at any cost cannot, should not exist. So, on the one hand, in my opinion there is certainly an attitude, pardon the term, a bit uncritical towards this phenomenon, that is, one says oh well, gosh, I have problems getting open access off the ground, now let's do the transformative agreements and the thing takes off. It doesn't work like that because, if, and let's go back to the first question, people's attitudes don't change, if you don't change their mentality, if you don't understand... Today there was a nice seminar on sustainability done within the XXXXXXXX by the University of Geneva that said the following thing, the French said: when one of our researchers asks for funding for Gold open access, we

Oggi c'era un bel seminario sulla sostenibilità fatto all'interno della XXXXXXXX dall'Università di Ginevra che diceva la seguente cosa, il francese diceva: quando un nostro ricercatore chiede finanziamento per il Gold open access si mette lo stesso finanziamento sul Diamond. Allora questa è una politica, noi purtroppo, e questo è l'altro problema italiano, non abbiamo politiche sulla *scientific communication*, quindi non abbiamo politiche, accettiamo, diciamo in maniera piuttosto acritica quelle che sono le condizioni poste dagli editori e poi, e questo è la cosa più grave, ancora oggi non abbiamo dati. Quindi noi non sappiamo, il ministero non sa quanto si spende per l'accesso aperto; quindi, questi sono tre elementi su cui a mio parere si dovrebbe riflettere.

0:13:18.870 --> 0:13:19.760

R

Grazie. Senza una consapevolezza della situazione, del contesto, difficile prendere decisioni in generale, su qualunque ambito. No? OK. L'ultima domanda riporta ancora il focus sui bibliotecari, se hanno o non hanno un ruolo chiave o comunque cosa c'è nel loro prossimo futuro?

0:13:45.670 --> 0:14:20.550

K2

Tu lo sai che io rimango una bibliotecaria, ma sono uscita dalle biblioteche, quindi

put the same funding on the Diamond. So, this is a policy, unfortunately, and this is the other Italian problem, we don't have policies on *scientific communication*, so we don't have policies, we accept, we say rather uncritically what are the conditions set by the publishers and then, and this is the most serious thing, even today we don't have data. So, we don't know, the ministry doesn't know how much is spent on open access; So, these are three things that I think we should think about.

0:13:18.870 --> 0:13:19.760

R

Thank you. Without an awareness of the situation, of the context, it is difficult to make decisions in general, in any area.

No? OK. The last question still brings back the focus on librarians, whether they have a key role or in any case what is in their near future or not?

0:13:45.670 --> 0:14:20.550

K2

You know that I remain a librarian, but I have left libraries, so I belong to other structures. So I believe that they have a key role, that the skills of librarians are fundamental to be able to read what is happening, that is, if you are a librarian you read, how to say, what has happened in the field of scientific communication, even these *merges*, these purchases made, precisely, what do I know from XXXXXXXX

afferisco appunto ad altre strutture. Allora io credo che abbiano un ruolo chiave, che le competenze dei bibliotecari siano fondamentali per poter leggere quello che avviene, cioè se tu sei un bibliotecario leggi, come dire, quello che è avvenuto nell'ambito della comunicazione scientifica, anche proprio questi *merge*, questi acquisti fatti, appunto, che ne so da Xxxxxxx che si compra il social research network, da Xxxxxxx che si compra xxxxxxxxxxx, da Xxxxxxx che gestisce xxxxxxx, eccetera... Allora se tu sei un bibliotecario secondo me hai, diciamo, sei su un gradino più alto, diciamo, hai un vantaggio nella lettura di quello che avviene all'interno della comunicazione scientifica, sempre, appunto, ammesso che tu lo voglia vedere, quindi sicuramente allora, quando noi siamo in due grosse alleanze, una è la XXXXXXXX e l'altra è xxxxxxxxxxx e all'interno appunto dei gruppi sull'Open science, perché ci sono proprio gruppi sull'Open science, ci stanno i direttori delle biblioteche, e ci sto io che però non sono direttore di una biblioteca, perché noi abbiamo appunto una struttura diversa. Scusa, i direttori dei sistemi bibliotecari, non i direttori delle biblioteche, e questi direttori di sistemi bibliotecari hanno sotto le mani, come dire, questo tema veramente non solo dal punto di vista economico, ma anche dal punto di

that buys the social research network, from Xxxxxxx buying xxxxxxxxxxx, from Xxxxxxx managing xxxxxx, etc... So if you're a librarian, in my opinion, you have, let's say, you're on a higher step, let's say, you have an advantage in reading what happens within science communication, always, in fact, assuming you want to see it, so surely then, when we are in two big alliances, one is XXXXXXXX and the other is xxxxxxxxxxx and within the Open science groups, because there are groups on Open science, there are library directors, and I'm there, but I'm not the director of a library, because we have a different structure. Sorry, the directors of library systems, not the directors of libraries, and these directors of library systems have this issue on their hands, how to say, not only from an economic point of view, but also from an ethical point of view, from a technological point of view, from the point of view of development, from the point of view of evaluation, Let's say with an all-round vision, that this is perhaps what we lack a little.

But of course, in my opinion they should play a fundamental role. In short, a fundamental role in reading and in the possibility of reading and facilitating the reading of these phenomena.

0:16:25.930 --> 0:16:52.130

vista etico, dal punto di vista tecnologico, dal punto di vista proprio dello sviluppo, dal punto di vista della valutazione, diciamo con una visione a tutto tondo, che è questo forse che un pochino da noi manca.

Però certo, secondo me dovrebbero avere un ruolo fondamentale. Insomma, un ruolo fondamentale proprio nella lettura e nella possibilità appunto di leggere e di facilitare la lettura di questi fenomeni.

0:16:25.930 --> 0:16:52.130

R

Quindi anche proprio di supporto alla strategia dell'ateneo nel suo intero ... mi vengono in mente altre cose, perché le domande in realtà sono finite qua, però se ci sono delle strategie che tu vedi possibili ... perché l'Italia ha questi difetti in generale no, che è sempre un po' sparsa, va un po' per conto proprio quello o quell'altro, c'è forse un po' più un'abitudine mentale che ci accompagna.

0:16:50.710 --> 0:17:7.820

K2

Si no, allora attenzione, perché poi c'è, cioè gli inglesi che si danno così tante arie, gli irlandesi che si danno così tante arie, spendono vagonate, vagonate di fondi sui contratti trasformativi. Però, loro ce li hanno.

Quindi, come dire, per carità, non che questa cosa li giustifichi eh, però, eh,

R

So also, to support the strategy of the university as a whole ... Other things come to mind, because the interview actually ended here, but if there are strategies that you see as possible ... because Italy has these defects in general, no, that it is always a bit scattered, it goes a little on its own this or that, there is perhaps a little more of a mental habit that accompanies us.

0:16:50.710 --> 0:17:7.820

K2

Yes no, then be careful, because then there is, that is, the English who give themselves so many airs, the Irish who give themselves so many airs, spend truckloads, truckloads of funds on transformative agreements. However, they have them. So, as if to say, for heaven's sake, not that this thing justifies them, eh but eh, when I see how little the Diamond is financed by us and how much the transformative ones are funded, I say to myself, in my opinion France has certainly identified an intelligent strategy. So, the Green above all, and then the more I put on the Gold, the more I put on the Diamond. This, in my opinion, could be an address; The other thing that is a little bit what we are doing now, with a working group, let's say informal, is the collection of data on open science, because our country is one of the

quando io, quando io vedo ecco quanto poco è finanziato da noi il Diamond e quanto tanto invece sono finanziati i trasformativi, mi dico, secondo me la Francia ha sicuramente individuato una strategia intelligente. Quindi il Green soprattutto, e poi tanto metto sul Gold, tanto metto sul Diamond. Questo, secondo me, potrebbe essere un indirizzo; l'altra cosa che è un pochino quella che stiamo facendo adesso, con un gruppo di lavoro diciamo informale, è la raccolta dei dati sulla scienza aperta, perché il nostro paese è uno dei pochi paesi che non ha diciamo statistiche pubbliche. Ecco quindi ehm, quello che stiamo cercando di sviluppare è proprio un modello di rilevazione dei dati che insomma, appena possibile poi condivideremo con tutte le università per potere un pochino raccogliere i dati sia dal punto di vista dell'output... questi sono i risultati, ma anche dal punto di vista dell'input, quanto ci è messo? Io, quanti soldi, quanti fondi, quante persone eccetera. Insomma, quindi è anche questo tema del monitoraggio, della presa di coscienza di quanto c'è e quanto potrebbe essere fatto, secondo me è importante.

0:18:58.50 --> 0:19:4.90

R

Grazie, grazie, mi vengono in mente altre domande, ma non so se posso ancora approfittare...

few countries that does not have, let's say, public statistics. So, what we're trying to develop is a data collection model that we will share with all the universities as soon as possible to be able to collect the data a little bit both from the point of view of the output... These are the results, but also from an input point of view, how long did it take? Me, how much money, how much funds, how many people, etc. In short, so it is also this issue of monitoring, of becoming aware of what is there and what could be done, in my opinion is important.

0:18:58.50 --> 0:19:4.90

R

Thank you, thank you, other questions come to mind, but I don't know if I can still take advantage of...

0:19:2.930 --> 0:19:6.450

K2

Yes, yes, look, I have time until four o'clock so yes, yes.

0:19:5.620 --> 0:19:30.500

R

Ah OK, then I'm also going to freewheel a bit because I'm pleased. For example, the National Plan for Open science is out, let's say, it's already almost a year old. In short, from the perspective of its application it should be fairly well received, right? And instead, perhaps many universities have not equipped themselves or the ministry

0:19:2.930 --> 0:19:6.450

K2

Sì, sì, guarda, io fino alle quattro ho tempo per cui sì, sì.

0:19:5.620 --> 0:19:30.500

R

Ah OK, allora vado anche un po' a ruota libera perché mi fa piacere. Per esempio, il Piano Nazionale per la Scienza Aperta è uscito, diciamo, ha già quasi un anno di vita. Insomma, nella sua prospettiva di applicazione dovrebbe essere abbastanza recepito, no? E invece forse tanti atenei non si sono attrezzati o lo stesso ministero, non so, ... che giudizio, che pensiero hai su questo?

0:19:30.340 --> 0:20:0.870

K2

Sì, anche qui secondo me, diciamo l'idea che sta alla base di questo gruppo di lavoro. Insomma, che abbiamo fatto insieme a questo gruppo di atenei, saranno 10-12, insomma, anche di dimensioni diverse, per cercare di vedere quali sono le diverse problematiche ed è proprio quella di avere, diciamo, un punto di partenza, no? Quindi il Piano della Scienza Aperta si sviluppa nel momento in cui tu sai, parto da qui, sennò se non sai da dove parti non puoi dire dove, dove vuoi arrivare, no? In questo momento io ho l'impressione che dopo la prima fase in cui c'è stata un po' di agitazione, molti atenei dove non c'è una,

itself, I don't know, ... What judgment, what thoughts do you have on this?

0:19:30.340 --> 0:20:0.870

K2

Yes, here too, in my opinion, we say the idea behind this working group. In short, what we have done together with this group of universities, there will be 10-12, in short, even of different sizes, to try to see what the different problems are, and it is precisely that of having, let's say, a starting point, right? So, the Open science Plan develops when you know, I start from here, otherwise if you don't know where you're starting from, you can't say where, where you want to go, right? Now I have the impression that after the first phase in which there was a bit of agitation, many universities where there is not one, let's say a particular awareness, have remained at the same point, in short, so things are not developing there, despite the fact that you still receive requests from the rest of Europe ... And I must say, however, that I have seen instead that in some universities where, um, in short, in some way this sensitivity was born, because unfortunately they really are, let's say, local situations, that is, at the University of XXXXXXXX, as far as I know two years ago nothing was done. Now they have a delegate for Open science, they have the project on data stewards, they have ... at the CNR they

diciamo una particolare consapevolezza, siano rimasti allo stesso punto, insomma, quindi lì le cose non si sviluppano, nonostante poi comunque ti arrivino le sollecitazioni dal resto d'Europa ... E devo dire però che ho visto invece che in alcuni atenei dove ehm, insomma, in un qualche modo è nata questa sensibilità, perché purtroppo veramente sono diciamo situazioni locali, cioè all'Università di XXXXXXXX, fino a che ne so due anni fa non si faceva niente. Adesso hanno un delegato per l'Open science, hanno il progetto sui data steward hanno ... al CNR hanno prodotto il loro piano, diciamo le loro linee guida, insomma, un piano sulla scienza aperta. A XXXXXXXX anche loro hanno un delegato e una commissione sull'Open science. La stessa cosa stanno facendo a XXXXXXXX. La stessa cosa hanno fatto a XXXXXXXX. Cioè, mi sembra che cose che prima erano assolutamente puntiformi, adesso diventano, cominciano a prendere piede. Però appunto, sempre su iniziative delle singole Istituzioni, cioè il ministero si è limitato, diciamo, a pubblicare il piano, ma poi A) non ci ha messo soldi, B) non ci ha messo politiche, di conseguenza a queste condizioni ovviamente non puoi aspettarti di avere dei risultati. Ecco.

0:22:15.740 --> 0:22:45.140

R

Sì, non accade da sé, diciamo, non tutto

have produced their plan, let's say their guidelines, in short, a plan on open science. In XXXXXXXX they also have a delegate and a commission on Open science. They are doing the same thing in XXXXXXXX. They did the same thing in XXXXXXXX. That is, it seems to me that things that were absolutely punctiform before are now becoming, beginning to take hold. But precisely, always on the initiative of the individual institutions, that is, the ministry limited itself, let's say, to publishing the plan, but then A) it did not put money into it, B) it did not put policies into it, consequently under these conditions obviously you cannot expect to have results. Here.

0:22:15.740 --> 0:22:45.140

R

Yes, it doesn't happen by itself, let's say, not everything happens by itself, of course. And instead, to go back to the experience that I also recounted last year at GenOA Week, I and other colleagues, we are, we have realized, let's say for better or for worse, that our researchers have begun to consider open access thinking and not even open science, only open access, in two phases, one when we communicated the existence of transformative agreements: We tried, and even here obviously the difficulty was to give a correct institutional communication, I personally would not

accade da sé, certamente. E invece per tornare anche un po' all'esperienza che raccontavo anche l'anno scorso a GenOA Week io e altre colleghe, noi siamo, ci siamo accorti, diciamo nel bene e nel male, che i nostri ricercatori hanno cominciato a considerare il pensiero open access e non neanche open science, solo open access, in due fasi, quando abbiamo comunicato l'esistenza di trasformativi: abbiamo cercato, e anche qui ovviamente la difficoltà era dare una comunicazione istituzionale corretta, io personalmente non avrei festeggiato più di tanto, ma avrei detto: questi soldi li avremmo pagati comunque, se volete approfittare ci sono queste situazioni qua. E due quando ci siamo trovati per la campagna VQR, l'ultima, quindi, con il requisito dell'articolo 8 per l'accesso aperto. Il tuo pensiero su questo: sono state occasioni buone oppure sono state occasioni sprecate?

Perché poi abbiamo visto un sacco di, come dire, di difficoltà, comunque, ecco, parlare di licenze, parlare di che cosa avevi fatto con l'editore a un ricercatore che, giustamente, non si era posto il problema fino al giorno precedente, è diventato complicato.

0:23:30.570 --> 0:23:49.830

K2

Sì, allora questa cosa fatta ex post, allora ti

have celebrated too much, but I would have said: we would have paid this money anyway, if you want to take advantage there are these situations here. And two when we found ourselves for the VQR campaign, the last one, therefore, with the requirement of Article 8 for open access. Your thoughts on this: were they good opportunities or were they wasted opportunities? Because then we saw a lot of, how to say, difficulties, anyway, here, talking about licenses, talking about what you had done with the publisher to a researcher who, rightly, had not asked himself the problem until the previous day, became complicated.

0:23:30.570 --> 0:23:49.830

K2

Yes, so this thing done ex post, then I have to tell you that we were the only university that did not reopen the VQR cards, that is, we left what was open access, we left it open access in the product selection phase, and it remained like this, it remained like this, so we did not do any additional work. We simply looked at the time of selecting the works that, if the file was open access that could be opened, no, then, what got to the institutions? In my opinion, the idea came as usual, oh well, I didn't think about it before now, then, you have to think about it, that is, in my opinion, that's not how you create, that you create awareness,

devo dire che noi siamo stati l'unico ateneo che non ha riaperto le schede della VQR, cioè noi quello che era open access, lo abbiamo lasciato open access nella fase di selezione dei prodotti, ed è rimasto così, è rimasto così, quindi noi non abbiamo fatto nessun lavoro aggiuntivo. Abbiamo semplicemente guardato nel momento di selezione dei lavori che, se il file era open access che potesse che potesse essere aperto, no, quindi, che cosa è arrivato alle istituzioni? Secondo me è arrivata come al solito, appunto, l'idea, vabbè, non ci ho pensato prima adesso, poi, ci devi pensare, cioè, secondo me, non è così che si crea, che si crea consapevolezza, no? Quest'anno noi abbiamo partecipato a questa conferenza tripartita di EOSC e io ho presentato un poster su sei mesi di formazione all'interno del nostro ateneo. In questi sei mesi di formazione noi abbiamo erogato più di 120 ore di formazione solo sull'Open science. Ecco secondo me, come dire, è questo il punto, cioè, è necessario mettere i ricercatori nella condizione di saper leggere i fenomeni: ti faccio un esempio. Forse sarà arrivato anche a voi e comunque ne parlerò in questo post che faccio su ROARS, di questa offerta di xxxxxxxx di corsi su come si fa una rivista, come si scrive un articolo scientifico e sui trasformativi, corsi in italiano che, diciamo sono promossi dalla xxxxxxxx, insieme a

right? This year we participated in this tripartite conference of EOSC, and I presented a poster on six months of training within our university. In these six months of training, we have provided more than 120 hours of training on Open science alone. In my opinion, this is the point, that is, it is necessary to put researchers in a position to know how to read phenomena: I'll give you an example. Maybe it has reached you too and anyway I will talk about it in this post that I do on ROARS, about this offer by xxxxxxxx of courses on how to make a journal, how to write a scientific article and on transformative, courses in Italian that, let's say are promoted by xxxxxxxx, together with CRUI-CARE, and now? I mean, one says, oh well, I'll follow this, let's say a person who doesn't have any particular sensitivity says okay, it can be interesting. I'm a PhD student, now I'm going to follow... My professors on the Committee wrote to me and said, Oh, what is this thing? But what do you plan to teach us? xxxxxxxx? That is, is it possible for a publisher to come and teach me, I am a researcher, or my students, how to write an article? So, in my opinion, this is what we have to get to, that is, the ability to say: things happen, but I place them, let's say in their proper context. Right now, in my opinion, we are very far from this situation.

CRUI-CARE, e ora? Cioè, uno dice, vabbè
seguo questo, diciamo una persona che non
ha particolare sensibilità dice vabbè, può
essere interessante. Sono un dottorando,
adesso vado a seguire... a me i miei
docenti della commissione, mi hanno
scritto e mi hanno detto, Oh, ma cos'è 'sta
cosa? Ma cosa pensa di venirci a
insegnare? xxxxxxxx? Cioè, è possibile che
un editore venga a insegnare a me che sono
ricercatore o ai miei allievi come si scrive
un articolo? Quindi, secondo me, è questo
a cui si deve arrivare, cioè la capacità di
dire: le cose avvengono però io le colloco,
diciamo nel loro giusto contesto. Ecco, in
questo momento, secondo me, siamo molto
lontani da questa situazione.

0:26:47.150 --> 0:27:17.190

R

Grazie, ho dei pensieri amari in questo
momento ... invece ho una curiosità, se mi
puoi raccontare un po' come funziona,
perché possa diciamo "prendere piede",
essere ascoltata una voce del genere,
almeno nel caso specifico di una piccola
università come la mia. La voce del
bibliotecario è l'ultima che viene ascoltata.
Il bibliotecario è un risolutore di problemi
spicci, anzi fondamentalmente ne crea
quando si presenta, se si presenta in
qualche frangente come questo, per
esempio, appunto nell'andare a recuperare
per la valutazione dopo che tutto era

0:26:47.150 --> 0:27:17.190

R

Thank you, I have some bitter thoughts
right now... On the other hand, I have a
curiosity, if you can tell me a little bit
about how it works, so that such a voice
can be heard, at least in the specific case of
a small university like mine. The
librarian's voice is the last to be heard. The
librarian is a solver of practical problems,
in fact he basically creates problems when
he comes, if he comes at some point like
this, for example, precisely in going to
recover for evaluation after everything was
published, we have created problems; So,
it's not that we go right with a serene face,
we don't present ourselves as... What is the
knot? Tell me why at xxxxxxxx, you have a
little more voice. What happened? There
are dedicated facilities, there are many of
you, it's transversal, tell me a little bit.

0:27:40.250 --> 0:28:6.540

K2

Yes, well, we have this structure. Well, it's
a bit of an anomaly, no, in the sense that
we have this structure that oh well, in one
way or another it's built around my skills,
so obviously, that is, what I have to do
between now and the moment I retire, is to
try to strengthen it to such an extent that it
doesn't fall apart.

The structure deals with evaluation, VQR,
ASN etc ... It deals with performance and

pubblicato, abbiamo creato problemi;
quindi, non è che andiamo proprio con una
faccia serena, non ci presentiamo come ...
il nodo qual è? Raccontami perché a xxxxx
avete un po' più di voce. Che cosa è
successo? Ci sono strutture dedicate, siete
in tanti, è trasversale, raccontami un po'.
0:27:40.250 --> 0:28:6.540

K2

Si beh, noi, appunto abbiamo questa
struttura. Eh, è un pochino un'anomalia no,
nel senso che noi abbiamo questa struttura
che vabbè, in un modo o nell'altro è
costruita intorno alle mie competenze,
quindi ovviamente, cioè quello che io devo
fare da qui al momento in cui andrò in
pensione, è cercare di rafforzarla a tal
punto per cui poi non mi vada in pezzi.
La struttura si occupa di valutazione, VQR,
ASN eccetera ... Si occupa di performance
e quindi anche [supporta] il Nucleo di
valutazione, il Presidio di qualità eccetera.
E poi ha una parte molto consistente che è
dedicata all'open science. Perché dico che è
molto consistente, perché dentro ci stanno
quattro persone che validano le
registrazioni di IRIS, ci sta chi gestisce
l'archivio dei dati della ricerca perché noi
abbiamo un'istanza di Dataverse, adesso
sono in arrivo 2, 3 anzi, assegnisti, che
dovrebbero essere formati come data
steward e ... Che altro c'è? Eh beh, poi c'è
l'University Press, quindi sia libri che

therefore also [supports] the Evaluation
Unit, the Quality Assurance Committee,
etc. And then it has a very substantial part
that is dedicated to open science. Because I
say that it is very substantial, because
inside there are four people who validate
the IRIS registrations, there are those who
manage the archive of the research data
because we have an instance of Dataverse,
now there are 2, 3 or rather, research
fellows, who should be trained as data
stewards and ... What else is there? Well,
then there's the University Press, so both
books and journals, then 60 Open access
Diamond journals and the Open access
Diamond University Press. So let's say this
industry, I mean, it's a pretty strong
industry. How do you build a reputation?
Well, certainly through something that we
have always done with great care, which is
precisely to report everything we do, so
through texts, but also through data, so this
is a first point.

0:30:2.60 --> 0:30:33.150

K2

The appointment of a delegate for Open
science was important, so let's say working
side by side with this. First, she was a
woman, now unfortunately she has gone to
xxxxx. Now we have a male delegate too,
but in short, with a good degree of
awareness and so this was, it was certainly
important that there was also a

riviste, quindi 60 riviste open access Diamond e la University Press Open access Diamond. Quindi diciamo questo settore, insomma, è un settore piuttosto forte. Come si costruisce una reputazione? Beh, sicuramente attraverso una cosa che noi abbiamo sempre fatto con grande cura che è quella appunto di rendicontare tutto quello che facciamo, quindi attraverso testi, ma anche attraverso dati, quindi questo è un primo punto.

0:30:2.60 --> 0:30:33.150

K2

È stata importante la nomina di un delegato per l'Open science, quindi lavorare diciamo fianco a fianco con questa. Prima era una donna, adesso purtroppo è andata a xxxxx. Adesso abbiamo appunto un delegato uomo anche lui, però insomma, con un buon grado di consapevolezza e quindi questo è stato, è stato sicuramente importante il fatto che ci fosse anche un rappresentante del corpo docente. La Commissione Open science è stata importante perché non sono io che vado nel dipartimento a raccontare. Si fa così, si fa così, ma è un loro collega che va nel dipartimento e dice, c'è questa cosa, c'è quest'altra cosa eccetera, quindi sicuramente diciamo questa, questa mediazione è fatta appunto dai membri, noi ne abbiamo uno per dipartimento; quindi, di solito è un associato piuttosto che anche

representative of the teaching staff. The Open science Commission was important because I'm not the one who goes to the department to tell the story. That's how it's done, that's how it is done, but it's a colleague of theirs who goes to the department and says, there's this thing, there's this other thing and so on, so we certainly say this, this mediation is done precisely by the members, we have one per department; So, it's usually an associate rather than even full professors, so they're very good at that, and they're very, very active. In short, proactive, that's it.

0:31:13.880 --> 0:31:14.630

R

I understand.

0:31:14.810 --> 0:31:39.220

K2

And yes, more or less that's it. Then, of course, they help you, I don't know, the fact that they have one or two objectives within the strategic plan, which at the departmental plans must have, let's say, must somewhat reflect the objective of the university. And then I don't know if your university participates in any European alliance.

0:31:40.0 -- > 0:31:42.370

R

Eh? Purtroppo, purtroppo no.

0:31:41.640 --> 0:32:15.40

K2

professori ordinari, per cui, insomma, sono molto bravi peraltro, e sono molto, molto attivi. Insomma, proattivi, ecco.

0:31:13.880 --> 0:31:14.630

R

Ho capito.

0:31:14.810 --> 0:31:39.220

K2

E sì, più o meno è questo. Poi ovviamente ti aiutano, che ne so il fatto di avere uno o due obiettivi all'interno del piano strategico, che ai piani dei dipartimenti devono avere, diciamo, devono un po' rispecchiare l'obiettivo dell'ateneo. E poi io non so se la vostra università partecipi a qualche alleanza europea.

0:31:40.0 --> 0:31:42.370

R

Eh? Purtroppo no, purtroppo no.

0:31:41.640 --> 0:32:15.40

K2

Ecco, è il vero, vero motore, qui lo devo dire proprio chiaro e tondo, la partecipazione a queste alleanze perché sia nella XXXXXXXX che in xxxxxxxx l'Open science ha un ruolo centrale e di conseguenza, come dire, a un certo punto nel 2017 tutte le università XXXXXXXX avevano una policy sui dati e abbiamo dovuto correre come dei matti per riuscire ad avere anche noi la policy sui dati. E in Italia comunque eravamo i primi a quel punto ad averla.

Well, it is the real engine, here I have to say it really loud and clear, the

participation in these alliances because both in XXXXXXXX and in xxxxxxxx

Open science has a central role and

consequently, how to say, at some point in

2017 all XXXXXXXX universities had a data policy and we had to run like crazy to

be able to have the data policy too. And in

Italy, however, we were the first at that point to have it.

0:32:15.110 --> 0:32:19.90

K2

So surely this stimulus that comes from the outside is very important.

0:32:19.240 --> 0:32:24.220

R

Right? Are there any other partner universities in XXXXXXXX participating?

0:32:24.250 --> 0:32:51.550

K2

No, Italian no. And even in xxxxxxxx no,

it's us, but let's say, the University of

Xxxxxxxx participates in the Guild, which

is another, another alliance, the University

of Xxxxxxxx participates in another

alliance. So, this thing about European

universities is very important because

there is always a specific point about Open science.

0:32:52.230 --> 0:32:59.660

R

0:32:15.110 --> 0:32:19.90

K2

Quindi sicuramente questo stimolo che viene dall'esterno è importantissimo.

0:32:19.240 --> 0:32:24.220

R

Giusto? Ci sono altre università partner in XXXXXXXXX partecipanti?

0:32:24.250 --> 0:32:51.550

K2

No, italiane no. E anche in xxxxxxxx no, siamo noi, però, per dire, l'Università di Xxxxxxxx partecipa alla Guild, che è un'altra, un'altra alleanza, l'università di Xxxxxxxx partecipa ad un'altra alleanza. Quindi questa cosa delle università europee è importantissima perché proprio c'è sempre un punto specifico sull'Open science.

0:32:52.230 --> 0:32:59.660

R

Bene, grazie, è una bella cosa, è un bel traino. Diciamo no? Beh, ha una bella funzione di traino l'alleanza.

0:32:59.590 --> 0:33:2.410

K2

Sì, perché impari tantissimo ... [...]

comunque sono sempre reti e contatti che sono fondamentali, insomma.

[...]

Well, thank you, it's a good thing, it's a nice tow. Are we saying no? Well, it has a nice function of pulling the alliance.

0:32:59.590 --> 0:33:2.410

K2

Yes, because you learn so much ... [...]

However, it is always networks and contacts that are fundamental, in short.

[...]

0:35:33.850 --> 0:36:4.340

R

We seemed to see that perhaps, with a booster effect typical of transformative agreements, being able to publish the postprint with a Creative Commons license has become an exact bet, at most there is the Creative Commons CC BY NC ND, that is quite the "non-creative commons" ... On this point, what do you think of what can be done? Here, how to do it? Because we were actually hoping for the postprint, we took it for granted that it could go with Creative Commons where it pleased, at least after a certain time.

0:37:28.710 --> 0:37:58.550

K2

We are now implementing a feature [in the institutional repository], both with Sherpa and Unpaywall, which allows us to find the correct version with the correct license.

0:35:33.850 --> 0:36:4.340

R

Ci è parso di vedere che forse, con un effetto booster proprio dei trasformativi, poter pubblicare il postprint con una licenza Creative Commons è diventata una scommessa esatto, tutt'al più c'è la Creative Commons CC BY NC ND, cioè la proprio la "non creative commons" quasi ... Su questo punto un tuo parere su che cosa si può pensare? Ecco, come fare? Perché effettivamente il postprint ci speravamo, lo davamo un po' per assodato che potesse andare con Creative Commons dove ci pareva, almeno dopo un certo tempo.

0:37:28.710 --> 0:37:58.550

K2

Noi stiamo implementando adesso una funzionalità [nell'archivio istituzionale], sia con Sherpa che con Unpaywall, che ci permette di individuare la corretta versione con la corretta licenza. Quindi questo, per quanto riguarda, diciamo l'attività, e verrà presentata peraltro a breve al Focus Group di Iris, per capire, questo è sicuramente appunto un elemento che potrà aiutare chi deve poi lavorare, chi deve associare le licenze corrette, eccetera ... dal punto di vista operativo.

Dal punto di vista invece teorico, sicuramente diciamo, questa è l'ennesima

So, this, as far as, let's say, the activity, and it will be presented shortly at the Iris Focus Group, to understand, this is certainly precisely an element that will help those who then have to work, those who have to associate the correct licenses, etc ... from an operational point of view. On the other hand, from a theoretical point of view, we certainly say, this is yet another trap of commercial publishers who obviously make things more and more complicated for you in one way, so that you necessarily go and get the other, which at this moment for them are the transformative agreements because they earn, I won't say double, for heaven's sake no, but in short, they earn more.

[...]

trappola degli editori commerciali che ovviamente ti rendono le cose sempre più complicate per una strada, in modo che tu necessariamente vai a prendere l'altra, che in questo momento per loro sono i contratti trasformativi perché guadagnano non dico il doppio, per carità no, però insomma guadagnano di più.

[...]

Interview with K3

R: The TA are with us. Do they really increase access to research? What is their impact?

K3: TAs are with us, and I would add... unfortunately. When they were presented at the Berlin conference back in 2018, they raised great expectations: if you go to the Berlin 14 statement, you read “We are all committed to accelerating the progress of open access through transformative agreements that are temporary and transitional, with a shift to full open access within a very few years. These agreements should, at least initially, be cost-neutral, with the expectation that economic adjustments will follow as the markets transform”. Did they meet this expectation? Not at all. They were not temporary or short term, they were not including all the journals but, in most cases, just a few hybrid ones, and all the more so they are not cost-neutral, they turned into an unpredictable increase in costs for libraries. And they did not bring Open access to all. They might have increased a bit the access for the readers, but they also created more entry barriers for authors in low-income countries not able to pay the requested APCs. Plus, they basically are maintaining the status quo as they secure paywalled access as the standard financial model in publishing. I recall a researcher from Indonesia at the Open science fair back in 2021 saying: it’s just a solution working for the global north, for those who can afford it, and it was not negotiated or even discussed with the vast majority of researchers not working in Europe or the US.

TAs had a scarce impact on effective transformation, too. If you look at the data provided by PlanS, only 1% out of the 2326 titles in their transformative programme shifted totally to Open access, and 68% failed to meet their targeted Open goals and therefore were removed. PlanS set 2024 as the timeframe by which transformation was supposed to happen, in line with the “temporary” principle stated in Berlin. If you go back to the rationale behind PlanS, the S was meant to “speed” up a process begun in 2001-2003 and still going at a desperately slow pace more than 15 years later. TAs turned out to be, in my opinion, the umpteenth way by which publishers exploit the current research communication system to their advantage.

On the economic side, the initial - agreeable - idea stemming from the Max Planck white paper (“there is enough money in the system to shift from subscriptions to global APCs”) collided with the unbalanced negotiating power of the publishers and their target of maintaining the huge gain, not leaving the big deals model. The APC costs were set based still on the historical paper-based prices, so TAs basically had no impact at all on the insane amount of public money spent every year to buy back a content produced with public money. TAs, moreover, mainly refer only to hybrid journals, which are again not the right way to transition to 100% access because of the well known double dipping issue. There was no increase in competition based on actual services, as expected back in 2018, because journals are still bundled and you can’t go by a single article basis. As there is no transparency on the actual costs of publishing, TAs are not even remotely touching the prestige factor which skyrockets prices. When you pay 11.500 dollars for an article to be published in Open access in Nature, it says it all: you pay for prestige, not for the actual publishing/editing services. That's why the reform of research assessment envisioned by COARA is absolutely needed, to dismantle the current system in which publishers can command the prices they want simply because their journals are a must-have for libraries.

So, all in all I would say the only favorable impact was, again, for commercial publishers.

R: What's next? TAs have strengths and weaknesses ...How can TAs be fair and sustainable?

K3: As they are negotiated now, at least in Italy, TAs are neither fair nor sustainable, due to their weaknesses:

- they are not inclusive, as they are only available to the global north institutions, further marginalizing the global south. TAs reinforce the existing inequalities
- they create a jigsaw access situation, in which something is open, and something still closed, randomly.
- there is no clear timeline for the transformation to 100% Open access - and of course publishers tend to perpetuate this “transition” forever as they gain a huge amount of money.
- they still combine subscriptions + APCs, at the only benefit of publishers.
- when you get to the maximum “tokens” of paid APCs, then institutions might spend more just to satisfy authors requests due to the easiness of prepaid APCs they have heard from colleagues.
- there is no transparency on cost and related services.
- there is no preference/obligation to associate a CC BY license, allowing also for restrictive licenses such as CC BY NC ND which basically are not open.

I see no strength in TAs but to streamline the workflow for authors - still without making them aware of all the mechanisms behind their choice.

As it clearly results from the Council Conclusions (9616/23) in June 2023, there is an alternative way to go, which is the so-called Diamond institutional publishing, for a “high-quality, transparent, open, trustworthy and equitable scholarly publishing”. Diamond journals are 100% in the hands of the community, they have low costs for scalable infrastructures, they are 100% open and authors retain their rights. This is the real Open access as foreseen in the Berlin Declaration.

But, again, due to the link to the prestige/research assessment vicious circle, initiatives like Diamond OA should be coupled with a strong, deep, and long-awaited reform of the research assessment criteria, as envisioned by COARA. We have more than 40 signatories from Italy to COARA, including our national agency ANVUR. If you don't move away from the journal ranking obsession, and you still evaluate the “box” and not the content, publishers will always sell at their prices “prestigious” journals - which, as Bjoern Brembs demonstrated in his studies, publish the less reliable science (it would be long here to discuss the perverse effects of the current research evaluation criteria, the retractions, the frauds and so on).

R: In Italy, how are research bodies, authors and librarians facing changes in scholarly communication brought by TAs?

K3: In Italy, as publicly pointed out by AISA, the Italian Association for the promotion of Open science, since 2019, TAs have been negotiated at particularly unfavorable conditions for institutions - and favorable for publishers: 5 years length, applied only to hybrid journals, no clear timeline for the transition etc.

Compared to other institutions (e.g. University of California) or countries (Germany) the situation in Italy is complicated by two factors: the complete lack of awareness among researchers about the costs and mechanisms of the current publishing system, and the lack of data about previous APCs costs, percentage of Open articles, etc. When negotiations with publishers to get effective and real transformative agreements were broken due to the intransigence of publishers in not meeting the libraries requests (with a subsequent no-access policy to the publishers platforms), researchers aware of the costs and mechanism of

publishing stood with negotiators and renounced to access for some months (in Germany, years) without complaining, as they knew they were fighting for a greater benefit, as it happened at the University of California. In Italy, where researchers still think that online equates to free, and have no idea of the millions a library is paying in subscriptions every year, if access to publishers' platforms is denied for 5 minutes, libraries are submerged by phone calls asking the reasons why.

All the more so, libraries were never asked to produce - and never collected, as it's not so easy due to administrative internal workflows - the annual expenditures for hybrid APCs, often budgeted in the most creative ways. During negotiations, hence, they had to rely on the data provided by publishers themselves... guess what? favorable to publishers, of course, and impossible to contradict.

In the future there should be a serious data collection and an intense awareness raising among researchers and administrators.

R: Do librarians have a "key-role"? What's in their near future?

K3: Libraries indeed can play a crucial role in training about what Open access really is (in Italy, we are still seeing in public debates and on social media all the worse myths about Open access), in publicly declaring the insane amount of money they spend every year in subscriptions - to avoid the misconception "today reading is for free, why should I pay to publish", in creating awareness among researchers about the mechanism of the current scholarly publication market and its link to the research assessment criteria, which guarantees huge net gains to publishers - paid by public money.

Libraries and librarians should play a more critical role in negotiations and take strong stances against the clear maneuvers of publishers to make this supposed "transition" last forever to their economic benefit.

Interview with K4

R: The TA are with us. Do they really increase access to research? What is their impact?

K4: From the outset, it was clear that they could only have increased access to a very limited part of research: that carried out by researchers working in very rich institutions that chose to sign them and continue to pay monopoly prices. And it was also quite clear that they would have made it increasingly difficult for researchers working in "poor" institutions to be visible in the so-called top journals, because they could not afford the same monopoly prices. But even if we are content with a limited open access, intended as a luxury for the rich, the Coalition S, which supported the TAs, is now recording their failure (see [here](#)¹⁵⁶).

Rebus sic stantibus, the best available options for making research accessible remain, legally, self-archiving in open access repositories and, illegally, Sci-hub.

If the so-called TAs are used as the only or preferred way of implementing Open access, as is the case in most Italian universities, they

1. do not reduce, and may even increase, the expenditure of academic and research libraries on "top" scientific journals.
2. [discourage](#)¹⁵⁷ universities and research institutions from promoting and funding local "diamond" and scholarly-driven OA initiatives, even if this is now the [EU's preferred option](#)¹⁵⁸.

R: What's next? TAs have strengths and weaknesses ...How can TAs be fair and sustainable?

K4: TAs could become fair and sustainable only if we do away with the reason for their monopoly and oligopoly high prices, that is an administrative research assessment emphasizing "publish or perish" and the proprietary bibliometric of Clarivate Analytics and Scopus.

If the value of a scientific article depended on its content, which should be read and understood, rather than on its container, publishers would become mere publishing service providers competing in the marketplace. On the other hand, if publishing in "Nature" continues to be crucial for a researcher's career and an institution's assessment, they will remain willing to pay almost [any price](#)¹⁵⁹ to get an article published there.

However, we have to be aware that TAs were planned from the beginning to achieve a certain degree of open access (for the rich) while preserving the current administrative system of research assessment, as we can see in the following passage from Ralf Schimmer's [proposal](#)¹⁶⁰ (2015):

¹⁵⁶ https://www.Coalition_S.org/blog/transformative-journals-analysis-from-the-2022-reports/ (accessed 13 May 2024)

¹⁵⁷ <https://www.timeshighereducation.com/opinion/transformative-open-access-publishing-deals-are-only-entrenching-commercial-power> (accessed 13 May 2024)

¹⁵⁸ <https://www.researchprofessionalnews.com/rr-news-europe-infrastructure-2022-9-eu-funded-project-to-guide-diamond-open-access-begins/> (accessed 13 May 2024)

¹⁵⁹ <https://www.timeshighereducation.com/blog/natures-oa-fee-seems-outrageously-high-many-will-pay-it> (accessed 13 May 2024)

¹⁶⁰ https://www.mpdl.mpg.de/images/documents/Nachrichten/schimmer_ResearchEurope.pdf (accessed 13 May 2024)

Many who advocate open access envisage the development of a new publishing environment—new journals, new ways of operating—in which researchers can eventually be resettled. But it may be preferable to work with the publishing habitat that has evolved organically and bring open access into it. This could be achieved by transforming the existing core journals' business models while simultaneously maintaining their function of providing quality assurance through peer review, publishing services and *brand value*. [emphasis added]

In a competitive market, peer review and publishing services could be organized and provided by other private publishers, or by public institutions through university presses and libraries. On the other hand, in the increasingly concentrated market of the "brand value", the latter cannot be replaced. And if you are willing to pay a monopoly price to publish an article in OA, you should be aware that you are recognizing that you are not getting editorial services: you are getting evaluation. It is so obvious that if you ask the publisher to publish your article, you have to pay for it.

It has been a wonderful business for the oligopolists of scholarly publishing: while it has become easier and easier to bypass them in reading, thanks to public repositories and Sci-hub, you cannot bypass them in writing, if the administrative research evaluation keeps on making you addicted to their "brand value". Not surprisingly, one of them (Wiley) was so pleased that it [hired Ralf Schimmer himself](#)¹⁶¹, giving us a masterful example of the so-called revolving door.

R: In Italy, how are research bodies, authors and librarians facing changes in scholarly communication brought by Tas?

K4: With some notable exceptions, such as the University of Milan's Open access group, the TAs have been accepted and implemented in the most uncritical way, even if the agreements negotiated by the CRUI centralize the negotiation but not the expenditure and the relative responsibility. In addition, authors are usually unaware that OA publishing in hybrid journals not only perpetuates the so-called serials crisis, but also exacerbates it, by the so-called [double dipping](#)¹⁶². Furthermore, we might add that paying to publish encourages publishers to behave in a predatory way, as the ["Journal of Political Philosophy" incident](#)¹⁶³ shows. But this is not a problem in Italy, if we do not consider the waste of public money, because our research evaluation system also encourages authors to be predatory.

R: Do librarians have a "key-role"? What's in their near future?

¹⁶¹ <https://www.infotoday.eu/Articles/News/Featured-News/Executive-changes-at-Clarivate-and-Wiley-158385.aspx>
(accessed 13 May 2024)

¹⁶² <https://aisa.sp.unipi.it/hybrid-open-access-why-paying-twice-%e2%80%a9/>
(accessed 13 May 2024)

¹⁶³ <https://dailynous.com/2023/04/27/wiley-removes-goodin-as-editor-of-the-journal-of-political-philosophy/>
(accessed 13 May 2024)

K4: Ralf Schimmer did play a key role: when he conceived the idea of TAs as a means of achieving open access without interfering with authors' normal publishing activities, he was head of scholarly information provision at the Max Planck Digital Library in Munich. And some - some, not all - Italian university librarians still play a key role when they promote TAs as the perfect solution to make research accessible and they organize Springer-Nature or Wiley seminars on Open access - which is like organizing seminars to help foxes teach chickens how to be good for their (predatory) lunch. And what's in their near future? Perhaps the loss of their job, to put it bluntly. If the European reform of research evaluation, promoted by the COARA coalition, is watered down in Italy, it is possible that TA's OA will remain the main Italian path to OA: but this implies a shift towards platformisation that will render most librarians and most libraries useless, if we mean them as repositories of literature they own. Thus, it would even be in their best interest to follow the advice of [this article](#)¹⁶⁴: “(1) educate researchers about commercial publishers and APCs; (2) allocate library budgets to support scholarly and library publishing; (3) engage in public research infrastructure development and copyright reform; and (4) advocate for research assessment reform.”

¹⁶⁴ <https://liberquarterly.eu/article/view/13561> (accessed 13 May 2024)

Trascrizione dell'intervista a K5

[...] indica parti di conversazione non rilevanti rispetto al tema.

[...]

0:0:25.60 --> 0:0:28.810

R

Allora la prima domanda è, i contratti trasformativi sono tra noi, sono qui per restare, così sembra, non so, allora, veramente aumentano l'accesso alla ricerca, qual è il loro impatto secondo te?

0:0:40.70 --> 0:0:53.790

K5

Lo aumentano senz'altro, guardando la cosa dal punto di vista dei ricercatori, bisogna dire che i contratti trasformativi stanno avendo un grande successo. Io posso essere testimone, diciamo così, di quello che succede nella mia università, che è una grande università. Logicamente, quindi i numeri sono ovviamente alti di per sé, l'accoglienza che hanno avuto questi contratti, è stata eccellente. Insomma, a parte qualche rara voce di dissenso, di matematici, al contrario, però, in genere i numeri degli articoli pubblicati sono eccellenti, anche il riscontro dai messaggi, telefonate, conversazioni che abbiamo avuto sono tutte di ringraziamento per l'iniziativa, perché sempre di più è richiesto

Transcript of the interview with K5

[...] Indicates parts of the conversation that are not relevant to the topic.

[...]

0:0:25.60 --> 0:0:28.810

R

So, the first question is, transformative agreements are among us, that's right, they're here to stay, so it seems, I don't know, then really increase access to research, what is their impact in your opinion?

0:0:40.70 --> 0:0:53.790

K5

They certainly increase it, looking at it from the researchers' point of view, it has to be said that transformative agreements are having a great success. I can be a witness, so to speak, of what is happening at my university, which is a great university. Logically, so the numbers are obviously high in themselves, the reception that these agreements have had has been excellent. In short, apart from a few rare voices of dissent, of mathematicians, on the contrary, however, in general the numbers of published articles are excellent, even the feedback from the messages, phone calls, conversations that we have had are all

l'accesso aperto per la pubblicazione di determinate ricerche e questi ricercatori pagavano e pagano le APC dal fondo della loro ricerca.

Sostanzialmente, quindi si tratta, per loro, di un bel risparmio e sono tutti molto contenti. Ecco poi quindi, al di là degli aspetti negativi che ci possono essere, l'impatto è senz'altro dal loro punto, mettendosi dal loro punto di vista, mi sembra di poter dire che sia senz'altro positivo.

0:2:18.250 --> 0:2:26.700

R

Grazie quindi andiamo un po' in profondità per dire il giudizio, ecco un pochino più articolato, cosa c'è dopo? I contratti trasformativi hanno punti di forza e debolezze, se ne vuoi parlare anche tu e individuare quali e come i trasformativi possono essere, diciamo, "giusti" e sostenibili. Che cosa ci sarà dopo?

0:2:45.770 --> 0:2:48.610

K5

Ecco se parliamo appunto, invece più da un punto di vista ...

0:2:50.70 --> 0:2:59.960

K5

Se parliamo da un punto di vista non dico astratto, ma insomma, comunque dal punto di vista di chi non è un ricercatore, non di chi pubblica, ma da chi li gestisce e qui vengono sicuramente dei problemi di

thankng for the initiative, because more and more open access is required for the publication of certain research and these researchers paid and pay the APCs by the funds of their research. Basically, therefore, it is, for them, a nice saving and they are all very happy. So, beyond the negative aspects that there may be, the impact is certainly from their point of view, from their point of view, I think I can say that it is certainly positive.

0:2:18.250 --> 0:2:26.700

R

Thank you so let's go a little deeper to say the judgment, here is a little more articulated, what's next? Transformative agreements have strengths and weaknesses, if you want to talk about them too and identify which and how transformative agreements can be, let's say, fair and sustainable. What's next?

0:2:45.770 --> 0:2:48.610

K5

Here's if we're talking precisely, instead more from a ...

0:2:50.70 --> 0:2:59.960

K5

If we speak from a point of view, I won't say abstract, but in short, in any case from the point of view of those who are not researchers, not of those who publish, but of those who manage them, and here there are certainly problems of economic

sostenibilità economica e diciamo così, etica, quelli di natura economica sono perché i contratti sono piuttosto onerosi. Perché anche se il sogno iniziale di vedere semplicemente trasformata l'entità di quello che si pagava per accedere in quello che si paga per pubblicare e magari questo il sogno è, diciamo così era, era un sogno, nel senso che gli importi sono, anche devo dire logicamente, maggiorati rispetto a [i contratti tradizionali] dal momento che gli editori nel momento in cui propongono un trasformativo, vanno a sommare, perlomeno in prima battuta, come prima richiesta quello che guadagnavano dall'accesso e quello che guadagnavano dalla pubblicazione, cioè dagli APC, e questo va però ad appesantire il budget dei sistemi bibliotecari, sostanzialmente, che sono quelli che pagano. Mentre prima le due voci erano distinte e i costi degli APC erano raramente a carico dell'università, in quanto il budget è proprio universitario, FFO, generalmente erano ripresi dai fondi di ricerca che i ricercatori avevano per conto loro e avevano delle provenienze le più diverse e invece in questo modo, diciamo, il sistema bibliotecario accollandosi l'intero ammontare, ha per forza di cose aumentato le richieste di budget alle proprie amministrazioni e quindi diciamo che non c'è assolutamente non solo, non c'è un risparmio, ma anzi,

sustainability and let's say, ethics, those of an economic nature are because the agreements are rather onerous. Because even if the initial dream of simply seeing the amount of what you paid to access transformed into what you pay to publish, and maybe this dream is, let's say it was, it was a dream, in the sense that the amounts are, even I must say logically, increased compared to [traditional agreements] since publishers when they propose a transformative one, they add, at least in the first instance, as a first request what they earned from access and what they earned from publication, i.e. from APCs, and this, however, weighs down the budget of library systems, basically, which are the ones that pay. While before the two items were distinct and the costs of the APCs were rarely borne by the university, as the budget is university-owned, FFO, they were generally taken from the research funds that the researchers had on their behalf and had the most diverse origins and instead in this way, let's say, the library system taking on the entire amount, It has necessarily increased the budget requests to its administrations and therefore we say that there is absolutely not only that, there is no saving, but on the contrary, if anything we say, there is a burden on the budgets, perhaps not very high, then it is that, the negotiations serve precisely to file

casomai diciamo, c'è un aggravio sui bilanci, magari non elevatissimo, poi è quello, i negoziati servono proprio a limare le richieste iniziali degli editori e a cercare di contenere entro dei limiti accettabili gli aumenti.

E però, diciamo così, il travaso, cioè il rapporto uno a uno fra quello che si spendeva prima e quello che si spende ora non c'è quasi mai, non c'è e non credo ci possa essere, perché gli editori sono editori commerciali che fanno i loro interessi, il loro lavoro e quindi non hanno nessun interesse a diminuire il loro guadagno, quindi qui sì, dal punto di vista economico, questo è chiaramente un limite. L'altro limite, quello di natura etica, a cui facevo riferimento, era il fatto che si dice che il contratto trasformativo non sposta il non va, diciamo così, neanche a cercare di risolvere, non ci va nemmeno vicino a risolvere il problema della del possesso della ricerca e del mantenimento della ricerca nell'ambito accademico istituzionale nella quale essa viene svolto, cioè comunque i grandi *publishers* mantengono un forte potere, per il fatto che le ricerche vengono comunque pubblicate sulle riviste; quindi, il traguardo di un accesso veramente libero, il traguardo di un'accademia che mantiene totalmente non solo i diritti, ma anche tutto il processo di pubblicazione dei risultati delle ricerche

the initial requests of the publishers and to try to contain the increases within acceptable limits.

And yet, let's put it this way, the transfer, that is, the one-to-one ratio between what was spent before and what is spent now is almost never, there is not and I don't think there can be, because publishers are commercial publishers who do their interests, their work and therefore have no interest in reducing their earnings, So here, yes, from an economic point of view, this is clearly a limitation. The other limitation, the one of an ethical nature, which I referred to, was the fact that it is said that the transformative agreements do not move, they do not go, let's say, not even to try to solve, it does not even come close to solving the problem of the possession of research and the maintenance of research in the institutional academic environment in which it is carried out, That is, the big *publishers* still have a strong power, because the research is published in the journals anyway; therefore, the goal of a truly free access, the goal of an academy that totally retains not only the rights, but also the whole process of publishing the results of the research is not achieved with the transformative agreements and are in some way, Some argue, a kind of drug of the market, as they move away from the finish

non è raggiunto con i trasformativi e sono in qualche modo, qualcuno sostiene, una specie di droga del mercato, in quanto allontanano dal traguardo la possibilità di trasformare veramente la *scholarly communication* verso la via verde, verso la pubblicazione su repository o quello che sia che abbiano una validità ai fini delle carriere concorsuali, eccetera eccetera. Il trasformativo è considerato in qualche modo una scorciatoia, molto comoda, appunto, come dicevo prima, di grande successo dal punto di vista degli autori, i quali non hanno in genere una grande preoccupazione etica riguardo l'open access. Io non ho mai incontrato, tranne pochi eletti e pochi "talebani", diciamo, dell'open access, non ho mai incontrato uno o, meglio, appunto, ho incontrato pochissimi docenti veramente preoccupati, portati ad accogliere, a condividere le istanze etiche dell'accesso aperto ... in genere il ricercatore medio, che sono la stragrande maggioranza, vede i suoi problemi, i problemi economici, l'open access fino adesso è stato considerato più una "scocciatura" che non una risorsa perché loro erano obbligati a pubblicare appunto, perché ormai l'Europa lo chiede, quell'altro bundle lo chiede, quel finanziamento lo chiede e loro però dovevano cacciare fuori i soldi perché le riviste sulle quali volevano pubblicare

line the possibility of truly transforming *scholarly communication towards* the green way, towards publication on repositories or whatever it is that they have a validity for the purposes of competitive careers, et cetera et cetera.

The transformative agreement is considered in some way a shortcut, very convenient, in fact, as I said before, very successful from the point of view of authors, who generally do not have a great ethical concern about open access. I have never met, except for a few elected ones and a few "Taliban", let's say, of open access, I have never met one or, rather, in fact, I have met very few teachers who are really concerned, inclined to welcome, to share the ethical demands of open access ... generally the average researcher, who are the vast majority, sees his problems, the economic problems, open access until now has been considered more of a "nuisance" than a resource because they were obliged to publish precisely, because now Europe asks for that other bundle, asks for that funding, asks for it and but they had to kick out the money because the journals in which they wanted to publish were the high-impact journals, therefore the journals are almost always hybrid and almost always, therefore, always subject to the payment of APCs. Apart from those few, the transformative agreement is an

erano le riviste ad alto impatto, quindi le riviste quasi sempre ibride e quasi sempre, quindi, sempre soggetti al pagamento delle APC. Esclusi appunto quei pochi, il contratto trasformativo risulta un'ottima soluzione per chi non si pone grandi problemi riguardo al futuro dell'open access e ha come obiettivo quello primario, quello basico, di pubblicare ad accesso aperto su ottime riviste in modo da rendere la sua ricerca più aperta, il più raggiungibile possibile e che possa essergli utile anche per la carriera, insomma ...

R

Cosa seguirà ai contratti trasformativi, altri contratti trasformativi oppure qualche ulteriore modello?

0:10:29.10 --> 0:10:39.450

K5

Beh, la parola trasformativo vuol dire, doveva inizialmente far capire che era una fase di transizione, cioè doveva, i contratti sono trasformare da una cosa all'altra e la fase trasformativa era una fase. Adesso ormai son passati diversi anni dall'inizio, dall'adozione di questo modello nella gran parte dei contratti e ancora non si vede un traguardo di trasformazione completa, anche perché è difficile che un editore possa considerare completamente trasformato il suo modello di business, perché non esiste solo l'Europa, non esiste

excellent solution for those who do not have major problems regarding the future of open access and have as its primary objective, the basic one, to publish in open access in excellent journals in order to make their research more open, as achievable as possible and that can also be useful for their career, in short...

0:10:23.530 --> 0:10:24.290

R

What will follow the transformative agreements, other transformative agreements, or some additional model?

0:10:29.10 --> 0:10:39.450

K5

Well, the word transformative means, he had to make it clear that it was a transitional phase, that is, he had to, agreements are to transform from one thing to another and the transformative phase was a phase. Now several years have passed since the beginning, since the adoption of this model in most agreements and there is still no goal of complete transformation, also because it is difficult for a publisher to consider its business model completely transformed, because there is not only Europe, there is not only North America, in short, the rest of the world does not follow this model so much, because they publish less and because it is a market that the big publishers would lose if almost all of their articles were available

solo il Nord America, insomma, il resto del mondo non segue tanto questo modello, perché pubblicano meno e perché è un mercato che i grandi editori perderebbero se la quasi totalità dei propri articoli fosse disponibile ad accesso aperto, perché mai dovrebbero continuare ad abbonarsi i ricercatori africani o il Sud America, insomma, dove l'impatto numerico degli articoli pubblicati, è senza dubbio inferiore quando la maggior parte, la stragrande parte degli articoli disponibili è gratis, questo costituirebbe una perdita secca da parte degli editori. Infatti, il vero problema che io ho sempre visto di questo tipo di contratti è il futuro, sul quale pochi hanno ancora le idee chiare. Gli stessi editori, secondo me non ce l'hanno perché, se l'obiettivo è quello di trasformare completamente le riviste in accesso aperto, dovranno fare i conti col fatto che non ci saranno più abbonamenti per chi vuole soltanto leggere, per tutti quegli enti per i quali la pubblicazione è residuale rispetto all'accesso e invece sarà una grande, una grande opportunità per chi pubblica molto.

[...]

0:16:50.820 --> 0:16:54.990

K5

E quindi stavo dicendo ...

0:16:54.970 --> 0:16:55.980

R

in open access, why should researchers continue to subscribe

In short, where the numerical impact of published articles is undoubtedly lower when most, the vast majority of the articles available are free, this would constitute a dead loss on the part of publishers. In fact, the real problem that I have always seen with this type of contract is the future, about which few still have clear ideas. The publishers themselves, in my opinion, do not have it because, if the goal is to completely transform journals into open access, they will have to deal with the fact that there will be no more subscriptions for those who just want to read, for all those institutions for which publication is residual compared to access and instead it will be a large, A great opportunity for those who publish a lot.

[...]

0:16:50.820 --> 0:16:54.990

K5

And so, I was saying...

0:16:54.970 --> 0:16:55.980

R

You said that even the publishers themselves may not be able to imagine models themselves, because it is difficult to give up the quotas [of subscriptions]

0:16:59.870 --> 0:17:8.50

K5

Dicevi che anche gli editori stessi non fanno forse immaginare a loro volta modelli, perché difficile rinunciare alle quote [degli abbonamenti]

0:16:59.870 --> 0:17:8.50

K5

Sì, ma è una questione, è una questione un po' particolare perché appunto, loro che si saranno fatti dei conti, non lo so, penso di sì, cosa pensano che saranno le riviste tra 10 anni, completamente ad accesso aperto oppure no? Tempo fa, ti posso dare questo dato, ma era prima del Covid, poco prima del Covid sarà stato '18 o '19, partecipando alla riunione con XXXXXXXX, anche se io non faccio parte del team negoziale di XXXXXXXX, però venne aperta un po' a tutti, così, perché c'era uno dei vicepresidenti, insomma, il quale proprio a questo proposito disse "ma noi non siamo molto preoccupati perché alla fin fine i contratti trasformativi copriranno anche nel cumulo degli anni non più del 30-40% degli articoli che noi pubblichiamo, quindi la maggior parte saranno sempre sotto [sottoscrizione], bisognerà pagare per leggerli e quindi non sposteranno poi tanto le cose. Io non lo so se questo sia ancora così, sono passati 5-6 anni da quando ho sentito queste parole. Indubbiamente lo avranno un problema tra un po', perché cioè uno appunto degli aspetti, un po' non negativi in questo caso, ma problematici

Yes, but it's a question, it's a bit of a peculiar question because they will have done the math, I don't know, I think so, what do they think the journals will be in 10 years, completely open access or not? Some time ago, I can give you this data, but it was before Covid, just before Covid it must have been '18 or '19, participating in the meeting with a XXXXXXXX, even if I am not part of the XXXXXXXX negotiating team, but it was open to everyone, like this, because there was one of the vice presidents, in short, who precisely in this regard said "but we are not very worried because in the end the transformative agreements will also cover in the No more than 30-40% of the articles we publish, so most of them will always be under [subscription], you will have to pay to read them and therefore they will not move things that much. I don't know if this is still the case, it's been 5-6 years since I heard these words. Undoubtedly, they will have a problem in a while, because that is, one of the aspects, a little not negative in this case, but certainly problematic, will be the one I mentioned even before the different, but completely different way of approaching between the entities that publish and the entities that do not publish, or that publish little, that is, that they will therefore find themselves paying to publish, when, on the other hand, they do

senz'altro, sarà quello a cui accennavo anche prima del diverso, ma completamente diverso modo di approcciarsi tra gli enti che pubblicano e gli enti che non pubblicano, o che pubblicano poco, cioè che si troveranno quindi a pagare per pubblicare, quando invece non pubblicano ed è un problema anche di natura meramente contabile. Alla fine, un revisore di conti, diciamo, perché stiamo spendendo in una università piccola, tanto per dirne e devo spendere, non so, 30.000 euro per sé per pubblicare quando pubblico uno o due articoli l'anno, quanto mi costano questi articoli l'anno ... allora facciamo un altro tipo di contratto, ci abboniamo alle riviste che ci servono e se serve pubblicare quei due articoli a 2.400 euro spenderemo i 2.400 euro.

In questo momento questo tipo di considerazioni non le vedo, non le stanno, nessuno le sta ponendo, magari ci stanno pensando, ma io non le ho mai viste nel dibattito, però è la prima cosa che pensai anche 4-5 anni fa, quando cioè dicevo ma che prospettive ha questo? Hai chiesto che prospettive ha? E io non lo so, cioè nel senso io come operatore non saprei dirlo, diciamo che ho delle preoccupazioni, delle curiosità anche perché andrà avanti così? Per quanto, quant'è questa trasformazione, quanto durerà? Si spera il meno possibile, oppure ancora si riuscirà a superarlo il

not publish and it is also a problem of a purely accounting nature. In the end, an auditor, let's say, because we are spending in a small university, just to say and I have to spend, I don't know, 30,000 euros for my institution to publish when I publish one or two articles a year, how much do these articles cost me a year... So, we make a different kind of contract, we subscribe the journals we need and if we need to publish those two articles for 2,400 euros, we will spend the 2,400 euros. Now I don't see these kinds of considerations, they don't stand them, no one is asking them, maybe they're thinking about it, but I've never seen them in the debate, but it's the first thing I thought even 4-5 years ago, when I said what prospects does this have? Did you ask what prospects it has? And I don't know, that is, in the sense that I as an operator I wouldn't be able to say, let's say that I have concerns, curiosities also why will it go on like this? How long, how long is this transformation, how long will it last? We hope as little as possible, or we will still be able to overcome the [pay for publish] model, that is, other types of open access publications will finally have weight, even with a "seal", which at the moment seems to be able to give them only, and perhaps it *is, the peer review that is* offered by the big journals, let's say that it is a moment in which there are more

modello [*pay for publish*], cioè, avranno finalmente peso altro tipo di pubblicazioni ad accesso aperto, anche con un “bollino”, che in questo momento pare che gli possa dare soltanto, e forse è così, la *peer review* che è offerta dalle grandi riviste, diciamo che è un momento in cui ci sono più domande che risposte, io direi, io la vedo così.

[...]

0:20:45.880 --> 0:20:51.60

R

Ehm, allora in Italia vabbè, più o meno in realtà già hai risposto comunque ti leggo anche la terza domanda: in Italia come gli enti di ricerca, gli autori e anche i bibliotecari fronteggiano i cambiamenti nella comunicazione scientifica, portati dai trasformativi.

0:21:14.550 --> 0:21:16.710

K5

Cioè il punto di vista dei ricercatori, dicevi?

0:21:16.410 --> 0:21:22.740

R

I tre punti di vista: delle istituzioni, degli autori e dei bibliotecari.

0:21:22.930 --> 0:21:23.630

R

Quello che vedi tu.

0:21:24.860 --> 0:21:27.750

K5

Quello dei degli autori te lo ho detto prima

questions than answers. I would say that's how I see it.

[...]

0:20:45.880 --> 0:20:51.60

R

Ehm, then in Italy oh well, more or less, actually you have already answered anyway I will also read you the third question: in Italy how research institutions, authors and even librarians face the changes in scientific communication, brought about by the transformative agreements.

0:21:14.550 --> 0:21:16.710

K5

That is, the researchers' point of view, you said?

0:21:16.410 --> 0:21:22.740

R

The three points of view: institutions, authors and librarians.

0:21:22.930 --> 0:21:23.630

R

What you see.

0:21:24.860 --> 0:21:27.750

K5

I told you before.

0:21:27.0 --> 0:21:29.110

R

You told me, in fact, yes.

0:21:27.960 --> 0:21:33.410

K5

0:21:27.0 --> 0:21:29.110

R

Quello me l'hai detto, infatti, sì.

0:21:27.960 --> 0:21:33.410

K5

No, no ... hanno sperimentato una grande soddisfazione. I bibliotecari credo che si sentano un pochino emarginati da questo processo ... già lo erano, hanno cominciato a esserlo quando sono stati un po' esautorati nei loro compiti tradizionali, nell'accendere abbonamenti, decidere quali accendere o spegnere, cioè, questo ancor di più penso che allontani il bibliotecario che lavora, magari a stretto contatto con la struttura di riferimento, cioè la facoltà, da questi aspetti perché c'è qualcun altro che se ne occupa, in genere sono i sistemi, gli uffici centrali, quelli che poi sottoscrivono le risorse e anche perché, appunto, mentre prima il ricercatore aveva qualche motivo di interpellare il bibliotecario su una rivista per chiedere un abbonamento eccetera, adesso da questo stretto punto di vista sa che deve rivolgersi a un ufficio che si occupa di questo. Noi, per esempio, in xxxxxxxx abbiamo una casella di posta elettronica dedicata e lì scrivono per sapere cosa fare, i problemi, eccetera e quindi bibliotecari, non lo so se sono proprio ... li vedo un po', appunto, marginalizzati. Gli enti? Beh, dal punto di vista dell'istituzione, quello che io ho potuto

No, no... They experienced great satisfaction. Librarians, I think, feel a little bit marginalized by this process... They already were, they began to be so when they were a bit deprived of their traditional tasks, in turning on subscriptions, deciding which ones to turn on or off, that is, I think this even more distances the librarian who works, perhaps in close contact with the reference structure, that is, the faculty, from these aspects because there is someone else who takes care of them, Generally they are the systems, the central offices, those that then subscribe to the resources and also because, precisely, while before the researcher had some reason to consult the librarian in a journal to ask for a subscription and so on, now from this strict point of view he knows that he has to turn to an office that deals with this. We, for example, in xxxxxxxx we have a dedicated mailbox and there they write to find out what to do, problems, etc. and then librarians, I don't know if they are really ... I see them a bit, in fact, marginalized. The institutions? Well, from the point of view of the institution, what I was able to verify in the boards of directors, when I went to trivially bring the practice, we at xxxxxxxx only bring those of very large agreements. Since we still have a three-year authorization budget, if

verificare nei consigli di amministrazione, quando sono andato per portare banalmente proprio la pratica, noi in xxxxxxxx portiamo solo quelli dei contratti molto grandi. Siccome abbiamo comunque un budget autorizzativo triennale, se è un contratto piccolo, non lo portiamo in CdA, però quelli grossi sì.

0:23:25.520 --> 0:23:29.910

K5

Perché, insomma, sono spese consistenti e anche lì ho sempre percepito una soddisfazione da parte loro, perché si è capita l'utilità, anche lì, sia la rettrice che gli altri membri del CdA, sono persone che percepiscono più l'aspetto economico e i vantaggi che non gli aspetti, come dicevo prima, etico filosofici, da lì non mi aspettavo infatti uno stop, non è venuta nessuna critica, nessuna, io mi aspettavo magari dover fronteggiare qualcuno che avrebbe detto però, quanto ci costa? Invece no, perché evidentemente, se n'è percepita l'utilità pratica proprio. Direi che appunto, la cosa positiva che abbiamo sperimentato è proprio la soddisfazione per gli aspetti pratici risolti, il fatto che risolvono un problema che c'era e in qualche modo lo risolvono, scaricandolo su qualcun altro. Però nessuno ha avvertito questo come uno scarico di un [problema] perché poi alla fine, alla fine anche gli aumenti che ci sono stati, poi si compensano, magari si

it's a small contract, we don't bring it to the Board of Directors, but the big ones do.

0:23:25.520 --> 0:23:29.910

K5

Because, in short, they are substantial expenses and even there I have always perceived a satisfaction on their part, because the usefulness has been understood, even there, both the rector and the other members of the Board of Directors, are people who perceive more the economic aspect and the advantages than the aspects, as I said before, ethically philosophical, from there I did not expect a stop, No criticism came, none, I expected maybe to have to face someone who would have said but, how much does it cost us? But no, because evidently, its practical usefulness has been perceived. I would say that the positive thing we have experienced is precisely the satisfaction for the practical aspects solved, the fact that they solve a problem that was there and somehow solve it, offloading it on someone else. But no one perceived this as an offloading of a [problem] because then in the end, in the end even the increases that have been made, then they are compensated, maybe the resources are cancelled, another one is taken ... Let's say that what it has, perhaps the only thing, which obviously caused a sensation that is topical, this increase, I don't know if you

cancellano le risorse, se ne prende un'altra ... Diciamo che quello che ha, magari l'unica cosa, che ovviamente ha fatto scalpore che è d'attualità, questo aumento, non so se voi avete il contratto xxxxxxxx, il xxxxxx anno prevedeva e prevede ancora un aumento dell'x%, aumento monstre che comunque deve essere negoziato. È stato l'unico momento in cui nel nostro CdA hanno sottolineato il fatto che hanno apprezzato il fatto che CARE abbia detto che quell'aumento comunque sarà oggetto di rinegoziazione, perché è impossibile sopportarlo, ma sennò altrimenti non ho avuto conservazioni nei suoi aspetti economici né sull'impianto generale del contratto.

0:25:27.450 --> 0:25:34.640

R

Grazie, grazie, i 18 punti di IVA, poi sono stati un aumento ...

0:25:32.250 --> 0:25:48.750

K5

...E infatti questo dimenticavo nell'elenco degli aspetti, dell'aggravio economico, il fatto che ecco qui c'è molta confusione tra l'altro, perché un contratto lo prevede, un altro fa esattamente il conto di quanto ... scomputando ...

[...]

0:29:1.150 --> 0:29:2.950

R

have the xxxxxxx contract, the xxxxx year foresaw and still provides for an increase of x%, monstrous increase that in any case must be negotiated. It was the only time in our Board of Directors that they emphasized the fact that they appreciated the fact that CARE said that that increase will be renegotiated anyway, because it is impossible to bear it, but otherwise I had no reservations in its economic aspects or on the general structure of the contract.

0:25:27.450 --> 0:25:34.640

R

Thank you, thank you, the 18 VAT points, then they were an increase ...

0:25:32.250 --> 0:25:48.750

K5

... And in fact, I forgot this in the list of aspects, of the economic burden, the fact that here there is a lot of confusion among other things, because one contract provides for it, another does exactly count how much ... Discounting...

[...]

0:29:1.150 --> 0:29:2.950

R

The last question was, but roughly we have already talked about it, however, if librarians in particular have a key role, but you mentioned, in fact, on the contrary, in reality that they are a bit isolated from the process, but maybe, but if we include in

L'ultima era, ma grosso modo ne abbiamo già parlato, comunque, se i bibliotecari in particolare hanno un ruolo chiave, ma tu hai accennato, infatti, al contrario, in realtà che sono un po' isolati dal processo, ma magari, ma se in se includiamo nell'insieme dei bibliotecari, anche i colleghi che lavorano negli uffici, che magari non so, non so se è il caso vostro in xxxxxxxx, se sono all'interno degli uffici, comunque avete personale bibliotecario, non solo amministrativo, non so. Ecco comunque la domanda, la domanda era se i bibliotecari hanno un particolare ruolo chiave e che cosa comunque c'è nel loro futuro?

0:29:39.20 --> 0:29:40.960

K5

Allora sì, la risposta è la risposta in questo caso è sì, nel senso che negli uffici del sistema bibliotecario c'è una persona che è un bibliotecario che si occupa di tutto ciò che riguarda le risorse elettroniche, a 360° compresi i contratti trasformativi, rapporti con gli autori, è lui, xxxxxxxx che risponde alla casella di posta sui contratti trasformativi.

Al centro, siamo tutti bibliotecari, tranne i due amministrativi che fanno la parte proprio contabile, altrimenti noi siamo tutti bibliotecari, quindi ce ne occupiamo in pieno.

Ecco, questo sì e questo è molto

the set of librarians, also the colleagues who work in the offices, which maybe I don't know, I don't know if it's your case at xxxxxxxx, if they are employed in the offices, anyway you have library staff, not just administrative, I don't know. The question was, however, whether librarians have a particular key role and what is in their future?

0:29:39.20 --> 0:29:40.960

K5

So yes, the answer is, the answer in this case is yes, in the sense that in the offices of the library system there is a person who is a librarian who deals with everything related to electronic resources, at 360° including transformative agreements, relationships with authors, it is he, xxxxxxxx who answers the mailbox on transformative agreements.

In the central offices, we are all librarians, except for the two administrative staff who do the accounting part, otherwise we are all librarians, so we take care of it in full.

Well, this

is true and this is very important because in any case a librarian point of view is indispensable and among other things, we have always collaborated a lot, even with the Research Office, as far as everything that is open access publications, etc. is concerned... And I think they're very happy

importante perché comunque un punto di vista bibliotecario è indispensabile e tra l'altro noi abbiamo sempre collaborato molto, anche con l'Ufficio ricerca, per quello che riguarda tutto ciò che è pubblicazioni open access, eccetera ... E loro credo sono ben contenti di non occuparsi anche di questo, perché sono oberati da tutta una serie di altre cose però, tutto ciò che riguarda il trasformativo, tutto ciò che va in generale per i contratti per la gestione risorse elettroniche fa tutto capo a noi.

[...]

0:31:58.220 --> 0:32:32.840

R

... abbiamo notato, diciamo forse un effetto “*booster*” dei trasformativi, è stato anche quello che pubblicare un postprint con una licenza Creative Commons è diventato per qualche editore difficile, nel senso che magari è consentito di depositare nel repository istituzionale, ma non associando una Creative Commons ma una licenza “*tailor made*” diciamo, non so se anche voi avete gestito questi aspetti e come lo avete fatto.

0:32:32.850 --> 0:32:34.950

R

Ecco, se vi siete occupati di questo.

0:32:33.540 --> 0:32:37.260

K5

not to deal with that too, because they're overburdened with a whole bunch of other things, but everything that goes into transformative agreements, everything that goes in general for agreements for the management of electronic resources is all up to us.

[...]

0:31:58.220 --> 0:32:32.840

R

... we have noticed, let's say perhaps a booster effect of the transformative agreements has also been that publishing a postprint with a Creative Commons license has become difficult for some publishers, in the sense that perhaps it is allowed to deposit in the institutional repository, but not associating a Creative Commons but a “*tailor made*” license let's say, I don't know if you have also managed these aspects and how you have done it.

0:32:32.850 --> 0:32:34.950

R

Well, if you've taken care of this.

0:32:33.540 --> 0:32:37.260

K5

And no, I don't have updated data on this, I don't know if we say that in Italy the publication in open access on the repository has always been rather difficult, in short, the teachers are very little literate, about this and therefore who is afraid and

E no, questo non ho dati aggiornati su questo, non so se diciamo che da noi la già la pubblicazione in open access sul repository è sempre stata piuttosto difficile, insomma, i docenti sono molto poco alfabetizzati, riguardo a questo e quindi chi ha paura e non ha mai messo l'articolo anche potendolo fare, chi invece l'ha messo senza accorgersi che non lo poteva fare, diciamo che da noi tutti i bibliotecari, i direttori di biblioteche in particolare sono incaricati di validare i prodotti che vengono messi quindi prima che venga pubblicato devo passare dal loro controllo che è un controllo di questo tipo, sulle licenze se sono corrette, se i metadati sono stati eseguiti correttamente, cioè non di contenuto ma di forma ovviamente e però non saprei cosa è successo, potrei, però è una buona cosa, potrei chiedere per vedere se è cambiato o se loro, se chi si occupa i colleghi e le colleghe della ricerca si sono accorti di qualche cambiamento rispetto a questo, perché in realtà dai contratti è sempre consentito, è rimasto solo, è sempre rimasta la clausola che è possibile la pubblicazione sui propri *repository* istituzionali, peraltro.

0:33:58.570 --> 0:33:59.360

R

Certamente.

0:33:58.60 --> 0:34:7.760

K5

has never put the article even if they could do it, On the other hand, those who put it without realizing that they could not do it, let's say that in Italy all librarians, library directors in particular, are in charge of validating the products that are put so before it is published I have to go through their control which is a check of this type, on the licenses if they are correct, if the metadata has been done correctly, that is, not of content but of form of course and yet I would not know what happened, I could, but it is a good thing, I could ask to see if it has changed or if they, if those who deal with the colleagues of the research have noticed any change with respect to this, because in reality the agreements are always allowed, It has remained alone, the clause has always remained that it is possible to publish on their institutional repositories, moreover.

0:33:58.570 --> 0:33:59.360

R

Absolutely.

0:33:58.60 --> 0:34:7.760

K5

In short, it would be a resounding own goal, it is already said that this type of contract limits the expansion of the green way.

0:34:7.770 --> 0:34:9.860

K5

Imagine if they don't even allow it

Insomma, sarebbe un autogol clamoroso, già si dice che questo tipo di contratto limita la l'espansione del della via verde.

0:34:7.770 --> 0:34:9.860

K5

Figuriamoci se poi neanche lo consentono

0:34:10.390 --> 0:34:12.830

R

Esatto, no, no, il deposito sì, ma abbiamo notato che, a parte xxxxxxxx che comunque permetteva la licenza meno coerente con l'open access, la CC-BY-NC-ND, altri tipo xxxxxxxx, xxxxxxxx, chiamano una loro licenza, la *bespoke license*, cioè praticamente non una CC, con cui puoi depositare, sostanzialmente concedere la visualizzazione, lo scaricamento del postprint e nulla più.

0:34:44.180 --> 0:34:48.330

R

Comunque grazie, se hai approfondimenti, mi confronto volentieri in futuro.

0:34:47.250 --> 0:34:49.430

K5

La cosa incuriosisce anche me.

[...]

0:34:52.250 --> 0:35:10.320

R

Vi sono diciamo idee su possibili interventi di perequazione per quello che dicevi tu prima, ci possono essere enti che sono molto esposti perché storicamente hanno pagato sempre un sacco di abbonamenti,

0:34:10.390 --> 0:34:12.830

R

That's right, no, no, the deposit yes, but we noticed that, apart from xxxxxxxx which in any case allowed the least consistent license with open access, the CC-BY-NC-ND, others like xxxxxxxx, xxxxxxxx, call their own license, the *bespoke license*, that is, practically not a CC, with which you can deposit, basically grant the viewing, the download of the postprint and nothing more.

0:34:44.180 --> 0:34:48.330

R

Anyway thanks, if you have any insights, I'll gladly compare it in the future.

0:34:47.250 --> 0:34:49.430

K5

I'm curious about it too.

[...]

0:34:52.250 --> 0:35:10.320

R

There are let's say ideas on possible equalization interventions for what you said before, there may be entities that are very exposed because historically they have always paid a lot of subscriptions, but in reality, they publish very little in those journals. What could happen?

0:35:13.550 --> 0:35:20.60

K5

And that's a good question, but I don't think I can answer it, I mean, I don't know,

ma in realtà su quelle riviste pubblicano molto poco.

Cosa potrebbe avvenire?

0:35:13.550 --> 0:35:20.60

K5

E questa è una bella domanda, ma non credo di poter rispondere, cioè non lo so, onestamente non lo so.

Secondo me è un nodo che verrà al pettine presto,

[...]

come una cosa che prima o poi bisognerà farci i conti però, ancora non sappiamo come e per ora gli enti piccoli non hanno ancora fatto sentire la loro voce. Ecco, questa è una cosa che io posso dire serenamente ad oggi, cioè, perlomeno nei contratti che seguo io, nessun ente piccolo ha detto no, io non ci sto perché non mi conviene. Forse sperano che questo invece, li incoraggerà a pubblicare di più, promuovendo la possibilità di pubblicare senza pagare può darsi che questo aumenti la produzione, ecco, questo sarà un dato interessante da verificare a valle, almeno della prima ondata che sta per finire.

Perché poi, insomma, i primi contratti, come xxxxxxx, sono quasi al termine, Eh sì, xxxxxxx è in fase di rinnovo e quindi si possono già tirare delle somme, ecco, vediamo.

[...]

I honestly don't know. In my opinion, it is a knot that will come to a head soon,

[...]

As something that sooner or later we will have to deal with, however, we still don't know how and for now the small entities have not yet made their voices heard. Well, this is something that I can say serenely to date, that is, at least in the agreements that I follow, no small entity has said no, I am not there because it is not convenient for me. Perhaps they hope that this will encourage them to publish more, promoting the possibility of publishing without paying, it may be that this increases production, well, this will be an interesting data to verify downstream, at least of the first wave that is about to end. Because then, in short, the first agreements, such as xxxxxxx, are almost at the end, oh yes, xxxxxxx is going to be renewed and so we can already draw conclusions, here, let's see.

[...]

But it is very interesting to have the picture of what is changing or has changed, how they have increased, how much has been saved, how much has been spent and how much has been spent per article, per download, in short, I like it, I have always liked this aspect so much a bit statistical,

Però è molto interessante avere il quadro di cosa sta cambiando o è cambiato, come sono aumentati, quanto si risparmiato, quanto si è speso e quanto si è speso per articolo, per download, insomma, a me piace, mi è sempre piaciuto molto questo aspetto così un po' statistico, applicato alle risorse elettroniche e noi, per esempio, abbiamo un costo per articolo bassissimo, perché tantissimi hanno pubblicato in questo modo e siamo molto contenti di questo.

[...]

applied to electronic resources and we, for example, We have a very low cost per article, because so many have published in this way and we are very happy with this.

[...]

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“Not science, but charity transformed the world, in some periods; and only very few men have gone down in history for science; but all of them will be able to remain imperishable, a symbol of the eternity of life, in which death is but a stage, a metamorphosis for a higher ascension if they dedicate themselves to good .” (Giuseppe Moscati)

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“Non la scienza, ma la carità ha trasformato il mondo, in alcuni periodi; e solo pochissimi uomini son passati alla storia per la scienza; ma tutti potranno rimanere imperituri, simbolo dell'eternità della vita, in cui la morte non è che una tappa, una metamorfosi per un più alto ascenso, se si dedicheranno al bene” (Giuseppe Moscati).